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Measuring What Matters For Australian Schools

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Statement of Originality

This is to certify that to the best of my knowledge;
the content of this thesis is my own work.

This thesis has not been submitted for any degree or other purposes.

I certify that the intellectual content of this thesis
is the product of my own work and that all the assistance
received in preparing this thesis and sources has been acknowledged.

Sara Ratner

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Dedication

Marion Thorpe

19.09.43 – 22.03.22

Mum,

You instilled in me a love of learning,
a yearning for knowledge and a wanderlust.

I miss you every single day.

This is for you.

When I started this journey
I never imagined you wouldn't be there
to watch me graduate at the end,
I know you'd be so proud.

Abstract

The federated education system in Australia provides a challenging context for its schools to operate within as it strives to serve the conflicting priorities and needs of a diverse and disparate nation. This study was situated at the convergence of the Australian K-12 education system, the national goals for it as agreed by the Australian education ministers from each State and Territory, and the instruments used to measure its efficacy whilst recognising the power exerted on it and by it through key stakeholders: educators, policy makers and the media.

Through the national measurement framework, Australians have consented to the authority of national and international large-scale assessments to determine the efficacy of the K-12 education system. It is therefore imperative that educators and researchers delve into analysis of the policies shaped by the interpretation of these results, including their intended and unintended consequences. Test instrument validity and the consequences (intended and unintended) of testing is a well-established area of research in the field of educational assessment and the need for further stakeholder engagement with this conversation is critical.

As the debate regarding how to best measure system-wide success continues, this thesis seeks to contribute to the conversation by asking:

Research Question (RQ) 1: To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

Research Question (RQ) 2: How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?

Research Question (RQ) 3: Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

Adopting a Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) methodology permitted the researcher to progress from the what (RQ1) and how (RQ2) of the problem to the why (RQ3). Challenged by the notion that the Australian education system is failing its stakeholders based on the interpretation of results from the National Assessment Program (NAP), this thesis analysed the key federal educational policies outlining the goals for schooling, examined the assessment instruments used to measure their achievement and engaged in ten semi-structured interviews with educational leaders seeking to envisage a better way forward. Throughout the study, considering validity as a key factor, the intent of the instruments used to measure the achievement of the agreed goals for schooling was examined alongside the consequences of their results and how they are interpreted and used.

As data were collected, they were coded line by line to identify common themes which have been summarised as: 1) the complex federated system, 2) accountability based on shared responsibility, 3) agreed goals and shared definitions, 4) focus on measuring growth, 5) critical consumers of data, and 6) the politics of performance. These themes aim to summarise the findings of the study and support critical conversations that better align the interpretation of the results from the instruments employed with the agreed national goals for schooling.

Current measures of school systems are predominantly informed by the performance of individual students on agreed test instruments. For education systems to meet the needs of every student and align with the nationally agreed goals for schooling, this study found that the complexity of the federated system must first be addressed. Then, equipped with valid and reliable test instruments used for their intended purpose, Australian schools can focus on supporting the growth and progress of its students as informed and critical consumers of measurement data.

To achieve an education system that is excellent and equitable for all students, it is imperative to measure what matters. If Australia chooses to consent to the authority of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results (or any other such instrument featured in the NAP) as the benchmark for success, then its nationally agreed goals must align with the PISA definition of a successful school system. Alternatively, Australia can find an alternative measure that better aligns with its nationally agreed definition of system-wide success. As a result of this study, stronger alignment between educational policy, the practice of measuring system-wide success and the performance of Australian schools is sought. Armed with a solid understanding of educational policy and the validity of the measurement instruments used to assess them will be beneficial as we seek to measure what matters most to Australia's society when it comes to providing an excellent and equitable education for all.

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List of Publications

Research articles

Ratner, S. (2022a). Re-imagining assessment in Australian schools. *Independent Education*, 52, 30-31.

Ratner, S. (2022b). Leading emotionally intelligent schools to drive school improvement. *Australian Educational Leader*, 44 (1), 40-42.

Wilson, R., Tognolini, J., Kesidou, S., Ratner, S., Walker, K., Hains-Wesson, R., & Bartimote, K. (2022, 17 June). Productivity Commission Submission.

Tognolini, J. & Ratner, S. (2020). Valuing the teaching profession: an independent inquiry: expert submissions. NSW Teacher's Federation.

Conference proceedings

Ratner, S. (2023). *Australia's National Assessment Program: what does it measure and why does it matter?* [Paper presentation]. World Congress on Education, Toronto, Canada.

Ratner, S. (2023). *Meeting students where they are* [Paper presentation]. The IAFOR Conference on Educational Research & Innovation, Washington D.C., USA.

Ratner, S. (2022). *Test fairness: taking a global perspective* [Invited panel]. European Conference of the Association of Test Publishers, London, England.

Ratner, S. (2022). Is this our moon-shot moment? 10th European Conference on Education, University College London. Conference presentation.

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List of Acronyms

ACARA: Australian Curriculum and Reporting Authority

AESOC: Australian Education Senior Officials Committee

COAG: Council of Australian Governments

ESA: Education Services Australia

IEA: International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement

ILSA: International large-scale assessment

LSA: Large-scale assessment

MCEETYA: Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training and Youth Affairs

NAP: National Assessment Program

NAPLAN: National Assessment Program – Literacy and Numeracy

NESA: New South Wales Education Standards Authority

OECD: Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development

PIRLS: Progress in International Reading Literacy Studies

PISA: Programme for International Student Assessment

SDG: Sustainable Development Goal

TIMSS: Trends in International Mathematical and Science Studies

UNESCO: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

UNICEF: United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund

List of Terms

ASSESSMENT: Assessment is an inclusive term that refers to the act of collecting data, interpreting it, deducing information, and making reliably informed judgements about student performance through any of a multitude of means or practices (Messick, 1989; Davidson & Tognolini, 2013; Tognolini & Stanley, 2007).

ASSESSMENT FOR LEARNING: The process whereby teachers seek and use evidence to decide where learners are in their learning, where they need to go, and how best to get there. (Stobart, 2021).

ASSESSMENT TOOLS: The tests, tasks and activities undertaken by schools, teachers, and students to generate data on the performance and achievement of students and schools.

AUSTRALIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM: State, Catholic and Independent schools across all the states and territories of Australia which cater for students from Kindergarten to Year 12.

CLASSROOM ASSESSMENT: A process through which teachers and students gather, interpret, and use evidence of student learning “for a variety of purposes, including diagnosing student strengths and weaknesses, monitoring student progress toward meeting desired levels of proficiency, assigning grades, and providing feedback to parents” (McMillan, 2013, p. 4).

COMPARABILITY: When referring to the comparability of an assessment, users are seeking to understand the viability of being able to compare test scores obtained at different times, locations or under different circumstances (Berman et al., 2020).

CONSEQUENTIAL VALIDITY: Consequential validity is defined by Messick (1995) as appraising the “value implications of score interpretation as a basis for action as well as the actual and potential consequences of test use, especially regarding sources of invalidity related to issues of bias, fairness, and distributive justice” (p.745).

CONSTANT COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: Completed by undertaking coding and category development in Grounded theory studies when ‘incidents’ or ‘units’ are identified in the data (Birks & Mills, 2015; Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

CONSTRUCT: A concept or a mental representation of shared attributes or characteristics assumed to exist because it gives rise to observable or measurable phenomena (Geisinger et al., 2013).

CONSTRUCTIVISM: Derived from the theories of Jean Piaget (1936), constructivists view learning as the active process of constructing meaning from practical experience and what they already know (Andrade & Brookhart, 2019).

DATA: For the purpose of this study, data are referred to in the plural form and as the information that is collected, organised, analysed, and interpreted (Tognolini & Mowbray, 2019).

EDUCATIONAL MEASUREMENT: The process by which the intelligence, interest, attitude, aptitude, personality, and educational achievements of the students are measured on the basis of definite standards and are expressed in definite words, symbols, or units (Ajayi, 2018).

EDUCATIONAL TESTING: The application of a standard scale or instrument to determine the degree to which educationally valuable knowledge, skills, and abilities have been acquired (Ajayi, 2018).

EQUALITY: The Australian Human Rights Commission (2019) defines equality as everyone being assessed and treated without regard to their particular circumstances.

EQUITY: Equity in schooling means ensuring that differences in educational outcomes are not the result of differences in wealth, income, power, or possessions. (Buckingham, 2011).

EVALUATION: The process of making a value-based judgement on the quality of the data.

FOUCAULT: French philosopher active during the structuralist and post-structuralist period who was regarded for his theories on the relations between power and knowledge (Gutting & Oksala, 2022)

g: General intelligence, also known as g factor, refers to a general mental ability that underlies an individual's multiple specific skills, including verbal, spatial, numerical, and mechanical (Spearman, 1904).

GROUNDING THEORY: An approach that develops new theories through the researcher's own lens or world view following their analysis of data (Charmaz, 2006; Birks & Mills, 2015).

INTELLIGENCE: There are many definitions of intelligence including Terman: "a unique, fixed, inherited characteristic of a human mind." (Terman, 1919, p.217). Vandenberg (2007) define intelligence as "the ability to derive information, learn from experience, adapt to the environment, understand, and correctly utilize thought and reason" (p.488).

INTELLIGENCE QUOTIENT (IQ): IQ is a standard measure of an individual's intelligence level based on psychological tests (American Psychology Association, 2023).

MEASUREMENT: In simple terms, measurement refers to the description of attributes by assigning them a number based upon a pre-determined, constructed scale (Geisinger et al., 2013). It is the "process of ascribing a number which summarises how much of the construct is present in the object" (Tognolini, 2016, slide 3).

MPARNTWE DECLARATION: The Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Education Declaration (Education Council, 2019) is the national policy agreed to and signed by all states and territories that outlines the agreed goals for schooling in Australia. It is named in honour of the location where the education ministers met and agreed its terms.

NEOLIBERALISM: Revival of classic liberalism following the defeat of communism and fascism post World War II (Mudge, 2008; Peters, 2011). It proposes that “human well-being can best be advanced by liberating individual entrepreneurial freedoms and skills within an institutional framework characterized by strong private property rights, free markets and free trade” (Harvey, 2005, p.2).

PSYCHOMETRICS: A field of study that focuses on the theory and techniques associated primarily with the measurement of constructs as well as the development, interpretation, and evaluation of tests and measures (Geisinger et al., 2013).

RELIABILITY: This refers to the consistency of a measure. It speaks to the ability of the test to reproduce the same results at varying times.

SCALE: A scale is a “linear continuum partitioned into equal units which provides the measurements, and scaling is the process of locating an entity on such a scale” (Andrich & Marais, 2019, p.10).

SELF-REGULATED LEARNING: This refers to the process of students being able to construct their own meaning whilst operating within a shared learning environment (Andrade & Brookhart, 2019).

SOCIAL CONSTRUCTIVISM: This builds upon the constructivist theories proposed by Piaget (1936; 1945; 1957) and emphasises the collaborative nature of learning (Andrade & Brookhart, 2019).

STANDARDISED TESTING: Standardised assessments provide “common test-taking conditions, questions, time to respond, scoring procedures and interpretations of the results. They may test knowledge, skills, attributes, or values. They may use multiple choice, short answer or extended written responses. They may be administered to whole populations, to samples from a population or to individuals. They may be marked electronically or by human assessors. Results may be reported in terms of standards achieved or in comparison with the achievements of a wider population. Results may be used for summative, formative, diagnostic or predictive purposes.” (McGaw et al., 2020., p.8).

SYSTEM-WIDE SUCCESS: Performance across the entire education system based on the achievement of agreed standards by a governing body.

TEST: A set of items or statements to which one responds in a controlled environment, and which results in a score of correct responses (Geisinger et al., 2013).

VALIDITY: Concerned with ensuring that assessments and measurements are of the trait intended (Andrich & Marais, 2019).

Chapter 1: Introduction

This study seeks to make a meaningful contribution to the existing body of knowledge at the intersection of educational measurement and assessment, policy and practice. Employing a Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) methodology, alignment is sought between the national goals and values for schooling in Australia as stated in the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Declaration (the Declaration) (Education Council, 2019) and the measurement instruments used to assess progress towards their achievement as stipulated by the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (Australian Curriculum and Reporting Authority (ACARA), 2020a). This measurement study reviews the impact and efficacy of the current measures on the educational policies enacted in Australia and the positioning of the Australian education system on the global stage. Whilst focused upon the Australian K-12 education landscape, this study is potentially of international interest as it seeks to better align a shared definition of system-wide success with the policies, practices and measurement instruments that will best serve it.

This research addresses the following questions:

RQ1: To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

RQ2: How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?

RQ3: Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

The answers are sought through a three phased study which includes policy analysis using Bacchi's (2012) "What's the Problem Represented to be?", analysis of the National Assessment Program (NAP) measurement instruments using Messick's (1989) theory of validity

and finally, semi-structured interviews with educational leaders who have working knowledge of the Australian educational measurement and policy landscape. The significance of this study lies in finding better approaches to the measurement of the national goals for schooling in Australia. At present, Australian schools, as in other education systems, are reliant upon a range of data-generating tools to measure their success. These assessments are routinely relied upon to paint a broad stroke picture of system-wide performance without attesting to whether they are measuring what matters most. As the debate regarding how to best measure system-wide success continues globally, this thesis is positioned to make a timely and relevant contribution to the field of educational measurement and assessment using Australia as an example. It seeks to advance the conversation by asking, are Australian schools measuring what matters and, in a way that empowers teachers to engage with the measures as critical consumers of assessment data?

This thesis begins by examining the history and politics of the Australian K-12 education system. Through a contextualised understanding of the power at play, insights into the policies that shape the Australian education system will emerge through a focus on the nationally agreed goals for schooling. Challenged by the notion that the Australian school system is failing to meet the needs of its students and society (Fahey, 2023; Mizen, 2023), this research examines the current measures of success used to ascertain the achievement of the stated and agreed outcomes for Australian schools in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). This is done through an analysis of the aforementioned policy using Bacchi's "What's the Problem Represented to be?" (WPR) framework (Bacchi, 2012; Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016) and an exploration of the assessments and measures employed in the national Measurement Framework for Schooling's National Assessment Program (NAP) in Australia (ACARA, 2020a). These include the large-scale assessments (LSA) such as the Programme for International Assessment (PISA), Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS), and the National Assessment Program: Literacy and Numeracy

(NAPLAN). Upon examining the guiding policies and measures of success, this research shares findings from educational leaders across Australia's K-12 school system. Ten semi-structured interviews were completed with purposively sampled participants and their responses helped inform a discussion of "Where to next?" for the Australian school system. These interviews, based on the participants' professional experience, are a valuable means for exploring the ongoing challenges of educational assessment.

1.1 Framing the study

Can the quality of an educational experience be reduced to a single quantitative measure? Krantz et al. (1971) explain that "measurement has always been problematic" (p. xvii) and as educators grapple with the challenges that measurement poses, the powerful role it plays in policy decision making cannot be overstated.

Validity is a critical consideration for both its psychometric accountability and its impact on broader policy implications (Angner, 2011). The definition of validity as the extent to which an instrument measures the construct it is intended to measure originated with Kelley (1927). In the years since, further definitions have evolved. Borsboom (2003) is resolute that validity is neither complex nor faceted. Rather, it is purely whether the instrument measures the intended attribute. However, this thesis is grounded in an epistemological position that acknowledges the role of the world around us in shaping knowledge of it. It favours an ontology that adopts a constructivist view of individuals as building knowledge through social interactions. Therefore, the conception of validity as being limited to the instruments' ability to measure the constructs, negates the influence of context, content and consequence. Thus, making Borsboom's definition incongruent with the researcher's position. Faced with the same incongruities, Kane (2006) and Messick (1989) shaped current understandings of validity accordingly. Their conceptions of validity reflect a shift to consider the ways in which the results of such measures are used (Larroulet Philippi, 2021). In Messick's (1989) understanding of validity, credence is paid to the

potential consequences arising from the interpretation and use of its results which aligns with the philosophical underpinnings of this thesis. In an educational context, one cannot view a singular measurement score in isolation from the context in which the test taker resides. Porter (1995) asserts that measurements are critical in solving the challenge of political weakness, “and our understanding of it is poor indeed if we do not relate it to the forms of community in which it flourishes” (p. x). Whether for political or educational reasons, when it comes to “human measurement” the two words cannot be separated. The human cannot be reduced simply to a quantitative measure and the measure cannot exist in isolation from the human.

For the results derived from a measurement instrument to be regarded as valid, the instrument must measure the construct it was intended to. What happens then, for example, if an instrument intended to measure student competency in reading literacy delivers results that are subsequently used to ascertain teacher salary increases? What are the consequences of using scores that were designed for one purpose and used for another? *The Daily Mail* newspaper in Australia featured a story in which they reported on the teachers of New South Wales striking for pay increases. They wrote, “Thousands of teachers across New South Wales are set to receive a pay rise after going on strike over their salaries” (Wilkie, 2019, para. 1). *The Daily Mail* then said, “the strike on Thursday came just a day after Australia's education system was given an abysmal report card. The 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results were released this week, where Australian 15-year-old students recorded poor results in reading, maths and science compared to their international counterparts” (Wilkie, 2019, para. 9). This is an example of what Skourdoumbis et al. (2023) call the “education blame mantra” where “bad teachers” are equated with “failing schools” (p.12). Whether the fallacy of such a conflation in the *Daily Mail* article is intentionally designed to confuse readers or not, the truth is that we abide in a conflated world where two seemingly unrelated matters are positioned side-by-side, and the reader is encouraged to infer a causal link that is not defensible. The argument of the teachers was that

“where people have the same experience and the same qualifications” they should not be “paid at two different levels” (Wilkie, 2019, para. 8), and the media response they received infers that teachers don’t deserve a pay rise because of the nation’s performance on PISA in 2018. The test’s intended purpose therefore becomes the adjudicator of this debate. When validating the PISA test instrument, there is no reference to determining teacher salary increases as an intended purpose. However, the media (and subsequently its readers) have used the results of the test in this manner which is not consistent with the instrument’s purpose. The misuse of the results in this way, by conflating them with the teachers’ demand for salary scale adjustments, impacts on the perceived fairness and trustworthiness in the eyes of key stakeholders across the Australian educational system.

The response of nations from across the world to the rankings and reporting on large-scale assessments (LSA) such as PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS and the International Assessment of Literacy Survey (IALS) show their significant impact in driving educational reform, policy review and change (Levin, 2012). Yet, there have also been concerns expressed regarding PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS with relation to the “provenance of the data collected, the ways in which it is disseminated and the limitations these impose on the interpretations that can be made in terms of international and over-time comparisons” (Goldstein, 2017, p.1).

This thesis seeks to examine the alignment between the goals for schooling outlined in Australian educational policy and the measurement instruments used to assess the effectiveness of the education system. In doing so, consideration is given to the validity of those instruments for their intended purpose and the impact of the instruments on the way in which the success (or failure) of the education system is reflected in some of the stories and lived experiences of those operating within it.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

This study is centred on a perceived misalignment between the agreed goals for schooling in Australia and the measurement instruments currently employed to measure and report on the success of the system against the goals. At present, this problem manifests itself as an inconsistency between the evaluation of the system based on results which are primarily standardised test scores (generally on tests or instruments that are designed for a different purpose) that show generally declining trends in performance and the perceptions of success within the system (supported by other indicators of performance) which are incongruent with the results of such measures. To make better informed evaluations regarding how the system is performing there is a need to better align the measures with the stated goals of the education system. This thesis seeks to answer three research questions which shape the study. They are:

RQ1. To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

RQ2. How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?

RQ3. Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

These questions echo those that Hattie and Timperley (2007) encourage students to ask of their own learning, "Where am I going?", "How am I going?" and "Where to next?".

The contested landscape of educational assessment is littered with a spectrum of opinions ranging from those who argue vehemently against the use of standardised testing (Kohn, 2000; Morgan, 2016) to those who favour providing evidence through standardised test scores that enable the ranking, sorting and filing of students and/or their teachers by performance to provide accountability to stakeholders. Extensive research has been done on evaluating the construct

validity of the test instruments included in Australia’s National Assessment Program (Schult & Sparfeldt, 2016; Stankov et al., 2018; Rose et al., 2020). So too, work has been completed on examining the headlines surrounding the announcement of results stemming from the measures employed (Baroutsis & Lingard, 2017; Davis, 2019; Davis & Wilson, 2019; Mockler, 2013). This thesis centres on the gap that exists between the policies that guide the education system in Australia, the measures used to attest to the impact of these policies on the performance of the system and its performance on the global stage. A detailed examination of these three aspects aims to contribute a new theoretical perspective on how to ensure Australia is measuring what matters when it comes to envisioning an education system that is excellent and equitable for all.

Figure 1

Performance Trends: Year 9 NAPLAN, PISA, Year 8 TIMSS (2003-2019)

Data from NAPLAN (ACARA, 2023b), TIMSS (Thomson & Fleming, 2004; Thomson et al., 2008; Thomson et al., 2012; Thomson et al., 2017; Thomson et al., 2020) and PISA (OECD, 2000a; OECD, 2007; OECD, 2016b; OECD, 2019b; Thomson et al., 2013).

Figure 1 depicts a declining trend in PISA (Reading Literacy and Mathematical Literacy), no significant change in performance on NAPLAN and no significant change in TIMSS at Year 8 (McGaw et al., 2020, p.41). Charts such as this, made available in the public domain, further highlight the problem being explored in this thesis which is the importance of situating such data in the “right” context. For stakeholders with little or no technical understanding of these measurement instruments it may be challenging to see anything but a declining trend once children move from primary to secondary school in Australia.

Several issues are evident in Figure 1. Firstly, NAPLAN mathematics is a curriculum-linked, census-based assessment delivered nationally to Year 9 students across Australia. TIMSS is a sample-based, international large-scale assessment of Year 8 students from across Australia. Similarly, PISA is an international large-scale assessment of students aged 15 years 3 months to 16 years 2 months. PISA is competency-based rather than curriculum-linked. In addition, the results from these tests are reported to participants in different ways, which may potentially influence test-taking motivation. For example, following participation in NAPLAN the students receive individual results which are shared with schools and parents whilst no results are issued to the participants in PISA and TIMSS.

Figure 2 below, also replicated from the NAPLAN Review Final Report (McGaw et al., 2020) compares the trends in reading performance across time of NAPLAN and PISA. It can be seen from Figure 2 that the performance in the curriculum-based, census assessment (NAPLAN) delivered to Year 9 students across the country shows a slight increase over time, whereas PISA, the competency-based assessment drawn from a sample of students aged 15 years 3 months to 16 years 2 months reflects a relatively steep decline.

Figure 2

Trends in Reading: Year 9 NAPLAN, PISA (2000-2019)

Source data from NAPLAN (ACARA, 2023b) and PISA (OECD, 2000a; OECD, 2007; OECD, 2016b; OECD, 2019b; Thomson et al., 2013).

In agreement with the findings of McGaw et al. (2020), the evidence is clear that there is an issue to be examined with regards to Australia's stagnating (if not declining) performance. Therefore, a careful review of the data and an understanding of the purpose of each of the tests

used is needed to guide the reader in correctly interpreting the results and informing the key stakeholders on what, if anything might be done, to maintain or improve the performance in reading and reading literacy, numeracy and mathematical literacy across the nation. Headlines that call for wide-spread reform in response to a system that is failing as a result of such results demand careful examination. That is a contribution this thesis seeks to make, by exploring the alignment between the goals for Australian K-12 schooling and the instruments employed to assess its' success.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This research hypothesises that in the Australian school system, a misalignment exists between what is measured and what matters to Australians as a society (as reflected in the goals for Australia's education system). If standardised scores of individual student achievement in Reading, Mathematics and Science are relied upon as the measure of system-wide success then there is a risk of losing sight of the overarching goals for equity and excellence that are the key policy drivers for the system. The significance of this study lies at the centre of every Australian classroom and in every teacher's daily work. It intersects policy, measurement, education, and power in the hope of theorising how education systems can better define their goals, set their targets, and measure their success.

In terms of the contribution it seeks to make, this study begins with an exploration of educational policy in Australia through a detailed analysis of the policies that inform the nation's shared goals for schooling and provide the purpose for the K-12 school system. Secondly, through the application of measurement theory with a focus on Messick's (1989) concepts of validity, this study seeks to help moderate the effects of PISA (Hopfenbeck & G6rger, 2017; Hopfenbeck et al., 2018) and view the tools used to measure system-wide success in an informed and considered manner. Thirdly, education systems around the world may benefit from this study as it will afford them the opportunity to engage in similar conversations and reviews of their own

policies to envisage a more appropriate way to measure the performance of their education systems against goals and values that are localised to their own context. Fourthly, through an examination of the power relations at play, this study hopes to contribute to a growing research agenda which seeks to empower educators with an increased understanding of educational policy. This supports educators who are operating within a contested policy space. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, this research looks to engage Australian classroom educators in this critical conversation. As an educator working to understand how Australia can better reflect upon and measure the success of its school system an extensive learning journey into the field of educational assessment ensued. Upon examining psychometric studies, the decision to engage in this study through CGT was purposeful. It enabled the researcher to situate lived experience within the study and locate the findings in a way that educators may find more accessible. Thus, elevating its usefulness for Australian schools, educators, parents and policymakers.

1.4 Thesis outline

The opening chapter begins by framing the study and situating the thesis at the convergence of policy, measurement, and practice. Chapter 2 reviews the literature which informed the study. Chapter 3 invites the reader to explore the theoretical frameworks underpinning this study including Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT), Measurement Theory and Foucault's (1977) work on power. Chapter 4 details the method employed in this study which is then followed by a series of three chapters, each of which address one of the research phases: policy analysis, measurement, and interviews. In Chapter 5, the application of Bacchi's "What's the Problem Represented to be?" (WPR) framework (Bacchi, 2012; Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016) to the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) provides a detailed account of the shared goals for Australian schooling. By exploring the policies and decision that guide and direct Australia's schools, this research is well placed to investigate the gap between the goals for schooling in Australia and the measures used to evaluate their achievement. Chapter 6 focuses on

the tools and measures agreed in the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a) and examines Australia's recent performance according to those measures. A detailed overview of each assessment tool and test is outlined in addition to an exploration of its historical background and political positioning through the Foucauldian perspective of power (Foucault, 1977). In doing so, this research calls into question the alignment between Australia's goals for its education system and the measures of its success through Messick's (1989) notion of validity. This is very much inspired by the wise provocations of Hargreaves and Fullan (2012), who asked if we are measuring what matters? The last of the research phases is explained in Chapter 7, where the insights of a sample of educational leaders are explored. This chapter explores the opportunities to transcend and transform the educational assessment landscape globally by empowering educators to attest to the validity, reliability and applicability of the measures employed to their contextualised definitions of success. Chapter 8 details the results of the study which leads to a discussion of the findings, answers the research questions posed. The thesis concludes with Chapter 9 which summarises the researcher's learning journey and makes recommendations for future practice and research.

1.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter sought to frame the study, state the problem and explain its significance to the field of educational assessment. After outlining the overall structure of the thesis in Chapter 1, the following chapter explores the literature that will inform this study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter reviews the literature that informs this study. Typically, when employing a CGT methodology, the literature review is positioned much later in the study after the data collection and the iterative process of theory generation has been completed. However, in keeping with the requirements of the thesis structure, this literature review has been positioned at the forefront. As this research is situated at the convergence of measurement, policy, and practice, the literature review has been organised under those broad headings which invariably link to the themes which emerged from the process of coding the data. It begins by setting the scene and situating the research which follows.

2.1 Setting the Scene

When devoting time to observing a young child at play with an array of colourful blocks, one would undoubtedly begin to see them sorting, matching, grouping, and comparing them according to their visual attributes. These natural, unprompted actions are not only the hallmark of early mathematical understanding but also reflect an innate, human fascination with sorting, measuring, classifying, and ranking. It is how one begins to make sense of the world. Therefore, it is little wonder that the field of education assessment exists. Since the earliest days of schooling, educators have relied upon their basic instincts to sort, measure and rank the students in their care to better understand them. Alfred Binet envisaged teachers as akin to engineers who, to ensure that a bridge will be safe to cross, must subject the material (iron or cement) to some testing to prove its strength and limit (Binet & Simon, 1916). The French physician, Theodore Simon asserted that one may very well believe they know a child simply because they live with them, but how can one really know what a child is truly capable of if one does not test their limits? (Binet & Simon, 1916).

Working together, at the request of the French government, Alfred Binet and Theodore Simon developed a tool that could help French teachers identify students in need of additional support to succeed at school. Together they created a test designed to ascertain attention, memory and problem solving - all elements that are essential to success at school but not necessarily explicitly taught. As the duo observed the children's responses, they noted a difference in their ability to answer despite being of the same chronological age and based upon this, the concept of mental age was formed. This test, the Binet-Simon scale, was the first standardised test of the intelligence quotient (I.Q.) (Hally, 2015).

As early as the 1920s, Cabós believed mental testing to be useful for the purpose of improving a teacher's daily educational practice. Educators in Spain knew that to improve the art of teaching, a deep knowledge of the intellectual and neurophysical dynamics of their students was needed and that this required involving them in a series of tests and experiments (Cabós, 1922). To this day, assessment remains at the core of pedagogical best practice and good teachers rely on quality testing tools, as one of a battery of assessments, to inform their endeavours. So, why is educational testing so contentious and the source of such debate in policy, media, and classrooms across the country?

Effective educators know that the data they collect must tell the truth they were designed to share (Tognolini & Mowbray, 2019). Educators and stakeholders must therefore engage with the right test, at the right time for the right purpose. Tests whose results cannot easily be manipulated to serve a need, fill a gap, or generate a headline. When considering the average Australian classroom there are many ways that teachers use to collect data to better understand their students. There are individual test scores available to them from assessments such as the National Assessment Program: Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN) by the Australian Curriculum and Reporting Authority (ACARA) and the Progressive Achievement Tests (PAT) by the Australian Council for Educational Research (ACER). There are also the teacher-made tests and

checks, formative assessments, digital learning platforms and tests designed to support progress mapping. The list of potential data sources in Australian classrooms is almost endless. In addition to tests of academic ability, there are also the social-emotional cues, the wellbeing data, the students' body language, their spoken language and other important anecdotal evidence. Teachers are consistently engaged in data gathering to inform their knowledge and understanding of the students they teach. Just like the young child playing with coloured blocks, educators are intuitively sorting, classifying, measuring the students in their care so they can meet them where they are and help them move forward in their learning (and life). Yet, data means very little unless analysed, interpreted, and reported in a manner that enables one to make consistent, fair judgements. This is where the art and science of teaching connect; a teacher's professional judgement is key to knowing what data are sought and why (Tognolini & Mowbray, 2019). For a long time, educators have known that measuring what a student knows is important as it provides the starting point for their learning and growth. If an educator starts from what the student already knows this is seen as a positive influencing factor (Ausubel, 1968).

When it comes to making professional judgements on student achievement, or system-wide success, the tests that Australian schools are encouraged to rely upon due to their inclusion in the NAP (ACARA, 2011a), are typically large-scale, summative, and standardised. Pertinent to this, recent years have marked the arrival of International Large-Scale Assessments (ILSA) to the field of educational assessment, and they are impacting educational policy nationally and globally (Addey & Sellar, 2018). The ILSA first arose as a solution to a call issued by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) to measure educational outcomes globally (UNESCO, 2015). The International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) responded in the form of a pilot study across twelve countries that lay the grounds for the establishment of what is now known as the Trends in Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) (Addey & Sellar, 2018). The Organisation for Economic

Cooperation and Development (OECD) developed its own ILSA, the International Adult Literacy Survey (IALS) which targeted participants aged 16-65 years, in partnership with Educational Testing Services (ETS) (Thorn, 2009; Addey & Sellar, 2018). Then, the ILSA that the OECD's Education Directorate is probably most renowned for, the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) launched in 1997, with its first implementation taking place three years later across 43 countries (Addey & Sellar, 2018). UNESCO's own ILSA followed a further three years later with the arrival of the Literacy Assessment and Monitoring Program (LAMP) which was designed to assess literacy and numeracy skills (Guadalupe, 2015; Addey & Sellar, 2018).

The rise of the ILSA programmes reflect a turning point in education policy as the data generated are frequently used to define the successes and/or failings of entire education systems (Addey & Sellar, 2018; Breiter et al., 2013). As they seek to provide comparative data across the globe, the ILSA are driving forward the rationalist approach to education espoused by organisations such as the OECD, UNESCO, and the World Bank (Addey & Sellar, 2018; Pokropek, Marks & Borgonovi, 2022). Thus, forcing policymakers around the world to look outwards through a lens of international competition in the pursuit of economic advantage.

More than any other ILSA, PISA has drawn the attention of education ministries (and the media) around the world and the data it generates is positioned front and centre in policy debates and reform the world over (Ertl, 2007; Grek, 2009; Breakspear, 2012; Takayama, 2008). Large scale assessments are typically used to measure the quality of schools and the educators within them (Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2007). Their results produce powerful levers to influence what happens next. Typically, society celebrates the good schools as those who have students who learn to regurgitate the policy-approved content that has been taught effectively and tested during regular, standardised tests (Butterfield, Williams, & Marr, 1999; Firestone, Mayrowetz, & Fairman, 1998; Smith & Fey, 2000). It is argued that such an approach helps

teachers know what their students need to know and is implemented in the interests of school improvement (Brown, 2013; Linn, 2000; Resnick & Resnick, 1992). The challenge with such an approach is that it has the potential to preclude the provision of a safe space for children (and their teachers) to make mistakes and learn from them.

The Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (DFAT) defines the Australian education system as encompassing pre-schools, primary schools (K-6), secondary schools (7-12) and tertiary education which includes higher education and vocational education. Responsibility for which is shared by the Federal Government and the States and Territories of Australia (DFAT, 2017). For this study, the Australian education system is defined as the 4,042,512 students who were enrolled in 9,614 schools primary and secondary schools, public and private, across every state and territory of Australia in 2022 (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2023). This aligns with the framework used to measure the success of the Australian education system in relation to the National Measurement Framework (ACARA, 2020a).

The Australian education system is regarded as promoting high levels of school choice, privatisation, and competition. Compared to other comprehensive education systems (United States of America, United Kingdom, Canada), Australia has been reported as having a significantly higher rate of privatisation with 40% of students attending privately-owned, fee charging secondary schools compared to 10% in other English-speaking countries (OECD, 2010). The long tradition of private schools in Australia arose from the provision of church-funded schools (Perry & Southwell, 2014). There is a perceived prestige associated with these private schools in Australia and they are typically long-established, high fee independent schools. This privatisation is seen to be promoted by the Federal government given the level of funding provided to non-government schools and the federally-funded *My School* website which publicises school performance on standardised assessments and exacerbates competition between Australian schools in the interest of promoting school choice (Perry & Southwell, 2014).

The education systems of today are rooted in constantly evolving histories. In its initial form, education was a private matter that was managed within a family, community, or religious structure. With the modernisation of society, the need emerged for a more formal, professional, and consistent system of educating young people and subsequently, the education systems of today evolved (Fan & Popkewitz, 2020). The Australian education system is no different. In 1793, Reverend Johnson opened the first formal school in New South Wales. Whilst Indigenous ways of knowing through rich, experiential learning and storytelling educated people residing here long before the arrival of the British, this date marks a time in history where education became formally documented. Upon the official opening ceremony of the school, Reverend Johnson declared that schooling in the new colony was to be for all children whether their parents were soldiers, settlers, native born or convicts (Lawry, 1965). This suggests the themes of equity, access and school choice have been recurring across Australia's education system from the beginning. It is now many years since the first formal school was opened in Australia. Over that time the education system has grown in size, purpose, and maturity, yet the question of excellence and equity remains.

Key moments in time have challenged the status quo of education systems and triggered global shifts in education (Fan & Popkewitz, 2020). The space race of the 1950s forged a connection between education and national security (Grunert, 2022). The emergence of the 'third world' saw education linked to national and economic development (Solarz, 2012). The connection between educational outcomes and economic prosperity deepened in the 1980s following the end of the Cold War, the disintegration of the Soviet Union and the rapid economic development in Japan (Benjamin, 1998). The interplay between the needs of the society and the success of the education system are inexorably linked.

In the face of the global health crisis resulting from Covid-19, once again education systems rapidly responded with agility and resilience to meet the needs of a society facing

unprecedented challenges. In a historically significant deployment of technology, schools undertook five years of digital transformation in less than eight weeks to take entire education systems online (McKinsey, 2020). Over time the greatest transformations in education systems have occurred at points in history where society faced a challenge for which the former system was no longer fit for purpose (Dewey, 1916; Durkheim, 1956).

Themes of technology, globalisation and democracy continue to drive the evolution of education systems and shape their future. So, when speaking of the desire for a better education system, in many ways this expresses the desire for a better world. A world in which the needs and wants of the society are realised through the potential embodied in its youth. In 2015, the Director-General of UNESCO echoed this, stating that if the world is changing, and it is, then education must change too. Bokova (2015) called for a move beyond literacy and numeracy to focus on issues such as justice, equity, and global unity as the world learns to live on a planet under pressure.

The global health crisis has led the move from institutionalised systems of education to an approach that involved all stakeholders in a hands-on capacity. It transported the traditional classroom into the four walls of a learner's home. In doing so, it cast a bright light on the role that schools play in creating an equitable, safe space for every child. As classroom walls became screens, the gap between the most and least advantaged in the society was visible. For many children, home was not a safe space nor an optimal learning environment. Children went hungry in the absence of school-funded meals and learning suffered through a lack of equitable access to technological devices and connectivity. The learnings arising from the global health crisis of 2020 and beyond have perhaps highlighted the greatest challenge facing the education system in Australia (Ratner, 2022). Once again, the critical interplay between the education system and the demands of the society are evident. How well is the Australian education system performing and how do we really know?

Australian schools rely upon a range of data-generating tools to measure their success. They are routinely relied upon to paint a broad stroke picture of system-wide performance without attesting to whether they are measuring what matters to Australians as a society or aligned to the shared goals of the nation. Considerable time is presently spent debating the performance of the Australian school system (Gonski et al., 2018; Mrozowska, 2020; Masters, 2019, Mizen, 2023). This study contributes to that debate by examining the extent to which the current tools used to measure Australian schools are supported by evidence of validity and aligned with Australia's national goals for schooling. It seeks to make a timely and relevant contribution to the field of study by asking, "Where to next?" of key thought leaders, educators and policy makers and using their insights to imagine an alternative approach. One that is more aligned to a shared vision for excellence and equity across Australia's K-12 education landscape.

Situated at the convergence of the system and the society, this study focuses upon the pursuit of excellence for an education system that Australians spend 20% of their life engaged with at a cost of more than AUD 100 billion annually (Mahmud Rice, Edwards & McMillan, 2019). To meet the shared goals for a system that provides a world-class education and meets the needs of every student for them to reach their full potential, it is imperative that the debate on Australia's educational goals is renewed (Tehan, 2019). Therefore, this study aligns the measures of system-wide success in Australia's education system with the policies and practices that elucidate common goals for the future of Australia. It is focused upon the Australian K-12 education landscape with the intention that the same methodology can be applied to any system wanting to answer the same question regarding the success of their own education system. Using Australia as the example, this study is applicable globally. By providing an understanding of the tools used to measure the performance of Australian schools, the detailed analysis of policy and practice that follows will explore their alignment with the nationally agreed goals for Australian schooling.

2.2 Measurement

The terms assessment and measurement are often used interchangeably. However, Andrich and Marais (2019) explain that “assessment provides the evidence which, under certain very strict conditions, may be transformed into measurements” (p.3). It is traits or constructs that are measured as they have properties that they can have more or less of. For example, more science ability or less science ability; more creativity or less creativity; etc. Inferences are made about how much of a construct or trait is possessed by an individual from observation. When this observation occurs in a controlled, scientific manner we call it assessment. The controlled environment that allows for the measurement of the manifestation is known as an assessment.

Whether checking the weather before heading out for the day or following the instructions on Google maps to turn left in 100m, this era is what Biesta (2009; 2015; 2017) calls the age of measurement. Measurement is characterised by numbers being “given to represent quantities of some kind, on some scales, to convey properties of some attributes that are of interest to us” (Wu, Tam & Jen, 2016, p.1). To make accurate policy in support of teaching and learning, the inferences drawn from the measures of teaching and learning must also be accurate or valid. Hence, validation or the collection of validity evidence resulting from a measure is the most important aspect of the assessment. To move students along a developmental continuum describing growth or improvement on the construct, which is learning, accurate inferences about how and why students grow must be made from the assessment of students’ progress. This is typically achieved via a measurement device, instrument or test.

Binet and Simon (1907) explained that perceptions of intelligence are defined by the means used to assess it. So too, it is the educational outcomes that are measured and how they are measured that affects our understanding of how well education systems are performing and the policy development needed for their improvement (Breakspear, 2014). Messick (1984b)

provides a truism that for educational purposes, achievement measures should not be measured in isolation but rather in the context of the conditions for instruction and learning (p.2).

The contemporary approach to validation adopted by the AERA et al. (2014) Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing as reported in the TARES Checklist (Iliescu et al., 2024, p.4) reinforces that the validity of a test score interpretation is linked to the intended test use and emphasises the need to offer justification (i.e. validity, evidence through data and analyses) related to the purpose of testing. According to the TARES Checklist (Iliescu et al., 2024, p.10), the validity evidence collected should represent the five sources of validity outlined by the Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing (AERA et al., 2014):

- a) Validity evidence based on test content – evidence of congruence between the test and its purpose
- b) Validity evidence based on response processes – evidence that intended cognitive processes are being used by the test participants
- c) Validity evidence based on internal structure – evidence that the hypothesised dimensionality (factor structure) is consistent with the theory underlying the assessment and, evidence regarding measurement invariance across source and target language (and subgroups)
- d) Validity evidence based on relations to other variables – evidence that the scores from the assessment display the hypothesised relationships with the other variables in a way that is consistent with the construct theory
- e) Validity evidence based on testing consequences – evidence that the intended consequences are occurring and that any unintended negative consequences are absent or minimised

(AERA et al., 2014)

This endeavour is a continuous process which requires the updating of evidence to support the inferences which are drawn from the assessment as it is used in an ongoing fashion. It is critical to note that not all five sources of evidence are required for every purpose and there is no ‘index of validity’ that needs to be reported. Rather, this corpus of evidence allows for consideration of all the facts and circumstances under which a comprehensive portfolio of evidence can be gathered to justify or defend the claims made and inferences rendered by using the assessment.

Valid assessments are imperative to measure the extent to which systems are achieving the goals and indicators that the system is tasked to deliver. In this case, these goals are captured in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) and a measurement framework has been established to enable evidence to be collected regarding how the education system is performing in relation to these goals. Given the importance of whether the measures really are assessing what they are supposed to assess, the next section examines the measurement framework that is used to align the goals of education to Key Performance Measures (KPMs)

2.2.1 Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia

At present, the relative performance of the Australian K-12 school system is judged against the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a). It measures student participation, achievement, and attainment and uses these as evidence regarding how well the national system is performing relative to the national Key Performance Measures (KPM). These KPMs were initially developed to align with the eight commitments to action outlined in the Melbourne Declaration, COAG targets and indicators outlined on state-level reporting frameworks (Tognolini & Mowbray, 2019). A later iteration of the Declaration was agreed, known as the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Declaration (Education Council, 2019).

2.2.2 Key Performance Measures

The KPMs outlined in the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a) are as follows:

1. Student Participation which is measured annually by “attendance (by rate and level), NAPLAN participation, retention rate (Year 10 to 12), participation of young people aged 15 to 19 years in Vocational Education and Training (VET), proportion of 15 to 19 year-olds in full-time education or training or work or both, proportion of 20 to 24 year-olds in full-time education or training or work or both, proportion of 17 to 24-year-olds who have left school that are in full-time education or training or work or both” (ACARA, 2020a, p.10). In addition, enrolment is measured quinquennially.
2. Student achievement: NAP – Literacy which is measured annually by the “proportion of students in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9 achieving (i) at or above minimum standards for reading, (ii) at or above the national proficient standard for reading, (iii) at or above the national highly proficient standard for reading; NAPLAN mean scale scores for reading in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9; proportion of students in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9 achieving (i) at or above the national minimum standard for writing, (ii) at or above the national proficient standard for writing, (iii) at or above the national highly proficient standard for writing; NAPLAN mean scale scores for writing in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9; proportion of participating 15 year-old students achieving at or above the proficient standard (Level 3) on the OECD PISA combined reading scale triennially; proportion of participating Year 4 students achieving at or above the proficient standard (Intermediate) in PIRLS quinquennially” (ACARA, 2020a, p.11).
3. Student Achievement: NAP – Numeracy which is measured by the “proportion of students in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9 achieving: (i) at or above the national minimum standard for numeracy; (ii) at or above the national proficient standard for numeracy;

- (iii) at or above the national highly proficient standard for numeracy; NAPLAN mean scale scores for numeracy in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9 ; proportion of participating 15 year-old students achieving at or above the national proficient standard (Level 3) on the OECD PISA combined mathematics scale triennially; proportion of participating students in Years 4 and 8 achieving at or above the national proficient standard (Intermediate) on the TIMSS mathematics scales quadrennially” (ACARA, 2020a, p.12).
4. Student Achievement: NAP – Science which is measured triennially or quadrennially by the “proportion of participating students in Years 6 and 10 achieving at or above the proficient standard in Science Literacy, proportion of participating 15 year-old students achieving at or above the national proficient standard (Level 3) on the OECD PISA combined scientific literacy scale, proportion of participating students in Year 4 and 8 achieving at or above the proficient standard (Intermediate) on the TIMSS science scales” (ACARA, 2020a, p. 13).
 5. Student Achievement: NAP – Civics and Citizenship which is measured triennially by the proportion of participating students in Years 6 and 10 achieving at or above the proficient standard in Civics and Citizenship (ACARA, 2020a, p. 13).
 6. Student achievement: NAP – Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Literacy which is measured triennially by the proportion of participating students in Years 6 and 10 achieving at or above the proficient standard in ICT Literacy (ACARA, 2020a, p. 13).
 7. Student attainment which is measured annually (and quinquennially through the Census of Population and Housing) by the proportion of the 20–24 year-old population having attained at least Year 12 or equivalent or AQF Certificate II or above, and proportion of the 20–24 year-old population having attained at least Year 12 or equivalent or AQF Certificate III or above (ACARA, 2020a, p. 14).

As seen in the KPMs, the measures of success for the Australian education system are linked to standards set by performance on the ILSA programmes (PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS). The measures fall into three categories: National Assessments, International and Standardised Census Data. The next section outlines each in the national and international categories.

2.2.3 National Assessment Program

The NAP (ACARA, 2011a) provides measures by which governments, education authorities and schools can determine whether young Australians are meeting important educational outcomes. The NAP, which is under the remit of the Australian Education Senior Officials Committee (AESOC) and operationalised by ACARA, includes the following assessments: National Assessment Program – Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN), NAP Sample Assessments in Science Literacy, in ICT Literacy and Civics and Citizenship, TIMSS, PIRLS and PISA. The next section will describe the characteristics of the assessments included in the NAP and associated Measurement Framework. Further detail on each assessment will later be explored in Chapter 6 with relation to their validity.

2.2.3.1 National Assessment Program: Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN)

NAPLAN is an annual assessment for all Australian students in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9 of school which informs the achievement of the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia against KPM 1, 2 and 3 (ACARA, 2020a). Students sit tests to measure their basic skill levels in Reading, Writing, Spelling, Grammar & Punctuation, and Numeracy. NAPLAN is delivered in every state and territory of Australia and in 2018, the digital version of NAPLAN online was introduced. Since 2023, all Australian schools can undertake a digital version of the assessment using NAPLAN online. NAPLAN results are reported directly to the student and school, and in addition, school results are published on the *My School* website by ACARA (ACARA, 2023f).

In 2023, there were two significant changes to the administration of NAPLAN beyond the full digital implementation. Firstly, the results and reporting of NAPLAN changed. From 2008 to 2022, NAPLAN results were reported on a 10-band scale and compared to national minimum standards (ACARA, 2023b). Since 2023, the results are reported using proficiency standards and student achievement is rated against four levels of proficiency: exceeding, strong, developing, and needs additional support (ACARA, 2023c). Secondly, the timing of NAPLAN's administration was shifted from Term 2 (May) of the school year to Term 1 (March). In 2023, the NAPLAN testing took place between the 15th and 27th of March 2023. For most states and territories this represents the seventh week of the new school year. Interestingly, by contrast the OECD Technical Guidelines for PISA restrict participation in the first six weeks of the academic year due to learning losses during the extended summer break from school (OECD, 2020). ACARA's former CEO, David de Carvalho explained the ministers' motivation for agreeing to the move as being so that results would be available earlier in the academic year to better inform teaching and learning programs, thus providing students with the support they need in the year it was identified (ACARA, 2023d). NAPLAN is a key component of the measurement framework but only provides evidence for literacy and numeracy indicators. The validity of NAPLAN as a measurement tool is explored in Chapter 6.

2.2.3.2 NAP Sample Tests

Australian Students also participate in the NAP sample tests which were developed using the national statements of learning to test Science, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Civics and Citizenship. The sample tests are completed by groups of students in Year 6 and Year 10 on a triennial cycle. The results are not shared with individual students. A school report is shared with the principal and a national report is shared with the public and governing bodies across Australia. These tests align with the national curriculum content and some of the goals for schooling agreed in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019).

The current performance data from the NAP tests is elaborated upon and a detailed link to validity is shared in Chapter 6.

2.2.3.3 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS)

The first international measure included in the NAP is the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS). TIMSS was established in 1995 and delivers an assessment of Mathematics and Science to students in Year 4 and Year 8, every four years. Australia has participated in TIMSS since its inception. There are currently 60 countries who participate in the international assessment which is run globally by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) in Boston, USA with the support of UNESCO. Further detail on Australia's performance in TIMSS and an exploration of its validity for this context are examined in Chapter 6.

2.2.3.4 Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS)

The Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) is a global assessment of Reading Literacy. It has been delivered every five years since 2001. There are currently 60 countries who participate in the international assessment which is run globally by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) in Boston, USA with the support of UNESCO. Australia has participated in PIRLS since 2011 with a sample of Year 4 students taking part but it is not formally part of the NAP (ACARA, 2011a). However, it is included here as it is referenced in national education policy, administered in an ongoing fashion and the interpretation of its results are typically bundled with PISA and TIMSS to paint a national portrait of performance. Further links to validity and Australia's goals for schooling including data on performance are provided in Chapter 6.

2.2.3.5 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA)

Students aged between 15 years 3 months and 16 years 2 months of age who are enrolled in an educational institution at Grade 7 or higher are eligible to be included in the sample of students who sit the PISA assessment on behalf of their country. Member and partner countries of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) participate in the survey that has occurred triennially since the year 2000. It assesses students nearing the end of their compulsory schooling in three areas: Mathematics, Science and Reading literacy by examining their ability to apply the knowledge acquired at school to real-world problems. The results are then reported by providing a rank order amongst the countries taking part (Thomson, Hillman & De Bortoli, 2013; Davis, 2019; Davis & Wilson, 2019; Pokropek, Marks & Borgonovi, 2022). PISA results for each country are scaled scores that represent degrees of proficiency in a particular domain. Interestingly, the definition of literacy in PISA is very similar to definitions of general intelligence (g). Literacy in reading, mathematics or science is “concerned with the capacity of students to apply knowledge and skills in key subject areas and to analyse, reason and communicate effectively as they pose, solve and interpret problems in a variety of situations” (OECD, 2007, p.16). Rather than focusing on the Australian Curriculum, or that of any other nation for that matter, PISA is a competency-based assessment that seeks to measure the preparedness of students to face real-life problems (OECD, 1999; OECD, 2000a; OECD, 2003; OECD, 2006; Thomson et al., 2013; Davis & Wilson, 2019).

Interestingly, while other international assessments focus on assessing overlapping content of national curricula, PISA evaluates the participating countries’ agreed desired outcomes of schooling (Adams, 2003). In addition to the domain testing, PISA uses a range of surveys and questions to explore additional educational outcomes such as student engagement, motivation, attitudes to learning and career aspirations. (Hatzinikita, Dimopoulos & Christidou, 2008).

Principals are questioned on their school's level of resourcing, staff qualifications, school culture and staff morale (Thomson et al., 2013).

Australia has taken part in the PISA testing since its inauguration in 2000 and it forms a key component of how the success of the Australian education system is measured. Performance in PISA is reported by the procured national provider, the Australian Council for Educational Research (ACER), and showcases how well students in different demographics and school sectors are performing (Department of Education, Skills and Employment, 2020). The Department of Education, Skills and Employment (2020) explain that PISA forms an integral part of the National Assessment Program as it provides an opportunity to monitor the Australian education system and equity across all states and territories.

The OECD, founded in the aftermath of World War II as part of the Marshall Plan to rebuild Europe, now dominates educational policy research globally. Wilby (2014) states that the OECD has a stronger influence on data generation and analysis than other institution. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) has been delivered for more than twenty years and has been criticized by researchers around the world for just as long (Baird et al., 2016; Baroutsis & Lingard, 2017; Bieber & Martens, 2011; Figazzolo, 2009; Hopfenbeck et al., 2018; Hopmann et al., 2007; Labaree, 2014; Lewis, 2017; Meyer & Benavot, 2013; Morrison, 2013; Rutkowski & Rutkowski 2016; Sahlberg, 2011; Sjøberg, 2015b; Stewart, 2013; Zhao, 2020). Yet, even in the face of global criticism from academics, the power of PISA continues to influence educational policy the world over. It is therefore imperative to consider the validity of its measure and how it is garnishing such influence. Zhao (2020) asserts that PISA exerts its influence by provoking the anxiety of stakeholders such as parents and politicians with three questions: "How well are young adults prepared to meet the challenges of the future? Are they able to analyse, reason and communicate their ideas effectively? Do they have the capacity to continue learning throughout life?" (OECD, 1999, p.7).

The results of PISA have been interpreted as a “valid measure of quality education systems” and used to make policy recommendations accordingly (Loveless, 2013). Interestingly, this declaration of validity is frequently echoed without a robust explanation of what makes it so. Is PISA valid because we are told it is so? As a classroom teacher without a deep working knowledge of psychometrics, how can one know? Zhao (2020) strongly asserts that “PISA treats economic growth and competitiveness as the sole purpose of education” and that “purpose of education in many countries includes a lot more than preparing economic beings” (p.252). Whilst the role of schools as doing so much more than preparing economic beings is beyond doubt (Masters, 2019), both things can be true at the same time. If PISA defines the purpose of education as preparing for future economic prosperity (Sjøberg, 2015a; Dall, 2011) and designs its measure accordingly, then the interpretation of the results must be viewed through that same lens. Issues of validity arise when a measurement instrument designed to measure a particular construct is used in an unintended way. Considering this, can an assessment designed with a view of schools as engineers of economic prosperity be used to determine the quality of a school that views itself as so much more than that? If so, how does this align with the agreed goals for schooling in Australia as outlined in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019)? Any misalignment will impact the validity of the results used to determine success.

2.3 Policy

Every education system is rooted in politics. This study is situated at the convergence of the interplay between the education system, the needs of the society it seeks to serve, the tools used to measure its efficacy and the powerful forces exerted upon it and by it. It is impossible to evaluate the performance of an education system without measuring its success against the needs and wants of the society in which it is embedded, an understanding of the relationship between them is essential. Fan and Popkewitz (2020) state that “modern education entails a continually complex set of relations with society” (p.v). Analysis of the policy documents in conjunction

with the National Assessment Program (ACARA, 2011a) and the goals for schooling as agreed in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) offers an understanding of whether Australia is measuring what matters. Key to the success of this is the ability to identify the gaps and the silences in the discourse.

2.3.1 Politics and Funding

This section considers the link between policy, power and funding to complete the picture of where we are now. The federated system in Australia gives way to a disjointed governance over schools and the ‘funding wars,’ as they have come to be known in Australia, have been fiercely debated for the past fifty years (Goss & Sonnemann, 2016). Federalism provides a challenging context for schools to operate within. Education traditionally falls within the remit of the State and Territory governments in Australia, yet in recent times an exertion of control has been apparent from the Federal government by way of changes to funding (Cranston et al., 2010).

In the United States of America, Chomsky and Polychroniou (2021) signalled the 1970s as the transition point from regulated capitalism to ‘incipient neoliberalism’ (p.130). Interestingly, they argue that there is no economic reason as to why we could not see free education flourish. Rather, the barriers are all political decisions based on the inequity of wealth and power. Barriers, however, that Chomsky and Polychroniou (2021) believe ‘can be overcome’ (p.131). During the 1970s in Australia, the Labor Government led by Whitlam brought an end to Australia’s centralised education system in the pursuit of greater access and equity (Cranston et al., 2010). In embracing a social democratic approach, the Karmel (1973) report was central to this reform. This report was prepared by the Interim Committee for the Australian Schools Commission and their goal was to review the K-12 schools of Australia and to make recommendations related to their financial needs. This report marks a seminal shift in the way Australian schools are funded.

The following decade brought with it a more market-driven approach to school-based management (Cranston et al., 2010). It can be argued that this coincided with a move from social mobility to social efficiency as schools were charged with planning and reporting on changes in student performance (Cranston et al., 2010). With the move from the centralist government of Whitlam in the 1970s to Fraser's decentralist, coalition government of the 1980s, a need to reduce the federal budget deficit resulted in greater privatisation of schools and devolution of responsibility to the States and Territories (Fletcher & Walsh, 1992; Smart, 1985).

In 1980, Prime Minister Fraser established a Review of Commonwealth Functions Committee (Wood, 1982). The Committee was tasked with cost reduction and in their report dated May 1981, they identified 350 tasks that could be eliminated, reduced, or transferred to other levels of government (Solomon, 1981). During these cuts, the Commonwealth's key educational research and curriculum development bodies were abolished, and the Schools Commission was weakened (Cranston et al., 2010). However, it was not until Hawke's leadership that Australia took an approach to corporate federalism by placing the education system at the centre of its economic restructuring (Lingard, 1993; Knight & Warry, 1996).

During the Hawke and then Keating era of Australian politics, education was positioned front and centre as a tool for the nation's economic prosperity and as such, informed all future educational policies accordingly (Cranston et al., 2010). That was, until another policy shift occurred and a subsequent move from a focus on the local towards international competition (Knight & Warry, 1996). Equity and access, whilst remaining a focal point, were now framed through the lens of social efficiency (Cranston et al., 2010).

During Howard's tenure as Prime Minister (1996 to 2007), his government narrowed the agenda to further align the education system with economic outcomes (Cranston et al., 2010). As the perceived contribution of educational outcomes to economic prosperity grew, the Federal government sought a greater role in governing schools and their agenda, tipping the balance of

power away from the States and Territories in favour of Commonwealth control (Cranston et al., 2010; Parkin & Anderson, 2007). David Kemp, Australia's federal education minister between 1996 and 2001, argued that primary schools were bereft of sufficient time to focus on literacy and numeracy thanks to an over-crowded curriculum (Knight & Warry, 1996). So began the crisis rhetoric which continues to pervade Australia's education system via the media today (Hare, 2023; Cassidy, 2023a).

Responding to the call to action, in 2008 the Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training and Youth Affairs (MCEETYA) launched Australia's "National Literacy and Numeracy Strategy" with national benchmarks and testing introduced (Cranston et al., 2010). The Howard government shifted educational policy away from progressive liberalism to showcase education as a means for social advancement in an Australia society that was becoming increasingly aspirational (Cranston et al., 2010). Where Hawke's funding model was designed to provide funding to those schools that needed it most, Howard favoured a postcode approach based on the income of parents (Stewart, 2005). A shift in funding alongside the removed cap on the number of new schools in 1997 saw the growth of the non-government schools in Australia (Meadmore, 2001). This represented a move to parents as consumers of education rather than stakeholders in it. A shift congruent with increased competitive tension and performance-related stressors for educators. Suddenly schools began hiring business managers, marketing consultants and school principals became CEOs (English, 2005). Yet, throughout this period, schools remained the mandate of the State and Territory governments whilst the Federal government provided grant funding aligned to the pursuit of key policy targets.

In 2007, the Federal government invested more than \$140 million towards schools with most going to government schools, thus representing a massive overstep into the jurisdiction of the States and Territories (Cranston et al., 2010). In the same year, Howard's Liberal party, and Rudd's Labor party both campaigned to win government on calls for a national curriculum

(Cranston et al., 2010). Prior to losing government, the Howard government replaced all state-based assessments with national tests of literacy and numeracy. From May 2008, census tests of all students, at all Australian schools from Years 3, 5, 7 and 9 were introduced (Harrington, 2008). At the first COAG meeting following Rudd taking office as Prime Minister of Australia the minutes reflect education being listed as a key part of the productivity agenda, demonstrating a continued focus on economic prosperity through education despite the change of power (Cranston et al., 2010). After winning the election, Rudd moved forward with his promised “education revolution” and a mission to make reporting and assessment more transparent (Mockler, 2013; Australian Government Department of Education Employment and Workplace Relations, 2010).

The last fifty years have demonstrated a narrowing of Australia’s educational agenda and a much greater focus on competition, performance, testing and reporting. During this time, Australian schools were increasingly privatised whilst the OECD reports Australia as falling below average in terms of its spending on public education according to Marginson (2007). In a media publication, Henebery (2023) reported that the most recent OECD report found that Australia spends “just 1.5% of total government expenditure on upper secondary school education, 28.6% lower than the OECD average of 2.1%. This is despite spending more than twice as much as the OECD average on funding private schools” (para. 2). So, the convoluted funding wars are symptomatic of the power alignment between education policy and the economic prosperity of the nation. However, in the most recent OECD (2022) report, Australia’s overall expenditure on primary to tertiary education as a share of national wealth is high by international comparison, at 6.1% of gross domestic product (GDP) in 2019 (OECD average: 4.9%). General upper secondary expenditure is shown at the OECD average whilst expenditure on vocational education in Australia is low (OECD, 2022). This example highlights the influence of the media in shaping the rhetoric based on such international data.

Cranston et al. (2010) argue that over time the public purposes of schooling have become less prominent and that Australian governments have prioritised private purposes instead. Labaree (1997) asserts that the democratic equality policies formed by Whitlam's Labor government of the 1970s have long been pushed aside in favour of social mobility and efficiency by both Labor and Liberal parties.

To best understand what success looks like for the Australian education system, it is imperative that the goals for schooling align with what matters to Australians as a society (Ratner, 2022). This is best articulated in our public policy documents. In the opening statement of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019), Australia's education ministers express the imperative for every student to realise their potential by providing them with the skills they need to participate in the economy and in society and in contributing to every aspect of their wellbeing. Yet, whilst the goals for schooling may address shared desires for students to be healthy, active, and well-informed global citizens capable of creative thinking and problem solving, it is their ability to contribute to Australia's economic prosperity which is an enduring driving force when it comes to Australian education policy (Ratner, 2022).

2.3.2. Human Capital Argument

Becker (1964) defined human capital broadly to include the knowledge, skills, values, and habits that people develop (Levin, 2012). This led to an economic view of the world which Becker hoped would lead to greater investment in people. In a Ryseron lecture, almost a quarter of a century after the publication of Becker's (1964) book on Human Capital, great pains were taken to explain that capital is about so much more than money. Education is capital too as it helps "improve health, raise earnings, or add to a person's appreciation of literature over much of their lifetime" (Becker, 1994, p.15). Therefore, any money spent on education is an investment in capital, the returns on which are embodied in the members of the society. Becker (1994) believes that of any investment in human capital, money spent on education and training offers the

greatest return. Becker concludes the Ryerson lecture by reflecting on the goals of human capital analysis as being to improve the workforce through education and to understand the economic and social world better (Becker, 1994). The proximity between education and work has always been close and schooling in Australia is openly viewed as the foundation for the future economic sustainability of the nation. It is perhaps for this reason that PISA, administered by the OECD triennially since the year 2000, resonates so strongly with the human capital argument favoured by education policy makers and politicians (Hanushek, 2013; Hanushek & Woessmann, 2015). In fact, the OECD PISA rankings led to Australian headlines such as “Students’ falling test scores costing the nation \$120b in lost GDP” (Robinson, 2018, p.1). Many conceptions of successful school systems are underpinned by assumptions that the economic viability of the nation is predicated upon system-wide success and that the benchmark of success is delivered through the academic performance of its young people on an international, comparative assessment (Levin, 2012). The human capital argument is also evident in proclamations that the decline of Australia’s education system and the demise of its results will negatively impact our future economic prosperity as a nation (Mrozowska, 2020). This implies that a successful education system in Australia is represented by a prosperous nation and high gross domestic product (GDP). So, perhaps we should start measuring the success of the school system by employment rates and GDP?

When it comes to the human capital argument, Levin (2009) calculated that preventing one student from dropping out of high school contributes USD 200,000 to the society over the course of that student’s life. In addition to this, in a society with a “more educated population the economy grows faster” (William, 2018, p.12). Considering this research, thoughts turn to the further impact of inserting the word quality into such a sentence. Is being educated enough or does the quality of that education serve to make an exponential difference? Hanushek and Woessmann (2015) believe so. They calculated that, based on recent results in PISA, if the USA

could ensure every 15-year-old student achieved minimum standards in reading and mathematics it would add USD 30 trillion to the economy.

Woodhall (1997) defines human capital as “the fact that human beings invest in themselves by means of education, training, or other activities, which raises their future income by increasing their lifetime earnings” (p. 219). Human capital theory has proven useful in affording governments the opportunity to conduct a cost-benefit analysis of their investment in education. The OECD (2012b) categorically asserts that investing in high quality schooling and equal opportunities for all from the early years of nursery to the end of upper secondary is “the most profitable education policy” (p.3). Many conceptions regarding successful school systems are underpinned by the assumption that the economic viability of the nation is predicated upon it and that the benchmark of success is delivered through the academic performance of its young people on an international, comparative assessment (Levin, 2012).

2.3.3 Data and Evidence

Funding policies are a valuable source of evidence as to what really matters to a society. Where and how the public dollar is spent says a great deal about the values and priorities of the society. The funding offered to government and non-government schools across Australia is provided to cover the cost of achieving federal priorities for schooling which include access, choice, equity, and excellence (Harrington, 2010). In 2023, this included \$10.8 billion to government schools and \$17.4 billion to non-government schools (Clark & Harrington, 2023).

At present, PISA is regarded as the gold-standard instrument for the evaluation of how well education systems are performing globally and is believed to have the capacity to shape education systems (Breakspear, 2014). The continuing decline in Australia’s results has dominated the media and driven lengthy discussion amongst educators, policy makers, parents, and politicians (Baroutsis & Lingard, 2017; Browne, 2012; Buckingham, 2004; Waldow,

Takayama & Sung, 2014). Amidst a conversation that is charged with the pursuit of system-wide improvement and the unashamed goal of lifting standards within Australian schools, this thesis is both timely and necessary.

The primary purpose of assessment in Australian classrooms is the collection of data to inform decisions. Whether those decisions relate to individual students, classes, schools, or the system, it is agreed that data and evidence are required to make informed judgements (Wyatt-Smith, Adie & Harris, 2024). Critically, that evidence must be generated from multiple sources of data. When educators engage with valid and reliable data that is suited to the task at hand, they are empowered with the information needed to inform policy and improve student learning (Tognolini & Mowbray, 2019).

Gathering data, whether via student interview or summative test, the result tells us very little until they are analysed, interpreted, and reported in a format through which educators can make evidence-based, informed, professional judgements. This is not just limited to standardised assessments; it applies to school-based and teacher-created tests as well. No matter what data one may be using, the process starts with knowing what data are being sought, why and how they will be used (Tognolini & Mowbray, 2019). To understand what data are sought and why, it is vital to first know what is important for Australian schools. The measures of system-wide success must align with those goals which the school system is setting out to achieve.

Anyone who has worked in, attended, or sent a child to a school knows that the success of a school system, is far more than its scores on a given test at a moment in time (Masters, 2019). Key Performance Measures (KPMs) are the tools with which we can perform a health check on Australian schooling. Currently, the Australian education system measures three areas that were drawn from the Melbourne Declaration: participation, achievement, and attainment (ACARA, 2019a; MCEETYA, 2008). Yet, it is evident that Australian schools are much more than the outcomes currently being reported. Rather than results in standardised tests and

examinations, it is the stories behind those learning achievements and the growth students have achieved that truly indicate a school's success (Wyatt-Smith, 2014). It appears this has been forgotten when discussing the success of Australian schools at the macro level.

2.3.4 Review to Achieve Educational Excellence

The Review to Achieve Educational Excellence in Australian Schools, known locally as the Gonski Review, stated that Australia has an excellent education system but that its results are plateauing or declining (Gonski et al., 2018). The problem with this is the absence of an agreed definition of excellence in the Australian context. To lay claim to the excellence of the education system requires one to first ask, what does excellence look like and according to what measure of success? For a system, or anything else to be deemed excellent it must be compared to a prior description or standard of what constitutes excellence. To what and to whose standard is Australia's school system being judged against, to label it as excellent or otherwise? It is imperative that we seek the evidence to support such claims and clearly define what excellence means in the context of Australian schooling. Every education system can and should establish criteria for excellence and then measure itself against these criteria to provide evidence and accountability to its key stakeholders – policy makers, leaders, students, teachers, and parents.

2.3.5 National Report on Schooling

The National Report on Schooling was first published in 1989 by the Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training and Youth Affairs (MCEETYA) as a joint annual report on schooling and in 2021, the 33rd edition was released (ACARA, 2023g). The report is prepared on behalf of the education ministers from every state and territory across the federation to update the nation on its progress towards achieving the eleven commitments made in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) against the KPM articulated in the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a). The National Report on Schooling 2021 (ACARA,

2023g) consists of two parts: the written report and the online data portal which provides open access to data including enrolment, staffing, funding and the key performance measure results for student participation, NAP achievement and attainment levels at Year 12 and post-compulsory schooling.

2.3.6 National Education Reform Agreement

The National Education Reform Agreement (Council of Australian Governments, 2013) recognised the integral relationship between quality schooling and community engagement to ensure Australia's economic prosperity and social cohesion. It was instigated by the Council of Australian Governments (COAG), which includes the Commonwealth of Australia (the Commonwealth); and the States and Territories, being: New South Wales; Victoria; Queensland; Western Australia; South Australia; Tasmania; Australian Capital Territory and Northern Territory. The agreement links the allocation of funding to the outcomes it outlines to ensure their reforms are enacted and enabled to drive school improvement across the nation. This policy is located within the consortium of the Melbourne Declaration on Educational Goals for Young Australians (MCEETYA, 2008) and the 2008 National Education Agreement (Steering Committee for the Review of Government Service Provision, 2009).

Interestingly, the basis of these policies was to achieve the national goal that by 2025, Australia would be regarded as one of the top five countries in reading, mathematics, and science based on the PISA rankings. A goal which has since been removed in later iterations of the policy. At the conclusion of the National Education Reform Agreement (COAG, 2013), it defines the top five countries as according to the definitions of the OECD and PISA. It is clear that Australia is consenting to PISA authority as the arbiter of system-wide success. Thomson (2013) believes that to achieve the goal of being in the top five by 2025 we need to focus efforts on lifting the performance of the weakest, most disadvantaged and underprivileged students. Most educators would support such efforts to reduce the gap between the most and least advantaged in

Australian schools as a necessary pursuit. However, in considering the goal of achieving top five status, it seems arbitrary. Let's hypothesise for a moment that across the world system-wide performance fell and Australia's performance remained consistent. In that scenario, Australia could achieve its target of being a top 5 country but there has been no substantive improvement in terms of the education goals that set the standards for performance in Australian schools. A fact that was proven in the PISA 2022 results which were released on 5 December 2023.

Australia found itself in the top ten globally as other countries had performed so poorly, yet the Australian results were still trending downwards (Cassidy, 2023b; De Bortoli, Underwood & Thomson, 2023).

2.3.7 National School Reform Agreement

The National School Reform Agreement (NSRA) is a joint agreement between the Commonwealth, States and Territories that has been designed to lift student outcomes across Australian schools. It outlines a set of strategic reforms in areas where national collaboration will have the greatest impact to build on current national reform efforts, complement state/territory leadership, and support local implementation. The ongoing implementation of these shared commitments remains a condition of funding under the Australian Education Act (2013). The NSRA was drafted in 2018 in alignment with the Quality Schools funding package which injected AUD 319 billion into Australia's K-12 school system as a reaction to the fall in Australia's performance as measured on international testing such as PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS.

In articulating the reforms for national school improvement, COAG (2013) consistently refer to meeting the national goal of ranking in the top 5 countries by 2025. However, of note, the 2018 version of the National School Reform Agreement (NSRA) has removed Australia's planned ascent in the PISA league tables from its targets. Instead, the updated NSRA (Department of Education and Training, 2018) is more focused upon excellence and equity. Recognising the diversity of each state and territory in conjunction with the complexity of the

world in which young Australians find themselves, COAG aspires for all Australian students to become ‘successful learners, confident and creative individuals, and active and informed citizens’ (Department of Education and Training, 2018).

On the 7th of April 2022, Treasurer Josh Frydenberg requested that the Productivity Commission undertake a review with the aim of “making recommendations to inform the design of the next intergovernmental school reform agreement and improvements to the National Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia” (Australian Government Productivity Commission, 2022, p.v). The report arising from the review was expected to examine the effectiveness and appropriateness of the National Policy Initiatives included in the agreement, and the appropriateness of the national Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia in measuring progress towards outcomes. Importantly, the Commission was also asked to make recommendations to inform the design of the next school reform agreement with the objective of providing “high quality and equitable education for all students” (Australian Government Productivity Commission, 2022, p.v). Three reform directions were proposed in the report which included eight national policies and agreements that are context specific for each state and territory.

The three agreed outcomes for Australian schooling are: achievement, attainment, and engagement (Australian Government Productivity Commission, 2022). They are assessed against seven measures (five of which are achievement based, one attainment and one engagement) and three targets regarding lifting the educational attainment of Australian students, a specific target for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students and a final target to lift international standing by 2025 (p.4). The report on the achievement of the national plan was not complimentary. In fact, it states that “few of the sub-outcomes have been achieved” (Australian Government Productivity Commission, 2022, p.8). Moving forward there were three key recommendations proposed: “Parties should focus the next school reform agreement on directly lifting student

outcomes” (p.10), “adapt accountability mechanisms to reflect a greater role for state-specific actions” (p.10), and “specify basic content, process, and reporting requirements for bilateral agreement” (p.11).

The Productivity Commission received 127 submissions including one made by Wilson et al. (2022) on behalf of The University of Sydney Centre for Educational Measurement and Assessment (CEMA) in which it was proposed that there was poor alignment between the goals stated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) and the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a). Six recommendations were made including:

- 1) Develop and make explicit a framework for educational evaluation to specify how progress towards the national goals for schooling will be supported, evaluated, and shared.
- 2) Derive measures and indicators from the national goals and map existing measures against them to fill the gaps.
- 3) Strengthen the analysis, reporting and transparency on equity and report on all groups longitudinally (10 years +).
- 4) Appoint an independent national body to oversee the design, management, operationalisation, and reporting of the national measurement framework.
- 5) Consult ALL stakeholders and bring them to the table when shaping and framing educational policy for the future.
- 6) Grant consideration to the work of teachers, their context, and their data literacy.

(CEMA Submission to the Productivity Commission, Wilson et al., 2022).

The Productivity Commission Review (2022) and submissions such as that made by Wilson et al (2022) reflect a shift in thinking which is set to reform how educational policy is shaped and formed with increased consultation from educators and stakeholders.

2.3.8 Policy makers, shapers, and announcers

On the 29th of March 2023, the current federal education minister for Australia, The Honourable Jason Clare MP announced the appointment of a panel of experts who would work to inform a better and fairer education system by guiding the development of the next iteration of the National School Reform Agreement (Productivity Commission, 2022). The panel has collected more than 100 submissions, and the final report is scheduled to be handed to ministers by 31 October 2023 (Clare, 2023). Further to this, in May 2023 the National School Reform Agreement Ministerial Reference Group was established. At a meeting that the Honourable Jason Clare MP chaired himself, the importance of the voice of the teacher and the student in educational policy making and review was made explicit (Department of Education, 2023). Engagement with key stakeholders in this way, enabling them to have a voice in Australia's education policy formation, will undoubtedly influence pedagogical practice in schools.

2.4 Putting it into Practice

Knowing how well students are currently performing and asking where to take them next is the core business of educators. They are valid questions worthy of time, interest, and pursuit. If, for example, Australian society consents to the authority of PISA as the global yardstick for success in schooling then the end-goals for the Australian school system must align to its definition of success. We can only do this with the requisite clarity as what kind of education system is most appropriate for all Australian children. As Australia progresses through its latest curriculum reform it is time to put the question of what matters to us as a society at the centre of the conversation. In Delors' (1996) report to UNESCO he proposed four pillars of education for the 21st century: learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together, and learning to be. What are the pillars of Australian education as we move forward and reimagine the future of schooling?

One of the most significant vehicles for the reproduction and transformation of power relations is language (Bourdieu, 1977; Pitsoe & Letseka, 2013). Therefore, it is essential to carefully examine what is being said or written but equally we must investigate the pauses, silences, and exclusions in the PISA data. The discourse surrounding Australian schools and education systems is increasingly constructed with a focus on PISA rankings and data (Lewis, 2017). It is for this reason that educators and researchers must become involved when it comes to interpreting and reporting on these studies. The use of PISA results to construct the school narrative is one thing, but the misuse is quite another (Hopfenbeck & Kjærnsli, 2016; Baird et al., 2016).

Labelling PISA as ‘global policymaking apparatus,’ Lewis (2020) speaks to the power of PISA and its presence in all school-systems across the world. The influence of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and PISA is frequently cited in research on national schooling systems (Breakspear, 2012; Lewis, 2017; Sellar & Lingard, 2014). As a result, the OECD is now regarded as the most influential intergovernmental organisation in education (Kofod et al., 2012). Such a role demands one to ask the following questions: To what extent has PISA informed educational policy and reform in Australia over the past 20 years? How can PISA data best be used to support the generation of a growth trajectory for Australian schools? How can we defend against PISA data being misappropriated to justify or drive a political agenda that is antithesis to the Australian education system’s goals? Moving forward, it is essential that rather than borrowing policy from other nations or being driven by the OECD’s consented truth, Australian educators must establish their own truth and ensure that educational policies are aligned with the goals for Australian schooling agreed upon in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019).

2.4.1 Equity in Practice

UNESCO (2018) defines equity in education as the achievement of equality by ensuring every student has the best possible opportunity to reach their full potential. The equity gap and growing disparity between socioeconomic classes continues to drive a strong commitment to the idea that schools are the engine of social mobility and change (Carpiano, Link, & Phelan, 2008; Flessa, Gallagher-Mackay & Parker, 2010; Green & Kesselman, 2006; Lin & Harris, 2008).

Schools may play a critical role in addressing the outcomes of the equity gap, but we cannot fall into the trap of accepting them as being responsible for it (Rothstein, 2008). Some feel that the role of schooling is in part to address the poverty cycle, seeking to explore how that may have been perpetuated in the past and most importantly, now broken, moving forward. Whilst policies such as the “No Child Left Behind Act” in the USA seek to identify achievement gaps caused by race, class, language and individual need, there are also many examples of schools and learners who are achieving better than expected and one must ask why they are outperforming others despite their common challenging experiences (Flessa, Gallagher-Mackay & Parker, 2010; Pederson, 2007). It is perhaps this learning that will support education systems to improve the most. What are these schools doing to help their students outperform those in similar schools? Learning from schools such as these provides a rich and valuable opportunity for school improvement.

Closing the equity gap whilst raising standards for all, remains a focus in the NSRA with reference made to additional policies including the National Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Education Strategy (Education Council, 2015) and the National Indigenous Reform Agreement (SCRGSP, 2019). Since the previous version of the NSRA in 2013, several reviews were completed and informed these policies such as the Review to Achieve Educational Excellence in Australian Schools (Gonski et al., 2018), the Independent Review into Regional, Rural and Remote Education (Halsey, 2018) and the STEM Partnerships Forum (Education Services

Australia, 2018). An interesting addition to the NSRA (Department of Education and Training, 2018) includes references to National Teaching Standards and Student Wellbeing. Whilst a significant omission of note from the NSRA (Department of Education and Training, 2018) is the lack of direct reference to PISA as a measure of system-wide success or the achievement of national goals. It appears that when it comes to the evolution of education policy there is as much importance in the omissions as there is in the additions (Bacchi, 2009; Foucault, 1977; Hastings, 1998).

Another omission of note is the exclusion of students from PISA, which is problematic (Hopfenbeck et al., 2018). Up to 5% of students (with certain characteristics) may be excluded from participating in the assessment although many education systems frequently surpass this figure (Rutkowski & Rutkowski, 2016). PISA allows for the exclusion of students with special educational needs and newly arrived immigrants which is concerning for the validity of the sample as it is then not truly indicative of the population being served by the education system (Araujo et al., 2017; Wuttke, 2007). The *PISA Technical Guidelines 2022* (OECD, 2020), explain that students should be excluded from participation for the following reasons: ‘they are functionally disabled in such a way that they cannot take the PISA test’, ‘they have a cognitive, behavioural or emotional disability confirmed by qualified staff, meaning they cannot take the PISA test’, ‘they have insufficient assessment language experience to take the PISA test’, ‘there are no materials available in the language in which the student is taught’, ‘they cannot be assessed for some other reason as agreed upon’ (p.27). These exclusions and thus drawing inferences from the data about populations and comparing performances challenges the validity of the results and the way they are being interpreted (Micklewright, Schnepf & Skinner, 2012).

The World Health Organisation (2023) reports that 1.3 billion people experience significant disability. This represents 16% of the global population. Article 24 of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNICEF, 2020) states:

Parties recognize the right of persons with disabilities to education. With a view to realizing this right without discrimination and on the basis of equal opportunity, Parties shall ensure an inclusive education system at all levels and lifelong learning (para 1).

Therefore, education systems are to be designed to meet the needs of every child. An education system can therefore not be deemed to be excellent if the measure used to declare it so excludes the most vulnerable amongst its population. The exclusion of students with disabilities and/or additional learning needs from the PISA sample is concerning from the perspective of validity. PISA aims to measure the quality of education systems, and excludes students with special needs (Schuelka, 2013). The OECD (2014) refers to itself as providing ‘the world’s premier yardstick for evaluating the quality, equity, and efficiency of school systems’ (p.2). Carnoy et al. (2015) argue that properly using information from an international test comparison also involves interpreting test results as reflective of deep social inequalities.

There are currently circa 250 million children out of school around the world for a range of reasons (UNESCO, 2023a). It is widely acknowledged that most school systems have children that are excluded from classrooms and who are not engaging meaningfully in formal learning (Florian & Rouse, 2009). Further to this, there are even more who are sitting in ‘failing’ schools or schools that fail to meet their needs. Whilst the OECD (2012b) asserts that equity and quality go hand in hand, when it comes to measuring the quality of global education systems the sample excludes so many children. A quality education system that meets the needs of its society must educate every child. Therefore, PISA is really a measure of the quality of the educational experience for able children who are actively engaged in their schooling. This calls into question the validity of the results unless the absence of these children is accurately reflected in the data.

In addition to the large numbers of children excluded from school for a variety of reasons, there is also shared global concern with the significant achievement gap between the top achievers and those who achieve least (OECD, 2012). Chmielewski (2019) studied thirty ILSA

over five decades which represented 100 countries and 5.8 million students. They found “strong and robust evidence of increasing SES achievement gaps over the past 50 years across the majority of countries examined” (p.537). Dealing with difference and diversity, whether it be social, emotional, behavioural or academic, continues to present significant challenges for inclusion (European Agency on the Development of Special Needs Education, 2005).

2.4.2 Excellence in Practice

Tognolini and Mowbray (2019) argue that researchers must investigate all available evidence relating to any issue to produce defensible decision making. This has never been more important than when assessing the success (or failure) of the Australian school system. Consider this, if the Australian education system were to achieve the level of excellence and equity defined and agreed in the shared, national goals for schooling, but still did not attain a top 5 spot in the PISA results, has the education system failed its young people? If it can be stated that the children are benefiting from equitable access to excellent facilities, excellent teachers, excellent learning opportunities and achieving excellent results across every school in Australia then does the PISA score matter? The answer is straightforward – it only matters if the PISA score is the agreed definition of excellence. Excellence must be defined more in terms of achievement of goals rather than a test score. Summarising a whole system’s performance and reducing it to a single test score, relative to the Declaration (Education Council, 2019), has the potential to undermine the whole system of education constructed by the Ministers and captured in the Declaration.

In 2013, the agreed objective of the Australian education system was agreed to be providing a high quality and equitable education for all students (COAG, 2013). Every subsequent educational policy has been designed to contribute to or measure progress towards the achievement of that objective. The four outcomes of these policies and endeavours are: excelling against international standards, transitioning from school to work/higher education

with ease, closing the gap between the most/least advantaged, and engaging all children in the benefits of schooling. COAG (2013) agreed to retain existing targets around the number of students completing Year 12 and reducing the gap in achievement between Indigenous and non-Indigenous populations. However, the National Education Reform saw the addition of new targets that included Australia being placed in the top 5 countries for Reading, Mathematics and Science by 2025, as well as being considered a high quality and high equity school system according to international standards. These outcomes and COAG targets are measured using performance indicators which shape Australia's National Assessment Plan. The key measures evolve from international assessments (PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS), Australian Qualifications Framework (AQF), NAPLAN and School attendance (COAG, 2013).

2.4.3 Quality in Practice

When it comes to education, too often quality is measured according to the abilities of the children (Munton et al., 1995). That is, if students are performing well on tests of individual student achievement the system is perceived to be delivering on quality. Moving away from the notion that “quality is what quality does” (Munton et al., 1995, p.12), a shared definition of quality must embrace the depth and breadth of what constitutes a quality educational experience. The features that are measured, identified, and contribute to quality are contested (Sheridan et al., 2009). Debate continues as to whether quality is an observable construct or a context-dependent, culturally defined experience (Klinkhammer & Schäfer, 2017; Fenech, 2011). In efforts to embrace the multidimensionality of quality in education, the following explanation is provided by Klinkhammer and Schäfer (2017),

Quality is viewed as a multi-perspective, discursive and modifiable construct while also referencing the classic quality model (input, output, outcome) central within the effectiveness/impact measurement approach, which in this reading is not based on rigid definitions of quality. Instead, it is recognized that the understanding of quality and its

creation in practice are not governed by strict principles but are dependent on their contexts and stakeholders in the broadest sense. (p. 11)

The earlier part of this chapter examined the measures used to determine the success of the Australian education system. However, quality cannot be reduced to a singular test score. In early childhood education, quality is referred to in terms of global quality (Association for Childhood Education International, 2006), pedagogical quality (Fonsén & Vlasov, 2017) and outcome quality (Sylva, 2010). The next section explores the definitions of quality as they pertain to the education system.

2.4.3.1. Global Quality

In a longitudinal study of early childhood education that was established in 1997, Sylva (2010) makes use of both the Early Childhood Environment Rating Scale – Revised (ECERS-R) (Harms et al., 1998) and the Early Children Environment Rating Scale – Extension (ECERS-E) (Sylva et al., 2003). The ECERS-R provides 43 items across seven sub-scales: space and furnishings, personal care routines, language-reasoning, activities, interaction, programme structure, and parents and staff. All these sub-scales are said to inform the global quality of the early childhood educational experience. It incorporates the structure and physical environment in which the learning is situated, ratio of carer to child, access to an array of activities, health, wellbeing, and the multi-dimensional nature of educating and caring for young children. Whilst limited to early childhood contexts, which are outside the remit of this study, this definition and associated measure of global quality is significant. It serves as a reminder that schools and their success are so much more than the academic gains of learners and their test scores. Schools are ecosystems of activity that ought to be measured accordingly.

2.4.3.2 Pedagogical Quality

By contrast, in early childhood education pedagogical quality is the focus of the ECERS-R (Sylva et al., 2003) which incorporates 18 items on four sub-scales: literacy, mathematics, science and diversity. Following a meta-analysis, Sheridan (2009) defined pedagogical quality as:

A multidimensional educational phenomenon in which interdependent dimensions and aspects constitute an environment that in different ways contributes to children's opportunities for learning and developing in educational settings. These dimensions and aspects are partly constituted of sustainable qualities and partly by dynamic and relative qualities that are inter-subjectively agreed on and subjectively conceived depending on perspective, time, and context. (p. 254)

The role of the learning context and the interrelatedness of the educational experience is paramount in the conception of pedagogical quality. Bronfenbrenner (1986) explains its foundation in the societal, political, and philosophical perspectives that will change over time. This is because according to Rogoff (2003), "human development is a process of people's changing participation in sociocultural activities of their communities.... As people develop through their shared use of cultural tools and practices, they simultaneously contribute to the transformation of cultural tools, practices, and institutions" (p. 52). This definition of pedagogical quality provides for a holistic approach to educational measurement which is well aligned to the goals of Australian schooling as articulated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019).

2.4.4 Influence of Context

The PISA, and assessments of a similar type, have set global education systems on a path leading to the homogenisation of processes and values (Carney et al., 2012; Lingard et al., 2015;

Sellar & Lingard, 2014; Sahlberg, 2012; Tröhler, 2013; Zhao & Gearin, 2016). Whilst there is a strong argument to be made for learning from other education systems of excellence (Zhao, 2020), every local context has its own needs, values and histories that cannot be denied.

An important learning with regards to improving education systems is that “everything works somewhere, and nothing works everywhere” (William, 2018, p.2) Before visiting the PISA policy library and borrowing the learnings of high performing educational contexts let us ask, how do we make the link between the high results of a particular country with the reasons for their success? Further to this, consideration should be given to the interventions that took place and when before any policy borrowing occurs. There is a Greek proverb that states, a society grows great when old men plant trees whose shade they know they shall never sit in. The same can be said of educational policy. Governments who reside for very short terms are charged with determining the outcomes of a system which they may not see the results of in their lifetime. When examining the actions of a high performing country the challenge is not to examine their current practice but to look back and ask, what policies and practices were implemented 10, 15, 20 years ago in this education system that we are observing the benefits of today in these 15-year-old students. What reading programs did they employ? What instructional strategies were engaged? Which mathematical approaches were utilised? How were they experienced across the nation? There are many factors that contribute to the success of children in the classroom. Hattie (2003) accounted for them as being chiefly influenced by factors relating to the student themselves (50%), followed by parental influence (30%), the home environment (10%) and then peers (5%) and the school (5%).

In a study of children from Eastern Asian backgrounds living in Australia, Jerrim (2015) reported that children of Chinese heritage in Australia performed better on PISA in 2012 than those living and attending schools in Shanghai. So, what drives the high performance of a

specific cultural group within a school system such as Australia that is an average performer according to the OECD results? Jerrim's (2015) findings investigate,

...how Australian children of East Asian heritage perform just as highly on the PISA maths test as children within the high-performing East Asian jurisdictions. This brings into question whether it really is the schooling system (and associated teaching methods) in these countries that are responsible for their dominance of the PISA and TIMSS rankings. Indeed, results suggest that making changes to the schooling system and teaching practices alone may be insufficient for Western countries to catch the top-performing East Asian nations. Rather, this goal may only be achieved with widespread cultural change, where a hard work ethic and a strong belief in the value of education is displayed by all families and instilled in every child. (p.21.)

With so much time and attention given to the results and outputs at the end of schooling it is worthwhile utilising the schools as a factory analogy to consider for a moment the inputs. To fairly measure the value-add of the Australian K-12 school system to the 15-year-old undertaking the PISA test, one must assume that they each commenced their journey at the same starting point. In one study of children's home lives before commencing school, Hart, Risley and Kirby (1997) found a difference of 25 million words between those spoken to children in affluent homes and those in economically disadvantaged homes by the age of three years. Whilst, value add models take account of the differing inputs of students, it is important to centre the argument not on where Australia is performing in PISA but rather, why Australia's performance is reflecting a downward trend.

It is critical that this thesis moves beyond the tests employed to measure Australia's system-wide success to also unpack the means, motivation, and manner behind the measurement instruments employed. Every assessment is a text and just like any other text, the creation of it is laden with cultural, political, and social context that must be openly acknowledged (Foucault,

1977). Unpacking the power at play is essential to attest to the validity, reliability, and applicability of the data it generates. This means not only examining the values attested to in Australian schools but also, the inherent values laden in the test construction and design. As a result of standardised testing, we can measure school success and draw comparisons between schools and school systems (Starr, 2014). However, we also risk disparaging those where education fails to serve as the great equalizer (Polesel, Dulfer & Turnbull, 2012).

2.4.5 Influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The commencement of this chapter referenced Binet and Simon (1907), explaining that the perception of intelligence is defined by the means used to assess it. It would therefore be remiss to ignore the recent and monumental shift in collective understanding of intelligence. In March 2020, as this PhD research journey was commencing and the world was locking down to prevent the spread of a virus called Covid-19, Sam Altman was concluding his time at the helm of Y Combinator (a technology startup incubator) and turning his full attention to a company he had launched five years earlier called OpenAI (Gray, 2021). Three years later and OpenAI has changed the landscape in which this research exists thanks to a tool known as ChatGPT. This is an important consideration for this thesis in situating the learner, the goals for Australian schooling and the measures used to assess the success of the education system in context.

2.4.5.1 What is ChatGPT?

ChatGPT was the first “easy to use generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tool” made available to the public and its impact has fuelled a technology race (UNESCO, 2023b, p.7). At its outset, the primary concern of educational institutions was the impact it may have on the facilitation of plagiarism (Anders, 2023) but this soon shifted as the world started to explore the myriad of use cases. Generative AI (GenAI) is an Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology that uses natural language models to automatically generate new content that comprises all symbolic

representations of human thinking including texts, images, videos, music, and software code. OpenAI, the company responsible for GenAI, trained the model using data from websites and other online media. The content is generated through a process of “statistically analysing the distributions of words, pixels or other elements in the data that it has ingested and identifying and repeating common patterns” (UNESCO, 2023b, p.8).

2.4.5.2 Why does it matter?

AI is not new. It has been a consideration for test developers at the OECD since 2016 when they began testing the performance of AI systems on the OECD Survey of Adult Skills of the Programme for International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC) (Elliott, 2017). However, the GenAI race, spurred on by the release of ChatGPT, has excited the world including educators, about what’s possible. UNESCO (2023) suggest that “by freeing humans from some categories of lower order thinking skills, this new generation of AI tools might have profound implications for how we understand human intelligence and learning.” (p.7). Yet challenges exist, as with any new opportunity. OpenAI (2023) confirmed this themselves when they said,

Despite its capabilities, GPT-4 has similar limitations as earlier GPT models. Most importantly, it still is not fully reliable (it ‘hallucinates’ facts and makes reasoning errors). Great care should be taken when using language model outputs, particularly in high-stakes contexts, with the exact protocol (such as human review, grounding with additional context, or avoiding high-stakes uses altogether) matching the needs of a specific use-case. (para.3).

With regards to assessment, ChatGPT has caused technologists and educators to re-evaluate the tools they use, the methods they employ and how they translate in a world where the transformation of education and research is set to be triggered by GenAI. Cavendish (2023) has gone as far as to assert that “ChatGPT will force school exams out of the dark ages. Too much of

our testing regime remains fixated on being able to regurgitate information” (para.1). Computer science research has already used different types of standardised human tests for AI evaluation, including IQ tests (Liu et al., 2019), mathematics examinations (Saxton et al., 2019) and science tests (Clark et al., 2020). The OECD has tracked the performance of ChatGPT and other such systems on PISA. Given a set of test items from the PISA mathematical literacy domain in March 2022, ChatGPT could answer 28% correctly. In March 2023, ChatGPT answered 46% of the tasks successfully. In the science domain, the corresponding percentages were 65% and 85% (Schleicher, 2023). The performance is demonstrated in the figure below:

Figure 3

ChatGPT Performance on PISA Test Items

Imagine if the countries of the world could enable their students to increase their performance on PISA by 20% in less than a year of schooling. What can we learn from AI about how to learn and about what such tests are designed to measure? In a discussion of ChatGPT and PISA, Schleicher (2023) again refers to PISA as “the global yardstick of educational success that over 80 countries use to assess the knowledge and skills of 15-year-olds” whilst also affirming that education is “no longer just about teaching students’ but about preparing them for a volatile and complex world. What does it say about this ‘yardstick of educational success’ if a machine can outperform most 15-year-olds in school?

UNESCO's (2023a) Guidance for generative AI in education and research reminds throughout of the importance of leveraging the full potential of GenAI for education whilst retaining a human-centred approach throughout. One could easily argue that teachers have always supported students to set their compass, chart their course ahead and steer their own ship as the tides of time rise and fall. Educators have taught students through many technological advancements and shifts in educational landscape as discussed earlier in this chapter. Concerningly though, across the OECD countries that participated in PISA 2022, the reading literacy survey found that less than 50% of 15-year-old students were able to distinguish facts from opinions. (Schleicher, 2023). Working with a system that OpenAI (2023) claims is prone to hallucinations and the dissemination of misinformation, how can we support young people to become critical consumers of the technology?

Most concerningly, the OECD reports that most economies, even the top performing ones, cannot manage to successfully educate more than 25% of their workforce with the literacy and numeracy skills required to outperform AI on their PIAAC tests of literacy and numeracy (OECD, 2023). This has serious ramifications not only for the future employability and viability of global economies but also raises concern for the way in which educational success is defined. Once more, an education system cannot be deemed as successful if up to 75% of its adult population cannot outperform artificial intelligence when it comes to proficiency in the fundamental skills of literacy and numeracy. Not only will this continue to exacerbate the equity gap but will also limit future learning opportunities.

Consideration for the impact of Generative AI on this research is a late addition but important as it demands an examination of not only how we assess student learning but also in the way we define intelligence and what constitutes system-wide success in a world where machines can outperform most 15-year-old students globally. Generative AI has the potential to transform and transcend education as we know it, which means the role of human agency is more

important than ever in determining what constitutes a successful education system for Australia's young people. So too, it has the potential to change to means for assessing the effectiveness of the system for all learners.

2.5 Chapter Summary

Following a review of the literature, key themes and concepts are already emerging that will invariably inform and shape this study. References to issues of measurement, consequential validity, accountability, the political and historical roots of the education system, policies, equity and definitions of excellence and quality form a solid foundation from which to build towards answering the research questions: To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them? How is the achievement of those goals currently measured? Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals? The next chapter, informed by the literature review, outlines the methodological approach used.

Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework

Commencing with the rationale for choosing qualitative research, this chapter examines three theories which have shaped the research design and method. Together they provide the foundation to address the research questions. This chapter examines Foucault's (1977) work on power, Charmaz's (2006) Constructivist Grounded Theory, Measurement Theory and Messick's (1989) Model of Validity.

3.1 Why Qualitative Research?

As Starks and Brown Trinidad (2007) explain, choosing the appropriate methodology is not easy for the novice researcher. Especially when both Constructivist Grounded Theory and interpretive phenomenology are “not philosophically contradictory,” “move beyond description of phenomena and delve into meanings” and “aim to understand and interpret the nature of experiences” (Burns et al., 2022, p.2). An interpretivist approach is favoured when it comes to a study of policy as it encourages the opportunity to better understand the world and how it is represented (Bacchi, 2009). However, the social construction of policy including the posing of the problem, the assumptions underpinning it, the power at play and the solutions it presents are all shaped by language and discourse thus making them products of the society (Hastings, 1998). A contextualised understanding of Australia's agreed goals for schooling, the system its schools operate in, and the measures used to assess their performance as social constructs are all key to this study. Therefore, a Constructivist Grounded Theory approach was selected.

Grounded theory arose from the work of Glaser and Strauss (1967) in the field of sociology to provide a legitimate alternative to quantitative research (Burns et al., 2022). In its original form, Glaser believed the “data to speak for itself” (Reay et al., 2016, p. 27) and that the theory would emerge to the researcher in keeping with a post-positivism paradigm (Burns et al., 2022). As grounded theory traditionally adopted a pragmatic approach, Charmaz (2014) sought

to build upon Glaser and Strauss' work by addressing the "subjective nature of human realities" (Burns et al., 2022, p.5). Adopting a constructivist approach, Charmaz proposed an alternative ground theory methodology which recognised the influence of human activity on constructing the phenomenon being studied and the study itself (Charmaz, Thornberg & Keane, 2018). For this study, perhaps the most appealing aspect of grounded theory is its ability to move the researcher from the "what" and "how" of the problem to the "why" (Charmaz, 2017). This is well aligned with the goals of this study. The purposeful choice to engage in qualitative research to inform a measurement study was designed to fill the gap where policy, measurement and practice intersect. The approach chosen enabled the data collection and analysis to move beyond numbers to gather the opinions of stakeholders in the context of current educational policy.

Every study utilising a grounded theory approach, whether that be Glaserian (Glaser & Strauss, 1967), Straussian (Corbin & Strauss, 1990) or Constructivist (Charmaz, 2006), follows the same seven principles as summarised by Qureshi and Unlu (2020):

1. Commences with a broad focus / question.
2. Literature review is completed in the later stages.
3. Data collection and analysis is completed simultaneously.
4. Constant comparison method is used throughout the process.
5. Memos are kept.
6. Theoretical sensitivity is employed.
7. Theoretical sampling is undertaken.

Commencing the research with broad ideas and questions to focus upon (Charmaz, 2006) proves somewhat challenging. However, there is an art to the patient practice of letting the problem, and subsequent solution, slowly reveal themselves during the study. Similarly, the development of the literature review as a continually evolving source of information provides for an up-to-date contribution. As data are collected, analysed, and coded to support theory

generation using a constant comparison method and memo writing, theoretical sensitivity is employed, relying upon the researchers' knowledge and insight to identify key discoveries.

3.2 Research questions

Inspired by the work of Hargraves (People for Education, 2014) to provoke conversation and drive change towards how one chooses to measure the success of a system, this study is focused on questioning whether Australia is measuring what matters when it comes to the performance of its federated school system. It investigates the extent to which there is alignment between the goals of the Australian education system and the measures that are currently used to evaluate the performance of that system. The following research questions helped shape the exploration:

RQ1. To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

RQ2. How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?

RQ3. Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

3.3 Ontology and epistemology

The researcher's world view is unequivocally influenced by their ontological and epistemological position (Mills et al., 2006; Urcia, 2021). Ontology refers to the perspective one takes on the nature of existence and the structure of reality (Crotty, 1998; Creswell & Poth, 2018). One's ontological position defines that nature of the world and how one knows what is possible about the world (Snape & Spencer, 2003). Given that ontology is concerned with the relationships between different aspects of society such as social structures and the actors in them, the influence of this on a study pertaining to the education system, one of society's key

structures, is pivotal (Jupp, 2006). Ontology questions one's beliefs about the things that exist within society, Bryman (2008) explores 'social ontology' which is concerned with the nature of social entities such as schools. Thus, questioning whether they can be objective entities that are independent of the social actors that occupy them or rather, they themselves are socially constructed by the perceptions, actions, and interpretations of the society (Bryman, 2008).

Questioning the reality of the social world in which we exist, this research is grounded in an ontological perspective underpinned by a constructivist approach. It is based upon the belief that humans are social beings who construct their knowledge based upon their interactions with others and the world around them. It takes the position that the world can only be fully understood from the perspective of an individual who is part of the action being researched (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007).

Epistemology refers to the means for acquiring knowledge and how knowledge is developed (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This project employs an interpretivist approach as it draws attention to the different ways one can understand the world and how that is then represented in policy (Bacchi, 2009). This approach was favoured as it asks what the problem is intended to be, the assumptions that underpin it, how it came about, the gaps or silences within it and its place in the discourse. Based on the understanding that reality is a social construct shaped by language and discourse, it appreciates policy problems as products of history and culture (Hastings, 1998).

3.4 Foucault and Power

In keeping with the interpretivist paradigm underpinning this research, this study is based upon the belief that we experience and interpret the world according to our own perspective. Philosophically, the researcher draws on the work of Foucault to examine the ways in which power is incorporated into everyday routines, spoken about in everyday discourse, and exercised by the subjects over others and themselves (Välikangas & Seeck, 2011). It is therefore impossible to research school-systems and the policies related to them without also examining

the power relations exerting influence upon them (Foucault, 1977). Questions such as “Who holds the power?,” “When is the power exercised?,” “Through what channels?” and “What impact does it have?” are critical in examining schools and educational policy. In the context of schools there are many ways that agencies, governments, and assorted bodies exercise power over the decisions made within. This is particularly evident when reflecting on the ‘datafication’ of the education system (Mayer-Schonberger & Cukier, 2013). Whenever an individual (or organisation) selects an approach to modelling data they impose their values upon that data (Zumbo, 2006; Zumbo & Rupp, 2004). It is therefore imperative that with the rapid advancement of technology and the burgeoning datafication of schools, one takes time to examine the resulting epistemological and infrastructural governance. How are these new systems and ways of thinking, asserting ‘soft power’? (Nye, 2004; Nye, 2009; Anagnostopoulou et al., 2013; Amirbek & Ydyrys, 2014). Pausing to reflect on the role of education in foreign policy and its ability to serve as soft power in driving international conversations using economic, cultural, and political capital is pivotal to this study. Especially as it explores the role of International Large-Scale Assessments (ILSA) in measuring the success of an education system’s national policies and goals for schooling. The provision of education is one of the most useful instruments in the soft power of the nation when it comes to taking a seat at the inter-governmental table (Amirbek & Ydyrys, 2014; Nye, 2009; Cowan & Arsenault, 2008). Bouhali (2015) poignantly reminds us that when investigating such policies one must ask, ‘whose interests are served?’ (p.119). Whilst in education policy the answer to this question, one hopes, would always defer to the same answer – the best interests of the children, yet in a neo-liberal, global context one does wonder if conflicting agendas may also be served.

Foucault’s study of power as a means to analyse the issues that it impacts is frequently utilised in the study of education management and policy (Deacon, 2006; Välikangas & Seeck, 2011). Researchers such as Pitsoe and Letseka (2013) claim that power and discourse are

interrelated constructs which the teacher uses to perpetuate Taylorism, Fordism, and bureaucratic domination in a classroom setting. By understanding systems such as these we better understand ourselves (Foucault, 1977). Therefore, the best and only opportunity to examine the relational nature of power is to observe it being exercised (Townley, 1993). This requires us to focus attention on the manifestations of power and the way it shapes and re-shapes us as individuals. Power is a network that includes us all (Feldman, 1997). Social power specifically refers to the power to determine social outcomes and influence the behaviour of others (Brey, 2008). This may be exacted through group power, organisational power, individual social power and finally, political power. All of which are at play in Australian schools and every other education system around the world.

Foucault (1972) speaks of how discourse constitutes an object whilst hiding its own invention. It is accepted that discourses exist in the form of oral and written information that are interwoven in the social practices of daily life. Most importantly, these discourses are inherent in the core of institutions such as our schools and homes (Weedon, 1997). Whilst it may be argued that the tapestry of discourse, power and knowledge is woven tightly in order to oppress the other, the urge must be resisted to fall into the mindset of a hegemonistic view of oppression (Pitsoe & Letseka, 2013). Whilst there are circumstances whereby controlling the knowledge, a situation is created where the other is oppressed in society, this is not the view of power being reflected here. It is simply proposed that the critical researcher must seek to expose the distribution of power and the influences at play in constructing it.

Gramsci developed his theory of hegemony, the extent to which ideological control is perpetuated through willing consent, following his efforts to organise Italian peasant farmers to act (Gramsci, 2000; Langman, 2015). Mayo (2008) describes hegemony simply as ruling by consent rather than force. Today, the idea of power being perpetuated through consent is readily observed in schools. Many education systems, as in Australia, work to maintain the power

relations of the society (Ball, Goodson & McGuire, 2007) and their discourses, centred on educational policy, are an example of education systems serving as both the instrument and object of power (Pitsoe & Letseka, 2013). This is especially evident in the willing consent of OECD member economies and non-members to engage with the PISA rhetoric and fall under the “supranational spell of PISA in policy” therefore, establishing its authority as a source of truth (Baird et al., 2016, p.133). How does society mediate such a discourse when the power rests with the institutions and thought leaders promoted as the source of truth? (Talbani, 1996). Every society has what Foucault refers to as its own truth which is established through the discourse presented (Pitsoe & Letseka, 2013). Part of the establishment of this truth is the creation of institutions such as schools where power can be legitimately exercised (Foucault, 1972).

3.5 Grounded Theory

In the pursuit of a methodology which provides for the flexibility needed and the complexity inherent in the research problem, grounded theory was selected as it offers the opportunity to construct theory from the data collected (Chamberlain-Salaun et al., 2013; Chun Tie et al., 2019). Further to this, a Constructivist Grounded Theory methodology was selected as it aligns best with the requirements of answering the research questions. Allowing for the generation of data that was informed by policy, participant experience (gained through semi-structured interviews) and the national measurements employed.

3.5.1 Constructivist Grounded Theory

Charmaz (2006) developed an approach to grounded theory with its roots in constructivism to focus on how meaning is constructed in relation to the study area. Charmaz and Bryant (2011) explain the job of a constructivist as being to co-construct experience and meaning with participants which this project endeavours to do through the interview questions developed to better understand the lived experience of key stakeholders working in the field of

study. This approach suits this study well as it enables the participants to contribute to theory generation through their insights, expertise and working knowledge of the field.

3.6 Measurement Theory

For this research, Measurement Theory informed the analysis of the educational tests outlined in the National Assessment Program (ACARA, 2020a). By engaging with measurement theory in this way, it takes measurement and assessment beyond a mathematical formula to examining the justification for the model and its application (Andrich, 2004). The fundamental concepts of measurement theory (validity and reliability) are used to assess both the technical quality and the usefulness of educational tests. Whilst both are critical to the appropriate use of education testing, there is widespread agreement that validity is the most important factor (Linn, 2000).

There are two schools of thought when it comes to test validity. The first adopts a narrowly defined view of validity as a fixed property of a test (Shepard, 1997). In contrast, the second school of thought favours a broad and complex definition of validity that encompasses the assessment's consequences as well as its procedures (Wolming & Wikström, 2010). Originally it was thought that the defining feature of validity was how well a test could do the job it was designed to do (Cureton, 1951). In further exploring the concept of validity, Cronbach (1971) put forward the notion that it is not actually the test that one validates but rather the interpretation of the data arising from that specific procedure. Thus, shifting the focus from the test instrument to the interpretation of the measurement (Wolming & Wikström, 2010). Building on the recommendation that validation requires a different approach that considers evidence from multiple sources, this study argues that it is not the test itself that should be the focus of this validation but rather the way in which the outcomes are measured, and the results interpreted and used (Cronbach & Shapiro, 1982).

The unitary validity framework developed by Messick (1989) holds validity at its core and examines the test score, its purpose, how its outcomes are used, what evidence or consequence will result and the value for stakeholders or society in general. Messick's framework marks a significant development in validity theory due to its inclusion of the social consequences of measurement outcomes (Wolming & Wikström, 2010). Previously, social consequences had been examined but were not formally recognised as contributing to the validity of a test. Interestingly, the inclusion of social consequences in a validity framework has not been without debate. Whilst Messick's framework has been widely accepted including in the Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing (AERA, APA, and NCME, 2014) it has been questioned by others claiming it merely made validity more complex than it need be (Popham, 1997; Mehrens, 1997).

Messick's (1989) model of validity provides a theoretical basis for this study. It enables the use and interpretation of assessment results for a clearly articulated purpose and makes it possible to evaluate impact. Kane (2006) states that without an interpretive argument it is impossible to effectively complete a validation process. Messick (1989) described validation as the process of making sure that the assessment process is really measuring what it is supposed to measure. This serves the study well to investigate whether the National Report on Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2018a), which serves as the measure of whether the education system is achieving the outcomes set by the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) is a "fair" measure, given that it samples so little of the construct.

Kane (2006) and Messick (1989) have worked to develop an integrated evaluative judgement of validity. However, the challenge remains in moving it from theory to practice. The opportunity to form an argument for validity based on the integration of key evidence from various sources continues. This research presents the opportunity to make a meaningful

contribution to modern validity theory, a research outcome that is mindful of the intended use of the instrument, rather than the instrument itself (Wolming & Wikström, 2010).

3.6.1 Validity Theory

According to the Standards (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014) validity is “the most fundamental consideration” in developing and evaluating assessments (p. 11). Validity is closely aligned to test purpose and is established through a process of validation (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014). Validity matters. It matters because it provides the basis upon which sound decisions can be made when it comes to the assessments which have important consequences for individuals and society (Pepper, 2020). It also matters because “validity gives meaning to test scores” (Wagemaker, 2020, p.12).

The standards advise that, “validation logically begins with an explicit statement of the proposed interpretation of test scores, along with a rationale for the relevance of the interpretation to the proposed use” (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014, p. 11). The issues relating to the interpretation of test results and their intended use is charged with requests for test developers to be “held responsible for validating intended interpretations, uses and consequences” and demands that “such documentation must be publicly available in a timely manner.” (Taut & Palacios, 2016, p.11). In reality, it is impossible to hold test developers accountable for those who use their tests inappropriately. However, speaking truth to their misuse and misinterpretation would go a long way to restoring and supporting their validity in the eyes of stakeholders.

When embarking on the process of validating an assessment instrument, five strands of validity evidence are explored: test content; response processes; internal structure; relations to other variables; and the consequences of the test (Pepper, 2020). Unfortunately, in this process the strand of response processes is often overlooked or forgotten (Launeanu & Hubley, 2017).

This is an important factor as the response processes are those which provide the empirical evidence of what is being assessed. Pepper (2011) argues that “if a test is intended to assess mathematical reasoning, it becomes important to determine whether test takers are, in fact, reasoning ... or following a standard algorithm” (p. 15). Wagemaker (2020) explains that “validity evidence provides the reassurance that the assessment measures what it purports to measure” but goes on to warn that, “no single summary statistic or procedure can adequately satisfy validity-related concerns” (p.12).

Currently, “validity theory is rich, but the practice of validation is often impoverished” (Brennan, 2006, p. 8). Fortunately, the Standards, whilst not a global authority (Lake & Wise, 2014) does provide a “global force for testing” (Zumbo, 2014, p.33) and have led greater action and understanding with regards to validity.

The agreed definition of validity (APA, AERA, & NCME, 2014) is drawn from Messick’s belief in validity as “an integrated evaluative judgment of the degree to which empirical evidence and theoretical rationales support the adequacy and appropriateness of interpretations and actions based on test scores or other modes of assessment” (Messick, 1990, p. 5). Messick (1989) viewed validity as moving beyond being a property of measurement instruments to see it as encapsulating the interpretation and meaning of test scores holistically (Fulcher, 1999).

The inclusion of social values and their consequences in Messick’s (1989) validity theory has not been without controversy. Yet it remains true that test scores may be interpreted and used in different ways, depending on the individual test takers and the context in which it is situated (Moss et al., 2006).

3.6.2 Messick's Model of Validity

Messick (1989) defines validity as “an integrated evaluative judgment of the degree to which empirical evidence and theoretical rationales support the adequacy and appropriateness of inferences and actions based on test scores or other modes of assessment” (p.6). The figure below shows the facets of validity according to Messick (1989). It is his belief that construct validity, relevance and utility, value implications and social consequences all work together and impact one another in test interpretation and use.

Figure 4

Facets of Validity (Messick, 1989, p.20)

	Test Interpretation	Test Use
Evidential Basis	Construct Validity	Construct Validity + Relevance / Utility
Consequential Basis	Value Implications	Social Consequences

When considering the validity of a test, Messick is cognisant of the fact that the test cannot be isolated from its political context. For instance, the scientific process of validating a test must include acknowledgement of the interplay with the political considerations (Messick, 1989). The inclusion of the value implications and the social consequences are critical in this

model as they serve to support the research efforts inherent in this study which seeks to evaluate how well aligned Australia's assessment tools are to the national goals for K-12 schooling. Messick acknowledges the social psychology of the assessment context in his work (Messick, 1989). Of relevance to this thesis is the ability to explore the social consequences of how test scores are interpreted and used. This will enable the research to examine whether it is the test itself or the way in which the scores are used which impacts the alignment between the tests used in the National Assessment Program (NAP) (ACARA, 2011a) and the national values for schooling. Equipped with this knowledge, Australians can reflect on how the measurement framework informs the purpose of schooling for their young people. The application of Messick's (1989) model is important as it is through this process that we will uncover whether it is the alignment between the test and the construct (National values for schooling) or the (mis-)interpretation (or misuse) of the scores that is problematic. For example, if NAPLAN is aligned with its purposes, then it probably has good content and construct validity. However, if it is being used to make judgements which go beyond its intended purpose then this detracts from the validity, and we know that the consequences of using the test for things that it was not intended to be used for can have a significantly negative impact on the system. The evidence supports the argument that NAPLAN is a valid assessment of literacy and numeracy (Klenowski, 2015). The question is, are the scores on literacy and numeracy appropriate measures of the quality of a K-12 school system? What happens when these don't align? Does that become an unintended consequence of NAPLAN and thus detract from the validity of the overall measurement? Much importance must be placed on distinguishing between the validity of the instrument and the validity of the purpose for which it is being used (Klenowski, 2015). Whilst most relevant in Economics and quantitative studies, Goodhart's law (Goodhart, 1975) which states that when a measure becomes a target it ceases to be a good measure. As soon as people begin to adapt their behaviour to optimise in favour of the measure (e.g. teach to the test), its validity is undermined.

Thus, the application of Messick's model of validity is pivotal to the examination of the measurement instruments featured in the NAP and discussed in this study.

3.6.3 Consequential Validity

The Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014) exert influence on shared understandings of measurement around the world. One such understanding is the concept of validity and the importance of paying particular attention to the evidence arising from the consequences of testing (Taut & Palacios, 2016). When exploring such consequences, the standards make an important distinction between "interpretations and uses of test scores intended by test developers," "claims made about test use that are not directly based on test score interpretations" and "consequences that are unintended" (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014, p. 19). Critically, the standards guide us that evidence about consequences is only "relevant to validity when it can be traced to a source of invalidity such as construct underrepresentation or construct-irrelevant components. Evidence that cannot be traced is not relevant to the validity of the intended interpretations of test scores" (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014, p. 21).

Cronbach (1988) argued strongly for the role of consequences as the obligation of the test developer including the social obligation of legitimising the usage of the test. By contrast, Messick (1989) argues for test invalidity only occurring when consequences are the result of flaws in the test, but not if they are external to features of the test. To this end, the standards advise that where a test user engages with a test in a manner that differs from its intended interpretations, the onus falls on the user to provide evidence of validity. The following example from AERA, APA & NCME (2014) explains:

...if the claim was made that PISA scores could be used to monitor the impact of a curricular reform in a certain country, then evidence must be produced that PISA is a valid measure of curricular reform impact in that country. This, however, is not the responsibility of the test developer but of the national policy makers who use the test for this purpose. However, if the claim was made that PISA results, in connection with other educational indicators measured through PISA questionnaires, could be used to describe the extent of educational equity achieved by a certain country – which corresponds to a claim actually made by the OECD, the PISA test developer – then the test developer must present evidence that PISA (as including the questionnaires and the tests) in fact offers valid information on educational equity in the participating countries (p. 20).

Consequential validity is not without contention (Solano-Flores & Milbourn, 2016). One such argument is provided by Popham (1997) who believes the consequences of testing to be very important but not so much so that it should not be considered part of validity. Mehrens (1997) agrees, viewing consequences as lying outside of validity. However, Messick (1995) maintains that “to appraise how well a test does its job, one must inquire whether the potential and actual social consequences of test interpretation and use are not only supportive of the intended testing purposes, but also at the same time consistent with other social values” (p. 744). Linn (1998) charged those working in educational measurement with the responsibility for evaluating the consequences of tests. Kane (2006) urges this evaluation to include a review of test effectiveness, cost and benefit.

The role of the intended and unintended consequences of testing has now been well established in the field of educational measurement and the interpretations (and misinterpretation) of educational testing results garnish strong attention from stakeholders (Taut & Palacios, 2016). It is imperative that stakeholders (teachers, parents, policy makers and other test users) equip themselves with some technical understanding and develop the capacity to fully

understand the intended and unintended interpretations and uses of test scores. Many testing programs have moved beyond the “traditional monitoring role, to the use of testing as the engine of reform and accountability in education” (Kane, 2006, p. 55). It is hoped that this would empower stakeholders with stronger resistance to the political pressures of test use (and misuse). This is especially pertinent to the use (and misuse) of PISA results which frequently serve political agendas (Taut & Palacios, 2016).

International large-scale assessments “rely on advanced statistical methodologies developed in fields commonly called psychometrics” and work with the goal of providing “mathematically rigorous methods for quantifying skills and knowledge based on observable data” (von Davier et al., 2020, p.188). This research explores the concept of consequential validity as a key facet of the construct validity of an assessment to reassure stakeholders regarding the planned implementation and usage of measurement instruments.

When it comes to the use of measurement instruments, the criticisms of them typically fall under two headings: methodology and ideology (Araujo et al., 2017). Both forces are integral to shaping measurement instruments and the ways in which their use is understood. The figure below provides an illustration of this:

Figure 5

Influential Forces on Measurement Instruments

An exploration of the methodological influences on a measurement instrument involves engaging with the statistical models, psychometric properties and test design employed by the measurement instrument (Araujo et al., 2017). For the purposes of this thesis, an exploration of the ideological forces including global conceptions of the purpose for education is more relevant. Take for example the issue of the global comparability data generated by PISA every three years. From a methodological perspective, one may question the reliability and validity of drawing such inferences from the data collected. Yet, from an ideological perspective, one may question whether by doing so the assessment fails to acknowledge cultural diversity and the innate difference of each local context.

Academics remain engaged with the ongoing validation of the PISA instrument from a methodological perspective (Meyerhoefer, 2009; Goldstein, 2004). Their primary concern being its cross-sectional design which “limits its usefulness” for global policy development (Araujo et al., 2017, p.24). By contrast, from an ideological perspective, congruency is continually sought between what PISA measures, how it is measured, and the world view it supports (Araujo et al., 2017). A view that conceptualises globalisation through a neoliberal lens (Sellar & Lingard, 2014).

3.7 Chapter Summary

Currently, when policy decisions are being informed by the consented authority of large-scale, international assessments such as PISA and school attendance records, it is imperative that we delve deep into an analysis of the policies that are being reformed and envisage a better future for Australia’s education system that better reflects its national values, aspirations, and goals for schooling. So too, an examination of the current measures used to assess the achievement of those stated goals and the validity of those instruments is needed. This must be done through both an ideological and methodological lens that appreciates the forces shaping educational policy. As a result of this study, stronger alignment between policy, practice and

performance is sought. Armed with a solid understanding of educational policy and the validity of the measurement instruments used to assess them will be beneficial as we seek to find out if there is a better way of measuring matters most to Australia's society.

In summary, this chapter outlined the research questions being addressed in this study and provided a detailed account of the researcher's ontological and epistemological position which informs it. Following an explanation the intentional choice to embark upon a measurement study using a qualitative approach, an overview of the theoretical framework ensued. At its conclusion, the chapter described Grounded Theory, Constructivist Grounded Theory in addition to the theoretical influences of Measurement Theory and Validity Theory which all govern the data collection and interpretation associated with this thesis. Equipped with an understanding of how the methodology has informed the study, the next chapter describes the research design and method used to answer the research questions posed.

Chapter 4: Method

This chapter outlines the method employed to complete this study. As a qualitative, Constructivist Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2014; Suddaby, 2006; Glaser & Strauss, 1967) was adopted, the chapter commences with an explanation of sample selection and participant recruitment before moving on to explore ethical considerations, data collection, analysis and the emerging themes arising from the coding, memo writing, and constant comparative analysis employed. A review of the importance of quality, rigour, and congruence (Morse, 2007) when employing this method of choice is also included before concluding with details of the data collection, triangulation, and credibility.

4.1 Sample Selection and Adequacy

The role of researcher as insider (Charmaz, 2014) and the interdependency of researcher and participant in Constructivist Grounded Theory has a significant impact on the subjects and participants in the study. As such, careful attention must be paid to its design (Mills et al., 2006). Strauss and Corbin (1998) explain the interplay between researcher, subject and participant as essentially reacting to and working with data. In many ways this makes sense as the methodology of choice as it reflects the daily work of teachers in Australian classrooms. Educators are consistently gathering, reacting to, and working with data whether it be achievement data, attendance data, participation data or the infinite number of incidental data points that arise in a teacher's day.

In this study, it is important to note that grounded theory does not take the views of participants as evidence but rather is seeking to analyse their contributions in a way that transcends their individual story to theorise whilst remaining connected to the data point from which it came (Mills et al., 2006; Charmaz, 2014). Considering the subjects of a study as including the organisations, documents and even societies being examined, the subjects of this

study are the Australian K-12 school system, the national policies that inform its goals and the tools used to measure their outcomes. The participants in this study are the people whose insights and experience contributed to it via semi-structured interviews. These participants comprised a purposive sample of ten education leaders working nationally with Australian schools who have a working knowledge of Australia's national goals for schooling and the assessments used to measure their achievement. The candidates for participation needed to meet the following criteria:

1. Experience of designing, delivering or debating educational testing nationally
2. Working knowledge of the assessments included in the National Assessment Program
3. Working knowledge of the Mparntwe Declaration and goals for Australian schooling
4. Working knowledge of the K-12 school sector in Australia

Qualitative studies benefit from smaller sample sizes that are purposively selected to increase the depth of understanding (Campbell et al., 2020) as opposed to a large-scale quantitative study that benefits from breadth. To achieve this, purposive sampling is used to identify and engage with participants who possess the knowledge and understanding needed to co-construct the theory being generated (Robinson, 2014).

This study uses purposive sampling to direct which data are to be collected or generated (Chun Tie, Birks, & Francis, 2019). In doing so, it provides for the purposeful selection of participants and sources of data for the researcher to be able to answer the research questions posed (Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Bryant & Charmaz, 2007; Charmaz & Bryant, 2011). Purposive sampling serves to provide the initial data that is analysed in a process that reflects the foundations of Grounded Theory which engages the researcher in generating data whilst concurrently analysing it (Birks & Mills, 2015).

Purposive sampling is utilised to increase in the rigour of the data that are generated and the subsequent results (Campbell et al., 2020). To answer the research questions posed in this study, federal policies were selected to facilitate a system-wide view at the national level. With sufficient time and word limit, additional policies may have been worthy of inclusion however, this study is currently limited to include an analysis of the NAP (ACARA, 2011a) and the national goals and values for schooling as stated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). These policies were selected as they represent the national position and have been endorsed by the representatives from every state and territory in Australia. This consensus is important in a study seeking to examine the role of policymakers and power players in the field. In addition, these policies provide an insight into the foundational goals, aims and purpose of schooling in Australia at this time as reflected in their language, theoretical basis and chosen sources of data.

Table 1

Allocation of Research Question to Chosen Method

Research Questions	Research Phase
To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?	Policy Analysis focused on the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Declaration (Education Council, 2019)
How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?	Measurement instrument validation: National Assessment Program (NAP)
Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?	Semi-structured interviews with educational leaders

Table 1 shows how each research question aligns to one of the methods employed - policy analysis, measurement and interviews.

To reflect the national policies sampled for the purpose of this study, interview participants were selected with a similar set of criteria. Following ethics approval from the University of Sydney, Protocol number 2021/662, suitable candidates for interview were identified through desktop research. This was important for alignment with the policies being discussed and their implementation nationally. In addition to a set criteria (see section 4.3) participants were sought who reflected the geographic diversity of Australia as well as its cultural and social diversity. This was not easy to achieve given the need to access participants who had working knowledge of the system at a national level. This often led to candidates who were working at high levels of government or school networks and who had relocated to Canberra, Sydney, or Melbourne as part of the role given the location of their offices. The next section describes the process used to select the purposive sample.

4.2 Participant recruitment

A sample of fourteen suitable participants were contacted and their participation was requested using the University approved Participant Information Statement (see Appendix B) and Consent Form (see Appendix C). Verbal agreement was granted by thirteen of the fourteen participants invited and written consent to participate was provided by ten of the sample approached. Ten interviews were completed and contribute to this study.

The participants' names have been anonymised by randomly assigning them a number from one to ten. For those participants who did not consent to having their identity shared, additional information was redacted to preserve and protect their privacy. In addition, information such as the demographics and area of expertise has also been omitted to avoid any concern with their current (or future) employers and to afford them the opportunity to speak openly.

4.3 Experience and Background of the Study Participants

In keeping with the Constructivist Grounded Theory approach, the use of purposive sampling techniques was utilised to ensure the data generated is grounded in professional knowledge and experience. The following criteria were used:

- a. Experience nationally to design, deliver or debate educational testing. This was identified through desktop research of professional networks and validated through conversations with stakeholders.
- b. Working knowledge of the National Assessment Program and the goals for schooling outlined in the Mparntwe Declaration.
- c. Working knowledge of the K-12 school sector in Australia.

The ten study participants who returned their consent forms were then invited to complete a pre-interview survey which was used to confirm they met the criteria for purposive sampling. Firstly, all ten of the participants met the criteria by either working in the field of test development, test delivery, or worked with the results of educational testing in either a policy, measurement, or practice endeavour at the national level. The diverse backgrounds of the participants in undertaking this required work made for interesting discussions and perspectives on the problems presented. In addition, many of the participants also brought international experience to the discussion which only enriched their perspectives as they were able to draw comparisons across their experiences. Secondly, each of the interview participants demonstrated a working knowledge of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). It was evident from their responses and engagement that they each possessed a deep working knowledge of the policy, its goals and associated key performance measures in the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a). Thirdly, the group of ten participants reflected a range of key stakeholders from the education sector required for the purpose of this study. There were representatives from each sector of K-12 schooling (government, catholic and independent) and

from each state of Australia (though most now live in Sydney or Melbourne). There was also an even distribution of genders and cultural backgrounds.

4.4 Ethical considerations

The analysis of public policy documents did not require ethics clearance from the University of Sydney. However, ethics clearance was required and approved for the semi-structured interviews which were conducted with educational leaders on system-wide success. The participants provided consent and were informed of their rights with regards to this study. They could elect to remain anonymous and were given the opportunity to review the interview transcripts prior to their use in this study. Participants were able to withdraw consent at any time. Data were securely stored in accordance with Australian and University of Sydney standards.

This project was approved by the University of Sydney Human Research Ethics Committee (see Appendix A). According to the purposive sampling process outlined above and in keeping with the approved procedure for outreach, participants in the semi-structured interviews were invited by email (see Appendix D) and sent a Participant Information Statement (see Appendix C) and consent form (see Appendix B).

Upon receipt of their consent to participate, the interviewees were provided with a set of interview questions by email prior to meeting at a mutually agreeable time. This step was important due to the demanding work loads of many of the participants.

Data security processes were designed to ensure the safe storage of participant information in keeping with the University's requirements. Interview participants were given the option to remain anonymous or may choose to consent to share their identity. Where participants opted to remain anonymous a pseudonym was applied and details that may reveal their identity, role or place of work were concealed.

4.5 Data collection

Semi-structured interviews were completed with the participants to generate data. The flexibility of the semi-structured interview was favoured as it enabled the researcher to guide the conversation whilst maximising the input from the participants with expertise in the field. The three questions that guided the semi-structured interviews were informed by the research questions outlined in Chapter 1:

1. To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?
2. How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?
3. Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

These interview questions were designed to stimulate a conversation relating to the research questions that this thesis seeks to answer. Given their semi-structured nature, the interviews took their own direction. What is perhaps of interest is that due to the nature of these interview to generate grounded theory, the positioning of the researcher as an insider was key, as the conversations relied on the interviewer having a strong working knowledge of the concepts being explored.

The semi-structured interviews were informed by the research questions and conducted virtually. Interestingly much of the co-construction of meaning arose from shared experiences elaborated upon in the conversations during the interviews. As the conversations continued, the lived experiences of the participants and the experience of the researcher in the field led to the exploration of emerging themes. Each of the interviews was audio recorded and transcribed by the researcher. The transcripts were then coded line by line to identify common codes, themes and to later shape them into a substantive theory.

4.6 Transcription of Interviews

The transcription of the interviews was completed manually. Whilst laborious, this process is critical to the grounded theory approach as it provides the researcher with the opportunity to get to know the data well (Wuest, 2012). The interview transcripts were typed into columns to allow for line-by-line coding. An example of the layout is included here:

Figure 6

Sample Layout of Interview Transcript for Coding

Line	Interview Transcript	Coding
1	Ok thanks. Sorry for the interruption. There's	Nil
2	a real question for me about what we want the	Goals for schooling
3	school to be. Actually, I do think there's a	Conversations
4	conversation to have. How do you measure what an	Measurements
5	effective teacher looks like that consciously separates	NAPLAN
6	it from the NAPLAN conversation and say, what are	Conversations
7	the attributes that make a teacher brilliant? Let's turn	Teacher performance
8	it into a web diagram and use it as a learning tool -	Professional learning
9	Where am I strong? Where do I need to help? Let's	Teacher attributes
10	use that to guide the professional development.	Professional development

All of the content was de-identified as it was transcribed from the audio recording to safeguard the identities and protect the confidentiality of the participants who shared openly and authentically with the researcher.

4.7 Coding

When it comes to the categories, the codes were either “descriptive” or “explanatory” (Taylor & Bogdan, 1984, p. 124) with the aim of moving towards a coherent explanatory model. Upon completion of the interviews, data were coded in a process that is integral to grounded theory as it provides the basis for the analysis which, through theoretical integration, forms the skeleton of the study (Charmaz, 2006). The coding was completed using three methods: initial, focused, and theoretical coding. Initial coding involves sparking thinking and generating ideas

with an open mind (Charmaz, 2006; Glaser, 1978). This highlights the role of the researcher as “insider” because as Dey (1999) explains, an open mind does not mean an “empty head” (p.251). The skill and prior knowledge of the researcher is integral to the coding process. The discovery process of initial coding supports the research to identify gaps in the data (Charmaz, 2006). This study relies upon line-by-line coding which includes reviewing the data and naming each line (Glaser, 1978). In Constructivist Grounded Theory, the codes are constructed by the researcher as they interpret what emerges from the data by drawing on their prior and professional knowledge of the topic (Giles et al., 2016). To facilitate this, interview transcripts and the selected policy documents were typed into a template with two columns: 1. Transcript and 2. Codes as shown in Figure 7. Given the volume of the content and to protect the confidentiality of participants, the interview transcripts are not included but an example of the process is shown here:

Figure 7

Sample of Coding Transcribed Interviews with Frequent Codes

Line	Interview Transcript	Coding
1	It's that those with sway in policy tend to be people who	National policy
2	are what you would call centrist or conservative	Centrist, conservative
3	influences around education policy.	Educational policy
4	And there are media pressures. And so whenever it	Media headlines
5	doesn't matter what people say about the NAPLAN score	NAPLAN

Whereas initial coding takes place with speed and spontaneity following data collection, focused coding methods involve raising the most frequent codes to allow for synthesis across a larger data set (Giles et al., 2016). This involved the “constant comparison of data with data, and codes with data” (Giles et al., 2016, p.E35). This process elevates the data in preparation for abstraction and theorising. Finally, theoretical coding methods were employed once saturation was achieved, and no further data were generating additional codes. An example of this is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8*Theoretical Coding Method***4.8 Elicited Data and Extant Data**

Grounded theory does not limit the researcher as both qualitative and quantitative may be used, for as Glaser states, all are data (Glaser, 1998). Typically, a grounded theory study ‘generates’ data through individual interviews, focus group interviews, surveys, letters, government reports, policies, white papers, videos and more (Mills, Birks & Hoare, 2014). The data generated by participants are referred to as elicited data and that data that already exist in policy documents and the like are referred to as extant data (Ralph, Birks & Chapman, 2014).

This study began by accessing extant data in education policy documents and then carried out a process of co-constructing and eliciting data through a series of interviews with leaders in the field who work in the measurement of system-wide success. The extant data informing this project predominantly relates to measures of school performance and governmental directives. The inclusion of policy analysis was important as time invested in policy analysis informs why policies are developed, by whom and in context (Blackmore & Lauder, 2005).

The elicited data required for grounded theory was generated through semi-structured interviews with education leaders who met the criteria for this study. The participants were invited to share their visions for school success and to propose their views on the best measures to use in assessing system-wide success.

4.9 Theoretical Sampling

Where purposive sampling is undertaken *a priori*, theoretical sampling occurs much later in the grounded theory process when the researcher is starting to reflect upon and evaluate an array of theories and speculations based on the data (Bagnasco, Ghirotto & Sasso, 2014; Charmaz, 1990). At times, this involves the addition of different participants or new documents to verify and clarify the understanding of emerging theories late in the research process. This selection of data to identify gaps and silences, clarify anomalies and test insights is referred to as theoretical sampling (Chun Tie, Birks & Francis, 2019). Following this process, grounded theory requires the synthesis of the data to reveal the full picture of the story (Birks, Mills, & Francis, 2009; Strauss & Corbin, 1998). The next section considers how the analysis is undertaken.

4.9.1 Theoretical sensitivity linking to memo writing and data analysis

The skill of theoretical sensitivity is key to the analysis phase of the study. Theoretical sensitivity was originally described by Glaser and Strauss (1967) as the ability of the researcher to know when an important piece of data emerged that will be of significance to the development of the theory. This has been further elaborated as the researcher's insight or ability to recognise moments of significant discoveries that will have relevance to the emerging theory (Strauss & Corbin, 1990; Birks & Mills, 2015). For the researcher, this is developed through immersion in the data and research processes to foster this critical skill. In summary, theoretical sensitivity is all about the researcher's insight, understanding and ability to make meaning from the data (McCann & Clark, 2003; Strauss & Corbin, 1990; 1998). In this study, this was operationalised through engagement with the data until saturation. An in-depth review of policy, measurement and interview data coupled with the professional knowledge of the researcher from working within the system being examined supported the recognition of critical data as it emerged.

4.9.2 Constant Comparative Analysis

Through a method of constant comparison, the lines of transcribed interview data became codes, codes became categories, then categories in turn informed concepts (Charmaz, 2006). Constant comparative analysis between data, codes, memos, and categories was applied in order to embrace grounded theory as an iterative and recursive process when it comes to the collection and analysis of data (Chun Tie, Birks & Francis, 2019). Maykut and Morehouse (1994) drew on the work of Glaser and Strauss (1967) to develop the constant comparative method, explaining that we create our world with our words. Through our words we understand our context, justify, and defend our actions. Therefore, the researcher's role is to locate the patterns in those words through the continuous comparison of data. This is particularly relevant in this study given the careful examination of words espoused by the philosophical underpinnings of Foucault (see Chapter 2) and the identification of gaps and silences in Bacchi's (2012) 'What is the problem represented to be?' Framework for policy analysis.

Throughout the process, constant comparative analysis was used to undertake coding and category development in grounded theory studies when 'incidents' or 'units' were identified in the data (Birks & Mills, 2015; Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Charmaz (2006) defines constant comparative analysis as "a method of analysis that generates successively more abstract concepts . . . through inductive processes of comparing data with data, data with category, category with category and category with concept." (p.187). As codes become categories, they take two forms as seen in Table 2. This is presented as an example of how the process of constant comparative analysis was conducted throughout this study to help generate the categories for further exploration as the study progresses.

Table 2

Example of Participants' Language and Researcher's Language Generated Categories

Participants' Language	Researcher's Language
'tests,' 'testing,' 'HSC,' 'VCE,' 'exam'	Measurement
'teaching and learning,' 'successful teaching,' 'quality teaching and learning,'	Pedagogy

Lincoln and Guba (1985) advise that the process of constant comparison between the two ensures that thoughts are stimulated which lead to both 'descriptive' and 'explanatory' categories. This is further elaborated upon by Taylor and Bogdan (1984) who explain that by employing the constant comparative method, the researcher is involved in a process of coding and analysis to develop concepts that through continual comparison of specific incidents leads them to a coherent explanatory model.

4.10 Quality, Rigour and Congruence

Interestingly, Gioia et al. (2012) asked, "What does it take to imbue an inductive study with "qualitative rigor" while still retaining the creative, revelatory potential for generating new concepts and ideas for which such studies are best known?" (p.15). Whilst Geertz (1973) famously described qualitative data as thick and rich, many have questioned its rigour in scholarly research (Denzin & Lincoln, 2008). Where experimental design seeks truth through measures of reliability and validity, Mishler (1990) explains that in qualitative research is the trustworthiness of the data that is sought.

This study affirmed the trustworthiness of the data through the authority of those interviewed as experts in the field and triangulated their input with policy analysis and an examination of the validity of the test instruments included in the NAP through the lens of

Measurement Theory and Messick's concepts of validity (1989). The use of triangulation as a means of finding how frequently the concepts being explored are referred to is important in qualitative research (Mathison, 1988). It is for this reason that data were not collected by interview alone. Rather, this study engaged in semi-structured interviews, policy analysis and an explanation of NAP assessment instrument validity in order to triangulate the validity and trustworthiness of the findings (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2007). Table 3 shows how the research questions linked to the data sources and the processes applied. The three phases of policy analysis, measurement instrument validity and semi-structured interviews were undertaken and through constant comparative analysis the common codes, categories and themes were drawn.

Table 3

Alignment of Research Questions with Data Sources and Method

Research Questions	Methodology	Sampling	Data	Analysis
RQ1. To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?	Constructivist Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2006). Policy Analysis: What's the problem represented to be? (Bacchi, 2012)	Select policy document	Policy analysis	Coding, Memo, Constant Comp. Analysis
RQ2. How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?	Constructivist Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2006). Measurement theory and Validity theory (Messick, 1989)	NAP	Measurement Instrument Validation	Coding, Memo, Constant Comp. Analysis
RQ3. Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?	Constructivist Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2006)	Select interview participants	Semi-structured interviews	Coding, Memo, Constant Comp. Analysis

Creswell and Miller (2000) proposed three lenses that the qualitative researcher may view a study through to verify its validity: the researcher, the participants, and external reviewers. They propose that the researcher should triangulate data to ‘disconfirm evidence,’ the participants should have ‘prolonged engagement in the field’ and, voices external to the study (such as in the literature) should provide thick, rich description (p.126). In this study, validity was achieved through the triangulation of data, engagement with experts who are respected for their professional experience in the field, and through deep engagement with the literature, media and related viewpoints. The nexus or focal point of this study is represented in Figure 9.

Figure 9

The Nexus of the Study

This shows the three phases of the study designed to generate data and answer the three research questions posed. Where these three phases meet, it is hoped that the hypothesised misalignment between the goals for schooling and the measures used to attest to their achievement is evident.

4.13 The potential threats to the validity of this study

To address the diverse needs of qualitative studies, Lincoln and Guba (1985) provided a criterion to determine rigour: truth value; neutrality and applicability; and consistency in lieu of validity, reliability and generalisability. Given that a rigorous process is fundamental to excellence in adopting this methodology (Morse, 2007), several software alternatives were

trialled before the researcher's preferred tool was found. A combination of manual physical sticky notes on the office wall were used and then transferred into a digital Trello Board for safe storage and mapping. This was found to be the most effective and efficient tool to map the trail as it provided for an iterative and dynamic interaction with different thought processes as the researcher engaged with the data generated.

In addressing the need to minimise researcher bias, it is important to note that the researcher's perspective is embedded in grounded theory exploration and is critical to its process. The constructivist philosophy underpinning the choice of grounded theory provides for this methodological congruence. Reflecting on the choice to adopt a Constructivist Grounded Theory approach, the experience was akin to that of Breckenridge et al. (2012) who shared the plight of fellow doctoral researchers and beginning researchers who face into the complex ambiguities of such a task. With a choice between a Constructivist (Charmaz, 2003), Classic (Glaser, 1978) or the Straussian (Strauss & Corbin, 1990) approach to grounded theory, the Constructivist approach was favoured as it is consistent with the social research perspective that humans make meaning by engaging with the world around them (Appleton & King 2002). Given the role of the humans, both researcher and participant, engaged in this study to construct the meaning, this changes the traditional views on researcher bias by challenging the notion that a single truth can be found (Crotty 1998). Rather, the approach proffered by Charmaz (2003) denotes a vision of the co-creation of knowledge in the pursuit of meaning and understanding. Inspired by this methodological approach, this study seeks not to re-tell the stories of its participants but rather to find the thread that connects each of their stories (Breckenridge et al., 2009; Charmaz, 2003; Glaser, 2002). In doing so, the researcher's voice cannot be relegated to that of the distant other as in classical grounded theory (Glaser, 2002). Rather, the interactive conversation between researcher and participant provides for the co-construction of data (Charmaz, 2003). In many ways, this serves not to diminish the role of researcher bias but in many ways to shine a light on

it and bring it to the fore of the study. In grounded theory, researcher bias is revealed, accounted for, and incorporated into the study as more data to draw upon (Glaser, 1998). Whilst researcher objectivity and bias remain a key concern in all research, it is imperative to note that the aim of grounded theory is to arrive at a theory rather than an authoritative, single truth and should be viewed accordingly (Glaser, 1992).

Every researcher brings their own world view to their project and examines questions and problems that are embedded in a context of beliefs and interpretations. It would be naïve to think that a choice of topic is not swayed by personal interests, passions, and endeavours. In fact, to spend four years dedicating one's life to the pursuit of knowledge in a niche area of specialisation almost demands it. That is why the active acknowledgement of this bias is critical to ensure a body of work that is robust, congruent and of the highest possible quality. The initial provocation for embarking on this study was the apparent dissonance between the researcher's own experience as an educator in Australian schools with the media headlines pertaining to system-wide failure on the part of the K-12 school system. Therefore, a methodological approach was selected that situated the researcher as a co-constructor of the theory. To address the researcher's own potential biases based on personal experiences of working within a particular sector of the K-12 school system it was imperative that participants represented a broad section of educational leaders from across as many locations and school sectors as possible.

In response to challenges from quantitative researchers during the 1960s, Glaser and Strauss (1967) addressed quality in Grounded Theory. Constructivist Grounded Theory has its own criteria for quality: credibility, originality, resonance and usefulness (Charmaz & Thornberg, 2020). Table 4 includes each with an explanation and then shows the application of each to the study.

Table 4*Applying the Quality Criteria for CGT (Charmaz & Thornberg, 2020)*

Criteria: CGT Quality (Charmaz, 2006; 2014).	Explanation	Application to the Study
Credibility	“having sufficient relevant data for asking incisive questions about the data, making systematic comparisons throughout the research process, and developing a thorough analysis” (Charmaz & Thornberg, 2020, p.315).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extant data drawn from policy, media, reports and research used to shape the semi-structured interviews (Chapter 7) • Iterative process of coding and reviewing both the extant and elicit data throughout (see Chapter 7 for examples)
Originality	“offering new insights, providing a fresh conceptualization of a recognized problem, and establishing the significance of the analysis” (Charmaz & Thornberg, 2020, p.316).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The bringing together of Policy analysis (Bacchi, 2012), Validity (Messick, 1989) and educational leaders to explore this topic provided an original perspective to discuss the recognised and significant issue of Australia’s K-12 system-wide performance through CGT (Charmaz, 2006).
Resonance	“researchers must fit their data-gathering strategies to illuminate their participants’ experience” (Charmaz & Thornberg, 2020, p.316).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong responses from the invited participants demonstrated early resonance with the need for this research (see Section 4.2) • Interviews with participants reflected strong resonance with the emerging theory and its illumination of their own experiences (see Chapter 7)
Usefulness	“clarifying research participants’ understanding of their everyday lives, forming a foundation for policy and practice applications, contributing to creating new lines of research, as well as revealing pervasive processes and practices” (Charmaz & Thornberg, 2020, p.317).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The positive shared experience and rich conversations during the interviews spoke to the usefulness of the research to the participants (see Chapter 7) • Brought perspectives relevant to policy and practice with application to the field of measurement (See Chapter 8) • Generated opportunities to explore better ways and new lines of research (See RQ3) whilst recognising the pervasive limitations of current practice in a federated education system (Chapter 8).

In summary, the careful selection of the methodology has increased the truthfulness, applicability and consistency (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) of this study. The positioning of the researcher within the study and drawing on their professional experience in the field is in keeping with the Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) methodology and contributes to the overall rigour of the study by mitigating for bias.

4.14 Policy Analysis

Given that this study intersects educational policy and measurement practice in Australian schools, an additional tool was used to support the analysis of the relevant policies. The “What’s the Problem Represented to be?” (WPR) framework (Bacchi, 2012; Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016) for policy analysis was selected to meet the needs of this study as it examines the broad patterns within the discourse rather than focusing on the intricate details of the policy. In the context of a Constructivist Grounded Theory study the chosen framework for policy analysis is consistent with the researchers’ ontological and epistemological positions. The adoption of the WPR framework for policy analysis to address RQ1 and identify the drivers that underpin the goals of the Australian education system involved reading and reviewing the documents with a ‘discerning eye’ to examine how the problem is being presented in order to establish the interplay between policy and politics (Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016). The Constructivist Grounded Theory approach refers to this process as applying the researcher’s theoretical sensitivity.

To utilise the WPR framework for policy analysis, the following questions are posed: ‘What’s the problem represented to be in a specific policy or policies?’, ‘What deep-seated presuppositions or assumptions underlie this representation of the ‘problem’ (problem representation)?’, ‘How has this representation of the ‘problem’ come about?’, ‘What is left unproblematic in this problem representation? Where are the silences? Can the ‘problem’ be conceptualised differently?’, ‘What effects (discursive, subjectification, lived) are produced by

this representation of the ‘problem?’, ‘How and where has this representation of the ‘problem’ been produced, disseminated, and defended?’, and ‘How has it been and/or how can it be disrupted and replaced?’ (Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016, p.20). Each of these questions was applied to the ‘problem’ being explored. To facilitate this process, the template shown in Table 5 was used (please note the completed table is shown as Table 6 later in the chapter).

Table 5

WPR (Bacchi, 2012) Policy Analysis Template

What is the ‘problem’ represented to be? What deep-seated presuppositions or assumptions underlie this ‘problem’? How has this representation of the ‘problem’ come about? What is left unproblematic in this problem representation? Where are the silences? Can the ‘problem’ be thought about differently? What effects are produced by this representation of the ‘problem’? How has this representation been produced, disseminated, and defended? How can it be questioned, disputed & disrupted?	
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This process of policy analysis supports the researcher in the pursuit of emerging categories for exploration. In addition, a key word search was used as part of the initial coding, and this elicited a selection of terms to inform the generation of codes and categories. So too, this proved useful in identifying the gaps and silences in the policy being reviewed.

As noted previously in Table 4 when discussing credibility in CGT, the output from this policy analysis, in addition to the researcher’s own experience and the research literature served to guide the conversations and semi-structured interviews with the participants. This approach

was advantageous as the policy analysis supported the development of key memos and themes that were explored with the participants during the interviews and across the study. Figure 10 shows the inputs that informed and shaped the themes as they emerged as a result of the coding and memo writing process:

Figure 10

Process From Policy To Theme

A semi-structured approach to the interviews allowed for the leaders to proffer their insights, experiences, and real-world learnings from engaging with national policies and assessments in their daily work over a number of years. Given the depth of expertise, experience and knowledge of the interview participants, the role of the researcher as a ‘co-constructor of the data’ was best achieved using a conversational style that engaged authentically with these leaders in the field and respected their contribution (Buys et al., 2022). This is explored in Chapter 7.

4.15 Reflexivity of the researcher

The reflexivity of the researcher is inherent in studies that adopt a Constructivist Grounded Theory methodology. Charmaz (2020) explains that this “prompts us not only to examine who we are in relation to the research but also to remain reflexive about how we use grounded theory strategies and make claims about our findings” (p.165).

One of the appeals of Constructivist Grounded Theory is that it recognises and situates the researcher in the field of study, allowing them to remain engaged with the events and themes as they emerge. By attending to the research with reflexivity and sensitivity, attention is paid to the nuances of language, meaning and the conditions under which the research moves into the public domain (Charmaz, 2020; Clarke, Friese & Washburn, 2017).

Throughout this study, the researcher remained reflexive in approach and undertook to delve into any preconceived ideas to thoroughly examine the diverse and powerful influences on the research. For example, at the outset this research hypothesised that there was a misalignment between Australia’s national goals for schooling and the measures used to assess the progress towards their achievement. Preconceived ideas of the researcher working in an independent school located in the affluent suburbs of Sydney may have led to the conclusion that the test data stating the system is in decline and failing its stakeholders are invalid or unreliable. However, remaining open and reflexive to the ideas presented during this research has enabled the researcher to examine the gaps and silences in the language used to describe the education system and the measurement instruments used to assess it. In summary, a willingness to doubt convenient explanations sparked deeper and richer conceptual insights (Locke, Golden-Biddle & Feldman, 2008).

4.16 Chapter Summary

This chapter outlined the methods employed to complete this study. It examined sample selection and participant recruitment before exploring the ethical considerations, data collection, analysis and the emerging themes arising from the coding, memo writing, and constant comparative analysis employed. A review of the importance of quality, rigour, and congruence (Morse, 2007) was particularly important as qualitative research is regularly questioned for its rigour. The chapter concluded with details of the data collection, triangulation, and credibility. Examples were included throughout to demonstrate the procedures employed. The research phases arising from this method fell naturally into three parts: policy analysis, review of measurement instruments, and interviews which are explored in detail over the next three chapters.

Over the next three chapters, the policy analysis, reviews and interviews undertaken are explored in detail. These chapters each detail how the methods have been employed to answer their respective research questions.

Chapter 5: Policy Analysis

This chapter begins with a reminder as to the important role policy plays in providing the education system with its purposeful intent and goals for success. Referencing Australia's National Education Policy and Reporting Framework (ACARA, 2013), the focal policies for this study are documented. To answer the first research question, 'To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?', an analysis of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) has been undertaken using Bacchi's (2012) WPR framework. The chapter concludes with a review of the limits and challenges. Figure 11 below shows the research process that was applied to the policy analysis in keeping with the Constructivist Grounded Theory methodology.

Figure 11

Research Process for Policy Analysis

5.1 The Role of Policy

The federal policy documents outlining the national goals for schooling were designed with the intent of providing the education system with a roadmap for success to provide educators with a sense of knowing where they are going. These policies serve to guide, mould, and shape the system to meet the needs of the society and are much needed by the educators who reside at the chalk face of the education system. A sense of significance is a basic human need and by working with a sense of purpose humans are both more engaged and motivated (Anderson, 2010; Maslow, 1943). Clear policy documents that are aligned to practice afford educators (and other key stakeholders) the purpose and motivation they need. Challenges arise for the teacher workforce when there is misalignment, misuse, and a lack of direction.

By adopting the strategies of assessment for learning, teachers regularly commence their lessons with stated learning goals and work with their students to co-create a criteria for what success looks like (Black & William, 1998; Clarke, 2001). Teachers use these strategies to support students with a clear path towards success, and they work. So too, education policy ought to provide educators and school leaders with the same sense of clear direction towards success. An examination of policy is therefore critical to the debate on the success of Australia's education system as the system is awash with policy layering and reform in the pursuit of school improvement (Ball, 2012; Stacey et al., 2023).

Sadly, an ever-changing flow of initiatives, demands and redirections is not new territory for teachers (Ball, 2003). In fact, Stacey et al. (2023) argue that for teachers in Australia, policy has become synonymous with change. The advent of 'fast policy' and 'policy layering' is adding considerably to teacher workload and their sense of disempowerment. There has long been an observed acceleration when it comes to technology, social change, and the pace of life but in recent times that rate of change seems to have increased (Rosa, 2003). The surge in the uptake of fast policy where governments lean on global models for adoption at national and local levels

(Peck & Theodore, 2015) may well be due to what Fawcett (2018) explains as the increased rate at which ideas are shared.

Trends in literature reflect a growing discourse centred on the neo-liberalist marketisation and privatisation of what has traditionally been the remit of the public sector (Ball, 2012; Hogan, 2016). This drives an interesting tension between the purpose of education policy and the motivations of for-profit businesses. Hogan poses the question as to whether these educational businesses are “working to construct policy problems which they can subsequently solve through their commercial activities” (Hogan, 2016, p.96). Further to this, Hogan (2016) asserts the role of a “pervasive neoliberal imaginary” at work in Australia’s education assessment landscape which is actively seeking to influence policy such that the privatisation of education is being used to drive school improvement and raise student achievement (p.93). In an inclusive governance structure where private companies and governments partner to co-create policy, there is a tendency for the establishment of relational assets and the lines between public and private to become increasingly blurred (Leitner & Sheppard, 2002; Storper, 1997). The policy drivers emerging from the collaboration of governments with private, for-profit companies are volatile, complex and at times, hard to unravel (Ball, 2012). This is most apparent through the rapid advancements in technology and the role these companies are playing in forcing policy to play catch up with what the technology can do in schools.

As a result of the contested policy space arising from the tensions between the public good and the private profits, the Melbourne Declaration on Educational Goals for Young Australians (MCEETYA, 2008) first hinted at a revision of the purpose of schooling. However, until issues such as the role of the states and territories alongside the federal government, the influence of educational businesses, and the ongoing tension between social mobility, social efficiency and equality is resolved in some way, the contestation of the purpose for schooling in

Australia continues. This makes the role of the school leader, who resides firmly at the juncture of such tensions, more complex and demanding than ever.

The role of the teacher has moved well beyond traditional instruction in reading, writing and arithmetic. At the policy level, the role of the teacher has evolved to create students who can think critically and creatively, solve complex problems, make evidence-based decisions, and work collaboratively (Weldon, 2019). Australia responded with the inclusion of general capabilities in the national curriculum (ACARA, 2011b) and UNESCO reports that approximately 90 countries now make generic references to competencies in their curricula (Tedesco, Opertti & Amadio, 2013). Far from shying away from the foundational aspects of the curriculum (reading, writing and arithmetic), education systems are required to equip students to apply their knowledge within the socio-cultural context of their societies (Kim, Care & Vista, 2019). This discussion of general capabilities is important as it resides within a wider conversation around curriculum and what it is that Australian students need, and how knowledge, skills, capabilities, and standards should best be prioritised and integrated (Yates, 2017). Looking to the future, the OECD has published the “Learning Framework 2030” which builds on their original key competencies and looks to develop young people to be future ready (OECD, 2018). Interestingly, the collaboration between the OECD and ACARA whilst working on this project is thought to have an impact on future policy decisions for Australia (Weldon, 2019).

The general capabilities of the Australian curriculum are designed to support young people in the development of the knowledge, skills and dispositions needed to actively contribute to society in a meaningful way (ACARA, 2011b; Weldon, 2019). Yet, what is not clear is how they are implemented in Australian classrooms, by whom and to what effect. There appears to exist a gap between policy and practice with teachers expected to play a role in the development of these capabilities in Australia’s young people without guidance as to how to operationalise that goal (Lamb, Maire & Doeke, 2017). A disconnect in policy and practice that is impacting

teacher agency and is predominantly due to the increasing role of non-educators in shaping and crafting education policy (Burgess & Lowe, 2022). This is important in terms of contextualising the contested space in which the NAP and the system-wide measures of success reside.

5.2 Australia's National Education Policy and Reporting Framework

To help educators and other key stakeholders navigate the complex interplay between policy and reporting, Figure 12 was included in the *Measurement framework for schooling in Australia 2020* (ACARA, 2020a). It shows how the key policy documents and reports interact with the national priorities and commitments to provide an iterative cycle of policy formation, review, reporting, and evaluation.

Figure 12

National School Education Policy and Reporting Framework (ACARA, 2020a)

(ACARA, 2020a, p.2).

For this study, there are three foci drawn from Figure 12. They are: 1) the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Education Declaration (Education Council, 2019) 2) the Measurement Framework (ACARA, 2020a) including the key performance measures it includes and, 3) the National Report on Schooling 2021 (ACARA, 2020a). The Declaration (Education Council, 2019) includes the nationally agreed goals and commitments. The National Report on Schooling in Australia 2021 (ACARA, 2020a) consists of: 1) a written report which addresses the eleven areas of commitment outlined in the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) declaration, the national policy and reporting for school education in Australia, and finally reports against the key performance measures (KPMs) for schooling as detailed in the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia 2020 (ACARA, 2020a), and 2) the online National Report on Schooling data portal.

5.3 Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Education Declaration

The Declaration (Education Council, 2019) is the policy at the centre of the National Education Policy and Reporting Framework (see Figure 12 above) and provides an overarching vision for Australian education. It is the fourth version of such a national agreement which has been endorsed by every state and territory government in addition to the federal government. It documents their shared vision for education in Australia. As such, the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) is a suitable policy to help answer the research question, to what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

The Declaration (Education Council, 2019) consists of four parts: preamble, goals, commitments to action, and concluding comments (achievements). The preamble introduces the document and situates young Australians at the centre of the policy. This is followed by two goals:

Goal 1: The Australian education system promotes excellence and equity.

Goal 2: All young Australians become:

- confident and creative individuals
- successful lifelong learners
- active and informed members of the community

(Education Council, 2019, p.4)

Next, the ministers' commitments to action are outlined. These are critical to this study as it is where the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) documents how the goals will be achieved through the government's commitment to work with and for young Australians. The concluding comments in the Declaration made by the Education Council (2019) are titled "achievements" and refer to good quality data, public reporting and a biennial forum.

5. 4 Bacchi's (2012) What is the 'problem' represented to be?' Framework

Bacchi (2012) developed the "What's the Problem Represented to be?" (WPR) framework as a tool to facilitate the critical reading and examination of public policies. It is based on the premise that if one decides to act on an issue it is because it has been found to be problematic. The policy analysis in this thesis was completed utilising Bacchi's WPR framework (Bacchi, 2012; Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016) with the goal of examining the broad patterns within the discourse rather than focusing on the intricacies of the policy. Thus, providing the opportunity to rethink the way these problems are being represented in policy. Bacchi's (2009) approach to policy analysis has been applied due to its synergy with the Constructivist Grounded Theory methodology (Charmaz, 2006) employed in this study. The WPR Framework provides a lens through which to determine the "particular kinds of problems" that such policies elucidate (Bacchi & Goodwin 2016, p. 14). By exploring how the problem is represented, Bacchi (2009) suggests that it is possible to make a better sense of it and appreciate how it became what Foucault refers to as a regime of truth (Foucault, 1977).

Bacchi (2012) describes WPR analysis as firstly requiring the researcher to read and review the selected policies with a ‘discerning eye’ as to how the problem is being represented before subjecting it to further scrutiny. In WPR analysis, the aim, Bacchi states, is to make the interplay between politics and policy visible (Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016). Thus, helping examine the gaps, silences, and omissions in the policy text.

Burgess and Lowe (2022) completed an analysis of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019), using Bacchi’s, “What’s the problem represented to be” (WPR) method, to examine the representation of Aboriginal perspectives in the policy and a similar approach will be employed here. The WPR method for policy analysis uses six questions to guide the reader as they engage with the document. For the purpose of this study, the researcher applied those questions (as outlined in the following table) to the selected policy and a summary of the answers to them is displayed in the table which follows:

Table 6

WPR Questions and Answers

WPR Questions (Bacchi, 2016, p.20)	Mparntwe Education Declaration
What is the ‘problem’ represented to be?	Defining the purpose for schooling in Australia
What deep-seated presuppositions or assumptions underlie this representation of the ‘problem’?	Economic prosperity, neoliberal discourse, human capital theory, individual achievement
How has this representation of the ‘problem’ come?	Fourth iteration of the Declaration
What is left unproblematic in this representation? Where are the silences? Can it be thought about differently?	Absence of creativity, spirituality, resilience, alternative ways of knowing, misalignment of policy and practice
What effects are produced by this representation?	Misalignment between the goals, measures and daily life in Australian schools
How has this representation of the ‘problem’ been produced, disseminated and defended?	‘good quality’ data and evidence, consented authority of that evidence

The way in which the problem is presented is critical to examine as it provides the researcher with insights as to how the issue is conceived by those in power, how people implementing the policy are being positioned to view it and how the issues will be addressed (Bacchi, 2009). Here, WPR guided the analysis of how the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Education Declaration (Education Council, 2019), has problematised the purpose for schooling in Australia (Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016).

As all levels of Australian government worked to drive the social mobility of the nation, the rise of the neoliberal ideologies created distinct shifts in the purposes of education (Cranston et al., 2010). In representing the problem as the purpose of schooling in Australia, it is opportune to examine a view which places education as the bedrock of society (Reid, 2019).

5.4.1 Problem Representation

What deep-seated presuppositions or assumptions underlie this representation of the ‘problem’ (problem representation)? The Declaration (Education Council, 2019) opens with the statement, “Young Australians are at the centre of the Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Declaration. Education has the power to transform lives” (p.2). Developed and agreed to by every education minister from each state and territory, the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) articulates the goals and vision for a world-class education system for Australia. Following the Melbourne Declaration (MCEETYA, 2008), this policy seeks to build on that knowledge and the inputs from stakeholders to “set out our vision for education in Australia and our commitment to improving educational outcomes for young Australians” (p.2).

Examining the presuppositions and assumptions underlying this policy, Skourdoumbis, Thomas and Rawolle (2023) argue that the commitments to action and goals articulated in the Declaration “reflect many of the social, political and economic values and beliefs common to and prevalent within the knowledge economy discourse” (p.12). Persistent messaging that

portrays education as the “panacea for economic prosperity” seemingly underpins this policy and is consistent with a very “western” conception of success (Burgess & Lowe, 2022, p.7). In their analysis of Australian education policy using WPR, Patrick and Moodie (2016) also examined the way the problem was presented and identified the growing influence of the neoliberal discourse evident in the education system as influencing the definition of success as individual achievement in a market economy. Table 7 draws together some of the research to identify the social, political and economic assumptions underpinning the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) to better understand how the problem is represented in the policy:

Table 7

Some Assumptions Underpinning the Declaration (Education Council, 2019)

Social	<p>"strong theme of publicness that aims to strengthen individuals and enrich the community" (Biesta et al., 2022, p.1219). "key democratic values of developing active, informed and engaged citizens", "diversity", "social cohesion" (Thorpe, ten Kate & Burgess, 2024, p.1).</p> <p>"commitments to action within the declarations involve 'developing,' 'supporting,' 'strengthening,' 'enhancing,' 'improving' partnerships between parents and schools, teachers and their teaching practice/s, the curriculum, accountability mechanism" (Skourdoumbis et al., 2023, p.13).</p>
Political	<p>Educationalisation as "thrusting social including economic problems and responsibilities onto the education system as the means for their solution" (Skourdoumbis et al., 2023, p.8).</p> <p>Gewirtz et al. (2021) suggest this represents a "...a top-down approach to governance that focuses on improving public service delivery processes by identifying goals, and measures to assess progress towards them (p.504).</p> <p>Neoliberal discourse (Patrick & Moodie, 2016; Burgess & Lowe, 2022).</p>
Economic	<p>"...designed to motivate and inform system improvements with respect to both excellence and equity and ensure that public money is well spent" (Gewirtz et al., 2021, p. 505).</p> <p>"panacea for economic prosperity..." (Burgess & Lowe, 2022, p.7).</p> <p>Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1964).</p> <p>Equity and fairness through the lens of economic rationality, market liberalism and productivity (Savage, 2014).</p>

5.4.2 Problem Generation

How has this representation of the ‘problem’ come about? Foucault explained that the way discourses are constructed in turn construct the objects of which they speak (Foucault, 1972; 1977). Therefore, it is imperative to examine the discourse constructed in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) to understand how the purpose of Australia’s education system is being shaped and the power relations inherent in it (Ball, 2012).

The Declaration (Education Council, 2019) is the latest iteration of the national policy outlining Australia’s goals and purpose for schooling. It supersedes the past three declarations: Hobart (1989), Adelaide (1999) and Melbourne (2008) to meet the needs of Australian children today. Each of these declarations was agreed upon and given signed endorsement by the leaders responsible for education in each state and territory as well as on behalf of the Commonwealth. These declarations reflect an evolution of education policy – its politics and its power – over the past 30 years.

From the late 1980s, Australia entered into a period of policy trends that saw the federal governments of the era actively pursuing a more coordinated national approach to school despite education historically being under the remit of the states and territories (Nevill & Savage, 2023). In the pursuit of a national approach and under the influence of standards-based reform advocated by the OECD, the Hobart Declaration on Schooling (Australian Education Council of Ministers, 1989) provided a means for all education ministers to agree on common learning goals and a national curriculum (Nevill & Savage, 2023).

In the 1990s, during the rule of the Keating Labor party, the Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training and Youth Affairs (MCEETYA) was formed with the aim of coordinating education policy and driving forward a national agenda for equity. It was building upon this work that the federal, state and territory ministers furthered the achievement of a

national approach to schooling with the signing and dissemination of the Adelaide Declaration on National Goals for Schooling in the Twenty-first Century (MCEETYA, 1999). The Adelaide Declaration (MCEETYA, 1999) reflected the assertion of the federal government as a controlling force that was reflected in renewed intergovernmental collaboration and a shift in the funding plans for schools (Lingard, 2000).

Ten years later, the Melbourne Declaration (MCEETYA, 2008) was agreed during the tenure of the Rudd / Gillard Labor government. Whilst continuing to uphold the tenets of neoliberalism and human capital theory, the Melbourne Declaration (MCEETYA, 2008) suggested a hint at revising the purpose for schooling to align once more with the public good (Cranston et al., 2010). With a renewed focus on the purpose for education, Australia's national priorities were shaped by the Melbourne Declaration on Educational Goals for Young Australians (the Melbourne Declaration) (MCEETYA, 2008). The Melbourne Declaration was pivotal in Australia's education policy development as it aligned with the launch of the national curriculum (ACARA, 2012a) and the National Assessment Program (ACARA, 2011a).

Given that the Melbourne Declaration (MCEETYA, 2008) was seminal in shaping Australian education over the past ten years, there was much anticipation for the most recent iteration (Brown & Warner, 2022). In 2019, the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) was signed and agreed by all federal, state and territory ministers. National education policies in Australia are a mammoth feat of collaboration as they are not the work of a single political jurisdiction (Brown & Warner, 2022). Interestingly, it is this very factor that made the Melbourne Declaration (MCEETYA, 2008) successful in achieving so many steps forward on the path to nationalise education in Australia as at the time there was great political synergy across the country under the Labor party (Lingard, 2014). The Alice Springs (Mparntwe) Education Declaration (Education Council, 2019) may not have benefited from the same synergistic political context but despite this it has been embedded successfully.

When reflecting on how the problem of the purpose for education in Australia is represented, it is therefore important to appreciate that this policy is the fourth iteration of a plan to document the national goals for schooling, and that it must be read in the context that the discourse was constructed with an awareness and understanding of the politics at play locally and globally.

5.4.3 Gaps and Silences

Where are the silences? Can the ‘problem’ be thought about differently? To commence exploring what remains unproblematic in the representation of the problem, let us first look to some of the ongoing problems.

The Declaration (Education Council, 2019) acknowledges the critical importance of human attributes such as creativity, resilience, and spirituality in its preamble:

Education plays a vital role in promoting the intellectual, physical, social, emotional, moral, **spiritual**, and aesthetic development and wellbeing of young Australians, and in ensuring the nation’s ongoing economic prosperity and social cohesion. They need to deal with information abundance and navigate questions of trust and authenticity. They need flexibility, **resilience**, **creativity**, and the ability and drive to keep on learning throughout their lives. (p.2)

Yet, these concepts are rarely referred to again throughout the remainder of the policy. Whilst the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) acknowledges the role of education in developing the young people of Australia holistically with consideration for every facet of thriving of in a volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) world (Mackey, 1992; MacArthur, 2020), the policy fails to address the development of these human attributes in an ongoing fashion. Little reference is made to these concepts beyond the preamble and there is no actionable policy for their inclusion in the daily life of schools, the National Assessment Program (NAP) or the

Measurement Framework which gives an indication of their relative importance in the system.

Yet, they are key aspects that the Australian ministers of education from each state and territory have agreed are pivotal to the success of young people in the future. A simple keyword search of the inclusion of the terms ‘creativity, ‘resilience’ and ‘spiritual’ shows the following:

Table 8

Policy References to Creativity, Resilience, and the Spiritual

Keyword	Number of appearances in the Preamble	Number of appearances in the body of text
Creativity	1	0
Resilience	1	1
Spiritual	1	2

The references to ‘spiritual’ in the body of the text refer to students being able to “manage their emotional, mental, cultural, spiritual and physical wellbeing” (p.6) or parents and guardians working to promote “social, emotional, intellectual, spiritual and physical wellbeing” in the child’s early years of development (p.10). So too, with the term ‘creative’ there are multiple references to it in the policy, but they are different in meaning to the concept of ‘creativity’ expressed in the preamble. This reflects a misalignment between the generic references in the preamble and the more specific references which follow in the indicators and commitments to action. Therefore, this remains problematic.

Another challenge presented in this policy analysis is the absence of an appreciation for the progress and growth of the whole student. Whilst cognisant of the frequency students attend school, little attention is paid to measuring the social, emotional, physical, and spiritual wellbeing of the student whilst they are there. Now, this does not mean these attributes should be

measured as part of the NAP but, they are significant outcomes that schools work tirelessly to achieve and yet are not featured in the measures of school success. As they are not explicitly referenced one may question how they are valued, taught, and reported at the school level? Hoffman and Miller (2020) reported, one of the key findings from the Covid-19 related school closures was the recognition of the significant role schools play in providing non-academic supports such as “health and mental health services, food assistance, obesity prevention, and intervention in case of homelessness and maltreatment” (p.201). There appears to be misalignment between the goals and commitments articulated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). A problem that will be further addressed in Chapter 6.

One of the silences in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) arises from aligning the purpose of education with economic outcomes without addressing the perceived decline in student performance preceding its adoption. Skourdoumbis et al. (2023) believe that an agenda driving educational and economic advancement through the key goals of equity and excellence permeate both Declarations (MCEETYA, 2008; Education Council, 2019). A vision that is presented against the backdrop of a decline in student performance from 2000 to 2019 as a “consequence of broader dysfunction in the education system” (Skourdoumbis et al., 2023, p.2) and which is not addressed directly in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). Skourdoumbis et al. (2023) conclude that within the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) there is a mismatch between policy and practice which is synergistic with the premise of this thesis.

5.4.4 Problem Effects

What effects are produced by this representation of the ‘problem’ by the Declaration? This questions seeks to contextualise the thinking and align it with lived experience rather than “cut off from daily life” (Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016, p.23). Take for example the problems caused by the misalignment of the terms ‘creativity,’ ‘spirituality’ and ‘resilience’ in the Declaration

(Education Council, 2019) as discussed in Section 5.4.3. The representation of the “problem” in this way is not congruent with the daily life of many schools in Australia.

One such example arises from the absence of a consistent use of the term spirituality. The Australian education system that is highly privatised (OECD, 2010) and in 2020 included approximately 2,900 catholic and independent schools who are predominantly faith based (Statista Research Department, 2023). That represents almost 30% of the approximately 9,600 schools across Australia in 2020. Without misleadingly conflating spirituality with faith, it is worth noting that many of these schools reference the development of their students’ spirituality as a key differentiator and their school leaders reference their own spirituality as underpinning and informing their perspectives (Striepe, Clarke & O’Donoghue, 2014).

Similarly, there are schools in Australia that are entirely dedicated to the pursuit of the Arts and the development of actors, musicians, artists, and other creatives. So, the absence of creativity from the national policy regarding the purpose for schooling is again problematic for these institutions who dedicated their time to it and focus their pedagogy through it. A society without creativity would be bereft of imagination and innovation, a world with no new inventions or ways of doing. Whilst the battle to determine the nature of creativity rages on (Lubart & Guignard, 2004), a reframing is in order. As creativity becomes entangled in a universalised discourse it is increasingly aligned with the innovation and resourcefulness needed to survive in an economically competitive climate (Craft, 2003). As a term, creativity is often used synonymously with innovation and both are regarded as being an essential component of individual and organisational success (Beghetto, Kaufman & Beier, 2017).

In *The Dakar Framework for Action: Education for All*, education was represented as a means for African peoples to navigate their own futures, free from oppression and moving forward with creativity, critical thinking, and resilience (UNESCO, 2000). In this way, creativity represents an imaginative and agile people who signify economic hope for the future (Harvey,

2007; Moran, 2010; Sahlberg & Oldroyd, 2010). Creativity need not be viewed as the antithesis to economic prosperity. Florida (2005) argues that creativity is a key driver of economic success. So, the issue of creativity in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) remains problematic chiefly because the inability to validly measure it in a standardised way at scale renders it so.

Resilience is best thought of as an “umbrella term to cover many aspects of overcoming adversity and adapting to one's environment” (McCubbin, 2001, p.3). In an effort to conceptualise resilience consideration must be given to the interactions between an individual and the environment they exist within (Langham et al., 2018). It would be simple to consider resilience as one’s ability to simply bounce back after a challenging situation (Zolkoski & Bullock, 2012) but recent developments in this field of study have seen a deepened appreciation for the impact of the socioecological environment, particular on those who are marginalized (Ungar, 2004). Facing into uncertainty, both economic and social, the education system must support young people to grow up as well-informed, resilient, and adaptable individuals (Lamb et al., 2020). Yet in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) the way the concept of resilience is inconsistently addressed throughout the document effects the representation of the problem.

In a world where human attributes such as resilience, creativity and spirituality will separate humans from the machines with the advent of Generative AI, it is anticipated that a further informed and enlightened version of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) may emerge in the future with a deeper consideration for such quintessentially human concepts. If the knowledge, skills, and capabilities acquired through education are seen to maximise one’s human capital (Becker, 1994), then the acquisition of creativity, resilience, and a sense of other through spirituality, will undoubtedly serve young people well in an increasingly VUCA world.

In addition to the inconsistent references and silences, perhaps the most concerning effect of representing the problem in this way is the misalignment between policy, practice and measurement in the K-12 education system. It is evident that the “problem” represented does not

adequately reference the need to align these three key components of education. Nor is it an acceptable reflection of what happens in Australian schools daily. This issue is a focal point of this study and will be further explored in the following chapters.

5.4.5 Problem Production and Dissemination

How and where has this representation of the ‘problem’ been produced, disseminated, and defended? How can it be questioned, disputed, and disrupted? Imbued with neoliberal ideology, the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) drives an agenda consistent with the belief that the social good is achieved by maximizing human capital and consequently, economic prosperity (Harvey, 2007). The Declaration (Education Council, 2019) is widely available online and has been published on government websites and in hard copy. It has also been disseminated in the media and widely through peer-reviewed research journals, papers, and conferences. Through this dissemination, there has also been the opportunity to question and dispute through the same means.

5.5 Limits and Challenges

After exploring the extent to which the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them (RQ1) through WPR policy analysis (Bacchi, 2012), it is evident that there is some misalignment between this policy and daily practice in Australian schools. Whether this is due to the neo-liberal discourse which drives the policy to rely upon measurement to standardise and regulate the system or the gaps that exist due to the misalignment between policy and practice in the document, limitations and challenges are evident.

5.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter sought to address RQ1, to what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them? Having explored the importance of education policy in providing a roadmap for success, this chapter examined the National Education Policy and Reporting Framework (ACARA, 2013) and undertook a detailed analysis of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) using Bacchi's (2012) WPR Framework. Towards its conclusion, the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) states, "good quality data and information is important for educators ... and governments. Good data will provide information ...including pathways into further education and employment. This will be used to inform policy development and ... track progress against the goals of this declaration." (p.11). The limits of what can be measured economically and at scale across the nation remains problematic in being able to align the agreed goals and measures of success with the daily lives of Australian schools, teachers and students. It is therefore timely to progress towards answering the next research question to examine how the achievement of the goals outlined in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) are currently measured? The next chapter will address this through a detailed review of the measurement instruments employed through the lens of consequential validity.

Chapter 6: Exploring the National Assessment Program

This chapter addresses the second research question, how is the achievement of Australia's goals for schooling currently measured? As such, the chapter commences with an overview of the NAP, a key component of the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a). It elaborates on the domestic and international assessments that are used nationally to report on the performance of Australian schools which were introduced in Chapter 2. This chapter engages in an exploration of Australia's national performance on the NAP measures from the year 2000 when Australia first participated in PISA up to 2020. The chapter concludes by deliberating whether ILSA such as PISA, PIRLS and TIMSS are exerting too much influence on educational policy in Australia (Gorur & Wu, 2015).

Tests and assessments are frequently used in Australian schools to provide a snapshot of performance at a given moment in time. However, these isolated data points must be examined in the context of the students' lived experience. Engaging with multiple methods, multiple opportunities and multiple judges will ensure educators are equipped with the reliable data needed to make informed, qualified decisions (Brennan, 1996). Is this what is meant by the subjective descriptor of data as 'good quality' (Burgess & Lowe, 2022)? Or is it rather a reference to valid, reliable, and fair data as defined by the Pillars of Sound Assessment (Gilmore, 2020)? What is good quality data and where is it defined in the Mparntwe Declaration (Education Council, 2019)?

The data referred to in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) assumes a positivist view of data which is relied upon to produce an accurate and reliable view of what is being measured (Burgess & Lowe, 2022). It also documents the ways in which the government intends to use the data to: "analyse how well schools are performing against each other and internationally", "identify schools with students with particular needs", "understand outcomes in

relation to educational disadvantage and target resources accordingly”, “determine where resources are most needed to support student learning needs and lift attainment”, “ensure equity of access to education”, “identify best practice and innovation”, “conduct national and international comparisons of approaches and performance”, and “develop a substantive, evidence base on what works” (Education Council, 2019). The transparency with which the Government shares how this ‘good quality’ data will be used is admirable but there is a concern about the validity of the results. Attention must be given also to the unintended consequences (consequential validity) of using the test instruments and measures in this way (Messick, 1989).

In Australia, the education assessment landscape is a richly contested space with some viewing it as ‘ubiquitous and unpopular’ (Care et al., 2019). Considerable work has been undertaken to define the skills and capabilities that students should be expected to achieve at different levels (Weldon, 2019) and the NAP outlines in detail how the nation will go about measuring its achievement of those national goals which can be assessed in a standardised way. The NAP provides measures of those components of the national goals for schooling that can be measured in a standardised way. It is through the NAP that governments, education authorities and schools determine whether young Australians are meeting important educational outcomes and learning milestones (ACARA, 2015). The NAP is overseen by AESOC and managed by ACARA. It includes the following assessments: NAPLAN, NAP Sample Assessments, PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS, as explained in Chapter 2. This chapter elaborates on each assessment to ascertain the national performance on each and how effective (valid) each has been in achieving its purpose.

6.1 NAPLAN

As explained in Chapter 2, NAPLAN is an annual assessment which tests all Australian students in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9 of their schooling journeys. Students sit tests that measure their basic skill levels in Reading, Writing, Spelling, Grammar & Punctuation and Numeracy.

NAPLAN is delivered in every state of Australia and since 2018 a digital version, NAPLAN online has been introduced. Since 2022 all schools are now able to participate in NAPLAN online. The individual student results are posted directly to the student's homes and school results are published on the *My Schools* website (ACARA, 2010).

In Australia during the 1980s there was an absence of broad perspective, standardised assessment information being reported to parents (McGaw et al., 2020). States and territories spent the late 1980s through to the 1990s developing and implementing census-based literacy and numeracy tests in an effort to fill the gap left by the removal of the comparative reports on student achievement the state-based examinations had previously provided (McGaw et al., 2020). By 2007, the Ministerial Council recognised and resolved the need for common tests and the National Assessment Program: Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN) was launched in 2008. The early 2000's in Australian education represented a period of reform emphasising system-wide monitoring and accountability (Wilson et al., 2021). During this time, NAPLAN was built on the foundation of almost 20 years of similar state and territory level testing (McGaw et al., 2019; 2020). This historical context is important to frame the purpose of NAPLAN.

NAPLAN serves five purposes as endorsed by the Ministerial Council: monitoring, system accountability and performance, school improvement, individual student achievement and growth, and information for parents on school and student performance (McGaw et al., 2020). To date, NAPLAN has enabled the federal education system to map and monitor the performance of students in Year 3, 5, 7 and 9. Over the period from 2008 to 2019, "national NAPLAN results have improved in Year 3 and 5 but not in Year 7 and 9. Writing achievement has been static in Year 3 and 5 and has declined in Year 7 and 9." (McGaw et al., 2020, p.28).

NAPLAN tests are cohort-based tests that are taken simultaneously during one designated week, in every school across the nation. During the 2023 delivery of NAPLAN, participation rates reached 93.3% of students enrolled in Year 3, 5, 7 and 9 at Australian schools.

This was a positive improvement after falling rates of participation through the covid-impacted years (ACARA, 2023e, p.1). The testing window in 2023 moved from May to March and saw “a record 4.4 million online tests submitted by more than 1.3 million students in 9,390 campuses and schools across Australia” (ACARA, 2023e, p.3).

Since its inception in 2008, NAPLAN has reported results to parents and schools using performance bands. Commencing in 2023, the reporting has changed to record student performance against proficiency levels: excellent, strong, developing and needs additional support. The results show that one in ten of Australian students need additional support (ACARA, 2023e). It is also worth noting that this number does not include the 2% of students that were exempt due to their status as a recent arrival (students with a language background other than English who arrived from overseas less than a year before the tests) or having significant disabilities (ACARA, 2023e). Concerningly, the 2023 results demonstrate that one third of Indigenous students are included in the category of needing additional support. 30% of students in remote schools achieve the higher proficiency levels whilst 60% of those in major city schools do. The gap remains between the advantaged and disadvantaged socio-economically and it appears that gender stereotypes prevail again with the girls outperforming the boys in Writing and the boys outperforming the girls in Numeracy (ACARA, 2023e).

The new reporting approach taken by NAPLAN has received a mixed reception but challenges arising from reporting are not new for this assessment. Reporting has long been a source of consternation. In efforts to meet the campaign promise of greater transparency in assessment and reporting on the performance of Australian schools, the Australian Curriculum Assessment and Reporting Authority (ACARA) launched the myschool.edu.au (MySchool) website in January 2010 (Mockler, 2013). The stated purpose of the site was for stakeholders to learn more about Australian schools (ACARA, 2010) but within days of the nation’s NAPLAN data going online alongside the comparative data from local and ‘statistically similar’ schools,

based on the Index of Community Socio-Educational Advantage (ICSEA), newspapers across the country had constructed and published school league tables (Mockler, 2013). Following this, a media frenzy followed and amid a mass of media, Mockler (2013) identified three recurring themes: distrust, performance, and choice.

It is important to acknowledge that NAPLAN effectively measures literacy and numeracy, both of which are indicators within the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). There is a significant volume of research which speaks to the content validity of NAPLAN (ACARA, 2023h; Ragusa & Bousfield, 2017; Rose et al., 2020; Wilson et al., 2021) and yet issues pertain as to how the results are used. Thompson, Adie and Klenowski (2018) examined the validity of test score interpretations in NAPLAN, finding that “the comparisons of the quality of student achievement made available on the My School Website have low validity due to the lack of regard to rates of participation in schools” (p.759). The question regarding the extent to which NAPLAN relates to the commitments to action made in the Declaration persists. Table 9 below outlines each of the commitments and marks those measured by NAPLAN.

Section 5.3 outlined the structure of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) including the preamble, the goals, indicators and eleven commitments to action. Table 9 lists the commitments to action agreed by all the education ministers representing every state and territory of Australia. Alongside, it then maps which of those commitments are measured using the NAPLAN test instrument. This table draws the commitments to action from the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) as they reflect the agreed points of action for each minister across every State and Territory of Australia. As the action points arising from the goals, it is ultimately these actions that will be measured to map Australia’s progress towards their achievement. Under the heading, NAPLAN, an X indicates that this commitment is not measured by NAPLAN and a ✓ indicates that it is. If these actions are ultimately the aspects of the education system that we value, it is timely to ponder, are we measuring what matters?

Table 9

Mapping the Commitments to Action in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) to NAPLAN

“Australian Governments commit to building partnerships that support learners’ progress through the education system, and to provide them with individualised, high quality learning opportunities and experiences, and personal development. Further, Australian Governments commit to fostering these partnerships to support young Australians as they continue learning throughout their lifetime” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to attract, develop, support and retain high-quality teachers, educators and leaders in Australia’s education system. Excellence in teaching, educating and leadership will be recognised, celebrated and valued” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to build quality and access to early years learning and development in environments that meets the needs of all Australian families. Australian Governments also commit to providing support and advice through a range of channels on how to support children to develop and flourish, including partnering with families, the broader community and other services for children.” (p.8)	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in primary school to provide a strong foundation for continued learning success throughout school and beyond” (p.8).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in the middle years, in ways which are challenging, engaging and rewarding” (p.9).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to provide a senior secondary education that equips young people with the skills, knowledge, values and capabilities to succeed in employment, personal and civic life” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to helping young Australians navigate the choices they will need to make for their education, training and employment by providing guidance” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring that all education sectors deliver world-class curriculum and assessment in Australian schools.” (p.10).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to empowering Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students to reach their potential and to ensuring the education community works to ‘close the gap’ for young Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples” (p.11).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring the education community works to provide equality of opportunity & educational outcomes for all students at risk of educational disadvantage” (p.11)	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to provide public reporting that: a. focuses on improving performance and student growth and outcomes for all students b. provides parents with information on their child’s performance, progress and outcomes c. is locally, nationally, and internationally relevant d. is accessible, timely, consistent and comparable” (p.12).	a. ✓ b. ✓ c. ✓ d. X

Key:

✓ Commitment to action is measured by this assessment

X Commitment to action is not measured by this assessment

Table 9 shows that NAPLAN addresses such commitments as delivering world class assessments and reporting to parents very well, but there are many of the commitments that are not addressed by NAPLAN. The more there are not assessed by NAPLAN and the other standardised measures, the less valid is the measurement of the educational system.

6.2 NAP Sample Assessments

The NAP sample tests have been developed using the national statements of learning in Science, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Civics and Citizenship (CC). The sample tests are completed by groups of students in Year 6 and Year 10 on a triennial cycle. Whilst individual results are not shared with participating students, a school report is shared with the principal and a national report is shared with the public and governing bodies across Australia.

When Australia agreed to participate in PISA, ‘science literacy’ was one of the constructs to be assessed. The Australian education ministers at the time therefore decided to use PISA data to monitor secondary students’ science achievement across the nation. However, there was an issue as PISA was only going to be assessing 15-year-old students and this left primary school science unmeasured in terms of national assessment and reporting. If Australia’s education system was to be evaluated through the PISA test assessing the performance in science of 15-year-olds, it would seem prudent that a similar assessment be developed for the primary school years to see if Australian students were getting a firm foundation in science (Ball, Rae & Tognolini, 2000). To this end, an assessment designed to measure primary students’ ability to apply their science learning to real-life problems was included in the NAP (Cheng, 2017). The NAP– science literacy (NAP—SL) sample assessments were designed to assess science literacy as a “student’s ability to apply broad conceptual understandings of science in order to make sense of the world; to understand natural phenomena; and to interpret media reports about

scientific issues. It also includes the ability to ask investigable questions; conduct investigations; collect and interpret data; and make informed decisions” (Connolly, 2017, p.12).

The Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training and Youth Affairs (MCEETYA), now superseded by the Education Council, met in July 2001 and instigated the establishment of the Performance Measurement and Reporting Taskforce (PMRT) which was challenged with undertaking a national assessment program. The Primary Science Assessment Program (PSAP) was commissioned in 2001 with a scheduled delivery of the assessment in 2003 (Connolly, 2017).

Pivotal to the purpose of these assessments was its contribution to mapping progress towards achieving the national goals for schooling outlined in what was then the Adelaide Declaration (MCEETYA, 1999). In their first administration, the assessments gathered baseline data for benchmarking purposes and since then a sample of Year 6 and 10 students have taken part triennially. In addition to the ongoing administration of the assessment, the NAP tests (minus some items that remain protected for the purposes of equating from one administration to the next) are regularly made available as educational materials for use by Australian schools to administer and measure their own performance relative to the Australian norms.

In the NAP-SL, the proficient standard is set at level 2/3 for Year 6 and level 3/4 for Year 10. In the most recent administration of the test to Year 6 students, the results by state reflect a concerning disparity due to location. Compared to the neighbouring states of Queensland, Western Australia and South Australia it is evident that more than half of Year 6 students selected to do the test in the Northern Territory did not demonstrate the minimum proficient standard in Science literacy. An exploration of these figures is essential to better understand the role of equity, advantage, postcode, provision and access in the data given that the goals for schooling articulated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) are for every Australian learner.

The following graph uses data sourced from the NAP-SL 2018 Public Report (ACARA, 2019b) to depict the percentage of Year 6 students achieving the proficient standard by state or territory.

Figure 13

Percentage of Year 6 Students Achieving the Proficient Standard on NAP-SL, 2018

NAP Sample Assessment Science Literacy 2018 (ACARA, 2019b, p.57)

Georgiou’s (2023) research questioned the persistent narrative of falling levels in the performance of Australian children in Science by asking, ‘are we really falling behind?’ (p.1). Through an examination of the latest available reports from PISA, TIMSS, NAP-SL and the NSW Department of Education’s VALID test, Georgiou’s research reiterates that “there are disagreements between tests on cohort achievement over time and distribution of attainment at different ‘proficiency levels’ which suggest caution when using these key results from these tests to inform policy and pedagogy” (Georgiou, 2023, p.1).

Figure 14 was generated using data from the national report and details the performance of Year 6 and Year 10 students on the National Assessment Program Sample Test: Civics and Citizenship (NAP-CC) by state from 2004 to 2019. It reflects their achievement of proficient

standards but should be read with care as the Northern Territory did not meet the sampling requirements for Year 6 or Year 10 and Tasmania failed to meet the sampling requirements for Year 10 (ACARA, 2020b). This is concerning as the NAP is designed to collect data to inform and account for the success of the education system. If a whole territory is excluded from the Year 6 data set and again alongside an additional state from the Year 10 data set due to failing to meet the sampling requirements one must question if the test instrument is fit for purpose. Figure 14 shows minimal variation in the achievement of proficiency over the fifteen year period from 2004 to 2019 which is cause for concern in itself but even more so as it means that close to 50% of students are not reaching proficiency in a curriculum domain that is designed to inform the future as a democratic society.

Figure 14

NAP-CC % of Year 6 and 10 Students Achieving the Proficient Standard Across Australia

Finally, sourced from the NAP Sample Assessment ICT Literacy (NAP-ICTL) data for Year 6 and 10 (ACARA, 2018b), Figure 15 reports on the percentage of Year 6 and 10 students achieving the proficient standard in NAP-ICTL since 2005. The proficient standard in NAP-ICTL is one of the Key Performance Measures (KPM) articulated in the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a) and is set at between level 2 and 3 for Year 6 and level 3 and 4 for Year 10. In a world where technology is evolving at pace and informing the future of education and work, a focus on ICTL is critical for future readiness. Concerningly, the Year 10 performance on the NAP-ICTL is trending downwards. At a time when the world is considering artificial intelligence (AI) and the importance of technology for the future of work, this needs to be examined carefully as young Australians progress to their final years of schooling.

Figure 15

Percentage of Year 6 and 10 Students Achieving Proficient Standard in NAP-ICTL

NAP-ICTL Years 6 and 10 (ACARA, 2018b, p.xxii; ACARA, 2023i).

Overall, the percentage of students who achieved the proficient standard in the latest administration of the three NAP Sample Assessments are shown in Table 10. The proficient standards have added importance as they also serve as the KPMs articulated in the Measurement Framework (ACARA, 2020a) as shown in section 2.2.1 of Chapter 2.

Table 10

Percentage of Year 6 and 10 Students Achieving Proficient Standard

NAP Sample Assessment	Year of Administration	Year 6	Year 10
Science Literacy	2018	58%	50%
Civics and Citizenship	2019	53%	38%
ICT Literacy	2022	55%	46%

Only 38% of Year 10 students achieved the proficient standards in Civics and Citizenship, a cause for considerable concern. Less than 50% of Year 10 students achieved proficient standards in ICT Literacy in 2022. Considering issues of equity and excellence, if only 50% are achieving the proficient standard it means that 50% of Australian students are not. This reiterates once more the need to clearly examine the conditions as to why the data is telling this story and then review the national definition for quality and success that aligns to this measure. It is hard to envisage a successful education system where it is acceptable for more than 50% of its population to be deemed lacking the proficiency needed to function effectively in that domain. If an aspect of the curriculum is important enough to warrant a substantial effort of time, money, resources and effort to undertake a national assessment of it surely that means it is important enough to demand that every child achieve proficiency in it. Table 11 shows the agreed commitments in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) mapped against what the NAP Sample tests measure.

Table 11*Mapping Commitments in Declaration (Education Council, 2019) to NAP Sample Assessments*

“Australian Governments commit to building partnerships that support learners’ progress through the education system, and to provide them with individualised, high quality learning opportunities and experiences, and personal development. Further, Australian Governments commit to fostering these partnerships to support young Australians as they continue learning throughout their lifetime” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to attract, develop, support and retain high-quality teachers, educators and leaders in Australia’s education system. Excellence in teaching, educating and leadership will be recognised, celebrated and valued” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to build quality and access to early years learning and development in environments that meets the needs of all Australian families. Australian Governments also commit to providing support and advice through a range of channels on how to support children to develop and flourish, including partnering with families, the broader community and other services for children.” (p.8)	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in primary school to provide a strong foundation for continued learning success throughout school and beyond” (p.8).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in the middle years, in ways which are challenging, engaging and rewarding” (p.9).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to provide a senior secondary education that equips young people with the skills, knowledge, values and capabilities to succeed in employment, personal and civic life” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to helping young Australians navigate the choices they will need to make for their education, training and employment by providing guidance” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring that all education sectors deliver world-class curriculum and assessment in Australian schools.” (p.10).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to empowering Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students to reach their potential and to ensuring the education community works to ‘close the gap’ for young Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples” (p.11).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring the education community works to provide equality of opportunity & educational outcomes for all students at risk of educational disadvantage” (p.11)	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to provide public reporting that: a) focuses on improving performance and student growth and outcomes for all students b) provides parents with information on their child’s performance, progress and outcomes c) is locally, nationally, and internationally relevant d) is accessible, timely, consistent and comparable” (p.12).	a) ✓ b) X c) ✓ d) X

Key: ✓ Commitment to action is measured by this assessment, X Commitment to action is not.

Earlier, section 5.3 outlined the structure of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) including the preamble, the goals, indicators and eleven commitments to action. Table 11 lists the commitments to action agreed by all the education ministers representing every state and territory of Australia. Alongside, it then maps which of those commitments are measured using the NAP Sample Tests. This table draws the commitments to action from the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) as they reflect the agreed points of action for each minister across every State and Territory of Australia. Through key word searches and content mapping across the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) and the Key Performance Measures (KPM) which are derived from the proficient standards and articulated in the Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia (ACARA, 2020a) as well as the NAP Sample Test publications (ACARA, 2018b; 2019b; 2020b).

Table 11 helps challenge whether the extent of the commitments from the Declaration being measured is adequate to reflect the performance of the whole system. The construct is defined by the components and indicators of the Declaration. While there is evidence that the NAP tests are well constructed and the results address what they are supposed to address, do they give a coverage of the full construct? If not, then statements about the effectiveness of the whole system cannot be supported by these tests by themselves.

The next section considers the ILSA assessments which are used to measure the performance of the education system against the Declaration (Education Council, 2019).

6.3 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA)

Australia has taken part in the PISA testing since its inauguration in 2000 and it forms a key component of the country's NAP. National results are shared in three main areas: Reading, Mathematics and Scientific literacy at national and state/territory levels. The Department of Education, Skills and Employment (2020) explain that PISA forms an integral part of the NAP as it provides an opportunity to monitor the Australian education system and equity across all states

and territories. However, is this a valid use of the results given the intent of the testing? Rust (2007) advises that in order for a test to be valid it must provide useful information for its intended purpose. This also links to Messick's (1989) conception of validity. Are PISA results able to report on the achievement of Australia's national goals for schooling validly and reliably? According to Schleicher (2019), PISA serves as the world's most comprehensive and reliable indicator of student achievement and is a powerful tool with which countries and economies can tweak their education policy. It is now viewed as the 'gold standard' means for evaluating education systems globally (Breakspear, 2014) and results are used to ascertain what makes educational systems across the world successful (Davis, Wilson, & Dalton, 2018; Chung, 2010).

Given the perceived importance placed upon PISA, Table 12 shows which of the agreed commitments are measured and reported using PISA according to the PISA technical guides (OECD, 2020). As with Table 9 and 11, section 5.3 outlined the structure of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) including the preamble, the goals, indicators and eleven commitments to action. Table 12 lists the commitments to action agreed by all the education ministers representing every state and territory of Australia. Alongside, it then maps which of those commitments are measured using the PISA. This table draws the commitments to action from the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) as they reflect the agreed points of action for each minister across every State and Territory of Australia. Through key word searches and content mapping across the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) and the PISA technical guidelines (OECD, 2020) it was possible to determine which of the commitments are measured by PISA in Australia.

Table 12*Mapping Commitments to Action to PISA*

“Australian Governments commit to building partnerships that support learners’ progress through the education system, and to provide them with individualised, high quality learning opportunities and experiences, and personal development. Further, Australian Governments commit to fostering these partnerships to support young Australians as they continue learning throughout their lifetime” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to attract, develop, support and retain high-quality teachers, educators and leaders in Australia’s education system. Excellence in teaching, educating and leadership will be recognised, celebrated and valued” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to build quality and access to early years learning and development in environments that meets the needs of all Australian families. Australian Governments also commit to providing support and advice through a range of channels on how to support children to develop and flourish, including partnering with families, the broader community and other services for children.” (p.8)	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in primary school to provide a strong foundation for continued learning success throughout school and beyond” (p.8).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in the middle years, in ways which are challenging, engaging and rewarding” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to provide a senior secondary education that equips young people with the skills, knowledge, values and capabilities to succeed in employment, personal and civic life” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to helping young Australians navigate the choices they will need to make for their education, training and employment by providing guidance” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring that all education sectors deliver world-class curriculum and assessment in Australian schools.” (p.10).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to empowering Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students to reach their potential and to ensuring the education community works to ‘close the gap’ for young Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples” (p.11).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring the education community works to provide equality of opportunity & educational outcomes for all students at risk of educational disadvantage” (p.11)	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to provide public reporting that: a) focuses on improving performance and student growth and outcomes for all students b) provides parents with information on their child’s performance, progress and outcomes c) is locally, nationally, and internationally relevant d) is accessible, timely, consistent and comparable” (p.12).	a) X b) X c) ✓ d) X

Key: ✓ Commitment to action is measured by this assessment

X Commitment to action is not measured by this assessment

Where PISA supports the ministerial commitment to action is in providing a lens through which to critically reflect on Australia's standing on the global stage when it comes to education. It is not surprising that a large-scale, international comparative assessment of student achievement has captured the attention of governments, policy makers and journalists (Davis & Wilson, 2019; Anagnostopoulou et al., 2013). Recognised as the world's premier yardstick for comparing education systems based on their quality, equity and learning outcomes, PISA is a powerful force driving practice and policy reform (Schleicher, 2019). In fact, the response of nations to the rankings and reporting on international large-scale assessments (ILSA) such as PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS and the International Assessment of Literacy Survey (IALS) shows their gravitas in driving reform, policy review and change (Levin, 2012).

Empowered with attention grabbing, headline generating data, it is no surprise that the world's media plays a powerful role in perpetuating the PISA rhetoric (Baroutsis & Lingard, 2017; Grey & Morris, 2018; 2022; Waldow et al., 2014; Waldow & Steiner-Khamsi, 2019). From 2015 to 2017 a dramatic increase has been reported in media articles related to PISA performance (Davis, Wilson & Dalton, 2018). Wiseman (2013) argues that the international media reporting of PISA results has played an influential role in informing the policymaking process of governments globally (p. 305). Prior to the development of PISA, the policy makers of the world were starved of data with which they could make international comparisons. PISA has certainly filled that vacuum, but it has also led to an overreaching of what the test results can validly tell us. PISA, like all tests, provides us with a snapshot in time (Schleicher, 2019). Tognolini warns that "we shouldn't be racing off and making policy changes and apportioning blame on the basis of a single test score, that, to be honest, has little significance to those students who are asked to complete the test as part of the international sampling exercise." (Baker, 2019, para.11).

Concerns have been expressed that the PISA data does not elucidate cause and effect (Suter, 2016). Schleicher (2019) uses the analogy of the bird's song at dawn. Just because the bird sings when the sun rises it does not mean that the sun rises because the bird sings. So too, knowing what one education system is doing does not tell us how to improve another system with aspirations to improve. PISA does not provide a "cookie-cutter" solution to excellence in education. However, it does turn the attention outwards and forwards in the pursuit of improved education outcomes for all.

PISA is driving education policy in Australia as it continues to provide evidence for more and more education policies to be formed (Buckingham, 2012; Thomson et al., 2013). Australia is using PISA results to examine what other education systems are doing to achieve excellence for their students and is endeavouring to learn from them. Perhaps the greatest influence PISA has had on Australian education policy can be attributed to former Prime Minister Gillard who, driven by Australia's comparative poor PISA performance regionally, set us a lofty goal (Starr, 2014). Australia's *My School* website was built upon the belief that ranking schools against each other would induce competition and promote school improvement and innovation (Starr, 2014).

PISA test results provide one piece of evidence in the education measurement framework. As such we cannot overstretch in terms of what we can extrapolate from the data. Some critics claim PISA is a sideshow distracting from the real work of the Australian education systems yet concurrently validate it as a reliable and legitimate research tool (Starr, 2014). Is it the OECD and PISA that is constructing this sideshow or is it the media and politicians who dwell on the narrative it provides in the absence of any other data? Too much power may be unfairly attributed to the PISA data and its ability to generate global education policy, intervention, and improvement. Deferring to the expertise of Andrich and Marais (2019), one is reminded that it is the properties of an object that is measured rather than the object itself. This can be said of schools, systems, governments and of course, individual students. Each of these have properties

that can be measured and may be thought of as being more-or-less. An individual student may be more-or-less able at a subject than another, but it must be remembered that one is measuring the variable rather than the individual as a whole. Too frequently, educational assessment and measurement is being made deeply personal and for the most part, this is due to the context it is delivered in rather than the construct of the test itself. So, one must question whether the problem resides with the measurement instrument or with the way it is applied to global education policy.

Naturally, the picture PISA paints of declining standards in Australia is cause for concern. Australia's score declined significantly between 2000 and 2009, from 528 score points to 515 score points, which is equivalent to about 4.5 months of schooling. Australia was somewhat unique in the drop as it only occurred in three other countries from the almost 100 economies that took part. Alarmingly, this decline was notably reported amongst Australia's high achieving students (Thomson et al., 2013). But is the picture being painted entirely accurate? Whilst PISA may portray an image of declining standards, Tognolini presented a contrasting picture over the same time frame with more NSW students than ever achieving Band 6 results in Chemistry, Mathematics and Advanced English (Baker, 2019). So, what is the answer? Is Australia's education system improving or declining? Which data should one ascribe to? The skill in answering that question lies in the ability to critically analyse a range of data points to gather as much evidence on the Australian education system as possible.

Given the positioning of PISA as a global benchmarking tool for system-wide performance it is important to position Australia's performance in this context. Drawing on data from countries who share some similarities with Australia whether in geography, goals for schooling or cultural background, the figure below shows the performance of Australia, Canada, Estonia, Finland, New Zealand, Singapore, United Kingdom, United States of America, and the OECD average in the domain of reading literacy over the years from 2000 to 2018 rankings.

Figure 16

PISA Reading Literacy Results: Selected Countries and Australia 2000-2018

Data from OECD (2000; 2003; 2006; 2009; 2012; 2015; 2018) PISA Results.

As can be seen from the linear trendline, the data demonstrates a steady decline in Australia's performance. By contrast, the trendline for Estonia reflects an upward trend. Interestingly, Finland the country that has been heralded as exemplary following their early success on the PISA rankings, demonstrates the same downward trendline as Australia, albeit from a higher starting point. In the United Kingdom, the trend shows a decline between 2000 and

2009 at which point it righted its trajectory and was on a steadily rising trend until 2018. By contrast, Figure 17 demonstrates the performance in the domain of Mathematical literacy.

Figure 17

PISA Mathematical Literacy Results: Selected Countries and Australia 2000-2018

Data from OECD. (2000; 2003; 2006; 2009; 2012; 2015; 2018) PISA Results.

Figure 18, the third in this series demonstrates the performance of the same countries, over the same period of time, in the domain of Science literacy. Again, a steady decline in Australia’s performance is observed.

Figure 18

PISA Science Literacy Results: Selected Countries and Australia 2000-2018

Data from OECD (2000; 2003; 2006; 2009; 2012; 2015; 2018) PISA Results.

The data presented in Figures 16, 17 and 18 raise the question as to why Australia’s performance in these areas is declining, based on PISA.

Around the world PISA is considered the arbiter of educational quality (Study International Staff, 2019). So much so, that the Australian Government's National Plan for School Improvement aimed to see Australia place in the top five countries in the world for Reading, Mathematics and Science by 2025 (Thomson et al., 2013). Achieving any such goal requires a committed and concerted endeavour focused upon a common aim. To do this, all stakeholders must understand the assessment which underpins the goal and what is required to achieve it. This is reminiscent of Conant's work who Bybee (1997) quoted as asking the question, "Can a school at one and the same time provide a good general education for all the pupils and future citizens of a democracy, provide elective programs for the majority to develop useful skills, and educate adequately those with a talent for handling advanced academic subjects - particularly foreign languages and advanced mathematics?" (p. 6) The challenges before schools are already immense. What would it take to equip them with the means, manner and methodology needed to achieve this goal? Thomson (2013) was careful in expressing concern regarding the goal based upon the TIMSS and PIRLS testing in 2010. Dinham (2012) took this concern further, describing the target as arbitrary. Buckingham (2012) pleads the case to make sure that Australia does not sacrifice some of the most valuable aspects of its education system in the pursuit of this lofty goal.

When international and national large-scale assessment (LSA) reports are released, they are often followed by academic and public debate on what they measure, their relationships with sociodemographic and educational factors, the usefulness of what they measure for students, teachers, parents and policymakers; and their unintended consequences for teachers and schools (Coburn, Hill, & Spillane, 2016; Hopfenbeck & Kjærnsli, 2016; Marsh, Roediger, Bjork, & Bjork, 2007; Lingard & Sellar, 2013; Zhao, 2020). Just as with the My Schools website (ACARA, 2010) in Australia, the PISA rankings and league tables instil a sense of competition and pressure on education systems. In fact, one of the criticisms of PISA is that it has become so

high stakes for policy makers that it is triggering ‘rank-seeking reforms’ (Breakspear, 2014). A high-stakes test is when “educators, students, or both are held accountable for test scores” (Koretz, 2008, p.11). So, in theory, PISA should not be deemed as high stakes. Yet what could be more high stakes for an education system than its public ranking of performance, the outcome of its investment in education, on the global stage?

Putting pressure on policy makers to address underperformance across education systems is surely something to be welcomed. Every child has the right to access quality education and anything that can be used to strengthen that opportunity is to be encouraged. So, it is positive that PISA identifies issues related to areas of concern within the Declaration that align with what PISA measures. The challenge, however, is to remember that Australia’s PISA results are just one piece of evidence from across the spectrum of indicators that represent the goals of the total education system and are captured in the Declaration.

Most athletes would probably argue that the best way to achieve growth is to strive to continually produce your personal best. This involves an in depth understanding of self, an appreciation for your own abilities (what you do well) and a goal of where to next that is aligned to your capacity for growth. Fostering a competitive tension between nations based on rank may not be considered the best way to optimise an education system as it does not value what we are already doing well, nor does it align to the local context and capacity. PISA is one measure of student performance in a limited range of domains that is used to generate data around systemic performance in schools globally. The key point here being it is just one. It would be naïve to solely rely upon one piece of data to drive systemic reform. The PISA data should be enough to start the conversation, raise the question and stimulate the dialogue. It should not be the justification for wide sweeping pay cuts and belittling of teachers (Wilkie, 2019). Nor should it drive nations to teach to the PISA test (Breakspear, 2014). PISA is often reported as the summative assessment on an education system’s performance. What if the lens is shifted and

PISA results are viewed not as an end point, but a starting point. A launch pad to excite the conversation around educational policy, school improvement and success.

Any teacher will share anecdotal evidence of the differences between year groups in their school. It is widely accepted by educators that some years are particularly sporty, highly academic, emotionally driven or dare one say it, problematic. Performance by cohort is driven not just by the economic needs of the nation, nor the pedagogical endeavours of the school but also by the very personalities and motivations of the students within it. At the end of the day, what must remain central to the discussion is that the subject is the education of people. Young people with their quirks, unique differences, individual experiences, backgrounds, and motivations.

Anyone who spends any time in schools immediately becomes aware of the huge differences in children, “their abilities, their interests, their beliefs and so on.” (William, 2018, p.3). How can a singular snapshot in time, the performance of a sample cohort of students on a test, be used to draw conclusions as to the quality of a school system and its contribution to society?

Educational testing has a powerful influence on public debate about societal concerns such as equity, excellence, economic advantage, culture, and global identity (Koretz, 2008). ILSA have significantly influenced policy globally (Breakspear, 2012; Jerrim, 2023). In Australia, PISA results have informed a successful case for more testing (Froese-Germain, 2010) including the introduction of the NAP Sample Assessments and NAPLAN. This, despite what Figazzolo (2009) refers to as the “dangers associated with national full cohort testing” (p.18).

In a further exploration of ILSA such as PISA, it has been asked whether they accurately reflect the performance of the education systems or rather, whether they are more akin to a reflection of the general ability (*g*) for the participants? Pokropek, Marks and Borgonovi (2022)

researched this by comparing the PISA results of 3472 Polish students with their scores on the Raven Progressive Matrices test (Raven, 2003). They found that the PISA scores mostly reflected g. PISA is not a direct test of Australian curriculum nor Australian teachers. Rather, it is a test of Australian students' ability to take all that they have learned and apply it to everyday situations. That is, the test measures Australian students' levels of scientific, mathematical, and reading literacy prior to completing their formal schooling and finding their own way in the world. Masters (2005) assures that the PISA tests are sound, reliable instruments that measure accurately what they were designed to measure. Perhaps the issue is not whether PISA is a valid instrument but rather, whether the misappropriation of its purpose renders it less valid as the foundation of education policy and curriculum reform. PISA provides interesting and informative data for comparing the performance of countries but has limited value as a guide for education policy (Schneider, 2009; Buckingham, 2012). Several researchers warn against falling into the trap of comparing ourselves against OECD averages (Buckingham, 2012; Norton, 2007; Sharrock, 2012; Thomson, 2013). Knowing how well students are currently performing and asking where to next is the core of educators' business. These are valid questions worthy of time, interest, and scholarly pursuit. Yet, the challenge is to use the PISA results to learn from the policies and practices of global peers but then to take that knowledge and apply it to real-world problems to craft an answer that meets the needs of each unique context.

The next section considers a second ILSA program that contributes to the measurement of Australia's education system.

6.3 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS)

In this section, Australia's performance on the TIMSS assessment (previously introduced in Chapter 2) is explored. Figure 19 depicts the performance of the 2019 Australian student sample which included 571 schools from across the government, catholic and independent sectors in a range of metropolitan, regional, and remote locations. The sample consisted of 5,890

Year 4 students and 9,060 students in Year 8 (Thomson et al., 2020). The figure shows the performance of Australian students compared to the international median and the sample of students tested in Singapore, the highest performing country on TIMMS in 2019, by way of comparison.

Figure 19

Proficient Standards on TIMMS 2019 in Australia and Singapore

Data from TIMSS 2019 Results (Thomson et al., 2020).

The TIMSS results show Australian students being out-performed since 1995 when Australian children first participated in TIMSS. Performance has somewhat stagnated, and this is cause for concern which is made even more alarming by the dramatic improvements being made by similar systems in England, Hong Kong, and Singapore (Thomson, 2013).

Figures 20, 21, 22 and 23 depict the changes in Australia's performance on TIMMS over time from 2000 – 2018 by year group and domain. They map trends in Year 4 Mathematics, Year 8 Mathematics, Year 4 Science and Year 8 Science. The proficient standard is 475. It has been compared to Singapore, USA, UK and New Zealand to provide comparative international data.

Figure 20

Year 4 Mathematics TIMSS Performance Trends Over Time by Country

Data from TIMSS 2019 Results (Thomson et al., 2020).

Figure 21

Year 8 Mathematics TIMSS Performance Trends Over Time by Country

Figure 22

Year 4 Science TIMSS Performance Trends Over Time by Country

Figure 23

Year 8 Science TIMSS Performance Trends Over Time by Country

Figures 20 to 23 show that in the 2019 administration of TIMSS Australia demonstrated improvement in Year 4 Mathematics and Science. Figure 20, Year Four Mathematics, displays a slight upward trend in Australia's performance. For Year 8 the Science performance increased whilst performance in Year 8 Mathematics remained stagnant. They also show similar trends in the USA, United Kingdom and New Zealand. The figures also clearly demonstrate the significant gap in performance between Australia and its regional neighbour, Singapore. This achievement gap is worthy of further consideration. In the 2015 administration of TIMSS, there was an achievement gap of 116 points between Australia's score in Year 8 Mathematics (505 points) and that of their counterparts in Singapore (621 points). The data are shown in the figure below:

Figure 24

The Achievement Gap: Australia and Singapore

Beyond the achievement gap between the two countries performance, the trendlines show that this pattern is set to continue. In terms of country rankings, Australia performed as follows in the 2019 administration of TIMSS:

Table 13

Australia’s Country Ranking on TIMSS 2019

Domain	Year Level	Country Ranking
Mathematics	4	23 rd
	8	= 7 th
Science	4	= 9 th
	8	= 7 th

Why does this matter? Importantly, in addition to providing country rankings and important data for the NAP, TIMSS provides a reliable measure of Australia's progress towards the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) in the pursuit of quality education for all (UNESCO, 2015). TIMSS has set a low international benchmark which serves as the global indicator of minimum proficiency in lower secondary mathematics (Thomson, 2020). In 2019, 90% of Year 8 Australian students achieved this global benchmark of proficiency (Mullis et al., 2020).

Moving from the global to the local, is TIMSS measuring what matters when it comes to the agreed goals for schooling in Australia? In terms of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019), TIMSS is a further ILSA for evaluating the comparative success of Australia's education system on the global stage. In this case for the curriculum areas of Science and Mathematics. This is illustrative of the type of data and reporting that are influencing policy decisions, and which are ultimately interpreted in a manner that delivers the Australian education system a failing grade in the media (Thomson, 2016). Yet, the tests themselves only measure a limited component of the goals and commitments to action outlined in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). As a result, the misalignment of these tests and their results detracts from the validity of the measure because it has consequences which negatively impact the system.

Table 14 show the commitments to action agreed by the ministers in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) that are measured by TIMSS. They have been compared using a key word search and content comparison to derive which of the commitments are measured by the TIMSS in Australia.

Table 14

Mapping Commitments to Action in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) to TIMSS

“Australian Governments commit to building partnerships that support learners’ progress through the education system, and to provide them with individualised, high quality learning opportunities and experiences, and personal development. Further, Australian Governments commit to fostering these partnerships to support young Australians as they continue learning throughout their lifetime” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to attract, develop, support and retain high-quality teachers, educators and leaders in Australia’s education system. Excellence in teaching, educating and leadership will be recognised, celebrated and valued” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to build quality and access to early years learning and development in environments that meets the needs of all Australian families. Australian Governments also commit to providing support and advice through a range of channels on how to support children to develop and flourish, including partnering with families, the broader community and other services for children.” (p.8)	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in primary school to provide a strong foundation for continued learning success throughout school and beyond” (p.8).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in the middle years, in ways which are challenging, engaging and rewarding” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to provide a senior secondary education that equips young people with the skills, knowledge, values and capabilities to succeed in employment, personal and civic life” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to helping young Australians navigate the choices they will need to make for their education, training and employment by providing guidance” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring that all education sectors deliver world-class curriculum and assessment in Australian schools.” (p.10).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to empowering Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students to reach their potential and to ensuring the education community works to ‘close the gap’ for young Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples” (p.11).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring the education community works to provide equality of opportunity & educational outcomes for all students at risk of educational disadvantage” (p.11)	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to provide public reporting that: a. focuses on improving performance and student growth and outcomes for all students b. provides parents with information on their child’s performance, progress and outcomes c. is locally, nationally, and internationally relevant d. is accessible, timely, consistent and comparable” (p.12).	a) X b) X c) ✓ d) X

Key: ✓ Commitment to action is measured by this assessment

X Commitment to action is not measured by this assessment

6.4 Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS)

Samples of Australian students have participated in PIRLS (introduced in Chapter 2) since 2011. In 2011 PIRLS data showed that Australian Year 4 students were surpassed in reading ability by all other English-speaking countries except New Zealand (Thomson et al., 2013). Yet, Australian students were shown to be falling below the benchmark for acceptable success as deemed by the Australian Ministerial Council for Education, Early Childhood Development and Youth Affairs (MCEEDYA) in Mathematics, Reading and Science (Thomson, 2013).

Hillman et al. (2023) reported on the results from the 2021 administration of PIRLS and shared that, “Australian Year 4 students scored higher, on average, in the PIRLS 2021 assessment than Year 4 students in 28 other countries.” (p.17). However, results from the PIRLS 2021 assessment need to be interpreted with caution given the major disruptions to the administration caused by the COVID-19 related school closures across the world. Many of the participating countries were forced to administer the test up to one year later which impacted the age of the students included in the sample. Hillman et al. (2023) explain, “differences in the timing ... mean that results for some countries are not comparable to results from other countries. For example, students in the United States were in Year 5 when they participated in their assessment so comparisons with Australian Year 4 students’ results are not valid.” (p.18).

Figure 25 shows the performance of Year 4 students on the PIRLS assessment over the decade by student background. Here, as in the PIRLS results report, the students are grouped by “first nations background” and “other background” (Hillman et al., 2023). The achievement gap is significant although the trendlines are heading in the same upwards direction. Reporting on results such as this achievement gap goes some way to aligning what is being measured with the commitments to action that matter in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019).

Figure 25*PIRLS 2021 Performance by Student Background*

PIRLS, along with the other assessments examined in this chapter, provides important data as mandated in the *Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia* (ACARA, 2020a). In particular, PIRLS is important as it not only charts the progress towards some of the commitments to action set out in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) but also sets the desired proficiency standard for reading as the PIRLS intermediate international benchmark. In the 2021 administration, of the 5,500-Year 5 student strong sample from across 281 schools in Australia, “80% of Year 4 students in Australia met the proficient standard (the PIRLS Intermediate benchmark), including 14% at the Advanced benchmark and 34% at the High benchmark” (Hillman et al., 2023, p.x).

Table 15 shows the correlation between the agreed commitments to action in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) outlined earlier in section 5.3 and those intended to be measured by PIRLS. To achieve this, a key word search and content comparison methods were used to identify which of the commitments are measured by PIRLS in Australia.

Table 15

Mapping Commitments to Action in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) to PIRLS

“Australian Governments commit to building partnerships that support learners’ progress through the education system, and to provide them with individualised, high quality learning opportunities and experiences, and personal development. Further, Australian Governments commit to fostering these partnerships to support young Australians as they continue learning throughout their lifetime” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to attract, develop, support and retain high-quality teachers, educators and leaders in Australia’s education system. Excellence in teaching, educating and leadership will be recognised, celebrated and valued” (p.7).	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to build quality and access to early years learning and development in environments that meets the needs of all Australian families. Australian Governments also commit to providing support and advice through a range of channels on how to support children to develop and flourish, including partnering with families, the broader community and other services for children.” (p.8)	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in primary school to provide a strong foundation for continued learning success throughout school and beyond” (p.8).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in the middle years, in ways which are challenging, engaging and rewarding” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to working with the education community to provide a senior secondary education that equips young people with the skills, knowledge, values and capabilities to succeed in employment, personal and civic life” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to helping young Australians navigate the choices they will need to make for their education, training and employment by providing guidance” (p.9).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring that all education sectors deliver world-class curriculum and assessment in Australian schools.” (p.10).	✓
“Australian Governments commit to empowering Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students to reach their potential and to ensuring the education community works to ‘close the gap’ for young Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples” (p.11).	X
“Australian Governments commit to ensuring the education community works to provide equality of opportunity & educational outcomes for all students at risk of educational disadvantage” (p.11)	X
“Australian Governments commit to continuing to provide public reporting that: a) focuses on improving performance and student growth and outcomes for all students b) provides parents with information on their child’s performance, progress and outcomes c) is locally, nationally, and internationally relevant d) is accessible, timely, consistent and comparable” (p.12).	a) X b) X c) ✓ d) X

Key: ✓ Commitment to action is measured by this assessment

X Commitment to action is not measured by this assessment

6.5 Global Rankings

Gorur and Wu (2015) conducted a study as to whether assessments such as PISA were leaning in too far when it came to informing policy based upon country rankings. They interviewed measurement and policy experts finding average performance scores, upon which such rankings are based, to be “uninformative and misleading” (p.647). This was consistent with the quote Gorur and Wu (2015) included from the former Deputy Director of Education at the OECD, Malcolm Skilbeck:

What’s the good of [the rankings]? What is the benefit to the US to be told that it is number seven or number 10? It’s useless, meaningless, except for a media beat up and political huffing and puffing. It’s very important for the US to know, having defined certain goals like improving participation rates for impoverished students from suburbs in large cities – whether in fact that is happening, and if it is, why it is happening and if not, why not. And it is irrelevant whether Chile or Russia or France is doing better or worse – that doesn’t help one bit – in fact, it probably hinders. Makes people feel uncertain, unsure, nervous, and they rush over there and find out why they are doing better. (p. 647)

This is not dissimilar to the opinions of the educational leaders interviewed for this study. One participant said,

The media in general are influencers ... they are often speaking to a non-technical audience and ... looking for a narrative that is going to attract readers. ... our natural human bias is to pay attention to things that are negative, and that’s a documented human cognitive bias, you know evolutionarily it made sense [laughs] ... and so you end up with a picture that an assessment must be bad or you must be doing badly in it, and that’s unhelpful almost all of the time, especially when a lot of the time comparisons are being made which are not to an objective benchmark but to a comparative like league tables or country rankings for example, and the most common misconception that I hear with the

large-scale assessment is about “oh, our country needs to improve, we’ve slipped seven places since the last time” or something to that effect. ... what does that even mean?

Does it mean six others moved up? Or does it mean everybody else stayed the same and we dropped down seven places, we were the only one who moved? Which is impossible.

You know, the narratives are unhelpful. And incorrect. And definitely damage the validity of, [pauses] oh, does it damage the validity of the assessment? It doesn’t change the instrument, so it doesn’t affect the instrument’s validity. What it changes is perceptions of it. And that, again, because it is largely non-technical audiences, it is very damaging.

(Participant 2).

Researchers concur that such rankings which lead to policy borrowing and aspirational goal setting are somewhat futile and represent such assessments leaning in too far (Buckingham, 2012; Gorur & Wu, 2015). At the conclusion of their study, Gorur and Wu (2015) comment that, “if Australia insists on using PISA to inform policy, it would do well to explore the data in much greater detail. Average scores obscure far more than they reveal. Using average performance scores and rankings to inform policy is leading to damaging policy decisions.” (p. 662). In agreement with this, it is evident that each of the assessments listed in the NAP (NAPLAN, NAP Sample Assessments, PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS) are valid instruments for use in an educational context but do they align with the goals articulated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019)? Are they valid for that intended purpose? Greater investigation and understanding of the data they generated and how it is used is needed to examine the consequential validity of such measures. Rather than being influenced by the human bias towards focusing on the negative / threat (Vaish et al., 2008), stakeholders (including parents, teachers, students, policy makers and policy announcers) must be more objectively informed of the data and how they are influenced by a myriad of factors as was demonstrated in the most recent PIRLS data under the administrative burden of Covid-related school closures.

6.6 Consequential Validity and the National Assessment Program

ILSA, such as TIMSS, PISA and PIRLS have each played an important role in educational policy (Solano-Flores & Milbourn, 2016). Unfortunately, the impact of PISA scores on educational policy is too often shaped by the misinterpretation and misuse of score rankings (Ercikan, Roth, & Asil, 2015).

In their exploration of assessment capacity, Solano-Flores and Milbourn (2016) relied upon Clarke's (2012) description of three key elements that a country needs: 1) an enabling context that is conducive to assessment activities; 2) the alignment of approaches to assessment with other aspects of their education system, and 3) the ability of the country to use the psychometric data generated to inform their policies and practices.

Australia is fortunate to benefit from advanced assessment capacity which informs its national testing. In many education systems, PISA has contributed to the capacity building of national testing centres (Solano-Flores & Milbourn, 2016). The role of PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS in supporting the development of in-country assessment capacity is a positive outcome. Yet conversely, those countries with limited assessment capacity may unwittingly diminish the validity of the assessment instruments. Local responsibility for the technical roles of working with samples, translated test items, marking, transferring data and reporting nationally demands a high level of assessment capacity that may not be inherent in some contexts.

To understand the consequential validity of large-scale assessments in Australia, the country's participation must be driven by a clearly defined and articulated plan of what needs to be improved and the resourcing needed to do so (Solano-Flores & Milbourn, 2016). Exercising the capacity to work effectively with large-scale assessment data demands time and expertise. So too, working with comparative, international assessment data in this way requires congruence with the local education system and should be free from political pressure to transform policy according to the needs of the learners in the system (Darling-Hammond, 2014).

Solano-Flores and Milbourn (2016) contend that a “critical level of assessment capacity is needed for a country to benefit from participating in international test comparisons. At the same time, participation in international test comparisons is a good opportunity for countries to increase their assessment capacities, as long as they pay proper attention to cultural validity and consequential validity.” (p. 11).

6.6.1 Consequential Validity and PISA

PISA is heralded for its policy orientation and the provision of reporting that meets the needs of global governments as they make decisions that impact their education systems (OECD, 2004; OECD, 2013a; Pepper, 2020). PISA responds to the OECD “member countries’ demands for regular and reliable data on the knowledge and skills of their students and the performance of their education systems,” which allows them “to track their progress in meeting key learning goals.” (OECD, 2019a, overview section). Taut and Palacios (2016) summarise the intended use of PISA results as: 1) country level diagnostic data; 2) within country time comparisons of data; 3) global comparisons with other countries.

The PISA Technical Report (OECD, 2020) contains considerable detail relating to the validity of PISA yet does not address the unintended consequences arising from its use. The only reference in that report is an external evaluation that was completed at the behest of the PISA governing board, and it sought to provide evidence of the intended and unintended uses at the country level (OECD, 2008). The Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014) state that test developers may not be held responsible for the unintended uses and consequences of measurement instruments unless they are due to flaws inherent in the test. Logically, this means that in the case of PISA and other assessments utilised in Australia’s NAP, the test designers cannot be held responsible for the ways in which policy makers and stakeholders (including the national media) arrive at the conclusions they draw from the data.

Whilst Taut and Palacios (2016) espouse that in the example of PISA, more could be done on the part of the OECD to draw attention to unsound practices with the data generated.

Meyer and Zahedi (2014) published a letter in the Guardian newspaper expressing the concerns of more than 80 expert signatories calling for a halt to the testing in 2015 to allow for unintended consequences in the program to be reviewed. Researchers such as Zhao (2020) add:

The consequence is a trend of global homogenization of education and celebration of authoritarian education systems for their high PISA scores, while ignoring the negative consequences on important human attributes and local cultures of such systems. (p. 253)

In the face of all the criticisms leveraged against PISA (Breakspear, 2012) its influence has still grown over time. PISA would not have been able to grow in the pace or influence it has if there had not been a vacuum to fill, a policy environment ripe for such a tool (Gorur, 2016). Australia's stated aspiration to be in the top five of PISA rankings demonstrates just one example of the power of PISA to influence policy (Gorur & Wu, 2015). Advice is needed on how to use PISA more wisely (Hargreaves & Sahlberg, 2015). Countries have bought into the PISA rhetoric to such an extent that many have reported it being more aligned to its policy needs than their own national tests and provided them with greater convergence in policy (Baird et al., 2011).

According to Porter and Webb (2007), the challenge with PISA is that rather than simply generating the data required to inform global educational policy, they are attempting to shape it. They do this through the selection of concepts they choose to prioritise and collect data on which in turn makes those things more visible. It is proposed that the power of PISA has resulted in the celebration of world-leading education systems such as Finland, Shanghai and South Korea (Takayama et al., 2013) and shaped them into influencers that are followed and revered by other nations (Waldow et al., 2014). The challenge of such influence is that it leads to policy borrowing across education systems and whilst there is much to be gained by learning from

beacons of excellence, it is imperative that educators never lose sight of the need to meet their students where they are. Local context matters and the educational policies developed must focus on the needs and wants of the society (and its members) that they seek to serve.

Adams (2003) reports that the OECD has confidence in the validity of its measures. “High levels of expertise and great technical capacity are applied to the world’s largest study of schooling” (Murphy, 2014, p. 904). However, the OECD also call for caution in the interpretation of results (OECD, 2007). Consider for a moment that a test, representing a snapshot of student performance in isolation, is being undertaken by a sample of students aged 15 years 3 months to 16 years 2 months and from the data collected a result is being inferred to determine the performance of that national education system. The OECD are eager to advise that caution must be taken accordingly. Knowing that the school in which that teenager sits the test may not be the same school that shaped their earlier learning experiences, the OECD warns that the contextual, background data collected provides an ‘imperfect proxy for the cumulative learning environments of students’ (OECD, 2007, p. 214). A further issue with the age of the participants is that in many countries young people of this age have already completed their mandatory formal schooling (Prais, 2003).

Test-taking motivation (TTM) and the concept of skill and will (Eklöf, 2010) are important attributes to address. In Brazil, a colleague shared the story of schools gifting students who turned up on the day of the PISA test a raffle ticket with the chance to win a new bicycle (personal communication, June 2022). It was the only hope they had of achieving the required sample. In other nations, reports are shared of the sampled students marching into testing centres behind their national flag to instil a sense of national pride and motivate their efforts (personal communication, June 2022). As PISA has grown in political gravitas, so too have the efforts to ensure their students have the skill and will to do well. TTM is defined by Baumert and Demmrich (2003) as “the willingness to engage in working on test items and to invest effort and

persistence in this undertaking” (p. 441). Given the right motivation, test takers can persevere, concentrate and improve their overall performance in exam situations (Harlen & Deakin Crick, 2003; Wise & DeMars, 2005).

In exploring TTM, it was found that there are four motivators that are key: attainment value, intrinsic value, utility value and cost perception (Eklöf, 2010). It is a truism that if doing well is important to them, test takers are motivated to make a greater effort. So too, if a topic holds great personal interest for them. The cost perception is more interesting. In this case, test takers regularly make subconscious judgements concerning the effort required to complete the task in relation to its benefit to them. Finally, test takers engage in a perception of how useful the task is to them (Wigfield & Eccles, 2002; Eklöf, 2010; Rivas & Scasso, 2021). It is therefore little surprise that a test like PISA, TIMSS or PIRLS which has no direct consequences for the test taker produces a lower motivation to do well (Finn, 2015; Gneezy, 2017).

It would be easy to confine this debate to being a PISA issue given the vast amount of media attention the OECD assessment receives (Araujo et al., 2017). However, the same debate can be applied to all of the measurement instruments incorporated in the NAP. Validity matters equally whether interpreting results from PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, NAPLAN or any other test instrument. The NAP in Australia draws on a number of measurement instruments but as Baird et al. (2011) state, it is always the PISA results “...that politicians look for first, and that they sometimes use, appropriately or otherwise, to initiate debate about system reforms and on occasion to justify reforms” (p.11).

PISA makes it easy for politicians. The provision of a ranking that positions Australia globally can easily be drawn upon to frame a vote-winning dialogue around the need to invest differently and re-shape the work of the education system for the benefit of all. A low ranking indicates the need for reform (Araujo et al., 2017) regardless of any understanding of inherent methodological flaws in making such an inference from the data.

Politicians, keen to prepare young people for prosperous lives, turn to PISA data for assurance and guidance. Yet, life satisfaction is about so much more than a student's achievement on cognitive-based assessments. It is skills such as resilience, optimism, cooperation, and perseverance that serve as better predictors of life outcomes (Kautz et al., 2014). Thus, the question is asked of global education systems as to whether a test of student cognitive ability is the most effective measure of school effectiveness for future life satisfaction? (Heckman et al., 2014).

In describing what he calls, the Global Education Reform Movement or GERM, (Sahlberg, 2007) outlines the following policies as being influential: a) standardisation of education through external assessment measures; b) back to basics approach focused on literacy and numeracy; and c) consequential accountability which connects school performance to teacher rewards and professionalism. A global convergence of educational policy has been observed and documented by many (Ball, 1998; Carnoy & Rhoten, 2002; Hargreaves, 2003; Moutsios, 2009; Pons, 2017; Ravitch, 2010).

Of particular interest is Sahlberg's (2007) reference to consequential accountability when it comes to educational policy and the impact of which is best seen in countries such as England, Australia, and the United States of America (Murphy, 2014). If test performance is linked to consequential accountability for teachers (i.e., it impacts their financial rewards) then what does this mean for the consequential validity of the test itself? What influence will the potential impact on a teacher's salary have on their preconceptions of the assessment? Is it any surprise we see educators 'teaching to the test' to influence the outcome positively? In a paper for the World Bank, Hanushek and Wöessmann (2008) explained that consequential accountability (including merit pay) would positively impact student performance. To date, evidence has not proven this to be true in the United States of America (Ravitch, 2010; Marsh et al., 2011) or England (Apple, 2004; Thrupp & Hursh, 2006).

Of all the large-scale assessments, PISA is viewed as the most powerful force, driving the convergence of education policies with measurement, skills, performance management and accountability (Rizvi & Lingard, 2006; Porter & Webb, 2007). PISA, just like NAPLAN, is represented as being a low-stakes assessment for students but it is high stakes for governments (Rivas & Scasso, 2021) and teachers who invariably have their financial reward tied to it (Sahlberg, 2007).

Baird et al. (2016) describe PISA as the ‘world league of education’ thanks to its table of rankings and vast media coverage. Its influence is profound in spite of a continued fundamental questioning of the validity underpinning it (Hopfenbeck & Görger, 2017; Solano-Flores & Milbourn, 2016). Studies such as those by Rivas and Scasso (2021) outlining the methodological issues in Latin America, the impact of revised scores due to the OECD’s changes to scaling in Brazil (Klein, 2011; Carnoy et al., 2015) and likewise, in Colombia (OECD, 2017; Rivas & Scasso, 2021). Rivas and Scasso (2021) recount the story of the Colombian president proudly celebrating an improvement to the national education system that never took place due to a “miscommunication from PISA and a rushed analysis of the results” (p.297). It is for this reason that yet again it is asserted that a better understanding of validity is needed in plain language that is accessible for all stakeholders.

6.6.2 Consequential Validity: TIMSS and PIRLS

Originating in Hamburg, Germany in 1958, the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) describes itself as an “independent nongovernmental nonprofit cooperative of national research institutions and governmental research agencies” (Wagemaker, 2020, p.ii.). Since their establishment, IEA has been developing and conducting large-scale, comparative studies with the goal of encouraging “international dialogue focusing on policy matters and technical evaluation procedures. The resulting debate integrates powerful conceptual frameworks, comprehensive data sets and rigorous analysis, thus

enhancing understanding of diverse education systems worldwide.” (Wagemaker, 2020, p.ii).

The IEA is responsible for both the TIMSS and PIRLS large-scale assessments.

IEA has published extensive works to contribute to the capacity building of countries as large-scale assessments have become embedded in the educational measurement landscape (Lockheed & Wagemaker, 2013; Wagemaker, 2011; 2013; 2014). Wagemaker (2020) explains the seriousness with which IEA seeks to meet the “demands of the twin imperatives of validity and reliability, tempered by a concern for fairness, [which] must be satisfied in the context of multiple, and diverse cultures, languages, scripts, educational structures, educational histories, and traditions” (p. 2).

A major debate has ensued regarding the belief that in addressing validity, test developers must consider the positive and negative consequences of the assessment, a concept referred to as consequential validity (Messick, 1989; Shepard, 1997). Messick’s (1989) call for the appropriate labelling of tests to support such interpretation has been heeded by IEA who include the consequences of assessment in their reporting (Wagemaker, 2020).

6.6.3 Consequential Validity and NAPLAN

In 2019, education ministers from New South Wales, Victoria, Queensland, and the Australian Capital Territory commissioned a review of the approach to NAPLAN by Emeritus Professor Barry McGaw AO, Emeritus Professor William Loudon AM, and Professor Claire Wyatt-Smith. In its concluding chapter, the Review made ten recommendations for potential changes to NAPLAN which relate to: the role of NAPLAN, content coverage, timing of tests, rebranding of programs, test development, updated writing test, new time series, annual reports, integration with school assessments and, evaluation. Whilst each of the recommendations are relevant to this study, several points are particularly pertinent and will be focused upon here: a) who should be tested, and b) what should they be tested on.

6.6.3.1 *Who should be tested?*

In their examination of the features of an assessment system, McGaw et al. (2020) explored census tests such as NAPLAN in contrast to sample tests such as PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS and the NAP Sample Tests. They explained that “census tests can be an appropriate source of information for monitoring national policy, system accountability, school improvement and reporting to parents/carers on school and individual performance” and that they provide a “... ‘point-in-time’ indication of a student’s position in relation to the whole population of which the student is a member” McGaw et al., 2020, p.115). By contrast, sample tests only monitor “progress towards national goals and accountability for system performance” (McGaw et al., 2020, p.115). Given the difference between the construct of NAPLAN, PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS and the NAP Sample Assessments it is reasonable to group them in this way when it comes to evaluating the National Assessment Program?

In exploring the potential for NAPLAN to be administered as a sample test rather than in its current census form, stakeholders were surveyed as part of the review and of the 300 participants, researchers found that 25% favoured a census assessment whilst 22% favoured a sample test with one participant citing, “While some data would be lost by moving to a sample system, it would certainly take the pressure off schools. System wide data might refocus efforts on equity measures, rather than punitive targeting of individual schools” (McGaw et al., 2020, p.115). When the same question was posed to experts, their responses reflected a return to the purpose of assessment commenting that census testing provides for greater accountability and reporting to individual parents (a driving purpose of NAPLAN’s creation as discussed earlier in Chapter 6) whilst sample testing would provide for test instruments with the ability to cover more of the curriculum (McGaw et al., 2020, p.117).

Who should be tested is inextricably linked to the purpose of the assessment. If the intention is to give parents one external piece of assessment then everybody should do the test. If it is just to monitor the progress of the system, then it could be achieved using a sample.

6.6.3.2 What should they be tested on?

To better align with the general capabilities documented in the Australian Curriculum, McGaw et al. (2020) recommend broadening NAPLAN to include tests of critical and creative thinking in science, technology, engineering, and maths (STEM) under a re-branded name, the Australian National Standardised Assessments (ANSA). This would in turn see the removal of the NAP-SL from the triennial delivery of the sample assessments and replacing it with an assessment of Australian's students' proficiency in "history and intercultural understanding" (McGaw et al., 2020, p.122). This broadening of NAPLAN would represent a first step in better reflecting the depth and breadth of capabilities and competencies that schools develop in their students over the course of their education.

In concluding their recommendations, McGaw et al. (2020) suggest ongoing formal evaluations of the "national standardised assessment program" whilst keeping the potential consequences (positive and negative) front and centre from the perspective of parents, teachers, students, and the system itself (p.134). In Chapter 2 of this thesis, the importance of omissions, gaps and word choice when reviewing policy documents was discussed (Foucault, 1972). To this end, the insertion of the word 'standardised' when addressing the National Assessment Program on page 134 of the Final Report is pertinent. In this scenario, it is a far more authentic title.

As part of the review many submissions and contrasting ideas were presented. One such submission came from Wilson et al. (2021) at the Gonski Institute who described NAPLAN as "deeply problematic" and "a lost opportunity to harness the potential of assessment to strengthen the fabric of education in schools" (Wilson et al., 2021, p. 4). Whilst disagreeing with this

sentiment, it is agreed that the need for ongoing review of NAPLAN's purpose, content and effectiveness for schools as part of the NAP is central to its continued purposefulness.

Baird et al. (2017) assert that if we want assessments to serve the goals of education, then they must be developed in closer alignment with theories of learning. As such, reaffirmation of the inherent symbiosis between student learning and assessment in Australian schools is important. The teaching and learning cycle, including assessment, is a pivotal feature of curricular across the country (NSW Department of Education, 2023). Keeping the students at the centre of the teacher's work and aligning assessments to a theoretical understanding of how young people learn best is key.

6.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter has examined the claim that Australia's performance on the global, comparative ranks generated by the international large-scale assessments is declining compared with a more positive outlook in the data generated from the early primary years in NAPLAN. In a close examination of consequential validity, it is apparent that themes of accountability, teacher professionalism, the influence of media and jargon-laden reporting is a cause of vexation for key stakeholders in the Australian education system.

Importantly, this chapter correlated the agreed commitments to action in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) with the agreed measures of system-wide success from the NAP and national measurement framework (ACARA, 2020a). It is evident that there is a misalignment between the two. Of the eleven commitments to action agreed by the Ministers in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) to achieve the nation's goals for schooling, only four are directly measured using the NAP. They are: "Australian Governments commit to ensuring that all education sectors deliver world-class curriculum and assessment in Australian schools." (Education Council, 2019, p.10); "Australian Governments commit to continuing to provide public reporting that is locally, nationally, and internationally relevant" (Education Council,

2019, p.10); “Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in primary school to provide a strong foundation for continued learning success throughout school and beyond” (Education Council, 2019, p.8); and “Australian Governments commit to working with all school sectors to ensure that schools are responsive to students’ developmental and learning needs in the middle years, in ways which are challenging, engaging and rewarding” (Education Council, 2019, p.9). This provides critical data as to whether Australia is measuring what matters. The next chapter seeks to unpack these themes and more as semi-structured interviews are undertaken with experts and leaders in the system.

Chapter 7: Semi-Structured Interviews

The previous chapter explored the assessments in Australia's NAP (ACARA, 2011a) that measure the achievement of the goals for schooling as outlined in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). It presented a summary of the K-12 education system's performance as reported using the current set of measures and elucidated those commitments to action in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) not currently measured by the NAP. While the standardised measures used to produce the image of system-wide success (or failure) are supported by evidence of content validity, there is a significant level of concern about whether the measures that are used sample broadly enough from the statement of goals as presented in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). Put simply, are Australian schools measuring what matters? In addition, Chapter 6 raises the question as to whether the consequential validity of schools being made to focus on the narrow set of goals that standardised assessments can assess in an economically viable fashion at scale has detracted further from the value of the measurements used to evaluate the performance of the Australian system.

Chapter 7 explores the opinions of educational leaders on valid measures of what matters to the Australian K-12 school system through a series of semi-structured interviews. In doing so, the chapter draws upon the insights and lived professional experience of the study participants in partnership with the findings from the literature. Considering where to next, this chapter asks: Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that is more aligned to the outcomes of schooling that matter to Australians? That is, could it be done better?

To generate data on system-wide performance, a common measure and shared definition for success must preside. At present, this relies upon a suite of testing (predominantly standardised) that is outlined in the NAP (ACARA, 2011a). Is a standardised test result enough to encapsulate a quality educational experience for all Australian children? Testing is incredibly

valuable and useful in many contexts. However, it may also miss many of the key elements that children, parents, and educators value in their schooling. It is indeed challenging, if not impossible to reduce the measure of success for schooling to a single definition. Education is not binary and able to be defined by a series of zeros and ones. There is an art and science to teaching that must be embraced to truly appreciate the value of learning and setting young people up for success, no matter who they are, where they come from or what their future may hold. The endless and rigorous pursuit of excellence and equity should be the goal of every education system. Yet, it also demands an appreciation of what excellence and equity look like, and an acceptance that they may be different in every nation, every classroom and for every learner. Meeting learners where they are, accepting them for who they are and engaging them in a learning journey that sets them on a path to growth and opportunity is the primary work of every school system. If this can be achieved, then success is within reach. It is essential then, to go beyond the tenets of a standardised test to measure the success of a school system (Mintrop & Trujillo, 2007; Fullan, 2007).

To answer the important question, where do we want to be?, Charmaz and Bryant (2011) explain the job of a constructivist is to co-construct experience and meaning with participants which this project endeavours to do. Many of the conversations were built upon the researcher's understanding from being situated within the system and sharing common lived experiences with the participants. This not only supports the operationalisation of the methodology but also enhances its reliability when compared to a methodology such as ethnography, where the researcher is entering the community as an outsider to observe and learn about its customs and community of practice. Figure 26 shows the research process which was discussed previously in Chapter 4 and referenced in Chapter 5.

Figure 26

Research Process for the Semi-Structured Interviews

To begin, this chapter outlines the backgrounds of the participants to demonstrate their expertise and authority in this domain. As discussed in detail in Chapter 4, these participants were purposively sampled to meet the agreed criteria.

7.1 Participant Background Statements

Each of the participants in this study needed to meet agreed criteria (shown below). Table 16 shows which of the ten participants (P1 – P10) meet the three criteria (a, b and c).

Table 16

Purposive sampling according to criteria

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10
a	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑
b	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑
c	☑	☑	☑	☑		☑	☑		☑	☑

The criteria to meet included:

- a) experience at the national level to design, deliver or debate educational testing,
- b) working knowledge of the National Assessment Program and the goals for schooling outlined in the Mparntwe Declaration, and
- c) working knowledge as an educator in the Australian K-12 school sector

Table 17 shows the locations in which the participants have lived and worked, their roles during their career with regards to their remit and coverage. Finally, it shows whether each of the participants have teaching experience and their gender. Note that P5 and P8 do not have any teaching experience: one is a policy leader who has held senior government positions and the other works for an intergovernmental organisation administering large-scale assessments.

Table 17

Interview Participant Data

Participant	Location	Roles	Teaching Experience	Gender
P1	NSW, ACT, VIC	School, National, International	40+ years	M
P2	WA	School, National, International	15+ years	M
P3	VIC	School, State	20+ years	F
P4	SA, NSW	School, State, National	30+ years	F
P5	ACT, NSW	National, International	0 years	M
P6	NSW	National, International	40+ years	F
P7	VIC	School	20+ years	M
P8	NSW	State, International	0 years	F
P9	NT, NSW	School, State, National	40+ years	M
P10	QLD	School	30+ years	F

7.2 Interview Data

The semi-structured interviews were guided by the research questions and conducted virtually with the participants' consent. Given their semi-structured nature, the interviews each took their own direction. As noted in the introduction to this chapter, due to the nature of these interviews to generate grounded theory, there was a reliance on the researcher being positioned within the study and having a working knowledge of the concepts being explored. Figure 27 shows the steps taken to complete the interviews.

Figure 27

Process of Data Generation From Interviews

Figure 27 not only shows the process employed to complete the interviews but also demonstrates the inter-relatedness of the data generation process using Constructivist Grounded Theory methodology. This iterative process provides support to the rigour of the study.

7.3 Results from the Initial Coding

As discussed in Chapter 4, Section 4.7 interview transcripts were coded line-by-line. In the first interview, 770 lines of data were examined and coded. Those lines were each allocated a code, resulting in 681 codes. The codes were generated using key words to describe the content. Any conversational lines such as “can you hear me ok?” and “thanks for your participation” were excluded from the data set. Given the repetition of codes, Table 18 shows the 114 unique codes.

Table 18

Codes Generated from Interview 1

Acquired knowledge	Excellence	Postcode lottery
Alignment	Future of schooling	Purposeful learning
Alternative paths	Future of work	Rankings
Articulate what they can do	Gap in reporting	Reporting
Artifacts of learning	Global comparisons	Real world learning
Assessing students	Goals for schooling	Resources, school
Assessment for learning	Growth	Role of teacher
Assumed knowledge	HSC results	Scale, measurement at
Australian schools	Improvement needed	School, by size
Barriers to success	Indicators of success	School, by type
Better measures of success	Influences, power	School, effectiveness
Capabilities	Irreconcilable differences	School, experience
Capability statements	Knowledge	Skills
Care for children	Lacking experience	Special needs
Catholic education	Language of performance	Students
Change needed	Leadership	Student agency
Classroom / school structure	League tables	Student capacity
Competencies	Learner dispositions	Student experience
Complexity	Measures of success	Sum of experiences
Can't reconcile headlines	Measuring what matters	Summative testing
Content driven	Measuring whole student	System failing
Contextualisation is critical	Measurement	System performance
Creativity	Media headlines	System policy
Creativity, lack of	Media, political agenda	System-wide success
Credentials	Meeting needs of learners	Teacher
Cultural perspectives	Metacognition	Teacher & student
Curriculum	Misconceptions	Teacher attitude
Data	NAPLAN results	Teacher performance
Definition of success	National assessment	Teacher training
Design new methods	National perspectives	Teaching career
Digital capabilities	National policies	Teaching experience
Digital platforms	Outcomes-based	Teaching standards
Digital solutions	Parent	Test results
Digital strategy	Pedagogy	Testing, influence
Diversity	Performance	University entrance
Educational policy	Performance bands	Value the whole student
Education system	Performance review	What can we measure?
Equity	PISA scores	What do we value?

Table 19*Codes generated from Interview 2*

Accountability	Independent school	Policy statements
Articulating learning	Indigenous students	Policy, influences
Aspirational goals	Infrastructure	Political agenda
Assessment	Instrument validity	Political ideologies
Australian schools	Intent	Political influence
Autonomy	Knowing students	Political narrative
Benchmarks	Large-scale assessment	Political nuance
Classroom	Learning progressions	Political scrutiny
Competence	Literacy/numeracy	Politics
Consequences	Localisations	Professionalism
Context	Marking tests	Psychometrics
Contextual validity	Measure growth	Public goods
Country rankings	Measure success	Purpose
Curriculum	Measurement	Quality education
Curriculum agnostic	Measuring growth	Reconciling results
Curriculum reform	Monitoring growth	Regional, rural school
Definition of excellence	Measuring success	Reporting
Definition of success	Media headlines	SDG goals
Developmental assessment	Media unhelpful	Seat at the table
Differentiation	Meet the needs	Student - growth
Disadvantaged students	Meet them there	Student - teacher
Diversity	Minimum standards	System - failing
Domains of learning	Misconceptions	System not homogenous
Education system	Misinterpretations	TAFE/VET
Educators	NAP	Teacher education
Equality	NAPLAN	Teacher knowledge
Equity	NAPLAN rubrics	Teacher training
Evidence	Narratives	Teacher workforce
Excellence	National testing	Teaching career
Faith-based	Needs of learner	Test development
Falling rankings	Non-technical audience	Test instruments
Fatten the pig	Observations	Test results
Federal v state	Opportunity	Test results, misuse
Funding	Participation	Test translation
Generalisations	Perceptions	Testing washback
Getting it right	Performance	Testing, cross sectional
Global comparison	Personalised	Testing, point in time
Goals for schooling	Perspectives	Testing, time separated
Governance	Plan to achieve	Time comparisons
Growth	Policy	Trajectories
High school teacher	Policy - NAP	Unintended consequence
Human bias to negatives	Policy announcers	University entrance
Immigrants	Policy influence	Validity
Impact	Policy makers	Where they're at

This process was repeated for each transcribed interview. A comparison method was used to elicit the common codes across all the interviews and distilled down to 90 codes. The common initial codes are listed in Table 20.

Table 20*Common Initial Codes*

Accountability	Media Headlines, Unhelpful
Articulating Learning	meeting students where they're at
Aspirational Goals	Misconceptions
Assessment	Multicultural context
Australian Schools	NAP
Autonomy	NAPLAN
Benchmarks	National testing
Carrying Baggage	Needs of learner
Competence	Non-technical audience
Consequences	Observations
Contextualisation	Participation
Country Rankings	Performance
Curriculum Reform	Personalised
Definition Of Excellence	Plan to achieve
Definition Of Success	Policy - announcers, makers, influencers
Differentiation	Political ideologies
Disadvantaged Students	Political scrutiny
Diversity	Professionalism
Domains Of Learning	Psychometrics
Education System	Public goods
Equality	Purpose
Equity	Quality education
Evidence	Reconciling results
Excellence	Reporting
Federal V State	SDG goals
Funding	Teachers taking a seat at the policy table
Generalisations	Skills
Global Comparison	Student - teacher relationship
Goals For Schooling	Student agency
Governance	Student growth
Growth	System, failing
Attend To Negatives	Systematic observations
Impact	Teacher education
Indigenous Students	Teacher wellbeing
Infrastructure	Teacher workforce
Intent	Test development
Knowing Students	Test instruments
Large-Scale Assessments	Test results / misuse / unintended
Learner Wellbeing	Testing, cross sectional
Learning Progressions	Testing, point in time
Literacy/Numeracy	Testing, time separated
Localisations	Unintended consequences
Marking Tests	University entrance
Measure Growth	Validity
Measure Success	Valuing the whole student

7.4 Generation of Concepts, Categories and Themes

In the initial coding, many of the codes were descriptive of the conversation occurring between the participant and the researcher. The next step was to further code them into concepts, categories, and themes (Charmaz, 2006; Saldaña, 2009; Sigauke and Swansi, 2020).

Figure 28

Process for Generation of Concepts, Categories and Themes

The initial codes were reviewed in the search for “sensitising concepts,” those “background ideas that inform the overall research problem” (Charmaz, 2003, p.259). The list below details the sensitising concepts which emerged from the data.

Table 21

Sensitising Concepts

Accountability	National – funding models
Australian school system	Policy – Influence of
Definitions of success	Policy – Makers, Announcers
Equity / Equality of access	Political narratives
Global comparisons / Country rankings	Professionalism, teachers
Goals for Schooling	Prior knowledge, teachers
Growth	Results incl. unintended consequences
Measurement – tools / testing	Reporting
Media	Testing – Tools, Influence, Misuse
Misconceptions	Validity
National – Federal v state/territories	Values

Informed and shaped by the sensitising concepts, Figure 29 shows how the codes were sorted into categories and then generated themes that were evident across the study.

Figure 29

Codes, Categories, Concepts and Themes

Aspirational, defining success and excellence, plan to achieve, goals for schooling, intent, purpose	Goals for Schooling	
Policy, politics, ideologies, policy makers, policy announcers, political scrutiny, public goods, societal needs, federal, local, state, federated nation, funding, governance, accountability	Government Policy and political parties	
Accountability, autonomy, governance, quality	Accountability	
Assessment, benchmarks, NAP, national testing, observations, psychometrics, evidence, large-scale assessment, marking, measure growth, measurement, tools, test instruments, test construction, test development, validity, reliability, fairness	Measurement and Testing	
Achievement, performance, competence, global comparisons, country ranking, growth, impact, learning progressions, reporting, data sets, results, system-wide success	Performance and Results	
Consequences, intended and unintended, testing washback, misuse, misconceptions, validity, media, headlines, misalignment	Misconceptions and the media headlines	
Australian schools, context, K-12, education system, local, national, curriculum, reform, learning domains, literacy, numeracy, differentiation, meeting students where they're at, diversity, multicultural, bias, equity, equality, Indigenous, inclusion	Australian K-12 School System	

7.5 Emerging Themes

Equipped with the sensitising concepts as the starting point, the concepts were then further categorised to start exploring how the categories relate to each other. The data reflects the emergence of the ideas that are informing the research problem as to whether the Australian K-12 school system is measuring what matters when it comes to the goals it has set for itself. The coding process is imperative to the study as it builds the bridges between data and meaning. Through inductive analysis, patterns emerge from the data rather than being imposed upon them (Patton, 1980). Several recurring themes emerged through this process. They are shown here:

Figure 30

Recurring Themes

The results from the data are explored below, in context, to better understand these themes and their impact on the research problem.

7.5.1 The System

During the interviews, the participants shared their perceptions of the federal education system based on its successfulness, equity, excellence and whether it may be considered as world class. As participants discussed their thoughts, it was soon evident that there was a recurring theme of dissatisfaction with the system itself. It became clear from their comments that the complex, federated system was a source of misalignment as stakeholders grappled with a shared definition of success that met the needs of every Australian child. Figure 31 shows the codes and categories that contribute to the generation of the ‘System’ itself as a theme.

Figure 31

Extracted Codes and Categories

It is not possible to examine educational success in Australia without firmly situating it in its unique context. Contributing factors to this include Australia's geographic diversity, federated structure, politics, policies, funding models, and teacher workforce. As Participant 2 explains, "They're very admirable goals. The idea of equity, the idea of personalised education, the idea of equal opportunity of access, they're all unarguably positive things that are absolutely things that an education should absolutely do." However, they went on to share some of the challenges arising by adding, "That being said, those goals are aspirational and difficult to implement ... they stand as visions and people are surprised when the vision hasn't been achieved but actually there hasn't been a plan to achieve them. Or support."

Further to the system itself, Participant 7 spoke to equity, sharing a concern that "...between Declarations we switched the order of priority between excellence and equity because it's easier to get some measures on excellence, and it's politically uncomfortable to look at equity...". Regarding equity, Participant 10 explained that "the biggest challenge of any goal related to equity is having the power to do something about it. Educators are tasked with addressing equity issues every day but are not given the power or means to do anything about it."

In exploring the notion of equity in these conversations, a common thread linked the issue of equity to the system itself and its design. Participant 6 shared that "Equity and excellence are the driving force of the Declaration". However, they also felt that "we are simply not doing enough to act on those goals." Participant 6 was concerned that "this should all fall into the lap of the teachers who are already doing so much with so little. Teachers around the world are struggling with the same challenge, but it makes no sense in an economy like ours."

Repeatedly, participants spoke to the challenges of operating in a federated system. Participant 8 shared that Australia is "operating as one system when in fact we are operating as states, territories, sectors and districts is a challenging arena to serve in". Participant 2 echoed this in their statement, "...if I was going to wave a magic wand for policy, I'd say we need to get

rid of the idea that “the system” is homogenous and that “the system” has one model or one method that is going to achieve outcomes”.

To conclude, many participants including Participant 2 called for greater “diversification, contextualisation, and local autonomy based in schools” to address the complex system Australian schools are situated in.

7.5.2 Accountability

Accountability was a recurring theme in the interviews as show in Figure 32.

Figure 32

Accountability Codes and Categories

The education system and its stakeholders are internally and externally accountable. For example, teachers are accountable to parents, students, school leaders, governments and society. Students are accountable to parents and teachers. School leaders are accountable to parents, sector leaders and politicians. Politicians are accountable to the society and their constituents who, are in turn, the students, parents, teachers and school leaders. Figure 33 below attempts to show the lines of accountability inherent in the system as it seeks to enact policy, the results of which are reported in the media. The accountability matrix, drawn from the interview data and

designed for the purpose of this study, seeks to show the interplay between the components of the system and where the accountability for its success lies.

Figure 33

The Accountability Matrix

The arrows show the direction of accountability within the system as explained in the various interviews completed as part of this study. It is of importance to note that the only stakeholders accountable to the teachers in this model are the students. Students are answerable to their teachers in terms of their behaviour and effort. Yet, teachers are accountable to all key stakeholders in the education system and the media who report on its performance. Situating teachers at the centre of the accountability debate, many participants expressed the myriad of challenges faced by educators who are made accountable to so many and for so much. As Participant 10 shared, “There are many aspects of what we do as teachers that is the human, the artistic, the creating of. And then there's the need to fit within an economic hierarchy in a system that demands accountability.”

Addressing accountability, it is important to ascertain who is at the helm of the education system and for how long. Interestingly, none of the participants referenced political parties or personalities yet they all referenced the soft power at play and in particular, the role of the media. Participant 9 shared, “I think the profession has absolutely got a right to call for appropriate wages...but with the cost of the pay rise, all of the support that's been rebuilt up for schools is going to disappear because the community has got to find billions of dollars to make it happen”. They went on to say, “this is what the media challenge constantly. Where will the money come from?”

In terms of accountability, Participant 10 was determined that educators and school leaders have the power to do something about the challenges they face. They said, “School leaders struggle to be in the staff room when they are not of the staff room. Every principal sat alongside their team and said, “You work too hard,” and “you’re not paid enough.” But then they don’t have the means or power to do anything about it.” Further to this, Participant 5 commented on the soft power at play in the education system, “There is such vested interest in education, by everyone, that it means planned interventions get softened.” They went on to explain, “We know changes are needed but people get frightened, they don’t have the political will to do what is needed and make the tough calls. There is a lot of soft power at play.”

Seeking the link between power and accountability, Participant 5 shared, “you know we speak of the invisible curriculum in schools, there is also, I think, in Education the invisible policies and politics that are unspoken”. Participant 3 concurred with their comment, “Being transparent ... in exploring the political power and influence is key. Unfortunately, the media often focus on this in a manner to the detriment of the system overall in my view.”

Looking to the role of teachers at the core of the accountability matrix seen in Figure 33, Participant 1 suggested this means it is time for a revisiting of the teaching standards, “I think we need to really look again at the Australian Professional Teacher Standards, they are probably due

for a rework”. It was repeated throughout the interviews that teachers are “responsible for too much,” have “too much asked of them” and “bear too much responsibility for the raising of successful citizens of the future.” Yet at the same time, participants echoed concerns with “teacher professionalism,” a “lack of expertise with data” and the need for teachers to “better engage with parents as academics and professionals.”

In conversation, it was apparent that there is a great deal of accountability for the success of the education system resting on the shoulders of teachers. Participant 5 articulated the role of teachers as a cherished one given; they are “carrying the burden of the society’s future in their daily work.” Yet equally, other participants (1, 2, 7 and 10) also saw potential for this burden to be better distributed. One example was the suggestion of an increasingly differentiated system with increased autonomy over what students need, when and how. As Participant 2 shared, “I think you can have a differentiated system with lots of autonomy in lots of different schools while having a tool that allows all schools to have common measures of growth.” They felt it important that as part of accountability teachers had a common means for talking about student growth. They said, “teachers can use it to talk about the student’s growth in their context from where the student started at to where they are now.”

In Figure 33, the media is seen as an influencer given its role as the platform for reporting on the outputs of the system to the society. Participant 10 spoke to this sentiment, “We have to have courage and be brave to stand up for what we know kids need”. It was evident from the interviews that teachers wanted to be trusted to do their jobs well. However, Participant 10 agreed that “to earn that trust it comes from being accountable to the society”. They went on to assert that “key to achieving this is working with the media to help translate all the jargon to engage Australians in a national conversation about what matters in education.” Participant 3 similarly said, “the media has the power to make or break us as a profession. I say we work with the media to lead the conversation about what matters most for our Aussie kids so they can

thrive, not just survive.” The prevalence of accountability to the media throughout the conversations was highly informative. Skourdombis and Rawolle (2020) propose that the media have become the measure of teacher effectiveness as they frequently discuss teachers as “key influences that impact student achievement scores, which then flow into the comparisons of nations’ performances on large-scale tests” (p.2). From these conversations, most participants seem to agree.

7.5.3 Goals and Definitions

Figure 34 shows the recurring theme of goals and shared definitions in terms of aspirations for excellence, success and quality across the education system.

Figure 34

Goals and Definitions: Codes to Categories

When asked for their thoughts on whether the Australian education system is meeting its agreed goals as per the Declaration (Education Council, 2019), the participants were divided. Their repeated struggle with the question stemmed from an inability to point to a shared definition for success. Each of the participants, in their own way, expressed that the definition of success for the Australian education system was different for every child, every teacher and in every context. However, this doesn’t necessarily help a system work towards a shared goal.

Participant 2 started by referring back to their own experience in schools, “You know, I have been in a school where the school is doing great things and the school, for me it’s about school autonomy, that’s a big missing piece from the picture because our definitions of success and excellence necessarily have to be contextualised”. In seeking to answer whether the Australian education system is meeting its goals, they went on to say, “I taught in a very small school, very multicultural and honestly, the ambitions of the young people there were not well served by the you know, University entrance exams for example.” Reflecting further, Participant 2 shared, “so the school was able to partner with the local TAFE, have a training facility built on site and really pivot all of its senior school courses to things which were relevant to students getting employment in their local community. That was when we experienced our greatest success.”

By contrast, Participant 7 looked at the question etymologically, “excellence is actually a comparative in the context of to excel. So, you have a standard that you think is appropriate, and you have gone beyond that and thus to excel? Or is it an objective standard that says, here we have reached excellence.” Building on this, they added “the first question that strikes me is, who determines what that excellence is? What comprises that excellence? And to what effect is that excellence applied.”

Participant 1 also sought greater clarity on the meaning of excellence to assess if Australia was meeting its national goals. They said, “I think the first stage to improvement and making a strong and effective education system would be to have an extensive discussion around what excellence means, and to do it without being held back by only setting goals you can measure with standardised tests.” During the interview, Participant 1 recalled “I had a terrific experience with working with Dr. Brown and Professor Gordon Stanley. You might be surprised that there are ways you can measure those things. The things that actually matter. Just because you haven't bothered thinking about it, and it hasn't been done. Doesn't mean it can't be done.”

Cuban (2000) argued that part of the reason it is so hard to arrive at a shared definition of success is that the goals of education are so diverse. However, applying the same diversity to the definition of success may remove the single-minded focus on test scores (Flessa, Gallagher-Mackay & Parker, 2010). Many attempts have been made to arrive at a shared definition of success, but increasingly, most find it easier to arrive at a statement of purpose. In their submission to the Education Council of the Council of Australian Governments (COAG) NAPLAN Reporting Review 2019, the Gonski Institute led at the time by Adrian Piccoli and Pasi Sahlberg, proposed the design of a national assessment and reporting system informed by Australia's agreed purpose for education. They defined this using the Melbourne Declaration on Education Goals for Young Australians which states that: "Australian schooling promotes equity and excellence and that all young Australians become, successful learners, confident and creative individuals and active and informed citizens" (MCEETYA, 2008a, p.2). As they proceed to make recommendations accordingly, Piccoli and Sahlberg (2019) express the pivotal importance of the national assessment and reporting system's role in monitoring system-wide performance against this agreed purpose. In doing so, it must remain focused on excellence, equity, wellbeing, and students' attitudes toward learning (p.2). Based on this agreed purpose of education in Australia and the related issues of importance, how does this shape a definition of success? Further to this, how does the shaping of this definition of success elucidate the soft power at play?

In schools, success could be determined in terms of outcomes but Weatherton and Schussler (2021) suggest they are more akin to components that merely facilitate success. At a university in California, Oh and Kim (2016) reported that students from a Korean American background defined success as attaining high grades whereas their Mexican American peers viewed success as surpassing their parents' levels of attainment and attending a university program. It is evident from these examples that success is context-specific and born out of an individual's lived experience. Harking back to the words of Binet (1907) in Chapter 2, if the

perception of intelligence is defined by the means chosen to assess it, then perhaps ones understanding of success is also defined by the means used to measure it. Ironically, this means that the definition of success may well become a barrier to success. As seen in the quotes above, this was certainly a recurring theme in the interviews completed as part of this study. Weatherton and Schussler (2021) argue that the definition of success is impactful on every aspect of the research process including the policy and practice emerging from it. They say that a “researcher’s definitions of success will impact how they choose to measure the construct, ... how data are interpreted and thus what recommendations are proposed. These recommendations often have real-world impacts on student outcomes ...in the form of changes in policy or practices such as pedagogies” (p.2). Gramsci (2000) asserts that the dominant forces in a society exert their power, often very subtly over non-dominant groups through choices such as words, values, and norms. Whilst often invisible to the society, these powerful forces prevail (Grimm, 2015). In a world where money is the measure of success, it is that which is pursued. In a world where learning is the measure of success, it is that which is pursued.

Throughout this study, as the policies and stakeholders that inform and lead the education system examine their own definitions of success, this research seeks to contribute to a new perception of what it means for a school system to be deemed a success. However, as Participant 9 shared, “Perhaps the greatest barrier to our success is our definition of success”.

7.5.4 Measurement and Performance

During the interviews, the participants considered whether the assessment tools listed in the NAP are aligned with their definition of success for Australian K-12 schools. In examining their thoughts on the alignment of the nationally-agreed measurement instruments to the goals for schooling they all expressed the desire for a better way, but few engaged in a detailed debate of the current tools.

Participant 2 was eager for a new way forward. They said, “the goal is not, or ought not to be, students at the end of primary school should meet this minimum benchmark. The goal should be, when we last measured you, you were here and when we’ve measured you again, we’ve seen this much growth. And then how do we make sure that growth continues.” The concept of measurement as being key to growth was evident and they added, “that’s the key I think... articulating the learning progressions in more domains and in more detail should go alongside national accountability in terms of measurement against them.”

By contrast, Participant 1 was more concerned with the consequences of the measurements than their alignment with the goals. They shared that “...it doesn't matter what people say about the NAPLAN results... when the NAPLAN results come out, there's invariably a league table and then there's usually the headline in some of the more conservative tabloid press around which of the post codes that didn't do as well in NAPLAN.” Not focused solely on the underperformers, Participant 1 said, “And then, on the other end of the scale, you've got the schools along the leafy suburbs who will hire electric signage to put on the side of the street to tout how many of their students got the top scores for NAPLAN”.

Participant 7 was vexed by the amount of time spent on the first national goal. They shared, “...we spend an inordinate amount of time on our first national educational goal. And we've got some really good metrics around that. PISA, NAPLAN, PIRLS, TIMSS... whatever mechanisms you want at the either jurisdictional or state, or even school level.” Their primary concern was that “our second educational goal is a beautiful and largely ignored context. How do you actually measure active and informed citizens?”

Figure 35 shows the repeated codes from the interviews with participants. The role of assessment and measurement is clearly key to this study; hence it features strongly in the conversations with experts in this field. Interestingly, every conversation focused on the consequences of these assessments and measures rather than on their construction or reliability.

Figure 35*Measurement and Performance: Codes to Categories*

The impact of testing was viewed through a far more ethical and pedagogical lens rather than a psychometric one. Therefore, the theme of performance is also included here. The interview participants viewed measurement as a means to discuss learning progressions, growth, reporting and system-wide success. In each of the conversations, all comments regarding system-wide performance were linked back to the existing measures. Participant 6 echoed this mindset best when they shared, “there is so much good work happening in Australian schools, but we just can’t capture it all on the tests we use”.

Participant 2 spoke to the issue of learning progressions and reporting on performance across schools. They said, “Australia has national learning progressions for literacy and numeracy, and they are part of the NAP. So, in terms of the monitoring and governance at the national level of how students are progressing in literacy and numeracy.” They added that “a tool like the NAP is needed, but I think the way it's reported needs to change because in my opinion it's been changed for the worst in recent months [laughs].”

This reference to the issues of reporting leads to the theme of trust and validity. As participants pondered the use and misuse of assessments and measurements to quantify the success of Australia's K-12 education system, questions of trust and mistrust arose.

7.5.5 Trust and Validity

The common codes cited in the interviews related strongly to misuse, misconception and mistrust which all invariably linked to the reporting of test results in the media. Fundamentally, consequential validity of the results and their perceived trustworthiness was an issue to most participants. This is shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36

Trust and Validity: Codes to Categories

Throughout the interviews the question of validity and trustworthiness were raised and grappled with frequently. These questions were amongst the most challenging for the participants to engage with judging by their body language and the long pauses. It was an aspect of the conversations that demanded deep thought from many. Every answer ultimately linked to validity with an emphasis on the consequential validity (Messick, 1989) of the assessment as the discussion turned to the role of the media, policy makers and policy announcers in impacting their intent and result.

Participant 3 articulated their struggle with this saying, “sometimes it’s really hard to know if I trust the assessment because I am so disturbed by the headlines they’re generating. It’s hard to trust a headline that says you’re failing your students when you are working so hard for them.” A struggle that was shared by Participant 10 who said, “I believe wholeheartedly in the instruments we rely upon as being valid, reliable, and fair. What I don’t trust is the intent behind their use and the impact of their results on our teachers, students, and education system.”

Participant 2 evoked the difficulties in evaluating the impact of such issues on the validity of the test instrument. They said, “You know, the narratives are unhelpful. And incorrect. And definitely damage the validity of, [pauses] oh, does it damage the validity of the assessment? It doesn’t change the instrument, so it doesn’t affect the instrument’s validity. What it changes is perceptions of it. And that, again, because it is largely non-technical audiences, it is very damaging, and I think educators often rebel against it as well.”

Further to this conversation grappling with validity, Participant 2 made an interesting comment regarding the use of national assessments, “You see assessment instruments are tools. Right. They are, they’re ways of gathering systematic observation, in terms of where students are in their learning.” With agreement, they continued, “then it gets more complicated because the results are used for purposes which are not necessarily related to the intent of the assessment.” Participant 2 therefore concluded that, “some of the purposes end up being inappropriate or they

end up having unintended consequences, they can end up having washback on the assessment and the test takers that was never intended”.

Reflecting on the role of teachers in assessment, Participant 4 shared “teachers have always approached assessment correctly. Teachers see assessments as a way to get information about the students in front of them that can either confirm or challenge what they already know about the students in front of them.” An approach that was recommended for all stakeholders.

It was evident from these interviews and the related literature on test validity and reliability, that there is a disconnect between the tests intended use and the ramifications their results and reporting has on the stakeholders who constitute the education system. This segues well to the final theme of policy and politics.

7.5.6 Policy and Politics

According to Participant 2, “Many professions are afforded autonomy, and appear to not operate with the same level of political influence and interference. Then there is teaching. Everything teachers do is a political football, and often cheap shots are made by politicians to sell their narrative through the media....”

Figure 37 shows the codes and categories generated which saw politics and policy recur.

Figure 37

Politics and Policy: Codes to Categories

The theme of policy and politics is further concerned with the reporting of results and the underlying ideologies that participants felt were being perpetuated as a consequence. Interestingly, every comment regarding reporting was linked back to the political narratives and policy being enacted by the education system. Reporting was almost seen as a tool for the dissemination of ideology rather than concerned with documenting student progress or achievement. Participant 2 argued this may occur as there is “a lack of educator expertise in the policy space. That’s not for lack of interest but because the policy makers and the policy announcers, who are the politicians, aren’t really interested in expert opinion.” Participant 4 saw the politicians as “driving the datafication of education” which informs and shapes the reporting.

By contrast, Participant 10 saw funding as “driving educational decision making as we pursue the Australian dream”. They said, “our governments are aspirational, which is great, but they’ve also got to realise that to innovate you have to be allowed to fail and learn from it without fear. Our reporting model doesn’t currently provide for such learning opportunities without making news headlines.”

When it comes to policy and politics, the soft power at play across the education system is apparent. Poignantly, one comment that had a lasting impact was from Participant 2 who, when discussing the task before us in terms of policy and political ideology said, “measurement is easy but supporting growth, that’s hard”. In conversation, the true purpose of education and the Australian K-12 school system is not to measure the growth but to achieve it. That is where the foundation of system-wide success resides. As participant 2 went on to say, “we all know the expression and have heard it a thousand times, you don’t fatten the pig by weighing it”. So, the focus needs to be not on what we measure but on why it matters and for whom.

Participant 7 reflected on the short term thinking of politicians and the need to look further into the future. They said, “Politicians in 2023 are making policy decisions, particularly about things, such as defence and finance that have 20 year horizons and they have no equivocation

about saying that the decisions we're making in 2023 will not have impact until 2045." Speaking to the education system they added, "the schooling journey for most students is thirteen or so years but the manifestation of the value of that journey well may not be understood until those students are 30 or 35 years old". Yet, looking to the future, Participant 7 shared, "leaving the issues of the Federation aside for a moment, the short-termism of our politicians is our issue. Education takes time and long-term commitments, yet after 2 or 3 years we are beating our breasts in anguish that we are going down the gurgler and splash it across the front page of the newspaper". The interplay between politics, policy and pedagogy is seemingly problematic.

7.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter set out to explore the perspectives of educational leaders through semi-structured interviews. The purpose was to elicit their responses to the third research question, is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals? As the interviews took their course, key themes emerged throughout the conversations: the system, accountability, goals and definitions, measurement and performance, trust and validity, policy and politics. From the perspectives of the participants, these thematic conversations supported the hypothesis that things could be done better and that the need exists to better align the goals for schooling with the measures to determine their successful achievement. The following chapter delves into a discussion of the findings in relation to all three research questions.

Chapter 8: Discussion of Findings

Chapter 8 seeks to summarise and discuss the findings of this research study. To do so, the chapter begins by reiterating the key themes documented in the previous chapter and proceeds to discuss them in relation to the research and findings generated throughout the study. Next, the chapter presents a theory regarding the misalignment between the national goals for schooling and the measures that are used to attest to their achievement. Prior to concluding with a vision for the future, the chapter explains how the findings of this study link back to the core research questions:

RQ 1: To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

RQ 2: How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?

RQ 3: Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

8.1 Findings

Key themes emerged through the process of coding and categorising the interview data:

1. System
2. Accountability
3. Goals and Definitions
4. Measurement
5. Performance
6. Trust and Validity
7. Policy and Politics

Figure 30

The themes which were generated using the Constructivist Grounded Theory approach align strongly with the findings echoed in the research literature (detailed in Chapter 2) and the policy analysis (explored in Chapter 5). As such they form the basis of the key findings elaborated upon here.

8.1.1 Finding 1: The Complex Federated Education System

With so many different opinions as to how things could be done better, measured differently, or approached from a different perspective, the greatest impediment to finding a way to evaluate the success / quality / excellence of the Australian school system is that it is not simply one system. Rather, it is situated in a contested and complex federated landscape. As Participant 2 declared, “the system is not homogenous”. In data sets there are notes that say, for example, “care must be taken in their interpretation as both Tasmania and the Northern Territory could not meet the sample requirements” (ACARA, 2020b, p. 24). There are vast differences between the states and territories of Australia that extend well beyond their geography.

To manage the federated system, the States and Territories of Australia came together with their commonwealth to form the goals for schooling articulated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) and the earlier versions of it. Working together they sought consensus on what a successful education system could look like for all and agreed upon measures to ascertain their performance against those shared goals. When reflecting on the NAP and the Australian goals for schooling outlined in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019), this study found that there are many practices that Australian schools should maintain. The most important one of all, is to keep questioning itself, its practice and how it can be continually improving. As Participant 7 said, “one of the things Australian education does well is maintain its questioning position by asking this is the way things might have been, but ought that be the way”.

However, an important finding from this research and the act of engaging in such questioning links back to the work of Hume (1739), which states that you can't necessarily deduce an ought from an is. Applied to the world of educational policy and PISA results, Australia may be engaging in what Hume would call an "ought fallacy" when assuming that because Country Y performed well on PISA and is engaging their children in X hours per day of face-to-face teaching that Australia "ought" to do that. This study has shown that context matters, definitions matter, people matter. What is right for one is not always right for the other. The process of policy borrowing from other nations which stems from the PISA country rankings has somewhat fuelled engagement with an "ought-is" fallacy.

The national K-12 schooling system is situated within the richer and deeper context of Australian society. One cannot make a change to the system without feeling its ripple effects across the society for years to come. So too, to support societal change, the schooling system needs to be empowered (morally, philosophically, financially, and operationally) by the society in which it is embedded. In a study of five jurisdictions that have "performed unusually well" on international achievements such as PISA, Masters (2022) found that they shared a common value of education as a path to "personal fulfilment and success", families that were supportive of student success, highly respected teachers and students who spent considerable outside of school hours engaged in learning (p.3). They also all shared a commitment to a new way of thinking about learning, assessment and the future shape of education systems that will meet the needs of their students. In setting their goals for the future of schooling, Finland, Estonia, British Columbia, Hong Kong and South Korea have all developed features of their learning systems to meet a new way of thinking that transcends "institutional arrangements, fixed time periods, and locations" (Masters, 2022, p.14). Learning from this, it is not the policy of these jurisdictions that Australia should borrow but rather, the mindset. Which leads to the next finding, Accountability and Stakeholders.

8.1.2 Finding 2: Accountability Based on Shared Responsibility

Questions regarding accountability and the role of key stakeholders in ensuring the effectiveness of the education system were explored in Chapter 7. From participant interviews, codes were generated that referenced governance, leadership, teacher quality, teacher development, teacher performance, stakeholder engagement and stakeholder management. Hargreaves and Shirley (2009) recommend an approach to accountability that is based upon shared responsibility,

...years of research in school effectiveness still show that most explanations for differences in student outcomes exist outside the school. Schools can and do make a significant difference but do not make all or even most of it. They cannot excel alone but need communities and society to work with and alongside them. This means more schools working with communities and more investment in community and family development. We can't expect to raise standards on the cheap. In schools as in business, there is no achievement without investment. High-performing Finland and other Nordic countries benefit from a welfare state that makes strong public investment not just in education, but also in housing, medical care, social services, and community development. While schools contribute a great deal, they are not expected to achieve miracles by themselves (p.79).

This statement by Hargreaves and Shirley (2009) not only supports Finding 1 regarding the situation of the school system within the context of the broader society, but also reinforces the significant contributions that schools already make. Participant 1 echoed this strongly when they said, “we need to tone down the language... we need to say that schools are places that contribute to the development of young people rather than saying that they are the places where it all happens. ... learning is a function of many inputs, schools being one of them.”

Changing the language and re-shaping the way the role of schools is positioned within the society holds promise. A simple shift in considering schools as contributing to the development of young people rather than taking full accountability for that strengthens the role of student agency in their own learning. It also reminds parents, politicians, policy makers and other stakeholders of their accountability to the educators that are working in classrooms across the system. If shared responsibility is to serve as accountability, then there is a need to re-shape the future of Australia's education system. It is known that the most effective means for transforming power relations is through language (Bourdieu, 1977). As such, a shift in the way the education system is referred to and spoken about could result in a positive change towards collective accountability for the future of Australian children. A point regarding accountability which was made in Section 7.5.2 with relation to teacher's building the trust of the society with the support of media platforms.

A quality education system begins and ends with the quality of the teacher in every classroom. That entails wrapping an entire support system around a suitably qualified and capable person. Instead, Australian teachers are subjected to media headlines such as "Teaching in Australia has become a refuge for the least able" the day before the new school term commences (Allen, 2023, 6 October). The article goes on to say that "allowing students with appallingly low ATARs into the teaching profession has helped to undermine their social standing." (para.1.). The quality of the teacher does matter. Hanushek (1971) estimated that the impact of the teacher on achievement between classrooms could vary by up to five months. In Hattie's (2003) examination of variance in student achievement, he found that teachers accounted for 30% and asserts that "it is what teachers know, do, and care about which is very powerful in this learning equation (p. 2).

In this study, there has been reference to the importance of teaching quality in the policies analysed (Chapter 5), the literature reviewed (Chapter 2), and the interviews conducted (Chapter

7). Repeatedly, participants argued for more support to be given to the development of quality teachers and quality schools. Yet, missing from these conversations is an agreed, national definition of what quality means for Australian schools. This links in turn to the next finding on the need for the goals to be articulated using agreed, shared definitions.

8.1.3 Finding 3: Agreed Goals and Shared Definitions

Many news articles, papers, and studies (including this one) have examined the notion of measuring what matters (Zhao et al., 2019), yet William (2018) reiterates a quote most often attributed to Alfred Binet, “why measure something if you cannot change it?” (p.133). In terms of the policy – measure – practice cycle, this means that there is a need to review the measurement tools used not in terms of the goals they seek to evaluate, but in terms of the work that will be undertaken as a result. Imagine if the responsibility for acting to resolve the findings of every ILSA that Australia participated in was taken seriously. For example, if Australia participates in an assessment that reports an issue with the inequity of results in a sample based upon the level of socio-economic advantage, there would be a need to act on that. In 2006, Australia’s performance on PISA raised alarm bells for equity measures compared to the OECD average. Figazzolo (2009) regarded this as the perfect opportunity to leverage the results to advocate for policies to “address the structural inequalities” and “underfunding of public education system” but instead, the Australian government called for “greater testing and accountability regimes” (p.17). Participant 2 referred to the tried-and-true expression in the field of educational measurement and assessment, “you don’t fatten the pig by weighing it”. Yet it appears that as goals are set for school systems and articulated in national policies a gap exists between the results they deliver and the interventions that will be staged in response. Instead, the action is to test again or explain the result away.

William (2018) challenges educators to move beyond the research that shows we know what to do and demands the creation of situations where what needs to happen can happen. To

achieve this, the stakeholders operating within the school system need to have a clear understanding of the goals to be achieved and a well-supported plan to make it happen. Based on the findings of this study, the problem is that the measures used are the ones which we have standardised tests for, rather than a set that truly reflect the values that we really do value.

Looking to the establishment of agreed, national definitions it is imperative to start by re-defining success. In fact, Hannon and Peterson (2021) go even further to propose that the time has come to replace the word ‘success’ and its links to the pursuit of material wealth with the biological metaphor, ‘thriving’ across four spheres: global, societal, intrapersonal, and interpersonal (p.xiv). In a school system whose purpose is for young people to thrive in a volatile and transforming global context, it is easy to conceive of a plan whereby every learner is “healthily flourishing whilst embedded in their own environment” (Hannon & Peterson, 2021, p.xiv). This study found that interview participants shared concerns for learner wellbeing, teacher wellbeing, student agency, equity, contextualisation, and autonomy (see list of codes at Table 14) amongst others. All issues that could be well served by a definition which favours human flourishing over the more competitively nuanced term, success.

Exploring further the analogy of the education system as an ecosystem, Hannon and Peterson (2021) describe a “community of interdependent organisms acting in conjunction with the natural environment” (p.185). Considering schools as learning ecosystems. integrated seamlessly with the social and technological world around them, learners and teachers could thrive in that ecosystem with purpose, clarity, and agency. Especially if they are engaged in learning that is suited to their need in a transforming world.

8.1.4 Finding 4: Focus on Measuring Growth

Spearman (1927) said that the power of measuring intelligence was that it enabled us to “make possible a proper treatment of each individual; to each can be given an appropriate

education, and therefore a fitting place in the state - just that which he or she demonstrably deserves” (Spearman, 1927, p. 8). It has been shown that if the nation can create situations whereby higher levels of educational achievement are attained then this is key to “empowering young people to take greater control of their lives” (William, 2018, p.21). The mission is clear and by engaging in the continuous quest for self-reflection, critical questioning, and improvement the system will benefit but only if supported by suitably qualified and empowered professionals.

This study has shown that Australian educators do not take issue with educational assessments as such but do react strongly to the way they are used, by whom and for what purpose. As participant 2 shared in Chapter 7, “they end up having unintended consequences, they can end up having washback on the assessment and the test takers that was never intended”. The participants spoke repeatedly of the invariable league tables following the NAPLAN or PISA results and the media headlines which followed. There was a pervading message in the conversations, the educators trusted the instruments as being valid, reliable and fair. What they didn’t trust was the intent behind their use and the misuse of their results. As participant 10 said, “I believe the instruments, what I don’t trust is their use and impact on our teachers, students, and education system”.

This study engaged with Messick’s (1989) work on validity in relation to the tests and measures used to determine system-wide success in the Australian K-12 school system. It was found that validity was a recurring concern across the measures used to determine the system’s achievement of the agreed goals for schooling (see Chapter 6) as the measurement instruments were frequently not being used for their intended purpose or covering the breadth of the commitments made by the ministers in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019), also discussed in Chapter 5. As such, the findings re-affirm the need to change the language used to define, determine, and report on performance. It’s essential that the narrative change. Reiterating

Binet's poignant words once more, "why measure something if you cannot change it?" (William, 2018, p.133). If student performance and growth are going to be measured, then responsibility must be taken for acting on the results generated. The study participants and policy documents agree, measurement must be used to ascertain the growth and progress of the students towards agreed educational outcomes. A focus on progression and growth will better support increased alignment between the measures used and the goals sought across the education system.

8.1.5 Finding 5: Critical Consumers of Data

The system is awash with data-fuelled debate. Consider school size and its impact on effectiveness as one example. Participant 1 reflected, "I think there's also a question within the scale of a school and we need reflection as to why we have schools with 700 or 1,100 or 2,000 students. I think something happens when schools get too big." This reflection appears congruent with the data. Research on school size shows that "the highest test scores are more often found in small high schools" (William, 2018, p.5) so the belief follows that small schools are optimal. However, the data also shows that the lowest scores are also attributed to the small schools (William, 2018). So, whilst the data matters, so too does the context and the verification of the data with other information.

Overwhelmed with data from an ever-increasing array of educational assessments, stakeholders are challenged with discerning the data that matters from the chaff. This requires educators to be savvy and critical users of both data and educational testing. This is where systems and stakeholders can better support teachers with clearly articulated trustworthy data sets that can be analysed in relation to the existing data on the students they teach. The participants in this study showed appreciation for the breadth of data available, yet struggled to see how teachers could possibly have the time or technical skill needed to be data analysts. As Participant 4 shared, "the only time I want kindy teachers worrying about data sets are when they

need to know where their kids are and where they need to take them next. And we need to make that as easy as possible for them to do.”

Other participants were concerned with the “secrecy of PISA” and the “black box” experience of NAPLAN for many teachers. As Participant 10 confided, “PISA is like a mystery to me. I struggle with not really understanding how it works.”

Addressing the need to make educational tests and their resulting data sets easy to use in a busy classroom context is a key outcome of this study and a recommendation to all providers and designers of educational assessments. So too, it is suggested that Initial Teacher Education and the Australian teaching standards address the need to attend to and further support the development of data literacy skills.

8.1.6 Finding 6: The Politics of Performance

When it comes to intelligence and the way brains work, the difference between short term memory and long-term memory is key. A child’s short-term memory may be tested on an assessment such as the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children (WISC) through the recitation of a string of numbers but even here the long-term memory matters. William (2018) explains that the ability to hold things in short-term memory rely upon what has already been stored in long-term memories. In many ways, this is analogous to the education system. There is a tendency to make quick short-term decisions based upon test results, policy guidelines and shifts in power, but then sometimes forget that their outcome is predicated on what already exists. Sweller’s (1988) Cognitive Load Theory states that tasks which overload short-term memory result in less learning. Could the same be said of the frequency with which teachers are required to deal with so many competing priorities in their classroom in the short term that therefore limit what can be achieved in the long term?

There is a tendency for politicians to suffer from the same issue. Too often they are not in office long enough to see their policies enacted in Australian classrooms and are consistently caught up in short-term cycles of action on issues that require long-term approaches. These same politicians are charged with creating narratives to inform their people of their efforts to be re-elected. In 1995, former UK Prime Minister, Tony Blair said, “education is the best economic policy there is” (Hannon & Peterson, 2021, p.6). Education and the mantras such as “back to basics” and “raise the standards” are regularly featured in political debate and it’s time to change the narrative (Hare, 2021; Hunter, 2019; Martin, 2014). Especially when it comes to reporting on the measures of education systems that the society struggles to define.

In discussing Finding 5 the need for teachers to engage as critical consumers of assessment data was evident. So too in Finding 3 we saw the need to clarify definitions and articulate them more effectively and purposefully. All of this speaks to the need to reconsider how the results of progress towards shared goals and the ultimate effectiveness of the Australian education system are reported.

In the Gonski Review (Gonski et al., 2018), equity in education was defined as ensuring that a difference in wealth, income, power, or possessions did not influence educational outcomes of Australian school children. The findings of this study incite the question: What does this really mean? Can we measure equity? and, if we measure it, what are we going to do about it? If we were able to answer those questions satisfactorily let us then ask, how will it be reported? As Participant 9 shared, “the problem of comparative assessments and reporting is that someone has to do well, and someone has to not do well”.

Thought and effort is needed to better demonstrate the many outcomes being achieved in the K-12 education system. There are so many things that schools are contributing beyond the results of the NAP that deserves to be reported on, showcased and celebrated. Too often the bridge between the political narrative and the performance of the school system is too narrow. Rather than

engaging in the politics of performance, this study advocates for the perception of performance as the outcome of intended actions and the enactment of clearly articulated, plain language goals for the education of all young Australians.

Having discussed the findings and key themes derived from this study, the next section outlines the substantive theory that was generated.

8.2 Substantive Theory

This study commenced with the hypothesis that there is a misalignment between what the NAP measures and the agreed goals of the Australian K-12 education system as stated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). In discussing the topic with leaders working in the field, this idea appeared to be credible. However, the hypothesis needed testing. To do that, the CGT methodology was selected as it supported the researcher's contribution and enabled the construction of theory that would be generated through an examination of policy, practice and the professional experience of leaders in the field of study. Through a process of coding, memo writing and constant comparison a substantive theory emerged that there is a misalignment between the goals Australia sets for its K-12 schooling and the tools used to measure the achievement of those goals due to the gap that exists between policy and measurement. Of the eleven nationally agreed commitments to action that support the achievement of the Declaration's (Education Council, 2019) goals for Australian schooling, only four are directly measured using the NAP. Add to this the media headlines and political narratives that fuel the misconceptions of non-technical audiences (parents, students and at times, teachers) and the rhetoric of a failing system gains credence and impacts the validity of the measures used.

The next section links the findings from the study to the research questions in an examination of what was learned.

8.3 What was learned?

This study sought to answer three core research questions:

RQ1. To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

RQ2. How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?

RQ3. Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

As a result, key themes emerged during the study: the system itself, accountability, goals and definitions, trust and validity, measurement, performance, policy and politics. Earlier in this chapter each of these themes and the subsequent findings was explained in detail. The question to address now is, what was learned from these thematic discussions?

Regarding K-12 schooling in Australia, a detailed examination of the federated system and the power relations inherent in it have resulted in the system itself being identified as one of the largest barriers to its success. Layers of complex funding agreements across a diverse and largely privatised school system are driving political debates that too often lose focus on what really matters – the students. So too, placing the onus for the system's success in the hands of elected officials that change office every four years is a potential issue. To reach consensus and effect change on issues that matter long term, a fresh approach to the governance of Australian K-12 schools is called for. There is no easy fix to the complexity of the system as it stands today. However, what has been found through this process is the absolute importance of a deep understanding of the context in which educators and other key stakeholders operate. The decisions made and the approaches taken must be informed by and operate within the bounds of the system in which it is situated. When looking to other nations, economies and education

systems and comparative studies ought to be completed with counterparts who share the same federated, highly privatised and diverse national profile.

When it comes to accountability and stakeholders, based on the findings of this study, the need for consensus on a shared, national definition of success and clarity in its articulation to all key stakeholders including via the media is critical. The measures of that agreed success must include varied sources of data that do not simply rely upon standardised measures to cover more than those things that are easy and economical to measure at scale. When schools and students are held accountable for a very narrow segment of the Declaration, issues of validity arise.

Regarding goals and definitions, a clearly articulated, plain language, shared understanding of pedagogical and global quality for the Australian K-12 school context is absent from the current rhetoric. Many attempts have been made to explore concepts of success, excellence and yet none seem to resonate in a meaningful way with consistency across the lingua franca of Australian schools and the policies that govern them. It has become clear that an agreed definition of quality, unimpeded by the necessity to have indicators that can be measured in a standardised manner is needed to help set the new barometer for system-wide success in Australia.

The analysis of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) made it apparent that many of the limits on the aspirations for the Australian education system are limited by things that are easy and economically feasible to measure across the vast and diverse Australian landscape at scale. The generation of good quality, robust and rich data that tells the story it was intended to tell is imperative to any vision for future iterations of the Australian measurement framework.

In addition, and most importantly, a key finding from this research is that if a system is going to measure student performance and growth, that system must be ready to accept responsibility for acting to change it once the results are received. As Participant 2 stated,

“measurement is easy, supporting growth is hard”. This speaks strongly to the disparity that is evident in the achievement gaps between states/territories and when the performance data is displayed according to student background as seen with the PIRLS data in Figure 25. William (2018) reminds again of a quote most often attributed to Alfred Binet, “why measure something if you cannot change it?” (p,133).

This thesis has attempted to reinforce a key finding that Australia must address the challenges of excellence and equity directly and in unison. One of the key findings from this study is that the issue of equity and the achievement gap must be positioned front and centre in any alternative approach to measurement of system-wide success. As Bloomberg (2023) said, “only what gets measured gets managed”. Therefore, any recommendations for improvements to the current measurement framework must place every child at the centre of all actions. Any newly developed policies must start with the adoption of four key perspectives: equity, quality, inclusion and accessibility. Their goal to equip young people with the core human traits of curiosity, creativity and resilience that will empower them in an increasingly complex, technologically enhanced way of learning and working. If these traits really matter, then they must be measured to show that the system is impacting positively on the development of them. Currently, the evidence shows (through omission) that they are not being measured and hence not valued in the system. In terms of aligning the needs of the individual with that of the system, Freire (2000) said,

Education either functions as an instrument which is used to facilitate integration of the younger generation into the logic of the present system and bring about conformity or it becomes the practice of freedom, the means by which men and women deal critically and creatively with reality and discover how to participate in the transformation of their world. (p.34)

The measures of growth employed, and more importantly the support provided to achieve growth, must be congruent with the context in which Australian students currently find themselves in. A crystal ball to know what that world may look like and how to ensure young Australians are future ready is not available. Therefore, it is imperative that our policies and endeavours are based on the principles of human rights and ethics to ensure young people are empowered as agents of change and education is viewed as a practice of freedom (Freire, 1998).

Throughout this study answers have been sought as to whether it is the alignment between the goals for schooling and the measurement instruments used that is problematic or whether it is the misuse and miscommunication of the data they produce. Or perhaps both? Ultimately, a misalignment is evident. Take for example the keyword search of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) outlined in Chapter 5 which referenced concepts such as creativity, resilience and spiritual facets to education with brief to no further mention throughout the policy or explicitly in the NAP measures. Or the limited number of commitments to action in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) being directly measured by the NAP. The misalignment was also explored as the researcher endeavoured to find out if it was the test itself or the way in which it was being used that was the cause of the issue. It became clear throughout the study that the role of test intent versus actual use was a key factor. This impacted what Messick (1989) refers to as the consequential validity of the instrument.

In Chapter 3, the standards for educational and psychological testing (AERA, APA & NCME, 2014) were discussed in relation to this. It is pertinent to reiterate here that if PISA data were used to monitor the impact of curriculum reform, then evidence must be granted that PISA is a valid measure of that, in that country or context. The responsibility for this does not lie with the test designers but rather with the national policy makers who choose to use it for this purpose. However, if it is used for an intended purpose such as educational equity then the responsibility for such evidence of validity rests with the test designer. A detailed understanding

of validity and how it applies to the measurement instruments engaged as part of the NAP must be undertaken to feel confident that the instruments are being used for their intended purpose and not misused or misaligned for the sake of convenience or headlines.

One of the key findings was the importance of equipping educators with the levels of data literacy needed to speak truth to the power of large-scale international assessment data sets. Too often these data sets are transformed into click bait headlines designed to draw the readership of non-technical audiences with a vested interest in the quality and success of the Australian education system. As a result, it is important to empower educators with plain language tools that are easy to use in busy classrooms and enable them to engage meaningful with students, parents and other key stakeholders about the value that such measurement instruments can bring to their teaching and learning experiences. Thus, this thesis finds the need for greater investment in the education of teachers, from initial teacher education and throughout their careers, to work knowledgeably and effectively with the data sets from large-scale national and international assessments as well as their own suite of classroom assessments to better inform and shape the pedagogical quality of their students' learning.

Many have questioned the validity of PISA as a measure of system-wide success (Zhao, 2020; Meyer & Zahedi 2014) and interrogated the authority of the data generated to inform global educational policy (Breakspear, 2014; Lingard & Sellar, 2013). Yet, few take the next step to propose a better way. "No matter how well we are doing, even if our students are the best in the world, they still need to be even better" (William, 2018, p.81). Is this achieved by competing to win the PISA competition? Perhaps not. Rather, this is achieved through a process of continual improvement whereby educators, policy makers, parents, economists, philosophers, artists, technologists and most importantly, students come together to generate a shared vision for the future and enact in a symbiotic and synchronous fashion. This requires educators to be well informed, articulate, and critical consumers of educational testing to ensure they can maximise

its potential to generate the best possible outcomes for their students and therefore, the system as a whole. This brings us to the final section of Chapter 8 and the final research question, is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals? Let's look to the future and build upon the findings to help move the research from theory to action.

8.4 Looking to the Future

In 1941, the year that the USA entered World War II, Dewey gave a speech at Colombia University in which he said of this tumultuous time, "You see the world is moving at a tremendous rate – no one knows where. We must prepare our children not for the world of the past, not for our world but, for their world, the world of the future" (Kandel, 1941). These words seem as relevant today as they did then. So too, a story that Dewey told in 1933. Dewey outlined an imagined, utopian vision of schooling by declaring that the most utopian thing of all would be "that there are no schools at all" (Dewey, 1933, p. 23). Proponents of AI and other techno solutionists of today seemingly share his vision, replacing schools with digital platforms and teachers with point in time robotic mentors accessible through a simple, natural language prompt (Richardson, 2012). Envisioned in Dewey's satirical, imaginative fiction, schools were replaced by places of free assembly to prioritise social interaction, promote artisanal style workshops, and cultivate intellectual inquiry through engagement with laboratories, libraries and museums with teaching provided via a sage, adult mentor for just in time moments as the learner is engaged in activity (Dewey, 1934). Dewey's story supports the notion that "the social change which had taken place with the abolition of an acquisitive economic society had... made possible the transformation of the centre of emphasis from learning (in our sense) to the creation of attitudes" (Dewey, 1934, p. 139). This is intriguing in the realm of a world where we are actively considering the role of AI in education and assessment. As we grapple with conceptions of

intelligence, learning and examine the role of human agency within them, it is timely to consider the impact of de-emphasising learning in favour of attitudes. There is an argument to be made that in a context where the computer can generate content, what role does the human's attitude to learning play? In reflecting upon what is learned about the Battle of Hastings by asking ChatGPT to write an essay on your behalf, perhaps the real question should be, what does the student outsourcing the learning to the computer say a) about the task and, b) about the learners' attitude towards the learning?

Papert (1998) asserts that the one competitive skill that will transcend the volatility of the world is the ability to learn. Ideally, the goal is to equip young people with the ability to know how to deal with situations for which they are completely unprepared. Every country in the world wants their children to succeed. In America, William (2018) shares that the problem is not that the school system is bad. It's that its 'variable' in terms of the quality of every child's educational experience (p.183). Sahlberg (2019d) said similar of Australia, "we have one of the best education systems anywhere. World class. But only for some children" (para.35). So, based on the learning from this study, an agreement is needed as to what quality teaching and learning looks like for every Australian child.

William (2018) wrote, "the schools our children attend need to be better; the things we are doing right now to improve our schools won't have much impact; and what we should be doing is both clear and possible" (p.1). It is agreed, our schools do need to do better. That is not to lay any criticism at the feet of those educators, leaders and elected officials working tirelessly for schools across the country. Rather, this is a timely reminder that the pursuit of quality is not easy and demands ongoing endeavour, reflection, iteration and improvement.

One of the discussions with an interview participant led to a rumination that has resonated more than any other. What if our education system had just one goal, that every child left primary school able to read? Imagine for a moment all of the key components to an

education system that would need to work together to achieve one shared goal – that **every** child in Australia finished primary school able to read. That singular goal speaks to the heart of what matters most.

Reading enjoyment has been reported as having a greater impact on a child's educational success than any other factor. Even more than their family's socio-economic status (OECD, 2002). A level of fluency in reading by the end of primary school would unlock learning pathways through senior school and beyond for every child that is not currently available to far too many Australian children. In the United Kingdom, Ofsted (2010) produced a report called, "Reading by Six", in which they outlined the conditions for success under which every child would learn to read at level 1A/2C by the age of six. First and foremost, it relied upon the leadership in the school and an overwhelming determination that every child will learn to read. It then went on to explore the conditions for success including: high expectations of students, a rigorous and sequential approach to teaching, consistency of approach, making every minute in the classroom count, providing high quality, expert instruction through carefully planned and well-structured learning experiences, opportunities for student agency, rich opportunities for engaging in diverse contexts, caring relationships with interested adults, the use of praise and reinforcement to motivate and ensure active participation from all learners, highly trained professional educators, regular feedback loops and assessment of individual progress towards well defined standards, support for the diverse learning needs of every child in the class and additional support as needed for both teachers and learners. All the hallmarks of a quality school according to this research. These conditions for success align well with the findings of this study and are more than applicable across the whole education system by way of defining what success looks like.

8.5 Chapter Summary

Chapter 8 began by discussing the research questions being explored, the findings from each phase of the study and the key themes that emerged. Throughout the chapter the key findings were shared in relation to the research and findings generated throughout the study. Next, the chapter presented a theory regarding the misalignment between the national goals for schooling and the measures that are used to attest to their achievement due to the absence of clearly articulated, plain language action plans and the role of media and political narratives in fuelling misconceptions amongst non-technical stakeholders. To conclude, Chapter 8 recommended that the Australian education system ought to re-visit the national goals for schooling and the measures currently used to assess them to reduce them to a more simplified, plain language set of actions that every stakeholder can invest wholeheartedly in. With the right conditions for success and a clearly articulated goal such as, every Australian child leaves school able to read at an agreed standard by the end of primary school, the system can turn the full force of its energy and efforts to the achievement of that goal. What appears at first glance to be an oversimplification of a very complex problem is in fact an opportunity to focus the attention of the education system where it matters. Reading is the key that unlocks life-long learning and proficiency in the primary years is the greatest indicator of future educational success. Reading underpins every other aspect of the national curriculum. It also affords every learner the opportunity to walk through the gateway of their mind into the world of books and the ability to engage their mind, body and soul in a quest for knowledge. What's more to ensure every child across Australia is able to achieve such a goal means applying a lens of accessibility, inclusion, equity and pedagogical quality to every policy, funding and operational decision we make. The operationalisation of such a goal across the education system would be akin to turning the Titanic, but it can be done with the will and determination of the educators and key stakeholders.

Chapter 9: Conclusion

The Australian K-12 education system appears misaligned when it comes to the enactment and measurement of its progress towards achieving the goals for schooling as agreed nationally in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) as discovered and documented in this thesis. A lot of the issues that arise when trying to support growth are because we don't often get a wealth of observations to assess the system, we get cross-sectional, time separated instruments which achieve some purposes and have clear intent. However, some other goals have no aligned measures and data from existing measures offers weak, tangential information which is often misunderstood and overgeneralized. It also seems that assessment literacy of the news reporting public and many politicians is such that they too can't determine if an assessment of data collection tool (or even the data itself) is fit for purpose..

At the outset, this thesis hypothesised that there was a misalignment between the goals for schooling as agreed in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) and the measures outlined in the NAP which are used to attest to their achievement nationally. This hypothesis arose in response to the 2018 PISA results and subsequent headlines regarding the "failing system" which did not resonate with the researcher's own experience as an educator in Australian schools. Jerrim (2023) has since shown that globally the interest in PISA "seems to have reached its peak" so it will be interesting how this helps shape the next steps in ILSA development for the OECD and IEA (p.24).

This final chapter links the findings from the study back to the research questions before reflecting on its contributions, limitations and the potential for further research. The following research questions shaped the study.

RQ1. To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

RQ2. How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?

RQ3. Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

To answer these questions, three phases of research were completed: 1) policy analysis of the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) (see Chapter 5), 2) an exploration of the validity of the measures in the NAP (see Chapter 6) and, 3) semi-structured interviews with leaders in the field of educational measurement and assessment in Australia (see Chapter 7). Throughout this study, every data point was generated in the pursuit of a substantive theory. Using CGT methodology, the research evolved through a series of codes and iterations which showcased the complexity of the Australian assessment landscape. By examining data at the intersection of policy, theory and practice in this way through the lens of validity (focusing on the evidence for construct and consequential aspects of validity), it was evident that there is a misalignment between the goals set for K-12 schooling and the tools used to measure their achievement.

9.1 To what extent do the goals of the Australian education system align with the policy drivers that underpin them?

Phase 1 of this study relied upon a preliminary understanding of the policy documents which outline the agreed goals and indicators for success in the Australian K-12 education system. As detailed in Chapter 5, the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) was pivotal to this, and analysis was completed using Bacchi's (2012) "What's the Problem Represented to be?" approach. This method was selected as it aligned well with the overarching CGT research methodology and enabled the researcher to engage deeply with the drivers underpinning the policy documents.

Reference was made to the goals for schooling agreed in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) throughout the thesis as it supported the investigation into the interplay between national policy, measurement theory and practice in schools. As discussed in Chapter 5, Foucault (1972; 1977) explained that the way in which discourses are formed constructs the objects of which they speak. Therefore, grounding the study with this frame of reference was important. It provided the means for understanding how the purpose of Australia's education system is shaped by the power relations at play (Ball, 2012).

As a result it was evident that the policy documents are informed by a series of social, political and economic assumptions or drivers which underpin the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) (see Table 7, Chapter 5). By exploring the assumptions and drivers underpinning the policy and what the problem is represented to be (Bacchi, 2012), the misalignment between the policy and its commitments to action, the measurement of the progress on those commitments and the daily experience in Australian K-12 schools is evident.

9.2 How is the achievement of those goals currently measured?

This question sought to develop a deeper understanding of the instruments included in the NAP which are used to report on the national success of the Australian K-12 education system. In doing so, it highlighted the importance of using the instruments for their intended purpose to safeguard their validity. From this perspective, the research aimed to offer contributions to the broader discussions pertaining to the success (or failure) of the system. It was evident that the system is effective in measuring some but not all the education ministers' agreed commitments to action outlined in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019). This is due to the system being constrained to standardised measures that can be delivered nationally in a manner that are both economically viable and deliverable at scale. Constraints that have invariably contributed to the validity issue addressed in Chapter 6, where the chosen test instruments only measured a very

limited selection of the commitments to action made by the education ministers in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019).

When it came to the measures of growth employed in the K-12 school system of Australia, recurring concerns with validity arising from the way the results of the tests are interpreted and used were expressed in Chapter 6 and 7. A discrepancy between the intended use of the measurement tools versus their actual use to report against the goals articulated in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) was frequently observed. For example, tools designed for one purpose (Reading Literacy, Science Literacy, Mathematical Literacy) are being used to determine societies' views on teacher salary increases in media articles (Wilkie, 2019).

Through the application of measurement theory with a focus on Messick's concept of validity, this study contributes to the moderation of the PISA effect (Hopfenbeck et al., 2018) by suggesting that the tools used to measure system-wide performance be interpreted in an informed and considered manner. It is imperative that the instruments used to attest to the achievement of the national goals for schooling as outlined in the Declaration (Education Council, 2019) are used only for their intended purpose to retain their validity.

This study found that the participants struggled to trust in the validity of the measurement instruments included in the NAP provided results that were often not well understood and prone to misuse. It is for this reason that increased efforts ought to be made to support teachers with the development of data literacy skills. This will support them to confidently speak about which aspects of NAP are in alignment with implemented efforts to improve teaching and learning and expose those that are not.

9.3 Is there an alternative way to measure the success of Australia's education system that increases the validity of the judgements that are made about performance by better aligning the measures with the goals?

To answer the third research question, data was collected from a group of purposively sampled stakeholders using CGT methodology. The semi-structured interviews outlined in Chapter 7, detail the insights gained from conversing with educational leaders working in the field. Undertaking research as an 'insider' in the field can raise complications but has many benefits too (Buys et al., 2022). In efforts to maintain a fair, unbiased representation of the problem being explored, researchers often opt to distance themselves and view such issues as an outsider looking in. However, this gap in the research was identified through the experience gained from working in the field. Whilst this can make it difficult to be objective when evaluating the evidence that has been generated throughout the study, the employment of a CGT methodology allows the researcher to make a meaningful contribution to the data generated rather than remaining distant from it (Charmaz, 2003; Breckenridge, 2009). Previous employment in delivering national and global computer-based assessments has certainly afforded the researcher the opportunity for a richer understanding of the field and granted access to key thought leaders operating nationally through professional networking. Each participant in this study was a professional working in or on the Australian education system with expert knowledge of educational measurement and assessment. Their engagement with the research questions and throughout the interviews has been consistent with their professional status and knowledge of best practice in ethical research. So too, the role of the researcher as an 'insider' is key to driving the purpose and meaning of this study.

Ultimately this question was seeking to find out the participants' vision for a better way forward. Their struggle to do so was most telling. In each interview, the participants were offered the opportunity to start afresh with a blank piece of paper, limitless budget and blue sky thinking to design the best possible means for measuring the success of the Australian K-12 education

system. Each of them struggled to move beyond the complexity of the current structure of the system to imagine a better way. The participants were able to generate many ideas and suggestions as to what was wrong with the current approach but were challenged to imagine a way forward that overcame the multi-layered, complex and federated context. One participant put forward a simple vision that on reflection was masterful. They proposed two things: 1) Funding follows the child not the school, and 2) One goal for all – that every Australian child leaves primary school able to read fluently. Yet struggled to agree upon how such goals would best be measured.

9.4 Contributions

This thesis can potentially contribute to the field by supporting an increased understanding of the interplay between policy, measurement and practice in the Australian context. In doing so, it may also contribute to the international knowledge gap. Drawing attention to the impact of power, particularly soft power, on policy and practice in schools this study contributes to a growing global research agenda which seeks to empower educators with an overt recognition of the drivers underpinning the education policies and why. This supports educators operating within a contested policy space that at present, limits their opportunity to be actively involved in key decision-making processes. Much more than a case study of the Australian experience, this study makes a contribution to the broader academic community.

Leaders have recounted that everything we need to know about successfully educating students is already known and that there is simply a lack of political will to do what is necessary (Aarons, 2009; Edmonds, 1979). It is hoped that one of the contributions from this research is the call to education system leaders to garnish the political will needed to make the changes required to better align the national assessment program to meet their national goals for schooling. In doing so, such educational policies can be better articulated to support quality teaching and learning for all.

This thesis has also contributed to the vexing debate as to the alignment between the goals for schooling and the measures used to report on their achievement from the perspective of valid measurement. Existing research points to the critiques of PISA (Baird et al., 2016; Baroutsis & Lingard, 2017; Bieber & Martens, 2011; Figazzolo, 2009; Hopfenbeck et al., 2018; Hopmann et al., 2007; Labaree, 2014; Lewis, 2017; Meyer & Benavot, 2013; Morrison, 2013; Rutkowski & Rutkowski 2016; Sahlberg, 2011; Sjøberg, 2015b; Stewart, 2013; Zhao, 2020). However, limited detail is offered as to how such assessments impact the policies and practices in Australian schools through the lens of validity. This study contributes to the field by addressing this gap and providing the insights of educational leaders and a review of the policy documents to examine the interplay of policy, measurement and practice using Messick's (1989) concept of validity.

9.5 Limitations and Implications for Further Research

Given the international comparability afforded by the PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS results, the focus of this study solely on the Australian education system may be perceived as a limitation. The potential to provide comparative data for another comprehensive education system such as the United Kingdom may well have proven valuable. Whilst this study certainly has applicability for other education systems facing the same challenges as Australia, the opportunity to engage in an international comparative study was beyond the current scope of this study. It is envisaged that this would be well placed for post-doctoral research. The generalisability of this study may be confined to the Australian context but there is an acknowledgement of the need to understand the validity of inferences resulting from PISA as being similar to all countries using PISA and other international large-scale assessments.

In studying the K-12 school system it is impossible to ignore the 250 million school-age children globally who are out of school (UNESCO, 2023a). A limitation exists when evaluating the effectiveness of the Australian K-12 school system given that so many children who should

be supported by it are absent for a myriad of reasons. All the current measures used to assess the system's success are limited to those students who are in school and participating in the assessments. The only exception is the attendance data that is collected which marks these children as absent. An education system is responsible for the education of ALL school age children, not just the ones that turn up. There is a need to address the challenge of measuring the performance of not only of those in school, but also those not in school but who should be.

Potential future research suggested by the findings of this study might also relate to making the assessments used to measure system-wide success more motivating and educative for the students completing them. So too, next steps ought to assess the whole learner and the school they are educated in to map the progress of the child and the school in a symbiotic way that illuminates their shared success.

Whilst this research is situated in the Australian context, there are clear messages and implications for those in other countries where similar educational policy agendas are core to their politics. Any country seeking to critically reflect upon how its educational policies are impacting the purpose of its education system will benefit from engaging with this research and asking similar questions. Future research applying these findings, themes and theories to other contexts would be beneficial to verify and validate its transferability to other contexts.

The small sample size and the researcher being involved in the research may be perceived as a potential limitation. The small sample size was explained in Section 4.3 when the issue of purposive sampling and the need for participants with specialist knowledge was addressed in detail. Similarly, in Section 4.5 the positioning of the researcher as an insider was examined as a key element of CGT.

9.6 Where to next?

In no way does this research negate the value or place for large-scale assessments, standardised testing, and other measures of student achievement. Rather, it calls for them each to

be viewed as one indicator of a school system's success rather than the ultimate definer. Levin (2012) argues that test scores are far less powerful than widely believed when it comes to predicting performance and economic productivity. Bending to the rhetoric of a "failing system," the Australian educators have been overwhelmed with demands to do more in the pursuit of success (Fahey, 2023; Mizen, 2023). It is hoped that thanks to this study educators feel better equipped to engage with the NAP and its related measurement instruments in an informed manner.

Traditionally, the reliance on test scores may have made more sense when there was an apparent correlation between educational attainment and higher income (Levin, 2012). Yet, in an era where high income yielding jobs (social media influencers, gamers and YouTube stars for example) are not necessarily dependent upon higher degrees of learning, the success of a school system is now much less aligned to the academic achievements of its students and the well-worn path to university and subsequent traditional careers. Add to this the increasing speculation of what AI may mean for education and the future of work and the next decade will be evolutionary. Reliance on valid data matched to the learners' context will be more important than ever.

It is beyond the scope of this thesis to judge how much responsibility PISA holds for any misuses of its results that have informed policy in the past. In fact, the external evaluation of PISA's intended and unintended policy impact (OECD, 2008) included two final recommendations in this regard: (a) "At a minimum, PISA should produce guidelines of dissemination for those who participate in the program"; and (b) "PISA should consider, at a minimum, the creation of a policy group for countries that request its advice on policy formation and better use of the PISA results" (p. 9). A good example constitutes the guidelines for uses of PISA-based tests for schools (OECD, 2013b). In any case, national players such as testing agencies, ministries and academics also play a key role in exerting influence so that PISA results are adequately interpreted and used in their respective countries.

The challenge of researching a complex, highly contested, and competitive education system in the context of a federated landscape is no easy feat (Alfrey et al., 2023). In fact, the challenge of Australia's federated system pervades this study. A key finding from this research was the issue of the multiple layers of government involved in the K-12 school system. Improving education nationally is a challenge because there isn't just one education system to reform. William (2018) explains that America "doesn't have an education system, it has 13,491 of them" (p.6). The same is true in Australia with its states, territories, school sectors, and high levels of privatisation. A simplified and unified education system with clearly articulated values and a shared, national understanding of success would be well placed to support Australian society in the future.

In terms of assessment, affording greater accountability to empowered and data-literate professional educators to meet the needs of their local context in the pursuit of those agreed aims would be valuable. So too, students and parents would benefit from a weighted measure that brings together a holistic, jargon-free report of a child's progress through formal schooling along with funding that follows the child not the school. When the results of the NAP and the subsequent reporting on them have such a significant impact on the development of education policies and the ways in which the K-12 school system is held to account, it is imperative that they are presented in such a way that is accessible, understandable and user friendly for non-technical audiences and all stakeholders.

9.7 Conclusion

Faced with claims of "system failure" and "performance in decline" that did not resonate with the teacher's lived experience of schooling in Australia, this study has evolved into a body of work that seeks to contribute to the field by investigating the policies, measurements and stakeholder perspectives that inform Australia's system-wide success. The significance of this study lies at the intersection of educational measurement, policy, pedagogical practice, and

power. Based on the learning from this and looking to the future, it is time to act boldly. As Ng (2007) asserted, “the education system reflects societal values and expectations, it can ... focus narrowly on grades and examinations. Or ... act with boldness and resolve to embark on a major transformation of mindsets and influence societal values and expectations” (p.124).

The time to transform and transcend current systems policies and practices is now. Governments around the world are embracing the opportunities afforded to their teachers, students, and schools through new digital technologies and AI. It is hoped that this research will evolve further and contribute to a much-needed national conversation about what the NAP will look like at a time when being intelligent means something very different.

It is hoped that a more holistic approach will reflect the rich tapestry of assessment designed to encapsulate the image of the whole child in the context of their lived experience (Ratner, 2021). By envisaging an approach that brings together the heart and mind of the student and provides significant agency as the learner completes the assessment, students will be expressing a strong voice in the assessment process and for teachers to have the professional recognition they deserve including a directional seat at the policy makers’ table.

Inspired by the work taking place in Singapore and embracing the idea of assuming that “every school is a good school,” a launch pad is provided into examining how it is possible to assess, monitor, and map the many successes of the Australian education system (Ang, 2018, para.12). Heng Swee Keat said, “Every school is a good school does not mean every school is the same school. But it does mean every school is good in its own way, seeking to bring out the best in every child” (Ang, 2018, para.12). Inspired by this, and the participants who echoed the call for greater localisation of policy and autonomy at the school level to best meet the needs of their learners, this research concludes by returning to the purpose of schooling in Australia.

For the child who could not read last week and now they can. For the child who was so crippled by anxiety they couldn't get out of bed but who is now attending schools two hours per day. For the child who won the Science prize despite sleeping in his Mum's car all week after the family was evicted. For the child who lives 100km from the nearest school and dials into class every day, even when the internet drops out. For the child who seems to have the perfect life, and for the ones that don't. For the happy child, the sad child, the curious child, and the disengaged child. For the child who just wrote their first book at the age of 9 and for the child who just arrived having fled their war-ravaged home and speaks no English. For the child who won the trophy at sports day and for the child who came last but was cheered on by all her friends and teachers who ran beside her when she crossed the finish line... for all these children, which is why we do what we do. That is why every Australian school deserves to be a good school. UNESCO (2019) affirms that quality education for all is paramount. There is often much debate about access to education but very little is said of its quality. Attending school is important but it's not enough. It also must be a school worth attending.

References

- Aarons, D. (2009). Philadelphia leader seeks faster change by closing schools: Strategic plan calls for more outside management. *Education Week*, 28(23), 9.
<https://www.edweek.org/leadership/philadelphia-leader-seeks-faster-change-by-closing-schools/2009/03>
- Adams, R. J. (2003). Response to ‘cautions on OECD’s recent educational survey (PISA)’. *Oxford Review of Education*, 29(3), 377- 389.
- Addey, C., & Sellar, S. (2018). Why do countries participate in PISA? Understanding the role of international large-scale assessments in global education policy. *Global Education Policy and International Development: New Agendas, Issues and Policies*, 97, 117.
- Ajayi, V. O. (2018). Scientific literacy. *Benue State University*, 1-11.
- Alfrey, L., Lambert, K., Aldous, D., & Marttinen, R. (2023). The problematization of the (im)possible subject: an analysis of Health and Physical Education policy from Australia, USA and Wales. *Sport, Education and Society*, 28(4), 353-368.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2021.2016682>
- Allen, C. (2023, Oct 06). Teaching in Australia has become a refuge for the least able. *The Australian (Online)* <https://www.proquest.com/newspapers/teaching-australia-has-become-refuge-least-able/docview/2873601853/se-2>
- American Association of Educational Research (AERA), American Psychological Association (APA) & National Council on Measurement in Education (NCME). (2014). *Standards*

for educational and psychological testing. Washington DC: American Educational Research Association.

American Psychological Association. (2023). *APA Dictionary of Psychology*.

<https://dictionary.apa.org/>

Amirbek, A., Ydyrys, K. (2014). Education as a Soft Power Instrument of Foreign Policy.

Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 143, 501-503.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.07.423>

Anagnostopoulou, K., Hatzinikitaa, V., Christidou, V. & Dimopoulou, K. (2013). PISA test items and school-based examinations in Greece: Exploring the relationship between global and local assessment discourses. *International Journal of Science Education*, 35(4), 636-662. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2011.604801>

Anders, B.A. (2023). Is using ChatGPT cheating, plagiarism, both, neither, or forward thinking? *Patterns*, 4(3).

Anderson, C. (2010). Presenting and evaluating qualitative research. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 74(8), 141. <https://doi.org/10.5688/aj7408141>

Andrade, H.L. & Brookhart, S.M. (2019). Classroom assessment as the co-regulation of learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2019.1571992>

Andrich, D. (2004). Controversy and the Rasch model: A characteristic of incompatible paradigms? *Medical Care*, 42(1), 7–16.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.mlr.0000103528.48582.7c>

Andrich, D., & Marais, I. (2019). A course in Rasch measurement theory. *Measuring in the educational, social and health sciences*, 41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-7496-8>

- Ang, M. (2018, 2 December). Heng Swee Keat popularised ‘every school, a good school’ phrase when he was education minister. *Mothership*. <https://mothership.sg/2018/12/heng-swee-keat-education-minister/>
- Angner, E. (2011). Are subjective measures of well-being ‘direct’?. *Australasian Journal of Philosophy*, 89(1): 115-30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00048400903401665>
- Apple, M. (2004). Creating Difference: neo-liberalism, neo-conservatism and the politics of education reform. *Educational Policy*, 18(12), 12-43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904803260022>
- Appleton, J.V. & King, L. (2002). Journeying from the philosophical contemplation of constructivism to the methodological pragmatics of health services research. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 40, 641-648. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.2002.02424.x>
- Araujo, L., Saltelli, A., & Schnepf, S. V. (2017). Do PISA data justify PISA-based education policy?. *International Journal of Comparative Education and Development*, 19(1), 20-34. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCED-12-2016-0023>
- Association for Childhood Education International. (2006). *Global guidelines for the education and care of young children in the 21st century*. v1AO
- Australian Bureau of Statistics. (2023). Schools. <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/people/education/schools/latest-release>
- Australian Council for Educational Research (2012). *National School Improvement Tool*. Commonwealth Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (DEEWR), Australia. https://research.acer.edu.au/tll_misc/18

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2010). *My school*.

<http://www.myschool.edu.au>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2011a). *Why NAP*.

<http://www.nap.edu.au/about/why-nap.html>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2011b). *General capabilities consultation report*. [http://docs.acara.edu.au/resources/General_Capabilities_-_](http://docs.acara.edu.au/resources/General_Capabilities_-_Consultation_Report_-_December_2011.pdf)

[Consultation_Report_-_December_2011.pdf](http://docs.acara.edu.au/resources/General_Capabilities_-_Consultation_Report_-_December_2011.pdf)

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority (2012a). *Curriculum Development Process: Version 6*.

https://docs.acara.edu.au/resources/ACARA_Curriculum_Development_Process_Version_6.0_-_04_April_2012_-_FINAL_COPY.pdf

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2013). *Measurement framework for schooling in Australia 2012*. [https://acara.edu.au/reporting/measurement-framework-](https://acara.edu.au/reporting/measurement-framework-for-schooling-in-australia)

[for-schooling-in-australia](https://acara.edu.au/reporting/measurement-framework-for-schooling-in-australia)

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2015). *Measurement framework for schooling in Australia 2015*. [https://acara.edu.au/reporting/measurement-framework-](https://acara.edu.au/reporting/measurement-framework-for-schooling-in-australia)

[for-schooling-in-australia](https://acara.edu.au/reporting/measurement-framework-for-schooling-in-australia)

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2018a). *Australian National Report on Schooling*. Commonwealth Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations (DEEWR), Australia.

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2018b). NAP Sample Assessment ICT Literacy Years 6 and 10: November 2018. [https://nap.edu.au/docs/default-](https://nap.edu.au/docs/default-source/default-document-library/2017napictlreport_final.pdf)

[source/default-document-library/2017napictlreport_final.pdf](https://nap.edu.au/docs/default-source/default-document-library/2017napictlreport_final.pdf)

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2019a). *National Report on Schooling in Australia: 2017*. Australia.

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority (ACARA). (2019b). *NAP Sample Assessment Science Literacy 2018 Public Report*. <https://nap.edu.au/docs/default-source/resources/nap-sl-report-2018.pdf>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2020a). *Measurement Framework for Schooling in Australia: 2020*. ACARA. <https://www.acara.edu.au/reporting/measurement-framework-for-schooling-in-australia>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2020b). *NAP Civics and Citizenship 2019 National Report*. <https://nap.edu.au/docs/default-source/default-document-library/20210121-nap-cc-2019-public-report.pdf>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2021). *National Report on Schooling in Australia: 2019*. ACARA.

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2022). *NAPLAN National report for 2022*. <https://nap.edu.au/docs/default-source/default-document-library/2022-naplan-national-report.pdf>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023a). *Measurement framework for schooling in Australia 2020*. ACARA. Updated September 2023. <https://acara.edu.au/reporting/measurement-framework-for-schooling-in-australia>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023b). *NAPLAN students results and reports: 2008-2022*. <https://www.nap.edu.au/naplan/results-and-reports/naplan-results-2008-2022>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023c). NAPLAN results and reports. <https://www.nap.edu.au/naplan/results-and-reports>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023d). Media release: NAPLAN begins on 15 March 2023. <https://www.acara.edu.au/docs/default-source/media-releases/20230314-naplan-2023-media-release.pdf>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023e). Media release: One in 10 students 'need additional support' to meet higher NAPLAN expectations. [Media release: One in 10 students 'need additional support' to meet higher NAPLAN expectations \(acara.edu.au\)](https://www.acara.edu.au/docs/default-source/media-releases/20230314-naplan-2023-media-release.pdf)

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023f). *My School*. <https://myschool.edu.au/>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023g). *National report on schooling 2021*. https://acaraweb.blob.core.windows.net/acaraweb/docs/default-source/assessment-and-reporting-publications/national-report-on-schooling-in-australia-2021.pdf?sfvrsn=f9184c07_0

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023h). *NAPLAN 2022: Technical report*. <https://www.nap.edu.au/docs/default-source/default-document-library/naplan-2022-technical-report.pdf>

Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority. (2023i). *Latest Data Reveals Digital Skills Amongst Young Australians*. <https://www.acara.edu.au/docs/default-source/media-releases/media-release-latest-data-reveals-digital-skills-amongst-young-australians.pdf>

Australian Education Act. (2013). Commonwealth, Section 3.

Australian Government Department of Education Employment and Workplace Relations.

(2010). *Transparency, reporting and assessment*.

http://www.deewr.gov.au/Schooling/Programs/SmarterSchools/Pages/Trans_report_asses.aspx

Australian Government Productivity Commission. (2022). *Review of the National School Reform*

Agreement: Study Report. <https://www.pc.gov.au/inquiries/completed/school-agreement/report/school-agreement.pdf>

Australian Human Rights Commission. (2019). *Let's talk about equality and equity*.

<https://humanrights.gov.au/lets-talk-about-equality-and-equity>

Ausubel, D. P. (1968). *Educational psychology: A cognitive view*. Holt, Rinehart & Winston.

Bacchi, C.L. (2009). *Analysing Policy: What's the Problem Represented to Be?* Pearson.

Bacchi, C. (2012). Introducing the “What’s the Problem Represented to be?” approach. In A.

Bletsas & C. Beasley (Eds.), *Engaging with Carol Bacchi: Strategic interventions and exchanges*. The University of Adelaide Press.

Bacchi, C., & Goodwin, S. (2016). *Post structural policy analysis: A guide to practice*. Springer.

Baird, J.-A., Isaacs, T., Johnson, S., Stobart, G., Yu, G., Sprague, T., & Daugherty, R.

(2011). *Policy Effects of PISA*. Oxford: Oxford University Centre for Educational

Assessment. <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:26c9fccd-ae47-424e-ba40-0c84ebedfc3e/files/m3781c5020f1ce13427a6bed35d8b7c6d>

Baird, J.-A., Johnson, S., Hopfenbeck, T. N., Isaacs, T., Sprague, T., Stobart, G., et al. (2016). On the supranational spell of PISA in policy. *Educational Research*, 58(2), 121–138.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2016.1165410>

- Baird, J., Andrich, D., Hopfenbeck, T.N., & Stobart, G. (2017). Assessment and learning: fields apart?, *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 24(3), 317-350.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2017.1319337>
- Baker, J. (2019, 15 December). 'The kids are OK': HSC band 6 data reveals the problem with PISA testing. *The Sydney Morning Herald*. <https://www.smh.com.au/national/nsw/the-kids-are-ok-hsc-band-6-data-reveals-the-problem-with-pisa-testing-20191214-p53j2b.html>
- Bagnasco, A., Ghirotto, L., & Sasso, L. (2014). Theoretical sampling. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 70(11), e6-7.
- Ball, S. (1998). Big Policies/Small World: an introduction to international perspectives in education policy. *Comparative Education*, 34(2), 119-130.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03050069828225>
- Ball, S. J. (2003). The teachers soul and the terrors of performativity. *Journal of Education Policy*, 18(2), 215–228. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0268093022000043065>
- Ball, S. J. (2012). *Foucault, power, and education*. Routledge.
- Ball, S. J., Goodson, I. F., & Maguire, M. (Eds.). (2007). *Education, globalisation and new times: 21 years of the Journal of Education Policy*. Routledge.
- Ball, S., Rae, I. & Tognolini, J. (2000). Options for the assessment and reporting of primary students in the key learning area of science to be used for the reporting of nationally comparable outcomes of schooling within the context of the National Goals for Schooling in the Twenty-First Century. National Education Performance Monitoring Taskforce. <https://ro.uow.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2505&context=sspapers>

- Baroutsis, A. & Lingard, B. (2017). Counting and comparing school performance: an analysis of media coverage of PISA in Australia, 2000–2014. *Journal of Education Policy*, 32(4), 432-449. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2016.1252856>
- Baumert, J., & Demmrich, A. (2001). Test Motivation in the Assessment of Student Skills: The Effects of Incentives on motivation and performance. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 16(3): 441–462.
- Becker, G. (1964). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education*. University of Chicago Press.
- Becker, G. S. (1994). Human capital revisited. In *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis with special reference to education*, third edition (pp. 15-28). The University of Chicago Press.
- Beghetto, R. A., Kaufman, J. C., & Baer, J. (2017). *Teaching for creativity in the Australian curriculum classroom*. Hawker Brownlow Education.
- Benjamin, G. R. (1998). *Japanese lessons: A year in a Japanese school through the eyes of an American anthropologist and her children*. NYU Press.
- Berman, A. I., Haertel, E. H., & Pellegrino, J. W. (2020). *Comparability of Large-Scale Educational Assessments: Issues and Recommendations*. National Academy of Education.
- Bieber, T., & Martens, K. (2011). The OECD PISA study as a soft power in education? Lessons from Switzerland and the US. *European Journal of Education*, 46(1), 101–116. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1465-3435.2010.01462.x>

Biesta, G. (2009). Good education in an age of measurement: On the need to reconnect with the question of purpose in education. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability (formerly: Journal of Personnel Evaluation in Education)*, 21, 33-46.

Biesta, G. (2015). Resisting the seduction of the global education measurement industry: Notes on the social psychology of PISA. *Ethics and education*, 10(3), 348-360.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17449642.2015.1106030>

Biesta, G. (2017). Lead Learner or Head Teacher? Exploring Connections Between Curriculum, Leadership and Evaluation in an 'Age of Measurement'. In: Uljens, M., Ylimaki, R. (eds) *Bridging Educational Leadership, Curriculum Theory and Didaktik*. Educational Governance Research, vol 5. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-58650-2_3

Biesta, G., Heugh, K., Cervinkova, H., Rasiński, L., Osborne, S., Forde, D., ... & Tesar, M. (2022). Philosophy of education in a new key: publicness, social justice, and education; a South-North conversation. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 54(8), 1216-1233.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2021.1929172>

Birks, M. & Mills, J. (2015). *Grounded theory: a practical guide*. 2nd ed. SAGE.

Birks, M., Mills, J. & Francis, K. (2009). A thousand words paint a picture: the use of storyline in grounded theory research. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 14, 405–417.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987109104675>

Binet, A., & Simon, T. (1907). Le développement de l'intelligence chez les enfants. *L'Année psychologique*, 14(1), 1-94.

Binet, A., & Simon, T. (1916). The development of intelligence in children (the Binet-Simon Scale). Henry H. Goddard, trans. Williams and Wilkins Co.

Black, P., Wiliam, D. (1998). *Inside the black box: raising standards through classroom assessment*. King's College London School of Education.

Blackmore, J., & Lauder, H. (2005). Researching policy. *Research methods in the social sciences*, 97-104.

Bloomberg. (2023, May 23). *What gets measured gets managed*.

<https://www.accesswire.com/756641/What-Gets-Measured-Gets-Managed--Record-Report-and-Act-to-Decarbonize-Using-SAP-Sustainability-Footprint-Management>

Bokova, I. (2015). *Rethinking Education: Towards a Global Common Good?*

<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000232555>

Borsboom, D. (2003). Conceptual issues in psychological measurement. [Thesis, fully internal, Universiteit van Amsterdam].

Borsboom, D., Mellenbergh, G., & Van Heerden, J. (2004). The Concept of Validity.

Psychological Review, *111*, 1061–1071. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0033-295X.111.4.1061>

Bourdieu, P. (1977). The economics of linguistic exchanges. *Social science information*, *16*(6), 645-668. <https://doi.org/10.1177/053901847701600601>

Bouhali, C.E. (2015). The OECD Neoliberal Governance. In: Abdi, A.A., Shultz, L., Pillay, T. (eds) *Decolonizing Global Citizenship Education*. Rotterdam: SensePublishers.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6300-277-6_10

Breakspear, S. (2012). The policy impact of PISA: An exploration of the normative effects of international benchmarking in school system performance. OECD Education Working Papers, No. 71, OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5k9fdfqffr28-en>

Breakspear, S. (2014). *How does PISA shape education policy making? Why how we measure learning determines what counts in education*. Centre for Strategic Education Seminar Series Paper No. 240. Victoria, Australia: Centre for Strategic Education.

allchildrenlearning.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Breakspear-PISA-Paper.pdf

Breckenridge, J., Jones, D., Elliott, I., & Nicol, M. (2012). Choosing a methodological path: Reflections on the constructivist turn. *Grounded theory review*, 11(1), 64-71.

Breiter, A., Groß, L. M., & Stauke, E. (2013). Computer-based large-scale assessments in Germany. In *Next Generation of Information Technology in Educational Management: 10th IFIP WG 3.7 Conference, ITEM 2012, Bremen, Germany, August 5-8, 2012, Revised Selected Papers 10* (pp. 41-54). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

Brennan, R. L. (1996). Generalizability of performance assessments. In G. W. Phillips (Ed.), *Technical issues in large-scale performance assessment* (NCES 96-802) (pp. 19-58). Washington, DC: National Center for Education Statistics.

Brennan, R. L., & National Council on Measurement in Education. (2006). *Educational measurement*.

Brey, P. (2008). The Technological Construction of Social Power. *Social Epistemology*, 22(1), 71-95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02691720701773551>

Bronfenbrenner, U. (1986). Recent advances in research on the ecology of human development. *Development as action in context: Problem behavior and normal youth development*, 287-309.

Brown, G.T.L. (2014), "AsTTle – A national testing system for formative assessment: How the national testing policy ended up helping schools and teachers", *A Developmental and Negotiated Approach to School Self-Evaluation (Advances in Program Evaluation, Vol. 14)*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 39-56.

[https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7863\(2013\)0000014003](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7863(2013)0000014003)

Brown, P. R., & Warner, S. A. (2022). Is Indigeneity hidden in the shadow of Australian national school reforms? *Australian Journal of Social Issues*, 57, 314 – 328.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/ajs4.187>

Browne, R. (2012, 5 September). World Rankings a Lesson in Valuing Role of Teachers. *The Sydney Morning Herald*. <https://www.smh.com.au/education/world-rankings-a-lesson-in-valuing-role-of-teachers-20120904-25clz.html>

Bryant, A. & Charmaz, K. (2007). Grounded theory research: methods and practices. In: Bryant A, Charmaz K. (eds) *The Sage handbook of grounded theory*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE, pp. 1–28.

Bryman, A. (2008). The end of the paradigm wars. *The SAGE handbook of social research methods*, 13-25.

Buckingham, J. (2004, 8 December). Aussies Get High Marks in World Test. *The Australian*.

Buckingham, J., 2011. School funding, choice and equity, Centre for Independent Studies.

Australia. <https://policycommons.net/artifacts/10741431/school-funding-choice-and-equity/11623151/>

Buckingham, J. (2012). Keeping PISA in perspective: Why Australian education policy should not be driven by international test results. *Issue Analysis*, 136, 1-14.

Burns, M., Bally, J., Burles, M., Holtslander, L., & Peacock, S. (2022). Constructivist grounded theory or interpretive phenomenology? Methodological choices within specific study contexts. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 21.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069221077758>

Burgess, C., & Lowe, K. (2022). Rhetoric vs Reality: The Disconnect between Policy and Practice for Teachers Implementing Aboriginal Education in Their Schools. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 30(97).

Buys, T., Casteleijn, D., Heyns, T., Untiedt, H. (2022). A Reflexive Lens on Preparing and Conducting Semi-structured Interviews with Academic Colleagues. *Qualitative Health Research*, 32(13), 2030-2039.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/10497323221130832>

Butterfield, S., Williams, A., & Marr, A. (1999). Talking about assessment: Mentor-student dialogues about pupil assessment in initial teacher training. *Assessment in Education*, 6(2), 225. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09695949992883>

Bybee, R. (1997). *Achieving scientific literacy: From purposes to practices*. Heinemann.

Cabós, L. (1922). Un ensayo de medición intelectual infantil [A trial of intellectual infantil measurement]. *Revista de Pedagogía*, 1(3), 90–94.

Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., Bywaters, D. & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive sampling: complex or simple? Research case examples. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 25(8), 652-661.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>

- Care, E., Kim, H., Vista, A., & Anderson, K. (2019). *Education system alignment for 21st century skills: Focus on assessment*. Center for Universal Education at Brookings. <https://www.brookings.edu/research/education-system-alignment-for-21st-century-skills/>
- Carpiano, R., Link, B., & Phelan, J. (2008). Social inequality and health: Future directions for the fundamental cause explanation. In A. Lareau & D. Conley (Eds.), *Social class: How does it work?* (pp. 232-263). Russell Sage Foundation.
- Carney, S., Rappleye, J., & Silova, I. (2012). Between faith and science: World culture theory and comparative education. *Comparative Education Review*, 56(3), 366–393.
- Carnoy, M. & Rhoten, D. (2002) What Does Globalization Mean for Educational Change? A Comparative Approach. *Comparative Education Review*, 46(1), 1-9.
- Carnoy, M., Khavenson, T., Fonseca, I., Costa, L., & Marotta, L. (2015). Is Brazilian Education Improving? Evidence from PISA and SAEB. *Cadernos De Pesquisa*, 45(157): 450–485.
- Cassidy, G. (2023a, 26 November). Australian education in long term decline due to poor curriculum report says. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2023/nov/27/australian-education-in-long-term-decline-due-to-poor-curriculum-report-says>
- Cassidy, G. (2023b, 5 December). Australian students' Pisa scores still declining despite climb into OECD top 10. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2023/dec/05/australian-students-2022-pisa-scores-results-declining-oecd>
- Cavendish, C. (2023, 23 January). ChatGPT will force school exams out of dark age. *Financial Times*. https://www.realclearpolitics.com/2023/01/23/chatgpt_will_force_school_exams_out_of_dark_age_589606.html

- Chamberlain-Salaun, J., Mills, J., & Usher, K. (2013). Linking symbolic interactionism and grounded theory methods in a research design: From Corbin and Strauss' assumptions to action. *Sage Open*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244013505757>
- Charmaz, K. (1990). 'Discovering' chronic illness: using grounded theory. *Social science & medicine*, 30(11), 1161-1172. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536\(90\)90256-R](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(90)90256-R)
- Charmaz, K. (2003). Grounded theory: Objectivist and constructivist methods. In N.K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Strategies of qualitative inquiry* (2nd ed., pp. 249-291). London: Sage Publications Limited.
- Charmaz, K. (2006). *Constructing grounded theory: a practical guide through qualitative analysis*. SAGE.
- Charmaz, K. (2014). *Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis*, 2nd ed. Sage.
- Charmaz, K. (2017). Constructivist grounded theory. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 12(3), 299-300. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439760.2016.1262612>
- Charmaz, K. (2020). "With constructivist grounded theory you can't hide": Social justice research and critical inquiry in the public sphere. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 26(2), 165-176. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800419879081>
- Charmaz, K. & Bryant, A. (2011). Grounded theory and credibility. In: Silverman D. (ed.) *Qualitative research*. 3rd ed. London: SAGE, pp. 291–309.
- Charmaz, K., Thornberg, R., & Keane, E. (2018). Evolving grounded theory and social justice inquiry. In N. K. Denzin, & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds), *The Sage handbook of qualitative research* (5th ed., pp. 411–443). Sage.

Charmaz, K., & Thornberg, R. (2021). The pursuit of quality in grounded theory. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 18(3), 305-327.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2020.1780357>

Cheng, K. M. (2017). Advancing 21st century competencies in East Asian education systems. *Center for Global Education. Asia Society*, 2, 26.

<https://asiasociety.org/files/21st-century-competencies-east-asian-education-systems.pdf>

Chmielewski, A. K. (2019). The global increase in the socioeconomic achievement gap, 1964 to 2015. *American sociological review*, 84(3), 517-544.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0003122419847165>

Chomsky, N., & Polychroniou, C. J. (2021). *The precipice: neoliberalism, the pandemic and the urgent need for social change*. Haymarket Books.

Chun Tie, Y., Birks, M., & Francis, K. (2019). Grounded theory research: A design framework for novice researchers. *SAGE open medicine*, 7.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/2050312118822927>

Chung, J. (2010). Finland, PISA, and the Implications of International Achievement Studies on Education Policy. In Wisemann, A.W. (Ed.), *The Impact of International Achievement Studies on Education Policy*, (pp. 267–294). Bingley: Emerald Group.

Clare, J. (2023, 29 March). Expert panel to inform a better and fairer education system.

<https://ministers.education.gov.au/clare/expert-panel-inform-better-and-fairer-education-system>

Clark, P., Etzioni, O., Khot, T., Khashabi, D., Mishra, B., Richardson, K., Sabharwal, A., Schoenick, C., Schoenick, C., Tafjord, O., Tandon, N., Bhakthavatsalam, S., Groeneveld, D., Guerquin, M., & Schmitz, M. (2020). From 'F' to 'A' on the N.Y. Regents Science Exams: An Overview of the Aristo Project. *AI Magazine*, 41(4), 39-53.
<https://doi.org/10.1609/aimag.v41i4.5304>

Clark, S., & Harrington, M. (2023). Early Childhood and School Education: Budget Resources.
https://www.aph.gov.au/About_Parliament/Parliamentary_departments/Parliamentary_Library/Budget/reviews/2023-24/EarlyChildhoodSchoolEducation

Clarke A., Friese C., & Washburn, R. (2017). *Situational analysis: Grounded theory after the interpretive turn*. Sage.

Clarke, S. (2001). *Unlocking formative assessment*. Hodder & Stoughton.

Coburn, C. E., Hill, H. C., & Spillane, J. P. (2016). Alignment and accountability in policy design and implementation: The Common Core State Standards and implementation research. *Educational Researcher*, 45(4), 243-251.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X16651080>

Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2002). *Research methods in education*. Routledge.

Commonwealth of Australia. (2022, 14 March). Budget Measures Budget Paper No. 2 2022–23.
https://parlinfo.aph.gov.au/parlInfo/download/library/budget/2022_02/

Connolly, N. (2017). NAP sample assessment science literacy 2015: public report
<https://apo.org.au/node/74438>

Corbin, J. M., & Strauss, A. (1990). Grounded theory research: Procedures, canons, and evaluative criteria. *Qualitative sociology*, 13(1), 3-21.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00988593>

- Council of Australian Governments (2013). *National Education Reform Agreement*.
- Cowan, G. & Arsenault A. (2008). Moving from Monologue to Dialogue to Collaboration: The Three Layers of Public Diplomacy. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 2008, 616(10), 10-30. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716207311863>
- Craft, A. (2003). The limits to creativity in education: Dilemmas for the educator. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 51(2), 113-127. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8527.t01-1-00229>
- Cranston, N., Kimber, M., Mulford, B., Reid, A., & Keating, J. (2010). Politics and school education in Australia: a case of shifting purposes. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 48(2), 182-195. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578231011027842>
- Creswell, J. W. & Miller, D. L. (2000). Determining validity in qualitative inquiry. *Theory into practice*, 39(3), pp. 124–130. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip3903_2
- Creswell, J., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Cronbach, L. J. (1971). Test validation. *Educational measurement*.
- Cronbach, L. (1988). Five perspectives on the validity argument. In H. Wainer & H. Braun (eds.), *Test validity*, pp. 3-17. Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Cronbach, L. J., & Shapiro, K. (1982). *Designing evaluations of educational and social programs*. Jossey-Bass.
- Crotty, M. (1998). *The Foundations of Social Research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process*. Sage.
- Cuban, L. (2000). Why is it so hard to get good schools? In L. Cuban & D. Shipps (Eds.), *Reconstructing the common good in education: Coping with intractable American dilemmas* (pp. 148-169). Stanford University Press.

- Cureton, E. E. (1951). Validity. In E. F. Lindquist (Ed.), *Educational measurement* (pp. 621–694). American Council on Education.
- Dall, A. (2011). Is PISA counter-productive to building successful educational systems? *Social Alternatives*; v.30 n.4 p.10-14; 2011, 30(4), 10–14. <https://doi/10.3316/aeipt.190636>
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2014). What can PISA tell us about U.S. education policy? *New England Journal of Public Policy*, 26(1), 4.
- Davidson, M., & Tognolini, J. (2013). Assessment, standards-referencing and standard setting. In Magdalena Mo Ching Mok (Ed.). *Self-directed Learning Oriented Assessments in the Asia-Pacific*. Springer Science+Business Media, Dordrecht.
- Davis, E.R. (2019). *The PISA Phenomenon: Analysis of its Ascendency in Media, Policymaker and Academic Discourses in Education* (PhD Thesis). University of Sydney, Australia.
- Davis, E.R., Wilson, R. & Dalton, B. (2018). Another slice of PISA: an interrogation of educational cross-national attraction in Australia, Finland, Japan and South Korea. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057925.2018.1510305>
- Davis, E. R. & Wilson, R. (2019). ‘Not so globalised’: Contrasting media discourses on education and competitiveness in four countries. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 13(1), 155–176. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-08-2016-0108>
- Deacon, R. (2006). Michel Foucault on education: A preliminary theoretical overview. *South African Journal of Education*, 26, 177-187.
- De Bortoli, L. (2021). Snapshots issue 16: How much effort are students putting into PISA?. *Snapshots*, 16(16), 1. <https://research.acer.edu.au/snapshots/vol16/iss16/1>

De Bortoli, L., Underwood, C., & Thomson, S. (2023). PISA 2022. Reporting Australia's results.

Volume I: Student performance and equity in education. Australian Council for Educational Research. <https://doi.org/10.37517/978-1-74286-725-0>

Delors, J. (1996). Learning: the treasure within; report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education for the Twenty-first Century.

Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2008). Introduction: The discipline and practice of qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Strategies of qualitative inquiry* (3rd ed., pp. 1–43). Sage Publications, Inc.

Department of Education. (2023). *National School Reform Agreement Ministerial Reference Group*. <https://ministers.education.gov.au/clare/national-school-reform-agreement-ministerial-reference-group>

Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations. (2010). OECD Review on Evaluation and Assessment Frameworks for Improving School Outcomes: Country Background Report for Australia.

Department of Education, Skills and Employment. (2020). National Assessment Program - Programme for International Student Assessment.

Department of Education and Training. (2017). *Review to Achieve Educational Excellence in Australian Schools*. <https://www.dese.gov.au/quality-schools-package/resources/review-achieve-educational-excellence-australian-schools>

Department of Education and Training. (2018). *National School Reform Agreement*. <https://www.dese.gov.au/uncategorised/resources/national-school-reform-agreement>

Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. (2017). Diplomatic Academy: Australian Education System. [The Australian Education](#)

[Shttps://www.dfat.gov.au/sites/default/files/australian-education-system-foundation.pdf](https://www.dfat.gov.au/sites/default/files/australian-education-system-foundation.pdf)system - Foundation level (dfat.gov.au)

Dewey, J. (1916). Nationalizing education. *Journal of Education*, 84(16), 425-428.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/002205741608401602>

Dewey, J. (1933). Dewey outlines utopian schools. *New York Times*, 23, 23.

Dewey, J. (1934). *Art as Experience*. Capricorn Books.

Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and education*. Collier books.

Dey, I. (1999). *Grounding grounded theory. Guidelines for qualitative inquiry*. Academic Press.

Dinham, S. (2012). Our Asian schooling infatuation: The problem of PISA envy. *The Conversation*.

Durkheim, E. (1956). *Education and sociology*. Simon and Schuster.

Edmonds, R. (1979). Effective schools for the urban poor. *Educational Leadership*, 37, 15-24.

Education Council. (2019). *Alice Springs (Mparntwe) education declaration*.

<https://www.dese.gov.au/alice-springs-mparntwe-education-declaration>

Education Council. (2015). *National Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Education Strategy*.

Education Council.

Education Services Australia. (2018). Optimising STEM Industry-School Partnerships: Inspiring Australia's Next Generation Final Report.

https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/sites/default/files/2019-11/optimising_stem_industry-school_partnerships_-_final_report.pdf

- Eklöf, H. (2010). Skill and will: Test-taking motivation and assessment quality. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 17(4): 345–356.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2010.516569>
- Elliott, S. (2017), Computers and the Future of Skill Demand, Educational Research and Innovation, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264284395-en>.
- English, R. (2005). Marketing razzle-dazzle and the success of new non-government schools. *Perspectives on Educational Leadership*, 15(1), 1-2.
- Ercikan, K., Roth, W.-M., & Asil, M. (2015). Cautions about uses of international assessments. *Teachers College Record*, 117(1), 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146811511700107>
- Ertl, H. (2007). Educational standards and the changing discourse on education: The reception and consequences of the PISA study in Germany. In *Comparative Inquiry and Educational Policy Making* (pp. 75-90). Routledge.
- European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education. (2005). *Inclusive education and classroom practice in secondary education: Summary report*. European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education.
- Fahey, G. (2023, 22 January). Why Australian schools are failing. *Australian Financial Review*.
<https://www.afr.com/policy/health-and-education/why-australian-schools-are-failing-20230122-p5cejh>
- Fan, G., & Popkewitz, T. S. (2020). *Handbook of education policy studies*. Springer Nature.
- Fawcett, P. (2018). Doing democracy and governance in the fast lane? Towards a “politics of time” in an accelerated polity. *Australian Journal of Political Science*, 53(4), 548–564. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10361146.2018.1517862>

Feldman, S. P. (1997). The revolt against cultural authority: Power/knowledge as an assumption in organization theory. *Human Relations*, 50(8), 937-955.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/001872679705000804>

Fenech, M. (2011). An analysis of the conceptualisation of 'quality' in early childhood education and care empirical research: Promoting the 'blind-spots' as foci for future research.

Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood, 12(2), 102-117.

<https://doi.org/10.2304/ciec.2011.12.2.102>

Figazzolo, L. (2009). Impact of PISA 2006 on the education policy debate. [http://download.ei-](http://download.ei-ie.org/docs/IRISDocuments/ResearchWebsiteDocuments/2009-00036-01-E.pdf)

[ie.org/docs/IRISDocuments/ResearchWebsiteDocuments/2009-00036-01-E.pdf](http://download.ei-ie.org/docs/IRISDocuments/ResearchWebsiteDocuments/2009-00036-01-E.pdf)

Finn, B. (2015). Measuring motivation in low-stakes assessments. *ETS Research Report*

Series, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ets2.12067>

Firestone, W. A., Mayrowetz, D., & Fairman, J. (1998). Performance-based assessment and instructional change: The effects of testing in Maine and Maryland. *Educational evaluation and policy analysis*, 20(2), 95-113.

<https://doi.org/10.3102/01623737020002095>

Flessa, J., Gallaher-Mackay, K., & Parker, D. (2010). Good, steady progress. *Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*, 101, 38.

Fletcher, C., & Walsh, C. (1992). Reform of Intergovernmental Relations in Australia: The

Politics of Federalism and the Non-politics of Managerialism. *Public*

Administration, 70(4), 591-616. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9299.1992.tb00958.x>

Florian, L., & Rouse, M. (2009). The inclusive practice project in Scotland: Teacher education for inclusive education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 25(4), 594-601.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2009.02.003>

Florida, R. (2005). *The flight of the creative class*. Harper Business.

Fonsén, E., & Vlasov, J. (2017). Leading pedagogical quality in the context of Finnish child care. *Nordic social pedagogical approach to early years*, 253-265.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-42557-3_15

Foucault, M. (1972). *The archaeology of knowledge and the discourse on language*. Pantheon.

Foucault, M. (1977). *Discipline and punish*. Pantheon.

Freire, P. (1998). *Pedagogy of freedom: Ethics, democracy, and civic courage*. Rowman and Littlefield.

Freire, P. (2000). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Continuum.

Froese-Germain, B. (2010). The OECD, PISA and the Impacts on Educational Policy. *Canadian Teachers' Federation (NJI)*.

Fulcher, G. (1999). Assessment in English for academic purposes: putting content validity in its place. *Applied Linguistics*, 20(2), 221-236. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/20.2.221>

Fullan, M. (2007). *The New Meaning of Educational Change* (4th ed.). Teachers College Press.

Geertz, C. (1973). *The Interpretation Of Cultures*. Basic Books.

Georgiou, H. (2023). Are we really falling behind? Comparing key indicators across international and local standardised tests for Australian high school science. *Research in Science Education*, 53(6), 1205-1220. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-023-10129-2>

Geisinger, K. F., Bracken, B. A., Carlson, J. F., Hansen, J. I. C., Kuncel, N. R., Reise, S. P., & Rodriguez, M. C. (2013). *APA handbook of testing and assessment in psychology, Vol. 2: Testing and assessment in clinical and counselling psychology* (pp. ix-605). American Psychological Association.

Gewirtz, S., Meg, M., Eszter, N., & Emma, T. (2021). What's wrong with 'deliverology'?

Performance measurement, accountability and quality improvement in English secondary education. *Journal of Education Policy*, 36(4), 504–529.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2019.1706103>

Giles, T. M., de Lacey, S. & Muir-Cochrane, E. (2016). Coding, Constant Comparisons, and Core Categories. *Advances in Nursing Science*, 39 (1), E29-E44.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/ANS.000000000000109>

Gilmore, A. (2020, 11 May). Pillars of sound educational assessment. *The Education Hub*.

<https://theeducationhub.org.nz/pillars-of-sound-educational-assessment/>

Gioia, D.A., Corley, K.G., & Hamilton, A.L. (2012). Seeking qualitative rigor in inductive research. *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(1), 15-31.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428112452151>

Glaser, B. G. (1978). *Theoretical sensitivity: Advances in methodology of grounded theory*. Sociological Press.

Glaser, B. G. (1992). *Basics of grounded theory analysis*. Sociology Press.

Glaser, B.G. (1998). *Doing grounded theory: issues and discussions*. Sociology Press.

Glaser, B. G. (2002). Constructivist grounded theory? *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 3.

Glaser, B.G., & Strauss, A.L. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: strategies for qualitative research*. Aldine de Gruyter.

Gneezy, U., List, J.A, Livingston, J., Sadoff, S., Qin, X., & Xu, Y. (2017). *Measuring success in education: the role of effort on the test itself*. NBER Working Paper No. 24004.

Goldstein, H. (2004). International Comparisons of Student Attainment: some issues arising from the PISA study. *Assessment in Education*, 11(3), 319-330.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594042000304618>

Goldstein, H. (2017). Measurement and evaluation issues with PISA. In *The PISA effect on global educational governance* (pp. 49-58). Routledge.

Gonski, D., Arcus, T., Boston, K., Gould, V., Johnson, W., O'Brien, L., Perry, L. & Roberts, M. (2018). *Through Growth to Achievement: The Report of The Review to Achieve Educational Excellence in Australian Schools*. Australia.

Goodhart, C. A. E. (1975). Problems of Monetary Management: The U.K. Experience. *Papers in Monetary Economics*. Reserve Bank of Australia.

Gorur, R. (2016). Seeing like PISA: A cautionary tale about the performativity of international assessments. *European Educational Research Journal*, 15(5), 598-616.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1474904116658299>

Gorur, R., & Wu, M. (2015). Leaning too far? PISA, policy and Australia's 'top five' ambitions. *Discourse: studies in the cultural politics of education*, 36(5), 647-664.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2014.930020>

Goss, P., & Sonnemann, J. (2016). *Circuit breaker: A new compact on school funding*. Grattan Institute. <https://grattan.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/881-Circuit-Breaker-New-Compact.pdf>

Gramsci, A. (2000). *The Gramsci reader: Selected writings, 1916–1935*. NYU.

Gray, C. (2021, 3 November). Sam Altman: CEO of AI Research company, Open AI. *AI Magazine*. <https://aimagazine.com/ai-strategy/sam-altman-ceo-ai-research-company-openai>

- Green, D., & Kesselman, J. (2006). *Dimensions of inequality in Canada*. UBC Press.
- Grek, S. (2009). Governing by numbers: The PISA ‘effect’ in Europe. *Journal of Education Policy*, 24(1), 23–37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680930802412669>
- Grey, S., & Morris, P. (2018). PISA: multiple ‘truths’ and mediated global governance. *Comparative Education*, 54(2): 109–131. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050068.2018.1425243>
- Grey, S., & Morris, P. (2022). Capturing the spark: PISA, twenty-first century skills and the reconstruction of creativity. *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2022.2100981>
- Grimm, J. (2015). Hegemonic framing of Malcolm X and Martin Luther King, Jr., in northeastern newspapers. *Howard Journal of Communications*, 26(3), 313–332. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10646175.2015.1049761>
- Grunert, J. (2022). The United States Space Force and the Future of American Space Policy: Legal and Policy Implications, 18.
- Guadalupe, C. (2015). How Feasible is it to Develop a Culturally-Sensitive Large-Scale, Standardised Assessment of Literacy Skills?. *Literacy as numbers: Researching the politics and practices of international literacy assessment*, 111-128.
- Gutting, G., & Oksala, J. (2022). Michel Foucault. In E.N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2022/entries/foucault/>

Hally, T. J. (2015). A brief history of IQ tests. *Pridobljeno*, 15(5), 2018.

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Thomas-Hally/publication/275354727_A_Brief_History_of_IQ_Tests/links/553ad9720cf29b5ee4b652be/A-Brief-History-of-IQ-Tests.pdf

Halsey, J. (2018). *Independent Review into Regional, Rural and Remote Education – Final Report*. Commonwealth of Australia.

Hannon, V., & Peterson, A. (2021). *Thrive: The purpose of schools in a changing world*. Cambridge University Press.

Hanushek, E. (1971). Teacher Characteristics and Gains in Student Achievement: Estimation Using Micro Data. *The American Economic Review*, 61(2), 280–288.

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/1817003>

Hanushek, E. A. (2013). Economic growth in developing countries: The role of human capital. *Economics of Education Review*, 37, 204–212.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econedurev.2013.04.005>

Hanushek, E. A., & Woessmann, L. (2008). The role of cognitive skills in economic development. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 46, 607–668.

<https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.46.3.607>

Hanushek, E. A., & Woessmann, L. (2010). *The high cost of low educational performance: The long-run economic impact of improving PISA outcomes*. OECD Publishing.

Hanushek, E. A., & Woessmann, L. (2012). Do better schools lead to more growth? Cognitive skills, economic outcomes, and causation. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 17(4), 267–

321. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-012-9081-x>

Hanushek, E., & Woessmann, L. (2015). The economic impact of educational quality. *Handbook of international development and education, 2*.

<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783473540.00009>

Hare, J. (2021, 16 April). Alan Tudge's 10-year plan to get schools back to basics. *Financial Review*. <https://www.afr.com/policy/health-and-education/alan-tudge-s-10-year-plan-to-get-schools-back-to-basics-20210413-p57ir9>

Hare, J. (2023, 14 July). Schools crisis: why a revolution might be underway. *Financial Review*. <https://www.afr.com/policy/health-and-education/crisis-in-our-schools-why-an-education-revolution-might-be-underway-20230712-p5dnn2>

Hargreaves, A. (2003) *Teaching in the knowledge society: education in the age of insecurity*. Teachers College.

Hargreaves, A., & Fullan, M. (2012). *Professional capital: Transforming teaching in every school*. Teachers College Press.

Hargreaves, A., & Sahlberg, P. (2015). The tower of PISA is badly leaning. An argument for why it should be saved. https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/answer-sheet/wp/2015/03/24/the-tower-of-pisa-is-badly-leaning-an-argument-for-why-it-should-be-saved/?noredirect=on&utm_term=.69275346b5d3

Hargreaves, A. P., & Shirley, D. L. (Eds.). (2009). *The fourth way: The inspiring future for educational change*. Corwin Press.

Harlen, W., & Deakin Crick, R. (2003). Testing and motivation for learning. *Assessment in Education: principles, policy & practice, 10*(2), 169-207. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594032000121270>

Harms, T., Clifford, R., & Cryer, D. (1998). ECERS-R. *INÉDITOS IDECCA, 23*.

Harrington, M. (2008). Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority Bill 2008.

<https://policycommons.net/artifacts/1765500/australian-curriculum-assessment-and-reporting-authority-bill-2008/2497114/>

Harrington, M. (2010). Australian Government Funding for Schools Explained. Parliamentary Library Background Note. Parliament of Australia.

Harrison, D. (2012, February 17). A class above. *The Sydney Morning Herald*.

<http://www.smh.com.au/national/a-class-above-20120216-1tbq7.html>

Hart, B., Risley, T. R., & Kirby, J. R. (1997). Meaningful differences in the everyday experience of young American children. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 22(3), 323.

Harvey, D. (2005). *Neoliberalism*. Oxford University Press.

Harvey, D. (2007). *A brief history of neoliberalism*. Oxford University Press.

Hastings, A. (1998). Connecting linguistic structures and social practices: a discursive approach to social policy analysis. *Journal of Social Policy*, 27(2), 191-211.

<https://doi:10.1017/S0047279498005248>

Hattie, J. (2003). Teachers Make a Difference, What is the research evidence?.

https://research.acer.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1003&context=research_conference_2003

Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of educational research*, 77(1), 81-112. <https://doi.org/10.3102/003465430298487>

Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible Learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge.

Hattie, J. (2016). Shifting away from distractions to improve Australia's schools: Time for a reboot. ACEL.

Hatzinikita, V., Dimopoulos, K., & Christidou, V. (2008). PISA test items and school textbooks related to science. *Science Education*, 92(4), 664–687.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.20256>

Heckman, J.J., Humphries, J.E. & Kautz, T. (2014). “Who are the GEDs?,” In Heckman, J.J., Humphries, J.E. & Kautz, T. (Eds), *The Myth of Achievement Tests: The GED and the Role of Character in American Life*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL, pp.341-430.

Henebery, B. (2023, September 15). Damning OECD report amplifies calls to boost public school funding. *The Educator Online*.

<https://www.theeducatoronline.com/k12/news/damning-oecd-report-amplifies-calls-to-boost-public-school-funding/>

Hillman, K., O’Grady, E., Rodrigues, S., Schmid, M., & Thomson, S. (2023). *Progress in International Reading Literacy Study: Australia’s results from PIRLS 2021*. Australian Council for Educational Research.

Hoffman, J.A., & Miller, E.A. (2020). Addressing the Consequences of School Closure Due to COVID-19 on Children's Physical and Mental Well-Being. *World Medical & Health Policy*, 12, 300-310. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wmh3.365>

Hogan, A. (2016). NAPLAN and the role of edu-business: New governance, new privatisations and new partnerships in Australian education policy. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 43(1), 93–110. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-014-0162-z>

Hopfenbeck, T. N., & Gørgen, K. (2017). The politics of PISA: The media, policy and public responses in Norway and England. *European Journal of Education*, 52(2), 192-205.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12219>

Hopfenbeck, T.N., & Kjærnsli, M. (2016). Students' test motivation in PISA: the case of Norway. *The Curriculum Journal*, 27(3), 406-422.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09585176.2016.1156004>

Hopfenbeck, T. N., Lenkeit, J., El Masri, Y., Cantrell, K., Ryan, J., & Baird, J.-A. (2018). Lessons learned from PISA: A systematic review of peer-reviewed articles on the programme for international student assessment. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 62(3), 333–353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2016.1258726>

Hopmann, S. T. (2008). No child, no school, no state left behind: Schooling in the age of accountability. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 40(4), 417–456.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00220270801989818>

Hopmann, S. T., Brinek, G., & Retzl, M. (2007). Pisa zufolge Pisa–Pisa according to Pisa. *Hält PISA was es verspricht*.

Hume, D. (1739). *Treatise of Human Nature*. Cambridge University Press.

Hunter, F. (2019, 9 December). Education Minister pushes for 'back to basics' approach in schools. *The Sydney Morning Herald*.

<https://www.smh.com.au/politics/federal/education-minister-pushes-for-back-to-basics-approach-in-schools-20191209-p53i7z.html>

IEA (2009). *TIMSS 2007 Technical Report*. TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Lynch School of Education, Boston College. IMS Question and Test Interoperability v2.1 Final Specification 31 August 2012.

Iliescu, D., Bartram, D., Zeinoun, P., Ziegler, M., Elosua, P., Sireci, S., ... & Camara, W. (2024). The Test Adaptation Reporting Standards (TARES): reporting test adaptations. *International Journal of Testing*, 24(1), 80-102.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/15305058.2023.2294266>

- Jerrim, J. (2015). Why do East Asian children perform so well in PISA? An investigation of Western-born children of East Asian descent. *Oxford Review of Education*, 41(3), 310-333. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2015.1028525>
- Jerrim, J. (2023). Has Peak PISA passed? An investigation of interest in International Large-Scale Assessments across countries and over time. *European Educational Research Journal*, 14749041231151793. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14749041231151793>
- Jupp, V. (2006). The Sage dictionary of social research methods. *The SAGE Dictionary of Social Research Methods*, 1-352.
- Kandel, I. L. (1941). *Education and Modern Thought*. Teachers College Record. <http://www.tcrecord.org/Content.asp?ContentId=15086>
- Kane, M. T. (2006). Validation. In R. L. Brennan (Ed.), *Educational measurement* (4th ed.) (pp. 17-64). Washington, DC: The National Council on Measurement in Education & the American Council on Education.
- Kane, M. (2013). The argument-based approach to validation. *School Psychology Review*, 42(4), 448-457. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02796015.2013.12087465>
- Karmel, P. (1973). *Schools in Australia: Report of the interim committee for the Australian schools commission*. May 1973.
- Kautz, T., Heckman, J.J., Diris, R., Weel, B.T., & Borghans, L. (2014). *Fostering and measuring skills: improving cognitive and non-cognitive skills to promote lifetime success*. Working Paper No.110, OECD Education.
- Kelley, T.L. (1927). *Interpretation of Educational Measurements*. Macmillan.

Kim, H., Care, E., & Vista, A. (2019, 30 January). Education systems need alignment for teaching and learning 21st century skills. *Brookings Institute*.

<https://www.brookings.edu/blog/education-plus-development/2019/01/30/education-systems-need-alignment-for-teaching-and-learning-21st-century-skills/>

Klein, R. (2011). A re-analysis of the PISA results: comparability problems.”[Uma re-análise dos resultados do PISA: problemas de comparabilidade]. *Políticas Públicas Em Educação*, 19(73). <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-40362011000500002>

Klenowski, V. (2015). Questioning the validity of the multiple uses of NAPLAN data. In *National Testing in Schools* (pp. 44-56). Routledge.

Klinkhammer, N., & Schäfer, B. (2017). Quality development and assurance in Early Childhood Education and Care - International Perspectives, in Klinkhammer, N. et al. (Eds.), *Monitoring Quality in Early Childhood Education and Care - Approaches and experiences from selected countries*, German Youth Institute, Munich.

Knight, J., & Warry, M. (1996). From corporate to supply-side federalism? Narrowing the Australian education policy agenda. 1987-1996. Proceedings of the AAER/ERA Conference, Singapore.

Kofod, K., Louis, K. S., Moos, L., & van Velzen, B. (2012). Historical perspectives on educational policy and political cultures. In *Educational policy in an international context: Political culture and its effects* (pp. 29-47). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.

Kohn, A. (2000). *The case against standardized testing: Raising the scores, ruining the schools*. Heinemann.

Koretz, D. M. (2008). *Measuring up*. Harvard University Press.

Krantz, D., Luce, D., Tversky, A., & Suppes, P. (1971). *Foundations of Measurement*. Dover.

Labaree, D. (1997). Public goods, private goods: The American struggle over educational goals. *American Educational Research Journal*, 34(1), 39–81.

<https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312034001039>

Labaree, D. F. (2014). Let's measure what no one teaches: PISA, NCLB, and the shrinking aims of education. *Teachers College Record*, 116(9), 1–14.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/016146811411600905>

Lake, B. S., & Wise, L. L. (2014). What is the role and importance of the revised AERA, APA, NCME standards for educational and psychological testing? *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 33(4), 4–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/emip.12045>

Lamb, S., Maire, Q., & Doecke, E. (2017). Key skills for the 21st Century: an evidence-based review. Sydney: NSW Department of Education. <https://education.nsw.gov.au/our-priorities/innovate-for-the-future/education-for-a-changing-world/research-findings/future-frontiers-analytical-report-key-skills-for-the-21st-century/Key-Skills-for-the-21st-Century-Analytical-Report.pdf>

Lamb, S., Huo, S., Walstab, A., Wade, A., Maire, Q., Doecke, E., Jackson, J. & Endekov, Z. (2020). *Educational opportunity in Australia 2020: Who succeeds and who misses out*. Centre for International Research on Education Systems, Victoria University, for the Mitchell Institute: Melbourne.

Langman, L. (2015). An overview: Hegemony, ideology and the reproduction of domination. *Critical Sociology*, 41(3), 425-432.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0896920515570208>

Larroulet Philippi, C. (2021). Valid for What? On the Very Idea of Unconditional Validity.

Philosophy of the Social Sciences, 51(2), 151-175.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0048393120971169>

- Launeanu, M., & Hubley, A. M. (2017). Some observations on response processes research and its future theoretical and methodological directions. In B. Zumbo & A.M. Hubley (Eds.), *Understanding and investigating response processes in validation research* (pp. 93–113). Springer.
- Lawry, J. (1965). Australian Education 1788-1823. *History of Education Quarterly*, 5(3), 166-173. <https://doi.org/10.2307/367115>
- Leech, N. L., & Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2007). An array of qualitative data analysis tools: A call for data analysis triangulation. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 22(4), 557–584. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/1045-3830.22.4.557>
- Leitner, H., & Sheppard, E. (2002). “The city is dead, long live the net”: Harnessing European inter urban networks for a neoliberal agenda. *Antipode*, 34(3), 495–518. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8330.00252>
- Levin, H. M. (2009). The economic payoff to investing in educational justice. *Educational researcher*, 38(1), 5-20. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X08331192>
- Levin, H. M. (2012). More than just test scores. *Prospects*, 42, 269-284. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-012-9240-z>
- Lewis, S. (2017). Policy, philanthropy and profit: The OECD’s PISA for schools and new modes of heterarchical educational governance. *Comparative Education*, 53(4), 518–537. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050068.2017.1327246>
- Lewis, S. (2020). *PISA, Policy and the OECD. Respatialising global education governance through PISA for schools*. Springer.
- Lin, A., & Harris, D. (Eds.). (2008). *The colors of poverty: Why racial and ethnic disparities persist*. Russell Sage Foundation.

Linn, R. L. (2000). Assessments and accountability. *Educational researcher*, 29(2), 4-16.

<https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X029002004>

Lincoln, Y.S., & Guba, E.G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage.

Lingard, B. (1993). Corporate federalism: the emerging approach to policy making in Australian schools, In Lingard, B., Knight, J. and Porter, P. (Eds), *Schooling Reform in Hard Times*, The Falmer Press, London, pp. 24-35.

Lingard, B. (2000). Federalism in schooling since the Karmel Report (1973), Schools in Australia: from modernist hope to postmodernist performativity. [Paper presented at the ACER Conference: 'Schools in Australia: 1973-1998 the 25 Years since the Karmel Report' (1998: Sydney).]. *Australian Educational Researcher*, 27(2), 25-61.

Lingard, B. (2014). A critical reflection on the Donnelly/Wiltshire Review of the Australian Curriculum. *Professional Educator*, 13(6), 10-13.

Lingard, B., Rezai-Rashti, G., Martino, W., & Sellar, S. (2015). *Globalizing educational accountabilities*. Routledge.

Lingard, B., & Sellar, S. (2013). Catalyst data: Perverse systemic effects of audit and accountability in Australian schooling. *Journal of Education Policy*, 28(5), 634–656.

Liu, Y., He, F., Zhang, H., Rao, G., Feng, Z., & Zhou, Y. (2019). How Well Do Machines Perform on IQ tests: a Comparison Study on a Large-Scale Dataset. In *IJCAI* (pp. 6110-6116).

Locke K., Golden-Biddle K., Feldman M. (2008). Perspective - Making doubt generative: Rethinking the role of doubt in the research process. *Organization Science*, 19, 907-918.

<https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.1080.0398>

- Lockheed, M.E., & Wagemaker, H. (2013). International large-scale assessments, thermometers, whips or useful policy tools? *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 8(3), 296-306. <https://doi.org/10.2304/rcie.2013.8.3.296>
- Loveless, T. (2013). PISA's China Problem. www.brookings.edu/research/pisas-china-problem/
- Lubart, T., & Guignard, J. (2004). The generality-specificity of creativity: a multivariate approach. In R. J. Sternberg, E. L. Grigorenk, & J. L. Singer (Eds.), *Creativity: From potential to realization* (pp. 43-56). American Psychological Association.
- MacArthur, H.V. (2020, 16 March). Leading in times of uncertainty: how to engage optimism and focus when nothing seems predictable. *Forbes*.
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/hvmacarthur/2020/03/16/leading-in-times-of-uncertainty-how-to-engage-optimism-and-focus-when-nothing-seems-predictable/?sh=29eeda047e20>
- Mackey, R.H (1992). *Translating Vision into Reality: the Role of the Strategic Leader*. US Army War College.
- Mahmud Rice, J., Edwards, D. & McMillan, J. (2019). *Education Expenditure in Australia*. ACER.
- Marginson, S. (2007). Federal/state relations in education the 2006 work relations case. Paper presented at the Institute of Public Administration Australia (IPAA) and Academy of Social Sciences Australia (ASSA) Policy Roundtable on Federalism, University of Canberra, Canberra, 17-18 May.
- Marsh, E. J., Roediger, H. L., Bjork, R. A., & Bjork, E. L. (2007). The memorial consequences of multiple-choice testing. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 14, 194-199.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03194051>

- Marsh, J., Springer, M., McCaffrey, D., Yuan, K., Epstein, S., Koppich, J., Kalra N., DiMartino, M. & Peng, A. (2011). *A Big Apple for Educators: New York City's experiment with schoolwide performance bonuses*. Rand.
- Martin, L. (2014, 12 October). PM calls for schools to go back to basics. *The Australian*.
<https://www.theaustralian.com.au/news/latest-news/review-calls-for-less-crowded-curriculum/news-story/1c46c5cc7b792c02e74d5b09174d0d8c>
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). Preface to motivation theory. *Psychosomatic medicine*, 5(1), 85-92.
- Masters, G. (2005). International Achievement Studies: Lessons from PISA and TIMSS. *Research Developments*, 13, 1-5. <https://research.acer.edu.au/resdev/vol13/iss13/2>
- Masters, G. (2019). *Nurturing wonder and igniting passion: Designs for a future school curriculum*. NSW Curriculum Review Interim Report. Sydney, Australia: NSW Education Standards Authority. <https://apo.org.au/node/264486>
- Masters, G. (2022). *Building a world class learning system*. Centre for Strategic Education.
<https://ncee.org/quick-read/building-world-class-learning-systems/>
- Mathison, S. (1988). Why triangulate?. *Educational researcher*, 17(2), 13–17.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X017002013>
- Mayer-Schönberger, V., & Cukier, K. (2013). *Big data: A revolution that will transform how we live, work, and think*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- Maykut, P. S., & Morehouse, R. E. (1994). *Beginning qualitative research: A philosophic and practical guide* (Vol. 6). Psychology Press.
- Mayo, P. (2008). Antonio Gramsci and his relevance for the education of adults. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 40(3), 418-435. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-5812.2007.00357.x>

- McCann, T.V., & Clark, E. (2003). Grounded theory in nursing research: part 3 - application. *Nurse Research, 11*(2): 29-39. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr2004.01.11.2.29.c5920>
- McCubbin, L. (2001). Challenges to the Definition of Resilience.
- McGaw, B., Louden, W. & Wyatt-Smith, C. (2019). NAPLAN Review Interim Report, November 2019. Reviewed commissioned by the state and territory governments of New South Wales, Australian.
- McGaw, B., Louden, W. & Wyatt-Smith, C. (2020). NAPLAN Review Final Report, August 2020. Reviewed commissioned by the state and territory governments of New South Wales, Australian.
- McKinsey. (2020, May 14). The COVID-19 Recovery Will Be Digital: A plan for the first 90 days. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/the-covid-19-recovery-will-be-digital-a-plan-for-the-first-90-days>
- McMillan, J. (Ed.). (2013). *SAGE handbook of research on classroom assessment*. SAGE.
- Meadmore, P. (2001). Free, compulsory and secular? The re-invention of Australian public education. *Journal of Education Policy, 16*(2), 113-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680930010025329>
- Mehrens, W. (1997). The consequences of consequential validity. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice, 16*(2), 16-18.
- Messick, S. (1984a). The psychology of educational measurement. *ETS Research Report Series, 1984*(1), i-55. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2330-8516.1984.tb00046.x>
- Messick, S. (1984b). Assessment in context: Appraising student performance in relation to instructional quality. *Educational Researcher, 13*(3), 3-8. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X013003003>

Messick, S. (1989). Validity. In R. L. Linn (Ed.), *Educational Measurement* (3rd ed., pp. 13-103). MacMillan.

Messick, S. (1990). Validity of test interpretation and use.

Messick, S. (1995) Validity of psychological assessment: Validation of inferences from persons' responses and performances as scientific inquiry into score meaning. *American Psychologist*, 50(9), 741-749. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0003-066X.50.9.741>

Meyer, H.-D., & Benavot, A. (2013). *PISA, power, and policy: The emergence of global educational governance*. Oxford University Press.

Meyer, H.D & Zahedi, K. (2014, May 5). An open letter to Andreas Schleicher. *The Guardian*. www.theguardian.com/education/2014/may/06/oecd-pisa-tests-damaging-education-academics

Meyerhoefer, W. (2009). Testfähigkeit–wasistdas? [Does PISA keep what it promises?], In Hopmann, S., Brinek, G. and Retzl, M. (Eds), *PISA according to PISA*, University of Vienna Press.

Micklewright, J., Schnepf, S.V. & Skinner, C.J. (2012). Non-response biases in surveys of school children: the case of the English PISA samples. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series A*, 175(4), 915-938. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1566338>

Mills, J., Birks, M. & Hoare, K.J. (2014). Grounded theory. In: Mills J, Birks M. (eds) *Qualitative methodology: a practical guide*. London: SAGE, pp. 107–121.

Mills, J., Bonner, A., & Francis, K. (2006). Adopting a constructivist approach to grounded theory: Implications for research design. *International Journal of Nursing Practice*, 12(1), 8–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-172X.2006.00543.x>

Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training and Youth Affairs. (MCEETYA). (1989). Common and agreed goals for schooling in Australia.

http://www.mceetya.edu.au/mceecdy/hobart_declaration,11577.html

Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training and Youth Affairs. (MCEETYA).

(1999). The Adelaide Declaration on national goals for schooling in the twenty-first century.

Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training and Youth Affairs. (2008). Melbourne declaration on educational goals for young Australians.

http://www.mceecdy.edu.au/verve/_resources/national_declaration_on_the_educational_goals_for_young_australians.pdf

Mintrop, H., & Trujillo, T. (2007). The practical relevance of accountability systems for school improvement: A descriptive analysis of California schools. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 29, 319-352. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0162373707309219>

Mishler, E. (1990). Validation in inquiry-guided research: The role of exemplars in narrative studies. *Harvard educational review*, 60(4), 415-443.

<https://doi.org/10.17763/haer.60.4.n4405243p6635752>

Mizen, R. (2023, 20 January). Gonski billions had 'little impact' on literacy, numeracy. *Financial*

Review. <https://www.afr.com/politics/federal/gonski-2-0-money-should-be-linked-to-clearer-goals-for-students-pc-20230119-p5ce3a>

Mockler, N. (2013). Reporting the 'education revolution': MySchool.edu.au in the print media. *Discourse: Studies in the cultural politics of education*, 34(1), 1-16.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2012.698860>

Moran, S. (2010). Creativity in school. *International handbook of psychology in education*, 319-359.

- Morgan, H. (2016). Relying on high stakes standardized tests to evaluate schools and teachers: A bad idea. *The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, 89(2), 67-72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00098655.2016.1156628>
- Morrison, H. (2013). PISA 2012 major flaw exposed. <https://paceni.wordpress.com/2013/12/01/pisa-2012-major-flaw-exposed/>
- Morse, J.M. (2007). Sampling in grounded theory. In: Bryant A, Charmaz K. (eds) *The Sage handbook of grounded theory*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE, pp. 229–244.
- Moss, P. A., Girard, B. J., & Haniford, L. C. (2006). Validity in educational assessment. *Review of research in education*, 109-162. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0091732X030001109>
- Moutsios, S. (2009). International Organisations and Transnational Education Policy. *Compare*, 39(4), 467-478. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057920802156500>
- Mrozowska, T., 2020. Measurement and outcome-based funding in New South Wales schools Informed by the Data:, Parliament of New South Wales. Australia. <https://policycommons.net/artifacts/4372110/measurement-and-outcome-based-funding-in-new-south-wales-schools-informed-by-the-data/5168543/>
- Mudge, S. (2008). Neoliberalism's Three Faces. EUI MWP, 2008/34. <https://hdl.handle.net/1814/9108>
- Mullis, I.V.S., Martin, M.O., Foy, P., Kelly, D.L. & Fishbein, B. (2020). *TIMSS 2019 International Results in Mathematics and Science*. USA: TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Lynch School of Education and Human Development, Boston College and International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA).

- Munton, A. G., Mooney, A., & Rowland, L. (1995). Deconstructing quality: A conceptual framework for the new paradigm in day care provision for the under eights. *Early Child Development and Care*, 114(1), 11-23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0300443951140102>
- Murphy, D. (2014). Issues with PISA's use of its data in the context of international education policy convergence. *Policy Futures in Education*, 12(7), 893-916. <https://doi.org/10.2304/pfie.2014.12.7.893>
- Nevill, T., & Savage, G. C. (2023). The changing rationalities of Australian federal and national inclusive education policies. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 50(5), 1343-1361. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-022-00555-y>
- Ng, P.T. (2017). *Learning from Singapore: The Power of Paradoxes* (1st ed.). Routledge.
- Norton, A. (2007). OECD-itis. Observations from Carlton's Lone Classical Liberal.
- Nye, J. (2004). Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics. *Public Affairs*, 16.
- Nye, J. (2009). Smart Power. *New Perspectives Quarterly*, 26(2), 7- 9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5842.2009.01057.x>
- Ofsted. (2010). Reading by six. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7eb861ed915d74e33f1ff7/Reading_20_by_20six.pdf
- Oh, C. J., & Kim, N. Y. (2016). "Success is relative": Comparative social class and ethnic effects in an academic paradox. *Sociological Perspectives*, 59(2), 270–295. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0731121415587115>
- OpenAI. (2023). Technical Report on GPT-4. <https://cdn.openai.com/papers/gpt-4.pdf>
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (1999). *Measuring Student Knowledge and Skills. A New Framework for Assessment*. OECD Publications.

- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2000a). *Measuring student knowledge and skills: The PISA 2000 assessment of reading, mathematical and scientific literacy*. OECD Publications.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2000b). PISA 2000 Technical Report. OECD Publications.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2002), Reading for Change: Performance and Engagement across Countries: Results from PISA 2000. OECD Publications.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2003). The PISA 2003 assessment framework: Mathematics, reading, science and problem-solving knowledge and skills. OECD Publications.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2006). Assessing scientific, reading and mathematical literacy—A framework for PISA 2006. OECD Publications.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2007). PISA 2006: science competencies for tomorrow's world. Vol. 1: Analysis. OECD Publications.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2008). External evaluation of the policy impact of PISA.
[http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=EDU/PISA/GB\(2008\)35/REV1&docLanguage=En](http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=EDU/PISA/GB(2008)35/REV1&docLanguage=En)
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (OECD). (2010). PISA 2009 Results: Overcoming social background, Volume 11. OECD Publications.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2012). Equity and Quality in Education: Supporting Disadvantaged Students and Schools. OECD Publications.

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (OECD). (2013a). PISA 2012

Results: Excellence through Equity Giving Every Student the Chance to Succeed (Vol. II). OECD Publications.

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2013b). General guidelines for the availability and uses of the PISA-based test for schools.

<https://www.oecd.org/pisa/aboutpisa/PISAbased-test-for-schools-guidelines.pdf>

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2016a). PISA 2015 results (volume I): Excellence and equity in education. OECD Publications.

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2016b). PISA 2015:

Results in focus. PISA. <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisa-2015-results-in-focus.pdf>.

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2017). PISA 2015 results:

Students' well-being. [http://www.keepeek.com/Digital-Asset-](http://www.keepeek.com/Digital-Asset-Management/oecd/education/pisa-2015-results-volume-iii_9789264273856-en)

[Management/oecd/education/pisa-2015-results-volume-iii_9789264273856-en](http://www.keepeek.com/Digital-Asset-Management/oecd/education/pisa-2015-results-volume-iii_9789264273856-en)

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2018). OECD Future of Education and Skills 2030 Project Background. OECD Publications.

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2019a). FAQ.

<https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisafaq/>

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2019b). PISA 2018

Assessment and Analytical Framework. OECD Publications.

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2020). PISA 2022

Technical Standards. <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisaproducts/PISA-2022-Technical-Standards.pdf>

OECD (2022), *Education at a Glance 2022: OECD Indicators*. OECD Publications.

<https://doi.org/10.1787/3197152b-en>

Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2023). Setting the stage:

Approaches to assessing AI's impact, In *Is Education Losing the Race with Technology?: AI's Progress in Maths and Reading*. OECD Publications.

<https://doi.org/10.1787/8ee0810f-en>.

Papert, S. (1998). Let's tie the digital knot. *TECHNOS Quarterly for Education and*

Technology, 7(4). <https://dailypapert.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Papert-Lets-Tie-the-Digital-Knot.pdf>

Parkin, A., & Anderson, G. (2007). The Howard government, regulatory federalism and the

transformation of commonwealth-state relations. *Australian Journal of Political*

Science, 42(1), 295-314. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10361140701320034>

Partnership for 21st Century Skills. (2007). 21st Century Skills Assessment: A Partnership for

21st Century Skills e-paper. <https://www.scribd.com/doc/269214250/21st-century-skills-assessment-e-paper>

Patrick, R., & Moodie, N. (2016). Indigenous education policy discourses in

Australia: Rethinking the "Problem". In T. Barkatsas & A. Bertram (Eds), *Global learning in the 21st century*. Sense Publishers.

Patton, M. Q. (1980). *Qualitative evaluation methods*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.

Peck, J., & Theodore, N. (2015). *Fast policy: Experimental statecraft at the thresholds of*

neoliberalism. University of Minnesota Press.

- Pederson, P. V. (2007). What is measured is treasured: The impact of the No Child Left Behind Act on non-assessed subjects. *The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, 80(6), 287-291. <https://doi.org/10.3200/TCHS.80.6.287-291>
- People for Education (2014). *Measuring What Matters: Beyond the 3 “R’s”*. In *Measuring What Matters*, People for Education. Toronto: November 8, 2014.
- Pepper, D. (2011). Assessing key competences across the curriculum—and Europe. *European Journal of Education*, 46(3), 335–353. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1465-3435.2011.01484.x>
- Pepper, D. (2020). When assessment validation neglects any strand of validity evidence: An instructive example from PISA. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 39(4), 8-20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/emip.12380>
- Perry, L. B., & Southwell, L. (2014). Access to academic curriculum in Australian secondary schools: A case study of a highly marketised education system. *Journal of Education Policy*, 29(4), 467-485. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2013.846414>
- Peters, M. A. (2011). Neoliberalism and after. Education, social policy, and the crisis of western. https://toc.library.ethz.ch/objects/pdf/z01_978-1-4331-1206-5_01.pdf
- Piaget, J. (1936). *Origins of intelligence in the child*. Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- Piaget, J. (1945). *Play, dreams and imitation in childhood*. Heinemann.
- Piaget, J. (1957). *Construction of reality in the child*. Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- Piccoli, A., & Sahlberg, P. (2019). NAPLAN 2019 Review Submission, 20 March 2019.
- Pitsoe, V., & Letseka, M. (2013). Foucault’s discourse and power: Implications for instructionist classroom management. *Open Journal of philosophy*, 3(01), 23-28. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/ojpp.2013.31005>

- Pokropek, A., Marks, G. N., & Borgonovi, F. (2022). How much do students' scores in PISA reflect general intelligence and how much do they reflect specific abilities?. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 114*(5), 1121-1135.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/edu0000687>
- Polesel, J., Dulfer, N., & Turnbull, M. (2012). The experience of education: The impacts of high stakes testing on school students and their families. Rydalmere, NSW: Whitlam Institute, The University of Western Sydney.
<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/30680023.pdf>
- Pons, X. (2017). Fifteen years of research on PISA effects on education governance: A critical review. *European Journal of Education, 52*(2), 131–144.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12213>
- Popham, W. (1997). Consequential validity: Right concern - wrong concept. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice, 16*(2), 9-13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3992.1997.tb00586.x>
- Porter, T.M. (1995). *Trust in numbers: the pursuit of objectivity in science and public life*. Princeton University Press.
- Porter, T. & Webb, M. (2007) The Role of the OECD in the Orchestration of Global Knowledge Networks. Paper for Canadian Political Science Association. <http://www.cpsa-acsp.ca/papers-2007/Porter-Webb.pdf>
- Prais, S. J. (2003). Cautions on OECD's recent educational survey (PISA). *Oxford Review of Education, 29*(2), 139-163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305498032000080657>
- Qureshi, H.A., & Ünlü, Z. (2020). Beyond the Paradigm Conflicts: A Four-Step Coding Instrument for Grounded theory. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods, 19*,1-10.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920928188>

- Ragusa, A.T., & Bousfield, K. (2017). 'It's not the test, it's how it's used!' Critical analysis of public response to NAPLAN and MySchool Senate Inquiry, *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 38:3, 265-286.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2015.1073100>
- Ralph, N., Birks, M. & Chapman, Y. (2014). Contextual positioning: using documents as extant data in grounded theory research. *SAGE Open*, 4, 1–7.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244014552425>
- Ratner, S. (2021, 21 December). The rich tapestry of assessment: How holistic testing ties together many threads to tell each student's story.
<https://www.janison.com/resources/post/the-rich-tapestry-of-assessment-how-holistic-testing-ties-together-many-threads-to-tell-each-students-story/>
- Ratner, S. (2022). Re-imagining assessment in Australian schools. *Independent Education*, 52, 30-31. <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.399727464838482>
- Raven, J. (2003). Raven Progressive Matrices. In R. S. McCallum (Ed.), *Handbook of Nonverbal Assessment* (pp. 223-237). Boston, MA: Springer US.
- Ravitch, D. (2010). *The death and life of the great American school system: How testing and choice are undermining education*. Basic Books.
- Reay, G., Raffin, B. S., & Rankin, J. A. (2016). Staying theoretically sensitive when conducting grounded theory research. *Nurse Researcher*, 24(1), 26–30.
<https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.2016.e1445>
- Reid, A. (2019). *Changing Australian education: How policy is taking us backwoods and what can be done about it*. Allen & Unwin.

- Resnick, L. B., & Resnick, D. P. (1992). Assessing the thinking curriculum: New tools for educational reform. In *Changing assessments: Alternative views of aptitude, achievement and instruction* (pp. 37-75). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
- Rivas, A., & Scasso, M. G. (2021). Low stakes, high risks: the problem of intertemporal validity of PISA in Latin America. *Journal of Education Policy*, 36(2), 279-302.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2019.1696987>
- Rizvi, F., & Lingard, B. (2006). Globalization and the changing nature of the OECD's educational work. *Education, globalization and social change*, 247-260.
<https://rest.neptune-prod.its.unimelb.edu.au/server/api/core/bitstreams/500b50ca-d8ae-551a-8a1b-e0fe09b64c55/content>
- Robinson, N. (2018, 20 March). Migrant children at the head of the class in Australia, OECD report finds. *ABC News*. <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2018-03-20/migrant-kids-are-finding-success-in-australian-classrooms/9563440>
- Robinson, O.C. (2014). Sampling in interview-based qualitative research: A theoretical and practical guide. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 11(1): 25–41.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2013.801543>
- Rogoff, B. (2003). *The cultural nature of human development*. Oxford university press.
- Rosa, H. (2003). Social acceleration: Ethical and political consequences of a desynchronized high-speed society. *Constellations*, 10(1), 3–33. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8675.00309>
- Rosa, H. (2015). *Acceleration: A new theory of modernity*. Columbia University Press.

- Rose, J., Low-Choy, S., Singh, P., & Vasco, D. (2020). NAPLAN discourses: A systematic review after the first decade. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 41(6), 871-886. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2018.1557111>
- Rothstein, R. (2008). Whose Problem Is Poverty?. *Educational leadership*, 65(7), 8-13.
- Rutkowski, L., & Rutkowski, D. (2016). A call for a more measured approach to reporting and interpreting PISA results. *Educational Researcher*, 45(4), 252-257. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X16649961>
- Sahlberg, P. (2011). PISA in Finland: An education miracle or an obstacle to change?. *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal*, 1(3), 119-140. <https://doi.org/10.26529/cepsj.418>
- Sahlberg, P. (2012). How GERM is infecting schools around the world. *Washington Post*. http://www.washingtonpost.com/blogs/answer-sheet/post/how-germ-is-infecting-schools-around-the-world/2012/06/29/gJQAVELZAW_blog.html
- Sahlberg, P., & Oldroyd, D. (2010). Pedagogy for economic competitiveness and sustainable development. *European Journal of Education*, 45(2), 280-299. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1465-3435.2010.01429.x>
- Saldana, J. (2009). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers* (2nd ed.). SAGE.
- Savage, G. C. (2013). Tailored equities in the education market: Flexible policies and practices. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 34(2), 185–201. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2013.770246>
- Savage, G. (2014). Why markets can't deliver excellence and equity in schools. *The Conversation*, <https://theconversation.com/why-markets-cant-deliver-excellence-and-equity-in-schools-25711>

- Saxton, D., Grefenstette, E., Hill, F., & Kohli, P. (2019). Analysing mathematical reasoning abilities of neural models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.01557*.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1904.01557>
- Schleicher, A. (2007). Can competencies assessed by PISA be considered the fundamental school knowledge 15-year-olds should possess? *Journal of Educational Change*, 8, 349–357.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-007-9042-x>
- Schleicher, A. (2019). *PISA 2018: Insights and Interpretations*. OECD.
- Schleicher, A. (2023, 21 June). ChatGPT and PISA: Ensuring our education systems keep up.
<https://www.oecd-forum.org/posts/chatgpt-and-pisa-ensuring-our-education-systems-keep-up>
- Schneider, M. (2009). The International PISA test: A risky investment for states. *Education Next*, 68-74.
- Schuelka, M. J. (2013). Excluding students with disabilities from the culture of achievement: The case of the TIMSS, PIRLS, and PISA. *Journal of Education Policy*, 28(2), 216–230. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2012.708789>
- Schult, J., & Sparfeldt, J. R. (2016). Reliability and Validity of PIRLS and TIMSS. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759/a000338>
- Sellar, S., & Lingard, B. (2014). The OECD and the expansion of PISA: New global modes of governance in education. *British Educational Research Journal*, 40(6), 917–936.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3120>
- Sharrock, G. (2012, 19 October). Why the OECD is not always right. *The Australian*.

- Shepard, L. A. (1997). The centrality of test use and consequences for test validity. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 16(2), 5-8, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3992.1997.tb00585.x>
- Sheridan, S. (2009). Discerning Pedagogical Quality in Preschool. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 53(3), 245-261. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313830902917295>
- Sheridan, S., Giota, J., Han, Y-M., & Kwon, J-Y. (2009). A cross-cultural study of preschool quality in South Korea and Sweden. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 24(2), 142-156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2009.03.004>
- Sigauke, I., & Swansi, K. (2020). “Classic” Grounded Theory: An Extraction of Saldana’s Coding Heuristics. *International Forum*, 23(1), 5-23.
- Sjøberg, S. (2015a). OECD, PISA, and globalization: The influence of the international assessment regime. In C. H. Tienken & C. A. Mullen (Eds.), *Education policy perils* (pp. 114–145). London: Routledge.
- Sjøberg, S. (2015b). PISA and global educational governance—A critique of the project, its uses and implications. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 11(1), 111–127. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2015.1310a>
- Skourdoumbis, A., & Rawolle, S. (2020). *The metrics of teacher effectiveness and teacher quality research. Sidelineing the issues that really count*. Routledge.
- Skourdoumbis, A., Thomas, M.K.E., & Rawolle, S. (2023). Being critical of the student achievement problem in Australia. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-023-00629-5>
- Smart, D. (1985). Fraser & Reagan" New Federalism": Politics of Education in Times of Economic Recession.

- Smith, M. L., & Fey, P. (2000). Validity and accountability in high-stakes testing. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 51(5), 334-344. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487100051005002>
- Snape, D., & Spencer, L. (2003). The foundations of qualitative research In J. Richie & J. Lewis (Eds.), *Qualitative Research Practice* (pp. 1-23). Los Angeles: Sage.
- Solano-Flores, G., & Milbourn, T. (2016). Assessment capacity, cultural validity and consequential validity in PISA. *Relieve*, 22(1), M12.
- Solarz, M. W. (2012). 'Third World': the 60th anniversary of a concept that changed history. *Third World Quarterly*, 33(9), 1561-1573.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2012.720828>
- Solomon, D. (15 May 1981). Australian states react angrily to cost cutting. *Christian Science Monitor*. <https://www.csmonitor.com/1981/0515/051544.html>
- Spearman, C. (1904). General intelligence objectively determined and measured. *American Journal of Psychology*, 15, 107-197. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/11491-006>
- Spearman, C. (1927). The measurement of intelligence. *Nature*, 120, 577-578.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/120577a0>
- Stacey, M., Mcgrath-Champ, S., & Wilson, R. (2023). Teacher attributions of workload increase in public sector schools: Reflections on change and policy development. *Journal of Educational Change*, 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-022-09476-0>
- Stankov, L., Lee, J., & von Davier, M. (2018). A note on construct validity of the anchoring method in PISA 2012. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 36(7), 709-724.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0734282917702270>

- Starks H., & Brown Trinidad S. (2007). Choose your method: A comparison of phenomenology, discourse analysis, and grounded theory. *Qualitative Health Research*, 17(10), 1372–1380. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732307307031>
- Starr, K. (2014). The influences and implications of PISA: An Australian perspective. *AASA Journal of Scholarship and Practice*, 10(4), 19-30. <https://hdl.handle.net/10536/DRO/DU:30061894>
- Statista Research Department. (2023, 3 January). Number of schools in Australia 2021, by affiliation type. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1156145/australia-number-of-schools-by-affiliation-type/>
- Steering Committee for the Review of Government Service Provision (SCRGSP). (2019). *National Agreement Performance Information 2018-19: National Indigenous Reform Agreement*. Productivity Commission, Canberra.
- STEM Partnerships Forum. (2018). *Optimising STEM Industry-School Partnerships: Inspiring Australia's Next Generation Final Report*. Education Services Australia.
- Stewart, J. (2005). Educational policy: politics, markets and the decline of 'publicness'. *Policy & Politics*, 33(3), 475-87. <https://doi.org/10.1332/0305573054325693>
- Stewart, W. (2013). Is PISA fundamentally flawed? <http://www.tes.co.uk/article.aspx?storycode=6344672>
- Stobart, G. (2021). An introduction to assessment for learning. <https://teachingenglishwithoxford.oup.com/2021/10/06/assessment-for-learning/>
- Storper, M. (1997). *The regional world: Territorial development in a global economy*. Guilford Press.

- Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1990). *Basics of Qualitative Research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded theory*. 1st ed. Sage Publications.
- Striepe, M., Clarke, S., & O'Donoghue, T. (2014). Spirituality, values and the school's ethos: Factors shaping leadership in a faith-based school. *Issues in Educational Research*, 24, 85-97. <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.352787861437366>
- Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998). *Basics of Qualitative Research; Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded theory*. 2nd ed. Sage Publications.
- Study International Staff. (2019). Does the PISA exam define education quality? <https://www.studyinternational.com/news/author/study-international-staff/>
- Suddaby, R. (2006). What grounded theory is not. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49, 633–642. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2006.22083020>
- Suter, L.E. (2016). Outside school time: an examination of science achievement and non-cognitive characteristics of 15-year olds in several countries. *International Journal of Science Education*, 38(4), 663-687. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2016.1147661>
- Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive science*, 12(2), 257-285. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-0213\(88\)90023-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-0213(88)90023-7)
- Sylva, K., Siraj-Blatchford, I., & Taggart, B. (2003). *The Early Childhood Environment Rating Scale-Extension (ECERS-E): Four Curricular Subscales*. Trentham Books.
- Sylva, K. (2010). Quality in early childhood settings. In *Early Childhood Matters* (pp. 86-107). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203862063>
- Takayama, K. (2008). The politics of international league tables: PISA in Japan's achievement crisis debate. *Comparative Education*, 44(4), 387–407. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050060802481413>

Takayama, K., Waldow, F., & Sung, Y.K. (2013). Finland has it all? Examining the media accentuation of 'Finnish education' in Australia, Germany, and South Korea.

Researching Comparative and International Education, 8(3), 307-325.

<https://doi.org/10.2304/rcie.2013.8.3.307>

Talbani, A. (1996). Pedagogy, power, and discourse: Transformation of Islamic education. *Comparative education review*, 40(1), 66-82.

<https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/447356>

Taut, S., & Palacios, D. (2016). Intended and unintended interpretations and uses of PISA results: A consequential validity perspective.

Taylor, S.J. & Bogdan, R. (1984). *Introduction to qualitative research methods*. John Wiley & Sons.

Tedesco, J. C., Opertti, R., & Amadio, M. (2013). The curriculum debate: why it is important today. Geneva: UNESCO International Bureau of Education.

www.ibe.unesco.org/sites/default/files/resources/wpci-10-curr_debate_eng.pdf

Tehan, D. (2019). Ministerial Media Release: Updating Australia's education goals in Sydney.

<https://ministers.dese.gov.au/tehan/updating-australias-education-goals-sydney>

Terman, L. M. (1919). *The intelligence of school children: How children differ in ability, the use of mental tests in school grading and the proper education of exceptional children*.

Mifflin.

Thompson, G., Adie, L., & Klenowski, V. (2018). Validity and participation: implications for school comparison of Australia's National Assessment Program. *Journal of Education Policy*, 33(6), 759-777.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2017.1373407>

Thomson, S. (2013). Racing for a top 5 place? Australia sits in the middle of the pack.

Professional Educator, 12(1). 20-25.

<https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.440582310216725>

Thomson, S. (2016, 29 November). Australian schools continue to fall behind other countries in maths and science. *The Conversation*. [https://theconversation.com/australian-schools-continue-to-fall-behind-other-countries-in-maths-and-science-](https://theconversation.com/australian-schools-continue-to-fall-behind-other-countries-in-maths-and-science-69341#:~:text=The%20TIMSS%20results%20show%20that%20around%20one-third%20of,Reporting%20Authority%20%28ACARA%29%20as%20the%20TIMSS%20intermediate%20benchmark.)

[69341#:~:text=The%20TIMSS%20results%20show%20that%20around%20one-](https://theconversation.com/australian-schools-continue-to-fall-behind-other-countries-in-maths-and-science-69341#:~:text=The%20TIMSS%20results%20show%20that%20around%20one-third%20of,Reporting%20Authority%20%28ACARA%29%20as%20the%20TIMSS%20intermediate%20benchmark.)

[third%20of,Reporting%20Authority%20%28ACARA%29%20as%20the%20TIMSS%2](https://theconversation.com/australian-schools-continue-to-fall-behind-other-countries-in-maths-and-science-69341#:~:text=The%20TIMSS%20results%20show%20that%20around%20one-third%20of,Reporting%20Authority%20%28ACARA%29%20as%20the%20TIMSS%20intermediate%20benchmark.)

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Thomson, S. (2020, 8 December). Australia lifts to be among top ten countries in maths

and science. *The Conversation*. [https://theconversation.com/australia-lifts-to-be-among-](https://theconversation.com/australia-lifts-to-be-among-top-ten-countries-in-maths-and-science-150275)

[top-ten-countries-in-maths-and-science-150275](https://theconversation.com/australia-lifts-to-be-among-top-ten-countries-in-maths-and-science-150275)

Thomson, S., & Fleming, N. (2004). Summing it up: Mathematics achievement in Australian

schools in TIMSS 2002. https://research.acer.edu.au/timss_monographs/3

Thomson, S., Wernert, N., Underwood, C., & Nicholas, M. (2008). Highlights from TIMSS 2007

from Australia's perspective: Highlights from the full report, Taking a closer look at

mathematics and science in Australia. https://research.acer.edu.au/timss_2007/1

Thomson, S., Hillman, K., & Wernert, N. (2012). *Monitoring Australian year 8 student*

achievement internationally: TIMSS 2011. Australian Council for Educational Research.

Thomson, S., Hillman, K. & De Bortoli, L. (2013). *A teacher's guide to PISA reading literacy*.

Australian Council of Educational Research.

Thomson, S., Wernert, N., O'Grady, E., & Rodrigues, S. (2017). *TIMSS 2015 Australian Year 8*

Data [SAS & SPSS]. Australian Council for Educational Research.

Thomson, S., Wernert, N., Rodrigues, S., & O'Grady, E. (2020). *TIMSS 2019 Australia Highlights*. Australian Council for Educational Research.

Thorpe, K., ten Kate, L., & Burgess, C. (2024). Reimagining democratic education by positioning Aboriginal Country-centred learning as foundational to curriculum and pedagogy. *Curriculum Perspectives*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41297-024-00233-2>

Thrupp, M. & Hursh, D. (2006) The Limits of Managerialist School Reform: the case of target-setting in England and the USA, in H. Lauder, P. Brown, J. Dillabough & A. Halsey (Eds) *Education, Globalization and Social Change*, pp. 642-653. Oxford University Press.

Tognolini, J. (2016). Introduction to modern assessment theory: A basis for all assessments. <https://slideplayer.com/slide/13002354/>

Tognolini, J., & Mowbray, B. (2019). *Excellence, Equity and Evidence: How do we know?* Catholic Schools NSW.

Tognolini, J. & Ratner, S. (2020). *Valuing the teaching profession: an independent inquiry: expert submissions*. NSW Teacher's Federation.

Tognolini, J. & Stanley, G. (2007). Standards-Based Assessment: A tool and means to the development of human capital and capacity building in education. *Australian Journal of Education*, 51(2), 129-145. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000494410705100203>

Townley, B. (2019). Foucault, power/knowledge, and its relevance for human resource management. In *Postmodern management theory* (pp. 215-242). Routledge.

Tröhler, D. (2013). The OECD and cold war culture: Thinking historically about PISA. In *PISA, power, and policy: The emergence of global educational governance* (pp. 141–161).

Ungar, M. (2004). A constructionist discourse on resilience: Multiple contexts, multiple realities among at-risk children and youth. *Youth & society*, 35(3), 341-365.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118X03257030>

United Nations. (2015) *Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. United Nations. <https://sdgs.un.org/publications/transforming-our-world-2030-agenda-sustainable-development-17981>

United Nations. (2019) Sustainable development goals. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/?menu=1300>

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (UNESCO). (2000, April 26-28). The Dakar framework for action: Education for all: meeting our collective commitments.

<https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/1681Dakar%20Framework20for%20Action.pdf>

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2015). *Incheon Declaration: Education 2030: Towards Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education and Lifelong Learning for All*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000233137>

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2023a). 250 million children out of school: What you need to know about UNESCO's latest education data. <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/250-million-children-out-school-what-you-need-know-about-unescos-latest-education-data>

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2023b). Guidance for generative ai in education and research.

<https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/guidance-generative-ai-education-and-research>

UNICEF. (2020). Inclusive education. Understanding Article 24 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

https://www.unicef.org/eca/sites/unicef.org.eca/files/IE_summary_accessible_2209_0.pdf

Urcia, I. A. (2021). Comparisons of adaptations in grounded theory and phenomenology: Selecting the specific qualitative research methodology. *International journal of qualitative methods*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069211045474>

Vaish, A., Grossmann, T., & Woodward, A. (2008). Not all emotions are created equal: the negativity bias in social-emotional development. *Psychological bulletin*, 134(3), 383–403. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0033-2909.134.3.383>

Välakangas, A., & Seeck, H. (2011). Exploring the Foucauldian interpretation of power and subject in organizations. *Journal of management and organization*, 17(6), 812-827. <https://doi.org/10.5172/jmo.2011.812>

VandenBos, G. R. (2007). *APA dictionary of Psychology*. American Psychological Association.

von Davier, M., Gonzalez, E., & Schulz, W. (2020). Ensuring Validity in International Comparisons Using State-of-the-Art Psychometric Methodologies, In H. Wagemaker (Ed.), *Reliability and Validity of International Large-Scale Assessment*, IEA Research for Education, 10.

Wagemaker, H. (2011). IEA: International studies, impact and transition, In C. Papanastasiou, T. Plomp, & E. Papanastasiou (Eds.), *IEA 1958–2008: 50 years of experiences and memories* (pp.253–273). Cultural Center of the Kykkos Monastery. <https://www.iea.nl/publications/iea-reference/iea-1958-2008>

Wagemaker, H. (2013). International large-scale assessment (ILSA) programs and the challenges of consequential validity. In M. Chatterji (Ed.), *Validity and test use: An international*

- dialogue on educational assessment, accountability and equity* (pp.217–233). Bingley, UK: Emerald Publishing.
- Wagemaker, H. (2014). International large-scale assessments: From research to policy. In L. Rutkowski, M. von Davier, & D. Rutkowski (Eds.), *A handbook of international large-scale assessment: Background, technical issues, and methods of data analysis* (pp.11–37). London, UK: Chapman & Hall/ CRC Press.
- Wagemaker, H. (2020). Reliability and Validity of International Large-Scale Assessment. IEA Research for Education, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53081-5>
- Waldow, F., & Steiner-Khamsi, G. (Eds.). (2019). *Understanding PISA's attractiveness: Critical analyses in comparative policy studies*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Waldow, F., Takayama, K., & Sung, Y. K. (2014). Rethinking the pattern of external policy referencing: Media discourses over the ‘Asian Tigers’ PISA success in Australia, Germany and South Korea. *Comparative Education*, 50(3), 302-321. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050068.2013.860704>
- Weatherton, M., & Schussler, E. E. (2021). Success for All? A Call to Re-examine How Student Success Is Defined in Higher Education. *CBE life sciences education*, 20(1), es3. <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.20-09-0223>
- Weedon, C. (1997). *Feminist practice and poststructuralist theory*. Blackwell Publishers.
- Weldon, P. (2019). *Changing priorities? The role of general capabilities in the curriculum*. ACER.

- Wigfield, A., & Eccles, J. (2002). The development of competence beliefs, expectancies for success and achievement values from childhood through adolescence, In *Development of Achievement Motivation*, edited by A. Wigfield and J. Eccles, 92–120. New York, NY: Academic Press.
- Wilby, P. (2014, May 6). Academics warn international school league tables are killing ‘joy of learning’, *Guardian*.
www.theguardian.com/education/2014/may/06/academicsinternational-school-league-tables-killing-joy-of-learning
- Wilkie, K. (2019, 5 December). NSW Teachers receive payrise. *Daily Mail*.
<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-7757785/NSW-teachers-receive-payrise-thousands-dollars-strike.html>
- William, D. (2018). Creating the schools our children need. *Learning Sciences International*.
- Wilson, R., Piccoli, A., Hargreaves, A., Ng, P. T., & Sahlberg, P. (2021). Putting Students First: Moving on from NAPLAN to a new educational assessment system (The Gonski Institute Policy Paper #2-2021). Sydney: UNSW Gonski Institute.
- Wilson, R., Tognolini, J., Kesidou, S., Ratner, S., Walker, K., Hains-Wesson, R., & Bartimote, K. (2022). Productivity Commission Submission. 17 June 2022.
- Wise, S. L., & DeMars, C. (2005). Low examinee effort in low-stakes assessment: problems and possible solutions. *Educational Assessment*, 10(1), 1–17.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326977ea1001_1
- Wiseman, A. (2013). Policy responses to PISA in comparative perspective. In Meyer, H.D. & Benavot, A. (Eds), *PISA, Power and Policy: The Emergence of Global Educational Governance*, (pp. 303-322). Symposium Books.

- Wolming, S., & Wikström, C. (2010). The concept of validity in theory and practice. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 17(2), 117-132.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09695941003693856>
- Wood, J. (1982). You Don't Kneed to Know: A Look at the Razor Gang Cuts. *The Australian Quarterly*, 54(1), 43–50. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20635153>
- Woodhall, M. (1997) Human Capital Concepts, in A. Halsey, H. Lauder, P. Brown & A. Wells (Eds) *Education, Culture, Economy and Society*, pp. 217-223. Oxford University Press.
- World Health Organisation. (2023, 7 March). Disability. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/disability-and-health#:~:text=An%20estimated%201.3%20billion%20people,earlier%20than%20those%20without%20disabilities>
- Wu, M., Tam, H. P., & Jen, T. H. (2016). Educational measurement for applied researchers. *Theory into practice*, 136. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3302-5>
- Wuest, J. (2012). Grounded theory: The method. *Nursing research: A qualitative perspective*, 5, 225-256.
- Wuttke, J. (2007). Uncertainties and bias in PISA. In S. Hopmann, G. Brinek and M. Retzl (Eds), *PISA according to PISA*, University of Vienna Press, Vienna, pp.241-264.
- Wyatt-Smith, C. (2014). What counts as quality education? *Catholic Schools Guide*, 7.
- Wyatt-Smith, C., & Adie, L. (2018). Assessment: The Trilogy of Standards, Evidence and Judgement in Australian Education Reform. In *The Australian Curriculum: Promises, Problems and Possibilities*, edited by A. Reid and D. Price, 163–176. ACT: Australian Curriculum Studies Association.

- Wyatt-Smith, C., Adie, L., & Harris, L. (2024). Supporting teacher judgement and decision-making: Using focused analysis to help teachers see students, learning, and quality in assessment data. *British Educational Research Journal*, 00, 1-29.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3984>
- Yates, L. (2017). Curriculum: The challenges and the devil in the details. In T. Bentley & G. C. Savage (Eds.), *Educating Australia: Challenges for the decade ahead*. Melbourne University Publishing.
- Zhao, Y. (2020). Two decades of havoc: A synthesis of criticism against PISA. *Journal of Educational Change*, 21, 245-266. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-019-09367-x>
- Zhao, Y., Wehmeyer, M., Basham, J., & Hansen, D. (2019). Tackling the wicked problem of measuring what matters: Framing the questions. *ECNU Review of Education*, 2(3), 262-278.
- Zhao, Y., & Gearin, B. (2016). Squeezed out. In D. Ambrose & R. J. Sternberg (Eds.), *Creative intelligence in the 21st century* (pp. 121–138). Springer.
- Zolkoski, S.M., & Bullock, L.M. (2012). Resilience in children and youth: a review. *Child and Youth Services Review*, 34, 2295–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.08.009>
- Zumbo, B. D. (2006). 3 validity: foundational issues and statistical methodology. *Handbook of statistics*, 26, 45-79. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7161\(06\)26003-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-7161(06)26003-6)
- Zumbo, B. D. (2014). What role does, and should, the test standards play outside of the United States of America? *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 33(4), 31–33.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1111/emip.12052>
- Zumbo, B. D., & Rupp, A. A. (2004). Responsible modeling of measurement data for appropriate inferences. www.ebook3000.com, 73.

Appendix A

University of Sydney Human Ethics Committee Approval

Research Integrity & Ethics Administration
HUMAN RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

Wednesday, 29 September 2021

Prof James Tognolini
Social Work; Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences
Email: james.tognolini@sydney.edu.au

Dear James,

The University of Sydney Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) has considered your application. I am pleased to inform you that after consideration of your response, your project has been approved.

Details of the approval are as follows:

Project No.: 2021/662
Project Title: Measuring the Success of K-12 Education Systems - Are we measuring what matters
Authorised Personnel: Tognolini James; Hains-Wesson Rachael; Ratner Sara; Kesidou Sofia;
Approval Period: 29 September 2021 to 29 September 2025
First Annual Report Due: 29 September 2022

Documents Approved:

Date Uploaded	Version Number	Document Name
26/09/2021	Version 2	PCF V2
26/09/2021	Version 1	Interview Qs
26/09/2021	Version 2	PIS V2
26/09/2021	Version 2	Recruitment Email V2

Condition/s of Approval

- Research must be conducted according to the approved proposal.
- An annual progress report must be submitted to the Ethics Office on or before the anniversary of approval and on completion of the project.
- You must report as soon as practicable anything that might warrant review of ethical approval of the project including:
 - Serious or unexpected adverse events (which should be reported within 72 hours).
 - Unforeseen events that might affect continued ethical acceptability of the project.
- Any changes to the proposal must be approved prior to their implementation (except where an amendment is undertaken to eliminate *immediate* risk to participants).
- Personnel working on this project must be sufficiently qualified by education, training and experience for their role, or adequately supervised. Changes to personnel must be reported and approved.
- Personnel must disclose any actual or potential conflicts of interest, including any financial or other interest or affiliation, as relevant to this project.
- Data and primary materials must be retained and stored in accordance with the relevant legislation and University guidelines.

Sara Ratner

From: Human Ethics <human.ethics@sydney.edu.au>
Sent: Friday, 21 October 2022 9:05 AM
To: Rachael Hains-Wesson; Sara Ratner; James Tognolini
Subject: 2021/662 Human Ethics: Annual or completion report outcome

Dear Prof Tognolini,

The report for the following project was submitted.

Project Title: Measuring the Success of K-12 Education Systems - Are we measuring what matters
Project number: 2021/662

Your annual report form has been processed and your ethics approval has been renewed for another year. Your next annual report is due on 29/09/2024

Thank you for updating us on the status of your project. Please retain a copy of this email with your study records.

Regards,
The Ethics Office
The University of Sydney
Research Integrity & Ethics Administration, Research Portfolio
Level 3, Michael Spence Building, F23 | The University of Sydney | NSW | 2006
+61 2 9036 9161 | human.ethics@sydney.edu.au | intranet.sydney.edu.au/ethics

Appendix B

Participant Information Statement

THE UNIVERSITY OF
SYDNEY

**Centre for Educational Measurement
and Assessment, School of Education
Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences**

ABN 15 211 513 464

Professor Jim Tognolini

Director

Centre for Educational Measurement and
Assessment

Room 333

Education Building A35

The University of Sydney

NSW 2006 AUSTRALIA

Telephone: +61 2 8627 5205

Email: jim.tognolini@sydney.edu.au

Web: <http://www.sydney.edu.au/>

The Australian Education System: Is it successful and how do we know?

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION STATEMENT

Ethics Approved Project: 2021/662

(1) What is this study about?

You are invited to take part in a research study about the Australian education system and whether the way we measure system-wide success is consistent with our goals for schooling.

You have been invited to participate in this study because you are recognised as a thought leader in education assessment with expertise in school improvement and national policy making. This Participant Information Statement tells you about the research study. Knowing what is involved will help you decide if you want to take part in the study. Please read this sheet carefully and ask questions about anything that you don't understand or want to know more about.

Participation in this research study is voluntary.

By giving consent to take part in this study you are telling us that you:

- ✓ Understand what you have read.
- ✓ Agree to take part in the research study as outlined below.
- ✓ Agree to the use of your personal information as described.

You will be given a copy of this Participant Information Statement to keep.

(2) Who is running the study?

The study is being carried out by the following researchers: Sara Ratner, PhD Student.

Sara is conducting this study as the basis for the degree of PhD at The University of Sydney. This will take place under the supervision of Professor Jim Tognolini, Dr Sofia Kesidou (NESA) and A/Prof Rachael Hains-Wesson.

(3) What will the study involve for me?

You will be asked to take part in a semi-structured interview of approximately one hour in length. The interviews may take place at the University of Sydney, online or in a mutually agreed location. The date and time is to be mutually agreed between the participant and the researcher.

The interview questions include:

1. Questions relating to the education sector/system you have experience in
2. Questions relating to measures of school success in your sector/system
3. Questions relating to national policy pertaining to system-wide success
4. Questions relating to innovative and imaginative ways to measure system-wide success

All interviews will be recorded and transcribed for coding and analysis in order to inform the research.

All recordings and transcripts will be made available for participants to review prior to use in the research. Please allow approximately 30 minutes to complete this review. The researcher is also happy to make available any reference to the participant and their interview in the thesis prior to making it publicly available.

(4) How much of my time will the study take?

The interview should take approximately an hour of your time. You may wish to spend additional time (approximately 30 minutes) reviewing the interview transcript prior to it being included in the study.

(5) Do I have to be in the study? Can I withdraw from the study once I've started?

Being in this study is completely voluntary and you do not have to take part. Your decision whether to participate will not affect your current or future relationship with the researchers or anyone else at the University of Sydney.

If you decide to take part in the study and then change your mind later, you are free to withdraw at any time. You can do this by advising me in writing at any time.

You are free to stop the interview at any time. Unless you say that you want us to keep them, any recordings will be erased and the information you have provided will not be included in the study results. You may also refuse to answer any questions that you do not wish to answer during the interview.

(6) Are there any risks or costs associated with being in the study?

Aside from giving up your time, we do not expect that there will be any risks or costs associated with taking part in this study.

(7) Are there any benefits associated with being in the study?

We cannot guarantee that you will receive any direct benefits from being in the study.

(8) What will happen to information about me that is collected during the study?

By providing your consent, you are agreeing to us collecting personal information about you for the purposes of this research study. Your information will only be used for the purposes outlined in this Participant Information Statement, unless you consent otherwise.

Your information will be stored securely, and your identity/information will only be disclosed with your permission, except as required by law. Study findings may be published, and you will be named in these publications if you agree by checking the tick box on the consent form.

The recordings of your interview will be stored according to University protocols and will meet the data security and privacy protection guidelines. The content will be used for analysis only, no audio will be shared in publications.

In the event that third party transcription services are used the details of the service provider will be shared with you in order to protect your confidentiality if requested.

The results of this study will be published in the student theses in order to meet the University of Sydney requirements. In addition, it may be included in journal publications and conference presentations.

The electronic and hardcopy data from this study will be stored according to the most up to date University of Sydney policies and cyber security requirements. Data will be retained for the duration of the study and upon the PhD being conferred the data will be destroyed.

(9) Can I tell other people about the study?

Yes, you are welcome to tell other people about the study.

(10) What if I would like further information about the study?

When you have read this information, Professor Jim Tognolini will be available to discuss it with you further and answer any questions you may have. If you would like to know more at any stage during the study, please feel free to contact Professor Jim Tognolini, Room 333 Education Building A35, The University of Sydney. Phone 02 86275205.

Email: jim.tognolini@sydney.edu.au

(11) Will I be told the results of the study?

You have a right to receive feedback about the overall results of this study. You can tell us that you wish to receive feedback by ticking the relevant box on the consent form. This feedback will be in the form of a copy of the completed study. You will receive this feedback after the study is finished.

(12) What if I have a complaint or any concerns about the study?

Research involving humans in Australia is reviewed by an independent group of people called a Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC). The ethical aspects of this study have been approved by the HREC of the University of Sydney. As part of this process, we have agreed to carry out the study according to the *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007)*. This statement has been developed to protect people who agree to take part in research studies.

If you are concerned about the way this study is being conducted or you wish to make a complaint to someone independent from the study, please contact the university using the details outlined below. Please quote the study title and protocol number.

The Manager, Ethics Administration, University of Sydney:

- **Telephone:** +61 2 8627 8176
- **Email:** human.ethics@sydney.edu.au
- **Fax:** +61 2 8627 8177 (Facsimile)

This information sheet is for you to keep.

Appendix C

Consent Form

The Australian Education System: Is it successful and how do we know?

Ethics Approved Project: 2021/662

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

I, [PRINT NAME], agree to take part in this research study.

In giving my consent I state that:

- I understand the purpose of the study, what I will be asked to do, and any risks/benefits involved.
- I have read the Participant Information Statement and have been able to discuss my involvement in the study with the researchers if I wished to do so.
- The researchers have answered any questions that I had about the study, and I am happy with the answers.
- I understand that being in this study is completely voluntary and I do not have to take part. My decision whether to be in the study will not affect my relationship with the researchers or anyone else at the University of Sydney now or in the future.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any time.
- I understand that I may stop the interview at any time if I do not wish to continue, and that unless I indicate otherwise any recordings will then be erased and the information provided will not be included in the study. I also understand that I may refuse to answer any questions I don't wish to answer.
- I understand that personal information about me that is collected over the course of this project will be stored securely and will only be used for purposes that I have agreed to. I understand that information about me will only be told to others with my permission, except as required by law.

I understand that the results of this study may be published, but these publications will not contain my name or any identifiable information about me unless I consent to being identified using the 'Yes' checkbox below.

Yes, I am happy to be identified.

No, I don't want to be identified. Please keep my identity anonymous.

I consent to:

- **Audio-recording** YES NO

- **Being contacted about future studies** YES NO

- **Permanent archiving of study materials** YES NO

I would like to review my interview transcripts YES NO

I would like to receive feedback about the results of this study YES NO

If you answered **YES**, please indicate your preferred form of feedback and address:

Postal: _____

Email: _____

.....

Signature

.....

PRINT name

.....

Date

Appendix D

Interview invitation

Recruitment Email

Dear XXX,

I hope this email finds you well. I was referred to you by XXX.

As a respected leader in the field of Education Assessment with expertise in school improvement at a national level, you are invited to take part in a research study about the Australian education system and whether the way we measure system-wide success is consistent with our goals for schooling.

Attached you will find a 'Participant Information Statement' which tells you about the PhD research study I am completing at the University of Sydney Centre for Education Measurement and Assessment thanks to a scholarship from the NSW Education Standards Authority (NESA). Knowing what is involved will help you decide if you want to take part in the study. Please read this sheet carefully and feel free to ask questions about anything that you don't understand or want to know more about.

Your participation will require approximately **one hour** of your time. During that hour together we will complete a semi-structured interview to explore your views and insights as to how we currently assess system-wide success in Education and whether you envisage an improved approach moving forward.

The interview will be recorded and then transcribed. You will have the opportunity to review the content prior to its use if you choose. The results of this study will be published in my student thesis in order to meet the University of Sydney requirements. Participation is completely voluntary, and should you choose not to take part this will not have any impact on your relationship with the University of Sydney or anyone else. Should you consent to take part and then change your mind, you may choose to withdraw your consent at any time by contacting my supervisor, Professor Jim Tognolini, in writing.

I sincerely hope you will support my research endeavour in examining this important topic in education policy and assessment. Please confirm by reply your willingness to contribute to this study and then I will be in touch to schedule a time to meet that is mutually agreeable.

Best regards

Sara Ratner